

Headquarters 49th Fighter Wing

Holloman Air Force Base, New Mexico

**INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PLAN
HOLLOMAN AIR FORCE BASE, NEW MEXICO**

For Plan Period

January 1999 - January 2004

**INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES
MANAGEMENT PLAN**

HOLLOMAN AIR FORCE BASE, NEW MEXICO

PREPARED BY

Holloman Air Force Base
49th Civil Engineer Squadron
Environmental Flight
Building 55
550 Tobosa Avenue
Holloman AFB, New Mexico

New Mexico Natural Heritage Program
University of New Mexico
Biology Department
851 University Blvd. SE
Suite 101
Albuquerque, New Mexico 87131

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APPROVAL

This Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan meets the requirements of the Sikes Act (16 USC 670a *et seq.*), as amended.

William J. Lake
Brigadier General, U.S. Air
Force
Holloman Air Force Base

Date

Jennifer Fowler-Propst
Field Supervisor
New Mexico Field Office
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service

Date

Daniel C. Frederick
Field Supervisor
Austin Field Office
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service

Date

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

CHAPTER 1 - PLAN INTRODUCTION

Western Burrowing Owl (*Athene cunicularia hypugaea*)

This Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan (INRMP) has been prepared by the New Mexico Natural Heritage Program (NMNHP) for the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE), Fort Worth District, in support of the 49th Civil Engineer Environmental Flight (CES/CEV) of Holloman Air Force Base (HAFB), New Mexico. Additional preparation was provided by 49 CES/CEV Natural Resources Manager and GIS Program Manager. The INRMP uses an interdisciplinary approach to ecosystem management, integrating all aspects of natural resources management within the context of the military mission. It is designed to provide a well-documented reference for base natural resources, including information on location, sensitive areas, management issues, and use constraints. This chapter addresses the INRMP process and the management philosophy used to develop the plan.

The plan was developed for access on the internet. This approach provides a unique opportunity to integrate pertinent research topics and supporting Air Force and government documents into the plan without increasing the size of the core document. Users are able to easily find in-depth information on topics pertinent to their interests by taking advantage of hypertext links. Links (signified by underlined blue text) "jump" the user either to other web sites or to other on-line documents. Additional links can be added throughout the plan period, making the document essentially adaptable to new natural resource data, changing management schemes, or laws governing management practices.

Introduction to Integrated Natural Resource Management

The Department of Defense is committed to the consideration and protection of biodiversity on military lands. The ecosystem management approach strives for sustainable use, consistent with operational readiness and mission. The Department of Defense Handbook for Natural Resources Managers “Conserving Biodiversity on Military Lands” (1996; Chapter 1) confirms that:

“[t]he 25 million acres of Federal and state land managed by the Department of Defense (DoD) include national assets of exceptional ecological value and biological diversity...In terms of acreage, DoD is the fifth largest Federal land manager...Although DoD-managed lands represent only about 3% of the total Federal land inventory, there is strong evidence that they have disproportionate value in terms of biodiversity...This biological diversity is a direct reflection of the wide range of training environments and strategic locations that the military requires to maintain readiness...There is no doubt that the DoD controls areas of land that have substantial biological significance. The American people expect this public land to remain ecologically viable and healthy in perpetuity.”

This plan is in accordance with Department of Defense policy Directives and [Instructions](#) designating procedures to develop comprehensive ecosystem management plans ([DoDI 4715.3](#), DoDD 4700.4). In addition, this plan is in compliance with Air Force Directives and Instruction AFPD 32-70, [AFI 32-7064](#) and AFI 32-7065.

The chief tool for managing natural resources in a coordinated manner within the context of operational mission on DoD installations is the Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP). In accordance with AFI 32-7064 (01 Aug 97) and the 1997 amendment to the Sikes Act, all military installations must have an INRMP by 1998, review it annually, and revise it every five years. Based on an interdisciplinary approach to ecosystem management, the INRMP ensures the successful accomplishment of the military mission by integrating all aspects of natural resources management with each other and with activities associated with the installation’s mission.

Biodiversity conservation on Air Force controlled lands and waters shall be promoted when consistent with the mission and practical. Maintaining biodiversity is crucial to overall ecosystem integrity and sustainability. Failure to maintain ecosystem diversity may result in severe degradation of the land and loss of public confidence in the Air Force’s stewardship of the land. If access to the land is subsequently denied to the Air Force, this will negatively impact the Air Force mission (AFI 32-7064).

This plan was developed in an interdisciplinary manner and involved military and/or civilian representatives of all relevant Holloman AFB groups. Two separate phases of meetings, held between March, 1997, and January, 1998, gathered input from base personnel and other stakeholders. During Phase I meetings, base personnel and stakeholders offered short presentations on their operations. These meetings provided a baseline of information to begin a Geographic Information System (GIS). The GIS was used to identify potential conflicts between base activities and Air Force management

directives. Phase II meetings addressed issues identified from the GIS and during Phase I meetings.

Early in the planning process, decisions were made to make the final INRMP available on the Holloman AFB internet site. Making the plan available on the internet will increase the user base and efficiency in implementing procedural guidelines. Using hypertext technology, the plan incorporates ancillary data, with the click of a mouse. The hypertext makes available in-house data reports, pertinent AFIs, and related web sites. The result is a robust and useful plan that is actually interactive, updateable and can be tailored by the individual user.

The plan closely follows the suggested format (AFI 32-7064). This document directs natural resource management policy for the five-year planning period. It is provided in both a hard copy and digital format. The hard copy is available through the 49th Civil Engineer Environmental Flight (CEV) and the digital format is located on the Holloman (AFB) [Web Site](#).

Policy Guidance

- Dr. William J. Perry, former Secretary of Defense, incorporated environmental considerations into the DoD mission (Leslie et al. 1996):

“Protecting our national security in the post-Cold War era includes integrating the best environmental practices into all Department of Defense activities.”

- The importance of ecosystem management on DoD lands is emphasized by Sherri Goodman, Deputy Under Secretary of Defense (Environmental Security) in a [memo](#) dated 8 Aug 94:

“I want to ensure that ecosystem management becomes the basis for future management of DoD lands and waters. Ecosystem management is not only a smart way of doing business, it will blend multiple-use needs and provide a consistent framework to managing DoD installations... Ecosystem management of natural resources draws on a collaboratively developed vision of desired future ecosystem conditions that integrates ecological, economic, and social factors... The goal is to maintain and improve the sustainability and native biological diversity of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems while supporting human needs, including DoD mission.”

- Working together to integrate environmental protection and military readiness is encouraged by General Joseph W. Ralston, USAF, Vice Chairman, Joint Chiefs of Staff (Leslie et al. 1996):

“By working as a team we can preserve both the natural diversity of military training areas and our opportunity to train the way we plan to fight now and in the future.”

- Air Force policy on Environmental Quality integrates environmental planning into comprehensive planning (Air Force Directive 32-70 Environmental Quality):

“Achieving and maintaining environmental quality is an essential part of the Air Force mission. The Air Force is committed to planning its future activities to minimize environmental impacts and managing responsibly the irreplaceable natural and cultural resources it holds in public trust...through effective environmental planning... Environmental opportunities and constraints will be the foundation of comprehensive plans for installation development.”

Purpose of Plan

The plan is designed to facilitate adaptive management policies to correspond to the changing natural environmental conditions while integrating base mission goals and strategic plans. The INRMP has the following basic purposes:

- *To create an easily accessible, well-used, integrated reference base for use by Command, Action Proponents, Base Planners, and Natural Resource Managers, that would:*
 - Identify locations of natural resources.
 - Identify locations and circumstances of potential conflicts and conflict resolution opportunities.
 - Identify unique and sensitive areas.
 - Provide information for proactive planning by action proponents.
 - Develop a “one-stop” planning document that integrates goals, purposes, management direction, and management activities for each natural resource, fully consistent with each resource component plan and complementary with other component plans.
- *To foster understanding of the jobs, roles, responsibilities, and needs of the various flights and functional operations as they relate to the protection, rehabilitation, maintenance, and enhancement of natural resources on Holloman Air Force Base to:*
 - Identify, coordinate, and clarify the cross-functional roles of the organizational representatives and action proponents within the base organization.
 - Open lines of communication for effective and timely planning, efficient mission operations, and pleasant, proactive, and cooperative relationships.
 - Identify various Federal, state, and local agencies and Indian tribes, and public and private stakeholders and interested parties, and provide appropriate means for participation in Base planning and management of natural resources.

- ❑ *To develop realistic management goals, management activities, programs, identify manpower (staffing) needs, and funding levels for Holloman Air Force Base natural resources that both support mission and increase the quality of work and recreation on the base.*
- ❑ *To direct natural resources management policy on base for the planning period, through cross-functional consensus and Command approval, so that all functional activities on Holloman Air Force Base can move forward together to:*
 - Identify areas dedicated to natural resource management.
 - Determine primacy of goals and management activities when activities and natural resources conflict, and provide rationale for changing existing natural resource management plans when necessary.
- ❑ *To ensure consistency of Holloman Air Force Base programs and functions with environmental laws, regulations, Executive Orders, DoD Instructions and guidance, and Air Force Instructions ([see Appendix A](#)).*

Background

In accordance with AFI 32-7064, as part of the integrated planning process of the INRMP, Holloman was required to conduct a scoping meeting for stakeholders at the initiation of the planning process. An internal scoping meeting was held on 27 February 1995 to identify natural resource issues. A preliminary list of these issues was developed and used to frame subsequent internal scoping meetings.

The INRMP scoping meeting for stakeholders and interested parties outside the base was held on 13 and 14 March, 1995. The purpose of the meeting was to initiate discussion and solicit recommendations on natural resource issues from a variety of interested groups, including federal and state agencies, other military installations, non-profit organizations, and university departments. Recommendations were solicited for future research opportunities, especially management and conservation biology-oriented research pertinent to the Tularosa Basin.

Following these meetings, Holloman AFB proceeded with a series of facilitated meetings to gather detailed input from military personnel and other groups, including tenants, that conduct business on the base. This series of meetings was instrumental in gathering baseline data for the Geographic Information System (GIS). To accommodate individual schedules and bring together groups that shared resource areas, meetings were conducted by operational area. For example, groups conducting activities within the Boles Wells Water System Annex were brought together. During this process, potential conflicts and problems were elucidated that were ultimately useful in proactive planning procedures.

The integrated natural resources planning process follows procedures necessary for quality cross-functional planning:

- Identify cross-functional (interdisciplinary) team members.
- Inventory and map natural resources and identify, describe, and map mission-related activities that could affect or be affected by natural resources and their management.
- Identify, coordinate with, and involve federal, state and local agencies, Indian tribes, other stakeholders and interested persons and organizations.
- Identify conflicts, opportunities, and constraints associated with operational and mission and activities, natural resources characteristics, and their interaction, condition, and trends.
- Identify desired future condition, measurable management objectives, and reliable measures of success for each natural resource, ensuring consistency with the Holloman Air Force Base General Plan.
- Identify alternative management strategies, mitigation, and opportunities, again ensuring consistency with the General Plan.
- Ensure consistency and compliance with NEPA and other laws, regulations, executive Orders, AFIs and DoD Instructions concurrently with integrated natural resources planning.
- Initiate review of plan review with MAJCOM and HQ USAF and obtain installation approval through the Environmental Leadership Council.
- Implement the plan and monitor its effectiveness.

INRMP Process and Partnerships

Under this plan, the diverse environments under the jurisdiction of the DoD are maintained for present and future human use, and their natural systems are allowed to function normally. The INRMP operates on the basis of the ecosystem management approach incorporating ecological, socio-economic, and institutional perspectives.

Partnerships include other military installations located within the Tularosa Basin, such as White Sands Missile Range and Ft. Bliss. These partnerships provide unique opportunities to share common land use issues that are particular to military activities. White Sands National Monument (WSNM) and the San Andres National Wildlife Refuge (SANWR) are valuable partners that help support conservation efforts of plants and animals endemic to the basin as well as providing seasonal migratory habitat for birds. The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) and New Mexico Department of Game and Fish (NMDGF) provide an invaluable service for guidance on listed threatened and endangered species, as well as information on sensitive mammals, reptiles and amphibians, fish, birds, and some invertebrates. The Bureau of Land Management

(BLM) shares management responsibilities with Holloman AFB at the Boles Wells Well Field Annex and portions within the base near Lake Holloman and Stinky Playa. Under the National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 1995, the Bureau of Land Management transferred ownership of 511.11 ha (1262 acres) covering portions of Lake Holloman and Stinky Playa to the Secretary of the Air Force. These partnerships help define activities within these withdrawal areas that meet the needs of both the mission of the base and BLM. Lincoln National Forest (LNF) manages lands east of the Boles Wells Well Field Annex and provides information on resource issues germane to the Sacramento Mountain foothills. Other agencies such as U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, U.S. Department of Agriculture - Jornada Experimental Range and the National Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) provide data on environmental processes specific to resources within the Tularosa Basin. Non-profit groups such as the Sierra Club, New Mexico Audubon Society, Mesilla Valley Audubon Society and New Mexico Native Plant Society are partners in conservation issues and provide volunteers for project-oriented tasks to improve wildlife habitat within Holloman AFB. University groups such as the New Mexico Natural Heritage Program (NMNHP) of the University of New Mexico provide database information on many of the endemics occurring on Holloman AFB and have conducted numerous field studies on the base and within the Tularosa Basin.

Relationship to Other Documents and Authorities

The Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan is cross-referenced with the *Holloman Air Force Base General Plan* (1996). Information from other survey and inventory reports and planning documents pertinent to integrated planning needs have been incorporated into the INRMP. An environmental impact analysis process (EIAP), required by the National Environmental Policy Act, AFI 32-7064, Chapter 2, and AFI 32-7061 is prepared concurrently with the development of the plan to support the proposed recommendations.

Information and direction incorporated in the INRMP will be integrated into and used in conjunction with the General Plan and appropriate component plans for base planning activities. Natural resource constraints are to be considered for all future installation development, including land use planning and the Housing Community Plan. Information in the General Plan will not be duplicated in the INRMP; however, this information is cross-referenced for ease of referral. Other base component plans, such as the [BASH Plan](#), the Pest Management Plan, and the Cultural Resources Management Plan are supported by and integrated into this INRMP.

Internal and external assessments of natural resources programs shall be conducted as part of the Environmental Compliance Assessment and Management Program (ECAMP), as outlined in AFI 32-7045, *Environmental Compliance Assessment and Management Program*. Since implementation of an INRMP may constitute a potentially significant

federal action, it may require consideration of potential environmental effects as described in AFI 32-7061, *Environmental Impact Analysis Process*.

Holloman Air Force Base component plans will be made consistent with the INRMP upon completion of all necessary planning requirements and administrative approvals. As appropriate, HAFB component plans will be reviewed and revised as needed based on the results of this integrated planning effort. The INRMP baseline information and its associated GIS layers will be reviewed annually, where necessary, using an interdisciplinary process, and revised and modified as necessary to ensure a quality foundation for integrated planning efforts and natural resources management at Holloman Air Force Base.

In accordance with AFI 32-1031 Civil Engineers Operations Management, activities affecting natural resources require one or more of the following forms submitted: Air Force Form 332 (Base Civil Engineer Work Request), AF Form 813 (Request for Environmental Analysis), AF Form 103 (Digging Permit, or DD Form 1391 (Military Construction Project Data).

INRMP and NEPA for Specific Projects and Programs

All ground-based military training exercises are evaluated in detail in the Programmatic Environmental Assessment for Ground-Based Training at Holloman Air Force Base. The results of this programmatic EA will be incorporated into this INRMP. Ground-based training exercises were identified as the primary impact on natural resources on base; it was decided to evaluate the environmental impacts in detail separately, but as a component of this INRMP. The intent of the programmatic EA is to develop a long-range training/exercise plan for HAFB, using NEPA as the basis for the comprehensive planning effort, that:

- meets the mission needs of HAFB organizations and units,
- minimizes scheduling conflicts on the same training areas,
- uses available sites optimally, including joint training,
- identifies sites not appropriate for training exercises,
- provides for long-term use of the training areas by maintaining necessary environmental requirements and components, and
- optimizes environmental quality, both short-term and long-term.

Through the INRMP planning effort, the following projects and programs were identified as requiring further study. As a minimum, they will also require specific planning and documentation efforts under the National Environmental Policy Act:

- Management of the HAFB golf course, including the addition of nine more

- holes, because of use of water, pesticides, and herbicides;
- Management of horse stable and trails on base, because of potential for soil erosion and spread of noxious weeds;
- Extension of the FamCamp, because it is in a floodplain and landscaping should include xeriscaping, not exotic ornamental plants;
- Management of a formal all-terrain vehicle (ATV) area near Dillard Draw, because of safety and environmental concerns;
- Management of the noxious weed program, because of use of herbicides and need for systematic program incorporating integrated management techniques.

The results of these NEPA planning efforts will be incorporated into the INRMP as the planning is completed and approved.

Management Philosophy

Holloman Air Force Base Environmental Mission Statement:

In a relatively small geographic area, Holloman AFB contains representatives of a high diversity of ecosystem types characteristic of the northern Chihuahuan desert. Holloman AFB is committed to supporting the military mission of Holloman AFB by restoring and maintaining these ecosystems and fostering biodiversity and the natural processes that maintain these ecosystems. The Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan uses an interdisciplinary approach to integrate all aspects of natural resources management with each other and with activities associated with the installation's mission.

Holloman AFB is dedicated to maintaining and enhancing populations of native plants and wildlife, and their respective habitats. Using an adaptive management strategy, Holloman AFB will continue to increase efforts to research, enhance, and monitor changing environmental conditions due to either natural or human influences. Long range goals include providing environmental education, fostering responsible stewardship, and enhancing appreciation of properly functioning ecosystems.

The AF has outlined specific goals for maintaining and when integral to the health of the system, restoring environments toward attaining properly functioning systems. In order to meet these goals, the following guidelines are recommended (AFI 32-7064):

- Maintain or restore remaining native ecosystem types across their natural range.
- Maintain or reestablish viable populations of all native species in an installation's areas of natural habitat when practical.
- Maintain evolutionary and ecological processes, such as disturbance regimes, hydrological processes, and nutrient cycles.

- Plan management for a long time period to ensure consideration of changing system dynamics.
- Perform all mission activities in concert with natural resources conservation.
- Accommodate human use.
- Use regional approaches incorporating cooperation with other DoD components, other federal agencies, and with adjoining property users.

Natural Resource Management at Holloman AFB

- Natural resources management has been active on Holloman AFB since 1994. The Environmental Flight (49 CES/CEV) is the recipient of:
- Natural & Cultural Resources Program Management Award 1992-1994 (best in ACC)
- Command Leader recognition for natural resources program from 1996 external ECAMP review process
- 1996 Conservation Award from the Mesilla Valley Audubon Society
- 1998 Air Combat Command Environmental Quality Award for Natural Resources Management Award-Large Base. As ACC winner, HAFB Natural Resources Program will compete in the AF-wide General Thomas D. White Award.

Holloman AFB was recognized by Southwest Environmental Center for outstanding service for the environment in New Mexico in 1996 for the constructed wetlands project associated with the new wastewater treatment plant.

The Natural Resources Program is involved with a number of research investigations:

- Funding cooperative research projects *on Effects of Helicopter Noise on Mexican Spotted Owls* (with Northern Arizona University, CERL, USDA Rocky Mountain Forest Range & Experiment Station)
- Conducting four research projects on White Sands Pupfish (with Savannah River Ecology Lab, University of Georgia, New Mexico State University, and North Dakota State University)
- Conducting study on control of African rue, a non-native exotic weed with USDA Forest Service Southwest Region
- Conducting surveys of Burrowing Owls and monitoring reproductive success (with University of New Mexico and New Mexico State University)
- Conducting historical and biological resources studies at the Cinetheodilite Missile Towers (with University of New Mexico)

- Initiating study of effects of military operations on gypsic soils of HAFB (with New Mexico State University, Jornada Range Experiment Station and National Biological Survey)
- Conducting a study of foraging requirements of migratory wetland birds on Holloman Lakes (with University of New Mexico)

Additional surveys and management resources include:

- Delineation of all wetlands and waters of the U.S. on high quality digitized color-IR aerial photos of the base;
- Completion of threatened, endangered and sensitive species management plan
- Completion of draft fish and wildlife management plan
- Delineation of detailed vegetation map

The natural resources manager (Dr. Hildy Reiser) is also a member of the White Sands Pupfish Conservation Team, a member of the state of New Mexico Wetlands Task Force, and a participant in the New Mexico Partners in Flight Program.

Plan Structure

The Holloman AFB INRMP was designed to incorporate DoD guidelines on ecosystem management and ensure compliance with AF, Federal, and State regulations in support of the military mission at Holloman. The following is a synopsis of the features discussed within each chapter.

Chapter 1 provides an introduction to the approach followed by Holloman AFB throughout the Integrated Natural Resource Management process. Cross-references to pertinent documents and partnerships are discussed. Specific projects and programs developed from the INRMP process are outlined.

Chapter 2 gives a geographic context for Holloman AFB in relation to nearby natural areas, including federal and state lands. Holloman AFB history is discussed in relation to military activities.

Chapter 3 presents an overview of the landscape characteristics of Holloman AFB, including physical and biological components. Threatened, endangered, and sensitive species and important cultural resources are introduced.

Chapter 4 provides detailed descriptions of ecosystem types within each Management Unit.

Chapter 5 incorporates military, tenant, and recreational activities into the context of potential and realized impacts on environmental processes.

Chapter 6 is a synthesis of management issues and concerns organized by categories, formerly encompassed within Component Plans.

Chapter 7 proposes the management direction and recommends solutions to natural resource issues explained in Chapter 6. This chapter is the consensus of all planning efforts providing management prescriptions for proactive, effective natural resource management at Holloman AFB.

CHAPTER 2 - INSTALLATION LOCATION AND FACILITIES

Since 1942, Holloman Air Force Base has played a decisive role in our nation's national security. Clear skies, a moderate climate, and low population densities provide a highly favorable environment for nearly year-round training and military readiness operations. Holloman AFB is currently home to the 49th Fighter Wing and is organized in five groups: 49th Operations Group, 49th Logistics Group, 49th Support Group, 49th Medical Group, and 49th Material Maintenance Group. A diverse group of tenants provide important research and testing integral to maintaining military excellence.

Setting

Holloman Air Force Base is located in Otero County, in southeastern New Mexico, approximately 13 km (8 miles) west of Alamogordo, NM. Within its contiguous boundaries (Main Base) are 21,089.5 ha (52,073 acres), including a recent land parcel transfer of 511 ha (1,262 acres) from the Bureau of Land Management near the Holloman Lakes complex in the southwestern portion of the base (National Defense Authorization Act 1994). *The Holloman AFB General Plan* (1996) outlines the general land use patterns of the base and economic impact on the local community (Section 4.7.1, pgs. 4-54 through 4-60; Section 3.72, pgs. 3-16-3-17).

Southeast of the contiguous portion of the base, the USAF also has jurisdiction over 1,091 ha (2,694 acres) called the Boles Wells Water System Annex (BWWSA, unofficially referred to as the Boles, Douglas, and San Andres well fields), which include fee purchase and condemnation tracts (Figure 1). The well field annex begins 8 km (5 miles) south of Alamogordo, adjacent to the western foothills (bajada) of the Sacramento Mountains. In addition to these parcels, Holloman AFB has sub-surface interests to protect and develop the underground water supply on 1,696 ha (4,187 acres) of public land withdrawn under Public Land Orders 3434 and 4667. Land surface management for these public lands lies with the Bureau of Land Management. The total acreage of the BWWSA is 3,001 ha (7,411 acres). North/northeast of Holloman AFB is the 46.6 ha (115 acre) Bonito Lake Water System Annex, with an additional 31 ha (77 acres) of easement and 31.6 ha (78 acres) of general use permits and licenses. The above parcels total 24,154 ha (59,639 acres).

The primary purpose of the Boles Wells Water System Annex, and the Bonito Lake Water System is to provide continuous sources of potable water for the base. Lands to the east of the Annex area are under the jurisdiction of the Bureau of Land Management on the north and the Lincoln National Forest on the south. The southern tip of the annex area borders McGregor Range, Fort Bliss, U.S. Army. Separating the north and south well field areas is Oliver Reed State Park. To the west of the well fields is a mosaic of private lands, Bureau of Land Management lands, and land held by White Sands National Monument. The Old El Paso Highway provides north-south public access through the southern part of the Boles Wells Annex area (Douglas and San Andres Well Fields areas). US Highway 54 intersects the extreme northwestern corner of the Annex area.

Holloman AFB is uniquely situated at the center of the Tularosa Basin within easy reach of several ecologically distinctive areas. These nearby managed areas include volcanic peaks and mesas covered in high mountain grasslands and conifer forests, dropping to desert shrublands mantled with cactus and yucca. Surrounding mountain fronts vary in vegetation cover from xerophytic shrublands, to juniper-pinyon savannas, to high mountain meadows at their peaks. Dominating the area are the diverse, broad expanses of lowland desert environments, including gypsum dunelands punctuated by playas and ephemeral drainages.

- [The White Sands National Monument](#), administered by the National Park Service, is located to the southwest of and contiguous with portions of the western border of the base (Figure 1). Over 500,000 visitors each year use the park, including recreational driving of the loop road through the Monument, self-guided hiking trails, and picnicking. A primitive overnight camping site is available by permit. Monument and Holloman AFB personnel jointly conduct a popular interpretive hike for the public through the dunes and White Sands pupfish (*Cyprinodon tularosa*) habitat once or twice a year. The Monument cooperates with Holloman AFB on fencing for oryx (*Oryx gazella*) management, and research and management for the White Sands pupfish. Due to the proximity of the Monument to HAFB, concerns over non-native plant infestations such as African rue (*Peganum harmala*) and salt cedar (*Tamarix ramosissima*) are a natural resource concern. The monument has begun a program to control the spread of salt cedar, which quickly colonizes riparian areas, usually displacing native species.
- [The White Sands Missile Range](#) (WSMR), administered by the US Army, is a 2.2 million acre expanse of nearly pristine desert plains, riparian areas, and montane ecosystems. The majority of livestock was removed from the Range by 1950. The basin within the Missile Range has not been grazed by livestock for over 45 years, with the exception of feral horses, oryx, and some trespass cattle, primarily along the eastern boundary. The Missile Range is west of Holloman AFB and stretches both north and south with some contiguous boundaries. Only approximately 3% of the missile range is actually used for military research and testing activities and associated disturbances (*See* Chapter 4, Geographically Separated Units, Figure 18). The Range has no public access except for limited escorted hunting of oryx, mule deer, and small to moderate mammals such as rabbit and coyote. Holloman and WSMR cooperate on management strategies and research for the White Sands pupfish. All vegetation communities within Holloman AFB are represented in the Missile Range, including wetland plant communities. However, a constructed wetland program, recently implemented at Holloman AFB may provide different habitat options than are currently unavailable on WSMR for resident birds and migrating waterfowl.
- The Bureau of Land Management (BLM), Las Cruces District Office manages areas within the Tularosa Basin from the Valley of Fires Recreation Area, west of Carrizozo, to joint management of the McGregor Range within Fort Bliss. McGregor Range is a multiple-use area open to grazing and hunting, in accordance with the Sikes Act (16 USC 670 et seq). Military use is varied over this extensive range that includes bombing and ground maneuvers. Three Rivers Petroglyphs Site allows camping and has an interpretive trail leading to petroglyphs and partially excavated ruins of the Jornada Branch of the Mogollon culture. BLM and Holloman plan to cooperate to manage and develop the Boles Wells Water System Annex at the base of the Sacramento Mountains. Additionally, a new tactical bombing range on Otero Mesa within McGregor Range is to be constructed. Holloman AF would be the principal unit operating these missions. The BLM-administered lands are typically interspersed with state and private holdings and support some endangered and sensitive plants. The BLM and Holloman AFB have cooperated in plant surveys within the Boles Wells Water System Annex for state and federally listed species such as the Alamo Canyon beardtongue (*Penstemon alamosensis*),

Villard's pincushion cactus (*Escobaria villardii*), button cactus (*Epithelantha micromeris*), and the Sacramento prickly poppy (*Argemone pleiacantha* ssp. *pinnatisecta*).

Figure 1. Holloman AFB and surrounding sites

- The Lincoln National Forest is located immediately east of Alamogordo in the Sacramento Mountains. Camping, hunting, hiking, timber harvests, and livestock grazing occur in the forest. The Sacramento Mountains provide a critical source of potable water for Holloman AFB and Alamogordo. The Mexican Spotted Owl (*Strix occidentalis lucida*), a Federally-listed threatened species is protected and managed following federal guidelines ([50 CFR Part 17](#)). The Sacramento Mountains thistle (*Cirsium vinaceum*), Kuenzler's hedgehog cactus (*Echinocereus fendleri* var. *kuenzler*), Todsens pennyroyal (*Hedeoma todsenii*), Sacramento prickly-poppy, and Peregrine Falcon (*Falco peregrinus*) are other federally listed species are also native to the Sacramento Mountains. The USDA Forest Service works with outdoor recreation (49 SVS/SVRO) at Holloman AFB through cooperative recreation agreements that provide both directed and self-directed activities.
- [Oliver Lee State Park](#) is located in Dog Canyon, 15 miles south of Alamogordo between the north and south Boles Wells Water Annex Systems. The canyon has diverse plant and animal life that are attracted to the springs and seeps. Facilities include camping sites, picnicking, hiking trails, and a visitor center. The park preserves and illustrates some of the history of turn-of-the-century ranch life found in Otero Country, particularly between 1885 and 1941, when the Oliver and Winnie Lee family owned much of the county.
- The Mescalero Indian Reservation is located approximately 25 miles east of the city of Tularosa and is surrounded by the Lincoln National Forest. The Tribe conducts timber thinnings, timber harvests, prescribed burns, and livestock grazing in its ponderosa pine and mixed-conifer forests.
- [Fort Bliss](#), administered by the US Army, comprises approximately 1.1 million acres south of Holloman AFB, extending into Texas. The base functions as a training area for the army, with ground maneuver activities occurring in the basin and adjacent mesas. One of the largest extents of black grama-blue grama (*Bouteloua eriopoda-Bouteloua gracilis*) grasslands in the state occurs on Otero Mesa, a large east-dipping tableland located south of the southern foothills of the Sacramento Mountains. Many sensitive and endemic species reside within this diverse landscape, which includes basin dunelands and montane forests. McGregor Range is jointly managed for multiple-use (mostly grazing and hunting) by the BLM. Extensive studies on vegetation and fauna are ongoing.

History of Installation

Broad, relatively flat and open spaces, clear skies, and sparsely populated areas within the Tularosa Basin suited the purposes of military missions for developmental testing of early space technology. Perhaps for some of these same reasons, long before this area was acquired for defense purposes, early man created solar observatories in the nearby Sacramento Mountains. One of these, Walley's Dome, has several upright rock formations supporting a horizontal rock slab that appears to be astronomically aligned to

record annual solstice events (Eidenbach 1981). The father of modern rocketry, Robert Goddard, also found the physical landscape of New Mexico favorable for his research near Roswell, New Mexico, throughout the 1930s. Today, a national center for ground-based observations of the sun, the National Solar Observatory, is located at Sunspot, New Mexico in the Sacramento Mountains.

Not until the Legacy Resource Management Program (Public Law 101-511) were archives explored and field explorations made to uncover the primary role Holloman AFB contributed to the beginnings of space exploration. Under the LRMP on Holloman AFB for National Register Surveys, a Thematic Survey of Early Missile, Instrumentation and Test Objects was conducted (Mattson and Tagg 1995). Following guidelines set by the LRMP, the objective of this survey was to "inventory, protect and conserve the physical and literary property and relics of the DoD connected with the origins and development of the Cold War" (Mattson and Tagg 1995). This research reveals that Holloman AFB was conceived nine months after the United States declared war against Germany, Italy and Japan and was thereafter integral in the early stages of the United States space program throughout the Cold War.

On 6 February 1942, the Alamogordo Army Air Field (AAAF) was established, and construction began on an extensive bombing and gunnery range later known as the Alamogordo Bombing and Gunnery Range. Facilities were designed after the Royal Air Force base, used in the British Training Program for World War II bomber crews. The Royal Air Force base is typically a cantonment area, west area and north area.

On 16 July 1945, in the northwest corner of the Alamogordo Bombing and Gunnery Range (now WSMR), the first atomic bomb was detonated at the Trinity Site. In 1946, more lands became available within the Tularosa Basin and the base was reassigned to a missile development facility. By 1947, the Air Force became a separate service and AAAF was transferred to the Air Material Command to conduct guided missile programs. On 13 January 1948, the base was renamed Holloman AFB after Col. George V. Holloman, an early pioneer in guided missile development. The range was 64 miles long, running north and south, and 38 miles wide. At this time, the Army Ordnance Corps built White Sands Proving Ground (WSPG) with a range just south of these lands. The combined range of these facilities was 100 miles long and 40 miles wide (Mattson and Tagg 1995). Under army management, on 1 September 1952, the Holloman AFB Bombing and Gunnery Range was combined with the Army Range to form the 'Integrated White Sands Range'.

From 1952 to 1970 missile development and testing included the Snark, Matador, Mace, Falcon, Aerobee, JB-2 Loom, and Firebee. High speed sled tests, high altitude balloon projects, and Aeromedical Field Laboratory experiments were also conducted. During this time the Central Inertial Guidance Test Facility and the Radar Target Scatter Test Facility were developed. The Primate Research Facility trained the first chimpanzee (HAM) to make a suborbital flight and the first chimpanzee (Enos) to orbit the earth. In 1972 the base was taken over by Tactical Air Command (TAC) and became primarily a fighter base with some developmental testing continued. Tactical Training Command

Holloman was inactivated and replaced by the 833rd Air Division on Dec. 1, 1990. On Nov. 15, 1991 command responsibility passed from the 833rd Air Division to the 49th Fighter Wing. Today, the 49th Fighter Wing provides leadership to the installation. Two projects begun during the Cold War continue on the base, the High Speed Test Track and the Primate Research Lab.

Current Military Mission

Maintaining over 50 years of 49er excellence by providing:

- *Mission-Ready Forces and Equipment to Meet Worldwide Contingencies*
- *The Best Training For Our People and International Aircrews*
- *Quality Support For All Base Personnel, Associate Units, and the Local Community*

The 49th Fighter Wing supports national security objectives as directed by the Joint Chiefs of Staff with F-117 Nighthawks and HH-60G helicopters. The wing can rapidly mobilize and deploy worldwide to meet peacetime and wartime contingencies. In addition, the wing conducts fighter fundamentals training for selected allied nation aircrews and the F-4 initial training and fighter weapons instructor courses for German Air Force aircrews. The wing is designated as a support unit for space shuttle launches when White Sands Space Harbor is selected as the abort once around (AOA) site. The 49th Fighter Wing provides morale, welfare, and administrative support for over 6,000 assigned personnel.

Military Activities

Holloman AFB is one of the Air Combat Command Resources under the 12th Air Force. The 12th Air Force Headquarters is at Davis-Monthan AFB, Ariz. The 12th controls ACC forces based in the western United States and Panama and is the air component for U.S. Southern Command and U.S. Strategic Command (battle management). It also has Joint Task Force/Battle Management responsibilities for U.S. Strategic Command. Holloman AFB is home to the 49th Fighter Wing: F-117A, T-38, HH-60G and German F-4E. The 49th Fighter Wing provides leadership to Holloman AFB, having three active runways and seven flying squadrons.

The 49th Fighter Wing units are (Figure 2): the 49th Fighter Wing Staff Agencies, 49th Operations Group, 49th Logistics Group, 49th Support Group, 49th Medical Group, and the 49th Material Maintenance Group. A summary of the leadership and groups of the 49th Fighter Wing are provided below; information was taken from the [49th Fighter Wing Home Page](#). Consult the 49th Fighter Wing Home Page for comprehensive information and contacts.

The 49th Wing Staff Agencies include agencies that make up the wing commander's staff. The staff agencies are the Inspector General, Staff Judge Advocate, Public Affairs, Wing Operations Center, Manpower-Quality Improvement, Chapel, Wing Plans and Inspections, Safety, Manpower, History, Social Actions, Environmental Office and the 49th Comptroller Squadron.

Figure 2. Holloman AFB 49th Fighter Wing Organization Chart

The 49th Operations Group operates and maintains the Air Force’s only F-117A aircraft, the world’s first combat aircraft to employ low-observable technology. In addition, the 49th Fighter Wing is responsible for training U.S. Air Force and allied aircrews in F-117A, T-38, and F-4E transition, instructor, and fighter weapons instructor courses. The *7th Fighter Squadron* serves as the transitional training unit, preparing experienced Air Force pilots for assignment to the F-117A Nighthawk. The *8th and 9th Fighter Squadrons* are designated to employ the F-117A Nighthawk in combat and maintain readiness to deploy in that role anywhere in the world, on a moment’s notice. The *20th Fighter Squadron* works in concert with the German Air Force Tactical Training Center to conduct instructor pilot and aircrew training. The 20th FS instructor pilots employ the McDonnell Douglas F-4E and F-4F Phantom II aircraft to train the German aircrews.

The *48th Rescue Squadron* is one of only six combat search and rescue units in the Department of Defense. The unit’s primary mission is to develop and maintain a combat rescue capability for worldwide deployment for all branches of the Armed Forces and to provide day or night-time low visibility extractions in either low or high-threat

environments. When not deployed, the Holloman unit also supports non-military search and rescue operations in neighboring communities and areas. The *49th Training Squadron* provides registrar, academic and simulator support for the F-117A Nighthawk upgrade program, and the German air force F-4E and F-4F foreign military sales training program. Finally, the *49th Operations Support Squadron (OSS)* is tasked to provide operational and administrative support to the various squadrons, which make up the 49th Operations Group. Five flights provide the 49th OSS with weapons and training flight coordinates, weather information, intelligence support, airfield operations, and material maintenance.

The 49th Logistics Group provides supplies, equipment, transportation and maintenance services needed to sustain the 49th Fighter Wing in wartime and peace. The group is responsible for intermediate level maintenance and repair of aircraft, propulsion, avionics and accessory systems. Additionally, the 49th Logistics Group directs aircraft maintenance qualification and on-the-job ancillary training. The *49th Logistics Support Squadron* provides thorough planning, comprehensive training, and effective resource management tools to prepare, support, and deploy forces and equipment at Holloman and around the world. The squadron is composed of three flights: Training Management, Logistics Plans and Logistics Operations. The *49th Maintenance Squadron* supplies quality production and repair of both on- and off-equipment systems and critical support equipment components for assigned aircraft. Additionally, the squadron's craftsmen provide crash recovery and transient alert support throughout southern New Mexico. The *49th Supply Squadron* supports the 49th Fighter Wing and its four weapon systems: F-117A Nighthawk, T-38A Talon, F-4E/F Phantom II, and HH-60G Pave Hawk aircraft. It also supports a research and development test group and 34 associate units. The *49th Transportation Squadron* consists of four major flights: Vehicle Operations, Vehicle Maintenance, Traffic Management and Combat Readiness and Resources. They provide transportation resources and training necessary to mobilize, deploy, and sustain the 49th Fighter Wing. The squadron manages and maintains the base vehicle fleet; arranges for the movement of freight, passengers, and personal property; and supports all transiting strategic airlift aircraft. The *49th Contracting Squadron* activities range from normal commodities, to services and construction, to highly complex contracts for operation and support of aircraft maintenance and support for several labs and test organizations. The squadron manages the small business program and works closely with local economic development agencies.

The 49th Support Group provides high quality engineering, communications, security, personnel and services support to the 49th Fighter Wing and its 26 associate units while maintaining a capability to deploy worldwide to support the wing's combat mission. The *49th Mission Support Squadron* consists of five flights: Military Personnel, Civilian Personnel, Education and Training, Mayo Professional Military Education Center, Family Support Center. The squadron provides administrative, personnel, and educational services to support military, civilian, and retired personnel. The *49th Civil Engineer Squadron* operates seven major flights: Operations, Fire Protection, Engineering, Readiness, Family Housing, Environmental and Explosive Ordnance Disposal. The squadron provides diverse services that include maintaining all Holloman facilities,

environmental restoration, and disposing of hazardous explosive ordnance. The 49th *Security Forces Squadron* provides law enforcement, security, and operational security for all base activities, including the F-117A and space satellite communications equipment. They also prepare policy positions on security, protection and law enforcement programs for the base and provide combat arms training to Holloman personnel. The 49th *Communications Squadron* maintains airfield radar and radio systems, navigational aids, meteorological radars and sensors, small computer systems, and cryptographic equipment, including secure telephones, land mobile radios, and deployable communications equipment. The squadron also manages and operates the base message center, telephone switchboard and systems, cellular phones, radio frequencies, base communications security program (COMSEC), and base visual information services, including the photo lab, graphics shop, deployable electronic imaging center and gun camera film-processing facility. The 49th *Services Squadron* provides leisure-time facilities and equipment to meet the social and recreational needs of the Holloman community. Leisure-time facilities include the officers club, enlisted club, community activity center, outdoor recreation, youth programs, bowling center, sports and fitness center, golf course, library, child development center, skills development center, auto skills development center, aero club, Flying "H" equestrian facility and sports range.

The 49th Medical Group maintains an air transportable hospital and three clinics in combat-ready status. In addition, it provides comprehensive healthcare and physiological training while promoting wellness and fitness through a proactive health promotions program. The four units are: the 49th Dental Squadron, 49th Medical Operations Squadron, 49th Aerospace Medical Squadron, and 49th Medical Support Squadron.

The 49th Material Maintenance Group is responsible for the storage, inspection, repair, deployment, and accountability of Bare Base assets belonging to Air Combat Command and the United States Central Command Air Forces. The group responds worldwide for the deployment, setup, operation, maintenance, teardown and reconstitution of equipment in support of contingencies, exercises, counterdrug operations, and other higher headquarters-directed requirements. Additionally, group personnel instruct other Department of Defense personnel in deployed Bare Base operations.

Facilities and Tenants

Holloman Air Force Base covers approximately 20,500 ha (51,000 acres) having 12.2% in developed lands and the remaining in undeveloped lands. Developed areas were calculated using satellite imagery. The greatest development occurs within the cantonment area and activities associated with the Test Track. Acreage counts differ between Holloman GIS layers and existing records held in Real Property. For the purposes of this report, values are calculated from GIS layers (Figure 3). For reference

purposes, Real Property counts are shown in the following table (Table 1) alongside GIS calculations.

Table 1. Holloman AFB Acreage Counts

Area of Interest	Holloman Real Property (Acres)	Holloman GIS (Acres)
Main Base	50,507.54	50,762.54
Main Base East Easement	1,400.00	1,372.17
Main Base West Easement	340.00	332.15
Main Base State Owned		42.11
Boles Wells Water System Annex	7,411.00	6,922.77

In support of military activities, Holloman has approximately 8.6 million square feet of building structures that include 1,526 family housing units and 1,900 dormitory spaces. Current staffing levels include 500 officers, 4,110 enlisted persons, and 960 civilian personnel.

Figure 3. Ownership and Acreage on Holloman AFB
Areas in hectares are in bold and acres are in parenthesis.

46th Test Group

The 46th Test Group is the largest tenant unit at Holloman Air Force Base. The 46th Test Group is part of the Air Force Material Command and is a unit of the 46th Test Wing, Air Force Development Test Center, Eglin AFB, FL. The Test Group's mission is to operate world-class test facilities for high speed sled track testing, navigation and guidance system testing, radar signature measurements, and weapon systems flight testing including airspace control of the White Sands Missile Range (WSMR).

The Test Group includes the 586th Flight Test Squadron, 846th Test Squadron, 746th Test Squadron, and the RATSCAT facility located on WSMR. The *586th Flight Test Squadron* is responsible for all Air Force flight test activity conducted over WSMR. The squadron owns and operates fighter and cargo aircraft in support of avionics, guidance/navigation, and weapon system testing. The *846th Test Squadron* operates the Holloman High Speed Test Track, which simulates selected portions of the flight environment under accurately programmed and instrumented conditions. The *846th Test Squadron* is DoD's "Center of Expertise" for all ejection seat testing and the lead facility for all supersonic tracks (Ackerman 1998). The *746th Test Squadron* is responsible for the test, evaluation, and verification of Global Positioning Systems (GPS) user equipment and GPS Integrated Navigation Systems. The *Radar Target Scatter (RATSCAT) Division* has two facilities located on WSMR. Their remote locations are ideal for testing highly sensitive targets producing monostatic and bistatic radar cross-section (RCS) measurements (*see* Chapter 4 - Geographically Separated Units).

4th Space Surveillance Squadron

The 4th Space Surveillance Squadron (SPSS) is a geographically separated unit assigned to the 21st Space Wing, Peterson Air Force, Colorado, and provides space surveillance capabilities for national command authorities and unified commanders world-wide. The 4th SPSS provides the critical link between squadrons and command authorities to ensure the space surveillance data are available. The squadron operates and maintains mobile space surveillance, communications, and data relay systems that support the Commander-in-Chief of U.S. Space Command and theater commanders during contingency operations. The unit conducts a number of mobile and transportable operations that provide critical connections between the National Command Authorities, U.S. Space Command, 14th Air Force, and squadron level elements. The professionals of the 4th SPSS support the warfighter by establishing dedicated inter-and intra-theater links for critical space surveillance data and communications. There are more than 9,000 man-made objects in orbit above the earth, ranging in size from a dime to the Mir space station. Whenever a space mission is launched, the squadron ensures it has a clear path into orbit.

Detachment 1, 82nd Aerial Targets Squadron

The Detachment 1, 82nd Aerial Targets Squadron provides full-scale aerial target support on WSMR for Department of Defense research, development and test projects. This includes supervision and monitoring the operations and maintenance on QF-106 and QF-4 drones. This squadron is a detachment of the 475th Weapons Evaluation Group, Tyndall AFB, Fla. Project support includes the advanced medium-range air-to-air missile (AMRAAM), Patriot, Chaparral, Stinger missiles and many more. The detachment is transitioning to the QF-4 aircraft.

German Air Force Tactical Training Center

The following information is taken from a report from the Congressional Research Service - The Library of Congress, *CRS Report for Congress German Military Presence in the United States: The Case of Holloman Air Force Base*, Karen Donfried, Specialist in European Affairs Foreign Affairs and National Defense Division.

In the fall of 1990, the United States offered the German Air Force (GAF) the opportunity to expand training at Holloman AFB, which led to the location of the German Air Force Tactical Training Center (TTC) at Holloman AFB. In addition to the F-4 Phantom jets that had been transferred to Holloman from George AFB, the United States agreed that the Germans could station German Tornado jets there. In May 1994, a memorandum of understanding was signed which covered construction of the German Air Force Tactical Training Element and the stationing of 12 Tornado air-to-ground and air defense fighters and roughly 300 military and civilian employees, along with their families. Known as Holloman I, these planes and personnel are part of a weapons instructor and flight training program; the Germans invested about 62 million German marks (\$40 million) to construct the necessary infrastructure, including hangers and maintenance facilities. On May 1, 1996, U.S. Defense Secretary Perry and German Defense Minister Ruhe activated the German Tactical Training Center at Holloman AFB. Starting in October 1999, the German Air Force will send an additional 30 Tornado jets and 600 military and civilian employees to Holloman to further expand training. This will allow the Germans to perform all basic and weapons systems training for Tornados at Holloman AFB and thus ensure "comprehensive training." This program is referred to as Holloman II. The Germans will invest another 175 million German marks (about \$114 million) to construct hangers, a noise suppression facility for engine test runs, a flight simulator, and housing for the permanent and training staff. Upon completion of Holloman II in the fall of 1999, 24 F-4 Phantoms, 42 Tornados, and approximately 900 German Air Force staff members will be stationed at the TTC at Holloman AFB.

The Germans find many aspects of New Mexico, and in particular, Holloman AFB that are not available to German pilots at home. Given New Mexico's sparse population and the existing special use air space, German pilots have a greater opportunity to conduct flying training at low altitudes and high speeds. They can use the full array of radar jamming equipment and conduct live bombing exercises. Second, the weather is much better in New Mexico than in Germany. Training continuity is ensured, because a pilot can fly a much greater number of hours per month or year than he can in Germany. In New Mexico, pilots can train all year long. Finally, Holloman AFB is relatively close to Fort Bliss, Texas, the headquarters for German Air Force operations in North America.

Chimpanzee Breeding and Research Colony

The Coulston Foundation

P.O. Box 1027

Holloman Air Force Base, NM 88330-1027

(505) 479-9220

FAX: (505) 479-4103

The basic research mission of the Chimpanzee Breeding and Research Colony is to develop vaccines and conduct infectious disease studies, as well as research in primate reproduction. A particular focus of research is retrovirology and hepatitis in chimpanzees and macaques. The colony consists of 1,363 macaques and 325 chimpanzees. Studies of the efficacy and safety of potential new pharmaceuticals are performed, including routine and special toxicology, metabolism, pharmacokinetics, residue, and immunogenicity.

CHAPTER 3 - NATURAL SETTING

Texas horned lizard (*Phrynosoma cornutum*)
Photo by: Wyman Meinzer

Views from Holloman AFB are spectacular. To the east rise the Sacramento Mountains, an impressive range that attains an elevation of 3,658m (12,003 feet), nearly 4,000 feet above the surrounding basin floor and extends north and south as far as the eye can see. Parallel to the Sacramento 54 kilometers (33.5 miles) to the west are the San Andres Mountains, equally extensive in reach to the north and south. Down dropped within Between these two ranges lie the Tularosa Basin and the White Sands. Sands from this ancient lake bed continue eastward to meet the most distal alluviated basin fill of the Sacramento Mountains. The nearly flat plains are dissected by broad natural drainages that terminate into the dunes seasonally filling small playa depressions. In the midst of rich desert floral and faunal diversity is Holloman Air Force Base.

Climate

Holloman AFB is located in a semi-arid region within the northern portion of the Chihuahuan Desert (Schmidt 1986). Its climate resembles other semi-arid regions with warm to hot summer days, cool nights, and mild winters. December through March are the coolest months with average temperatures ranging from 41-46 (°F) ([Appendix C.1.](#)). Freezing temperatures are common from late November through early March (Noyes and Schmader 1988). Snowfall averages 12.2 cm (4.8 inches) annually and occurs primarily between the months of December and February ([Appendix C.2.](#)). July is typically the hottest month with average temperatures of 81 (°F) and mean maximum temperatures of 93 (°F). Daytime temperatures in summer commonly reach 100 (°F). In the Tularosa basin, evapotranspiration is usually high due to dry air, large daily solar radiation totals, seasonally high winds, and warm temperatures. The annual evaporation rate at Holloman AFB is between 165 and 178 cm (65 and 70 inches) with 102 to 114 cm (40 to 45 inches) lost from May to October (Bennett 1986).

Seasonal fluctuation in precipitation rates is a result of prevailing wind directions, which can bring in frontal storms from the north or the Pacific or Caribbean cyclonic systems. Holloman averages 21 cm (8.58 inches) of rainfall annually ([Appendix C.1.](#)). Nearly half this amount falls within the months of July and September, referred to as the summer monsoons. Monsoon thunderstorms are generally short in duration and high in intensity. Occurrences are highly variable from year to year and one or two short-term events may contain a large percentage of the net annual precipitation (Anschuetz et al. 1990). Low precipitation amounts and high rates of evapotranspiration deplete the soil of moisture making summer rains critical to the survival of plants.

Winds are also seasonally variable, occurring at peak speeds in the spring. When the ground heats, intensifying convection this diverts stronger winds aloft down to the ground, where they maintain horizontal momentum (Bennett 1986). The highest wind speeds occur from April through July, reaching median wind speeds of 25 mph. At 13-18 mph velocities are great enough to pick up large amounts of dust, and winds from 32-46 mph will break twigs from trees. During the month of May, wind velocities are greater than 17 mph approximately 90% of the time ([Appendix C.3.](#)). Prevailing winds are from the west from February to June. During the months of July through September the prevailing winds are south to southeasterly and from October through January winds are from the north.

Topography and Geomorphology

Holloman AFB is located in the Mexican Highland section of the Basin and Range Province. These landscapes were formed by Rocky Mountain orogenic processes during the late Pennsylvanian or early Permian period (Hawley 1986; Noyes and Schmader 1988). Within the Mexican Highland section lies the Tularosa Basin, a broad, internally

drained basin situated between two north-south trending fault-block mountain ranges (Figure 4). The watershed for the Tularosa basin covers 1,766,162 ha (4,364,187 acres). The principal range defining the western edge of the basin is the San Andres Mts., a west-tilted fault block that rises in elevation to 2733.4 m (8,968 ft) at Salinas Peak (Muldavin and Mehlhop 1992). The corresponding east-tilted fault block is the Sacramento Mountains reaching 3,658 m (12,003 ft) at Sierra Blanca Peak. During Pleistocene glacials, Sierra Blanca Peak was the southernmost glaciated peak in the continental United States (Hawley 1986). The Tularosa Basin ranges in elevation from 1,175 m (3,855 ft) in the southern range to 1,558 m (5,000 ft) in the northern section of the range. The topographic relief between Sierra Blanca Peak and the Tularosa Basin constitutes the greatest local relief in New Mexico (Hawley 1986).

The San Andres and Sacramento Mountains are Precambrian age granites overlain with Pennsylvanian and Permian lithologic units. These north-south trending mountains dip gradually to the west and east, respectively, with steep mountain fronts joining the piedmont and basin fill deposits of the Tularosa Basin. The basin landscape is relatively flat, distinguished by dunes, lava flows, gypsum lake deposits, and alkali flats. The nearly level plains are occasionally interrupted by isolated, discontinuous mountain ranges such as Phillips Hills and the Jarilla and Franklin Mountains that rise abruptly from broad, alluvium-filled basins.

Tularosa Peak is the highest point within the Main Base reaching an elevation of 1,320 m (4,330 feet), the lowest point being the extreme southern tip of Stinky Playa at 1,224 m (4,015 feet). Average elevation is 1,240 m (4,086 feet). The major landforms of the Main Base include a small Permian Age rock outcrop, gypsum sand dunes, flat to gently sloping alluvial plains, and alkali flats and playas. Tularosa Peak is a solitary rock outcrop located in the far northeast corner of the base. Rising 380 m (1,246 feet) above the surrounding plains, it is girded by colluvium and alluviated materials. Gypsum dunes cover the western portion of the base and form the easternmost extent of the white sands. A line of sharp crests form the leeward side of the boundary of the active dunes which abruptly grade into slightly undulating interdune grasslands and shrublands. The alluvial plains are dissected from east to west by at least nine prominent intermittent streams that typically terminate on the western portion of the base, creating broad drainage bottoms. Large alkali flats and playas have formed at the end of these arroyos and small permanent and ephemeral lakes and ponds are scattered across the basin floor. The most prominent of these is Lake Holloman, a Pleistocene lakebed, lying above Highway 70 and containing water throughout the year. Stinky Playa is separated from Lake Holloman by a dam and intermittently holds water. The waterbodies were originally the terminus for one of the arroyos but have subsequently been altered by dams and earthen canals that alter flows and holding capacity (*See Chapter 3-Hydrology*). The system of playas west of the golf course and east of Lake Holloman have also undergone extensive management. The largest of these, Lagoon G, is surrounded by an earthen dam and is part of the constructed wetlands wastewater treatment facility (*See Chapter 6-Wetlands*).

The Boles Wells Water System Annex lies on the Sacramento Mts. bajada. Elevations range from 1,246 m (4,087 feet) in the northern Boles Well Field to 1,424 m (4,671 feet)

extending eastward into the alluvial fan. Boles Well Field is nearly level and is covered with spreading sand sheets and scattered playas. The sections south of Boles Well Field (Douglas San Andres Well Fields) are situated higher within the alluvial fans and are composed of cobbly to gravelly undivided sediments dissected by numerous ephemeral arroyos.

Soils and Geology

The soils on the main base are basin fill deposits formed primarily from alluvial and eolian processes. All soils have a high gypsum and salt content, primarily due to the eastern migration of gypsum sands from White Sands Missile Range and White Sands National Monument. Alluvial floodplains on the eastern and southern portions of the base are basin fill deposits from the western slope of the Sacramento Mountains. Subsoils are formed from sediments of Lake Otero, a Pleistocene lake formed during a climatic cycle of increased moisture. During periods of low precipitation this large lake, reaching a depth of several hundred feet, would contract and leave salt and gypsum evaporites. These soils overlay Mesozoic and Paleozoic sedimentary rocks (Wilkins 1986).

Soils on Holloman AFB were mapped by the Soil Conservation Service (now the Natural Resources Conservation Service) on two separate soil surveys; one north of Douglas Road (Neher, et al. 1976), the other south of Douglas Road (Derr, et al. 1981), which includes the Well Fields (Figures 5 and 6).

The Main Base has three primary soil types: Several associations and complexes of Holloman, Gypsum Land, and Yesum soils, located in the flats; Dune Land, found in the White Sands dunes, and Mead silty clay loam soil, found in the alluvial floodplains (including most jurisdictional wetlands). None of the soil types is very productive, due to high gypsum and salt content, and all are highly subject to both wind and water erosion when the vegetation is sparse or the soil exposed.

Figure 4. Holloman AFB within the Tularosa Basin

Map shows Holloman AFB located within the center of the Tularosa Basin between the San Andres Mountains and the Sacramento Mountains. .

The Holloman-Gypsum land-Yesum soil complex (HOB) represents the most common soil type, covering approximately 66.5 percent of the base. It is a complex of shallow and deep well-drained soils and exposed gypsum. The soils have less than 5 percent slope and were deposited by both water-borne and wind-borne soil particles. The Holloman soil (approximately 35% of the complex) has a light brown surface layer of very fine sandy loam about 13 inches deep. White gypsum underlies the surface soils. Gypsum land, consisting of less than one inch of very fine sandy loam overlies white gypsum and is found mostly along the margins of arroyos, making up less than 30% of the mapping unit. The Yesum surface soil is a light brown very fine sandy loam about 3

inches thick, underlain by brown or pink fine sandy loam extending deeper than 60 inches. This soil makes up approximately 20 percent of the complex. The remaining 15 percent of the complex consists of small areas of Prelo, Largo, Tome, and Bluepoint soils. These mixed alluvial and eolian sediments lie upland to the east from Holloman and are the source for the alluviated red beds found in drainages such as Hay Draw.

The Duneland Yesum association comprises approximately 14.7 percent of the Main Base and lies north and south of the Active Dune Land Gypsum type. Both mapping units cover the western portion of the north half of the base, lying predominantly west of the Test Track. The Duneland Yesum association is 55 percent active dune and 30 percent Yesum very fine sandy loam. The Yesum soils are wind deposited, partly-stabilized gypsum dunes. The Active Dune Land is highly unstable and continually shifts, moving in a predominantly northeasterly direction. The dunes are primarily made up of very fine gypsum crystals from Lake Otero, a relict Pleistocene lakebed.

The Mead silty clay loam (MEA) covers approximately 4.5 percent of the Main Base. This poorly drained soil is limited to deeply incised drainages and alkali flats and playas. The soil type consists of fine textured silty soils on less than 1 percent slope. The soils contain a high salt content because of frequent flooding and become extremely sticky when wet. They are characterized by a 5-inch thick surface layer of reddish-brown silty clay or clay loam, underlain by approximately 48 inches of clay high in salt. Beyond 48 inches deep, the subsoils are formed from lakebed sediments. About 15 percent of the Mead mapping unit consists of gully sides or knolls with Holloman soils or gypsum land.

The Rock Land (RL) mapping unit is found only on Tularosa Peak covering less than 1 percent of the Holloman lands. This peak is an intrusive volcanic formation capped with limestone (Doleman 1988) comprised of sedimentary units of the Yeso Formation (Dane and Bachman 1965). This Permian Age unit is 35 percent rock outcrop, 30 percent colluvium, and about 20 to 25 percent in shallow to very shallow soils. The remaining 10 to 15 percent of the unit are mixed alluvium and deeper soils found at further distances from the uplifted hill.

The soils in the Boles Well Field were formed on the lower parts of the alluvial fan piedmont at the base of large drainages. These nearly level soils are formed from alluvial and eolian materials deposited by periodic runoff from upland areas. The Douglas and San Andres Well Fields cover more elevated units of the alluvial fan. These soils are deep and gravelly throughout (Figure 6).

The topographically lowest units within the Boles Well Field are the nearly level Mimbres-Tome association (MTA) and the Tome silt loam (TDB). These deep, well drained soils are formed in medium textured alluvium derived from limestone and siltstone having some calcareous eolian material. Permeability is moderately low and they may be flooded for short periods following intense rainstorms. Combined these soils cover 28.5 percent of the entire BWWSA. The Largo-Orgal complex (LGB) is on the lower part of dissected toe slopes at the base of the piedmont covering the eastern extent of the Boles Well Field and cover only 5 percent of the entire BWWSA.

Permeability of these soils is moderately rapid and water capacity is low. The remainder of the BWWSA is covered by the Nickel-Tencee association that occurs on pediment toe slopes and alluvial fans. These landscapes are deeply dissected by numerous drainages. The soils are formed in highly calcareous, coarse textured sediment, derived from limestone. These soils are strongly calcareous throughout and moderately alkaline with moderate permeability and very low water capacity. Unmapped areas are at the eastern boundary of the Well Fields near the Lincoln National Forest lands.

Figure 5. Soil map of Main Base

Map shows major soil units for the Main Base (Neher, R.E. et al. 1976; Derr, et al. 1981)

Figure 6. Soil Map of Boles Wells Water System Annex
Map shows soil units for the BWWSA (Derr, et al. 1981)

Hydrology

The only permanent water in the Tularosa Basin is found in small streams between Alamogordo and Three Rivers (Garza and McLean 1977; Anschuetz et al. 1990). There are no perennial streams within Holloman AFB or in the nearby surrounding landscape; however, there are at least nine prominent east-west drainages that receive intermittent

flows during seasonal thunderstorms (Figure 9). These drainages are broad and deeply entrenched where extensive downcutting has occurred by as much as 15 m (50 feet) below the basin floor. A total of 351.9 ha (867.88 acres) of jurisdictional [waters of the U.S.](#), including 48.6 ha (119.98 acres) of wetlands and 302.9 ha (747.9 acres) of non-wetland waters, has been identified within HAFB ([USAF 1996](#)). The largest of these drainages is the Lost River drainage system, including Malone Draw, Carter Draw, and Ritas Draw. Prior to extensive management of the surface topography and construction of U.S. Highway 70/82, Dillard Draw emptied into the Main Base, creating a network of alkali flats and ephemeral playas including what are now Lake Holloman, Stinky Playa, and Lagoon G. Construction activities have disrupted the natural flow of this wetland ecosystem.

The primary hydrologic processes in this desert ecosystem are summer monsoons and large storm events falling on the rocky slopes of the Sacramento Mountains. Most of the thunderstorm precipitation is absorbed quickly into the gravels and sandy surfaces at the base of the alluvial fans. At the terminus of the alluvial fan channels, ephemeral playa-like depressions can hold water for several weeks, creating hydric soil conditions ([USAF 1996](#)). "A hydric soil is a soil that formed under conditions of saturation, flooding, or ponding long enough during the growing season to develop anaerobic conditions in the upper part." (Federal Register, July 13, 1994). These hydric conditions create desert wetland habitat for native plants and animals. Alkali flats occur most notably within the low lying area between Lake Holloman and Lagoon G but also are dispersed sporadically throughout the various drainages. These flats are generally not densely vegetated but may have an algal layer on the surface ([USAF 1996](#)). During the growing season, which corresponds with summer monsoons, these vegetated and bare flats provide important wildlife habitat and essential wetland feeding areas for waterfowl.

The historic desert wetland ecosystem which existed between Lagoon G and Lake Holloman is currently being converted to a constructed wetland to provide valuable habitat for wildlife. This has developed a network of earthen berms and channels to direct stormwater runoff from the cantonment area along with treated wastewater effluents into these alkali flats (*See* Chapter.6, Wetlands). Flows into the completed constructed wetlands began in November, 1997.

Groundwater recharge occurs largely from rainfall and snowmelt in the Sacramento and San Andres mountains, where intermittent streamflow infiltrates into the coarse, loosely consolidated alluvial fan material. Although streamflow is greatest during the summer monsoons, most recharge occurs in the winter months (McLean 1970; Wilkins 1986). Recharge for the Tularosa Basin is estimated to be greater than 100,000 acre-ft per year with the greatest portion accumulating at the base of the Sacramento Mountains (Meinzer and Hare 1915). HAFB lies within the groundflow gradient from the Sacramento foothills to the lowest point within the basin, Lake Lucero, to the southwest of the Main Base. Groundwater at the margins of the basin within the bajada of the Sacramento Mountains grade from fresh water (containing less than 1,000 milligrams per liter [mg/L] total dissolved solids [TDS]) to highly alkaline sources near the center of the basin with more than 100,000 mg/L TDS ([USAF 1996](#)).

A recent study reported that the Boles Well Field area contained approximately 2.21 ha (5.47 acres) and 8,409 m (27,589 linear feet) of [jurisdictional waters of the U.S.](#), including 0.29 ha (0.72 acres) of wetlands and 1.92 ha (4.75 acres) of non-wetland waters of the U.S ([USAF 1996](#)). These water resources include one non-vegetated ephemeral basin, one vegetated ephemeral basin, and one permanently flooded pond. The remainder of the BWWSA has not been surveyed for jurisdictional water resources. These lands south of the Boles Well Field are dissected by many ephemeral arroyos. The BWWSA groundwater is the primary source for potable water for HAFB.

Ranking Sensitive Species

Endangered, threatened, and sensitive species of New Mexico are variously tracked by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, the New Mexico Department of Game and Fish, the New Mexico Forestry Division - Energy, Minerals and Natural Resources Department, and The Nature Conservancy through the New Mexico Natural Heritage Program. (*See Science/Natural Resource Abbreviations for an alphabetical listing*)

The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service maintains a list of Federally protected species. This list is published in the Federal Register and includes the status of endangerment according to the [Endangered Species Act](#) (16 USC 1531 et seq). This law was established in 1973 and defined categories for endangered and threatened species. New Mexico falls within the jurisdiction of the [U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service Southwest Region](#). The key to federally listed and candidate species is as follows:

LISTED SPECIES (50 CFR 17.11 and 17.12):

Listed Endangered (LE). Taxa in danger of Extinction throughout all or a significant portion of their range.

Listed Threatened (LT). Taxa likely to be classified as Endangered within the foreseeable future throughout all or a significant portion of their range.

Proposed Endangered (PE). Taxa proposed to be listed as Endangered (formal rulemaking in progress).

Proposed Threatened (PT). Taxa proposed to be listed as Threatened (formal rulemaking in progress).

CANDIDATE SPECIES (Federal Register 61(40):7596-7599, February 28, 1996). Candidate (C) species. Taxa for which the USFWS has on file sufficient information on biological vulnerability and threats to support issuance of a proposed rule to list, but issuance of the proposed rule is precluded.

The New Mexico Department of Game and Fish, under the [Wildlife Conservation Act](#), has the authority to establish rules and regulations that it may deem necessary to carry out the purpose of the Wildlife Conservation Act (17-2-37 to 17-2-46 NMSA1978) and all other acts pertaining to protected species. The Commission, established under the Act may list threatened and endangered, native and foreign wildlife. The commission may choose to adopt the federal listings in whole or in part. In addition, species may be listed within the state not yet covered under the federal listing. They also maintain a database called the Biota Information System of New Mexico ([Bison-M](#)) detailing occurrence, habitat and management of birds, fish, invertebrates, mammals, reptiles and amphibians. A current list of state listed species is included in the Natural Resources and Wildlife Endangered and Protected Species List of Threatened and Endangered Species (Title 19 Chapter 33 Part 1). The N.M. Department of Game and Fish have the following designations:

ENDANGERED - any species or subspecies whose prospects of survival or recruitment in New Mexico are in jeopardy.

THREATENED - any species or subspecies that is likely to become endangered within the foreseeable future throughout all or a significant portion of its range in New Mexico.

[The New Mexico Forestry Division - Energy, Minerals and Natural Resources Department](#) produces a list of threatened and endangered plant species for New Mexico. They have adopted a three element ranking code (The R-E-D Code). The three components are rarity, endangerment and distribution and to each element, the code is divided into three classes or degrees of concern. The classes are 1, 2 or 3 whereby the greater the number, the greater concern. The system is defined as follows:

R (RARITY)

1. rare, but found in sufficient numbers and distributed widely enough that the potential for extinction is low for the foreseeable future.
2. occurrence confined to several populations or to one extended population.
3. occurrence limited to one or a few highly restricted populations, or present in such small numbers that it is seldom reported.

E (ENDANGERMENT)

1. not endangered.
2. endangered in a portion of its range.
3. endangered throughout its range.

D (DISTRIBUTION)

1. more or less widespread outside New Mexico.
2. rare outside New Mexico.
3. endemic to New Mexico

The [New Mexico Natural Heritage Program](#) has compiled species lists to track "Possible Species of Concern" which may or may not be protected by federal or state agencies.

Numeric ranks of relative endangerment are based primarily on the number of occurrences of a species. Global ranking (G1 through G5) is established by the Nature Conservancy and State ranking (S1 through S5) is designated by the New Mexico Natural Heritage Program. In addition to numeric ranking, alpha characters are used to relate more information such as historic occurrences.

GLOBAL RANKS

- G1 Critically imperiled globally because of extreme rarity (5 or fewer occurrences or very few remaining individuals or acres) or because of some factor(s) making it especially vulnerable to extinction.
- G2 Imperiled globally because of rarity (6 to 20 occurrences or few remaining individuals or acres) or because of some factor(s) making it very vulnerable to extinction throughout its range.
- G3 Either very rare and local throughout its range or found locally (even abundantly at some of its locations) in a restricted range (ie, the Mogollon Plateau) or because of other factors making it vulnerable to extinction throughout its range; in terms of occurrences, in the range of 21 to 100.
- G4 Apparently secure globally, though it may be quite rare in parts of its range, especially at the periphery.
- G5 Demonstrably secure globally, though it may be quite rare in parts of its range, especially at the periphery.
- GH Of historical occurrence throughout its range, ie, formerly part of the established biota, with the expectation that it may be rediscovered (ie, Bachman's Warbler)
- GU Possibly in peril range-wide but status uncertain; need more information.
- GX Believed to be extinct throughout range (ie, Passenger Pigeon) with virtually no likelihood that it will be rediscovered.
- T Taxa below the species level can be ranked by placing a T-rank next to the global rank.
- Q A Q next to a global rank indicates the taxonomy of the species or taxon has been questioned

STATE RANKS

Note: Migratory species receive 2 state ranks, one for Breeding status, one for Non-breeding status.

- S1 Critically imperiled in state because of extreme rarity (5 or fewer occurrences or very few remaining individuals or acres) or because of some factor(s) making it especially vulnerable to extirpation from the state.
- S2 Imperiled in state because of rarity (6 to 20 occurrences or few remaining individuals or acres) or because of some factor(s) making it very vulnerable to extirpation from the state.
- S3 Rare or uncommon in state (on the order of 21 to 100 occurrences)
- S4 Apparently secure in state, with many occurrences.
- S5 Demonstrably secure in state and essentially ineradicable under present conditions.

SA	Accidental in NM, including species (usually birds or butterflies) recorded once or twice or only at very great intervals.
SB	Migratory species that breeds in the state.
SE	An exotic established in state; may be native elsewhere in North America; includes fish native to NM but introduced into watersheds where the species is non-native.
SH	Of historical occurrence in state, perhaps having not been verified in the past 20 years, and suspected to be still extant, or if occurrence known to be destroyed or extensively and unsuccessfully looked for
SN	Regularly occurring, usually migratory and typically non-breeding.
SR	Reported from the NM, but without persuasive documentation which would provide a basis for either accepting or rejecting (ie., misidentified specimen) the report.
SX	Apparently extirpated from New Mexico.
SXC	Apparently extirpated from its natural habitat in the state, but being held in captivity.
SU	Possibly in peril in NM but status uncertain; need more information

Vegetation

Non-random patterns of plant assemblages repeat across the landscape in response to similar environments (Silvertown and Wilson 1994; Dick-Peddie 1993). These assemblages may contain similar species and can be grouped into a category or type, called a vegetation classification (Dick-Peddie 1993). The vegetation classification used to map Holloman AFB (Muldavin et al. 1997) is based on a hierarchically organized system developed by the New Mexico Natural Heritage Program and corresponds to the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service GAP analysis classification (Muldavin 1994). The classification draws on the UNESCO Framework (Driscoll et al. 1984) and the National Vegetation Classification Standard approved by the Federal Geographic Data Committee ([FGDC Vegetation Subcommittee](#)) as well as other classifications from the Southwest (Donart et al. 1978; Brown et al. 1979; Dick-Peddie 1993). Three levels of the classification hierarchy are used to describe plant occurrences; they are the Alliance Group, Series, and Community Type. The Alliance Group (Level I below) is primarily defined by structural and morphological features along with climatic indicators. Series (Level II below) and Community Type are floristically defined, where Series is a set of Community Types related by a common dominant or set of species. Community Types are plant associations that also connote structural complexity. According to this classification, Holloman AFB is dominated by xerophytic shrubland and grassland communities having plant assemblages biogeographically related to the Great Basin and Chihuahuan Desert. Below is a subset of the classification hierarchy used in the vegetation classification .

- I. **Alliance Group:** Great Basin Microphyllous Desert Scrub
- II. **Series:** Fourwing Saltbush (*Atriplex canescens*)
- Community Type:**

- Fourwing Saltbush /Alkali Sacaton (*Sporobolus airoides*)
- Fourwing Saltbush/Sparse
- Fourwing Saltbush/Gyp Dropseed (*Sporobolus nealleyi*)
- I. Chihuahuan Desert Scrub
 - II. Creosotebush (*Larrea tridentata*)
 - Creosotebush /Sparse
 - Creosotebush / Alkali Sacaton
- I. Chihuahuan Broadleaf Deciduous Desert Scrub
 - II. Honey Mesquite (*Prosopis glandulosa*)
 - Honey Mesquite / Alkali Sacaton
 - Honey Mesquite -Fourwing Saltbush
- I. Chihuahuan Microphyllous Desert Scrub
 - II. Pickleweed (*Allenrolfea occidentalis*)
 - Pickleweed /Sparse
 - Pickleweed -Mojave Seablite (*Suaeda moquini*)
 - Pickleweed /Alkali Sacaton
 - II. Hoary Rosemarymint (*Poliomintha incana*)
 - Hoary Rosemarymint/Sandhill Muhly (*Muhlenbergia pungens*)
 - Hoary Rosemarymint/Mesa Dropseed (*Sporobolus flexuosus*)
- I. Great Basin Lowland/Swale Grassland
 - II. Alkali Sacaton
 - Alkali Sacaton /Monotypic
 - Alkali Sacaton /James' Seaheath (*Frankenia jamesii*)
- I. Chihuahuan Lowland/Swale Desert Grassland
 - II. Gyp Grama (*Bouteloua breviseta*)
 - Gyp Grama-New Mexico Bluestem (*Schizachyrium neomexicanum*)
 - Gyp Grama/Hairy Coldenia (*Tiquilia hispidissima*)
 - II. Gyp Dropseed
 - Gyp Dropseed / Hairy Coldenia
 - Gyp Dropseed - Alkali Sacaton
- I. Riparian/Wetland
 - II. Saltcedar (*Tamarix ramosissima*)
 - Saltcedar /Sparse
 - Saltcedar /Sporobolus airoides
 - II. Inland Saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*)
 - Inland Saltgrass/Monotypic
- I. Miscellaneous
 - II. Rock Outcrop
 - II. Surface Water
 - II. Golf Course
 - II. Urban Vegetation
 - II. Barren Alkaline Playa
 - II. Development/Ground Disturbance
 - II. Airfield

An innovative methodology was used to integrate field data and remotely sensed data to map vegetation at Holloman AFB (Link to Muldavin report). Satellite imagery and high resolution (two meter) color infra-red photography were merged to take advantage of the quantitative spectral qualities of Landsat Thematic Mapper data and the spatial resolution of photography. The survey data was collected from April to May, 1997 and included: community type, floristic inventory (% cover), landform, soil surface characteristics, aspect, slope, elevation, and brief descriptive comments. Field data "plots" were geographically referenced using global positioning units taken in relatively homogeneous stands, representing all community types found within the base. In addition, the geographic extent of community types represented by field plots were placed on field maps. These data were used in an iterative, computer process to model community types based on spectral data. A supervised classification was run on the merged images resulting in a vegetation classification composed of community types. These community types were then aggregated into mapping units. Mapping units include man-made features and other non-vegetated surfaces as well as groups of floristically similar community types. Twenty- four map units were defined for the Main Base and the Boles Wells Well Field. At this time, the Southern Well Fields have not been mapped. Twenty-two of these map units are included within the Main Base (Figure 7) and seven map units are within the Boles Wells Well Field (Figure 8). A more complete discussion of these mapping units is included in Chapter 7 within their respective Management Units.

A separate study was conducted from August to October, 1996, to document the floristic diversity on the Main Base. 201 plant specimens were collected and vouchered for the Holloman AFB herbarium collection. A database was developed that includes voucher number, species scientific and common name, location, elevation, habitat, frequency of occurrence, soil unit, and field notes. Over 110 species were identified during the collection period. Some annuals and forbs may have been missed since collections did not cover the spring growing season.

Figure 7. Vegetation Map of Main Base

Map shows the distribution of vegetation mapping units for the Main Base (Muldavin et al. 1998).

Figure 8. Vegetation Map of Boles Wells Wellfield

Distribution of vegetation mapping units for the Boles Wells Wellfield ([Muldavin et al. 1998](#)).

Fauna

Considering its relatively small size, Holloman AFB provides a relatively large diversity of habitats for aquatic and terrestrial species. Throughout the Tularosa Basin suitable wildlife habitat is limited due to ranching, farming, and urban and rural development. Within this patchwork, wildlife is typically left to survive in increasingly smaller pockets of native habitat further fragmented by roads and fences. Because larger areas can accommodate natural or anthropogenic disturbances easier than small, fragmented landscapes (Leslie et al. 1996), we use a regional perspective and approach to consider wildlife on Holloman. Particular species are considered in more detail under their respective management units (*See Chapter 4*).

Little work has been done to reconstruct some of the faunal history of this region; however, oral histories taken from early settlers provide some clues (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997). For instance, prairie dogs resided on Holloman AFB around the turn of the century and, with the exception of one sighting in 1988 (Doleman 1988), no other

observations have been made. Grassland habitats of the basin and its drainages have been structurally altered, probably changing the native invertebrate and small mammal communities. Because little is known of pre-settlement fauna and their environments within Holloman AFB and the Boles Wells Water System Annex, this plan discusses inventory, research, maintenance, and monitoring of contemporary fauna and their habitats.

New Mexico has one of the most diverse mammalian faunas in North America, with eighty-nine taxa described from New Mexico, ten of which are holotypes from Otero County (Frey 1996). The most common mammals at Holloman AFB are various rodents and the Black-tailed jackrabbit (*Lepus californicus*), found ubiquitously in the Great Basin Desert Scrub habitats in New Mexico (Frey and Yates, 1996). The Main Base and Boles Wells Well Field have small colonies of bats that forage for insects at the numerous playas, wetlands and riparian habitats (Johnson, et al. 1997). Bats help regulate insect populations (Ross 1967) and likely play a significant role in "insect-related ecological processes" (Chung-MacCoubrey 1996). Bats on Holloman AFB roost in abandoned and inhabited buildings. The bats identified on Holloman are: the Pallid bat (*Antrozous pallidus pallidus*), Small-footed myotis (*Myotis ciliolabrum melanorhinus*), California myotis (*Myotis californicus*), and Spotted bat (*Euderma maculatum*). Surveys conducted within habitats at the periphery of the dune found fourteen species of rodents (Table 2). The Ord's Kangaroo Rat (*Dipodomys ordii*), Desert Pocket Mouse (*Chaetodipus penicillatus*) and Plains Pocket Mouse (*Perognathus flavescens gypsi*) were found primarily within the dunes and others were found equally distributed or too few were captured to determine the habitat affinity.

Table 2. Rodents trapped within the HAFB dune periphery

Rodent surveys were conducted at the HAFB dune periphery in three vegetation types: Rosemary mint dune shrubland, Gyp grama interdune grassland, and fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed shrubland.

SCIENTIFIC NAME	COMMON NAME	HABITAT
<i>Chaetodipus penicillatus</i>	Desert Pocket Mouse	Primarily dunes
<i>Dipodomys merriami</i>	Merriam Kangaroo Rat	Equally distributed
<i>Dipodomys ordii</i>	Ord's Kangaroo Rat	Primarily dunes
<i>Mus musculus</i>	House Mouse	Too few captured to determine habitat
<i>Neotoma micropus canescens</i>	Southern Plains Woodrat	Too few captured to determine habitat
<i>Onychomys arenicola</i>	Mearn's Grasshopper Mouse	Too few captured to determine habitat
<i>Perognathus flavescens</i>	Plains Pocket Mouse	Too few captured to determine habitat
<i>Perognathus flavescens gypsi</i>	Plains Pocket Mouse (lighter pelage)	Primarily dunes
<i>Perognathus flavus</i>	Silky Pocket Mouse	Equally distributed

SCIENTIFIC NAME	COMMON NAME	HABITAT
<i>Peromyscus eremicus</i>	Cactus Mouse	Too few captured to determine habitat
<i>Peromyscus leucopus</i>	White-footed Mouse	Too few captured to determine habitat
<i>Peromyscus maniculatus</i>	Deer Mouse	Too few captured to determine habitat
<i>Reithrodontomys megalotis</i>	Western Harvest Mouse	Too few captured to determine habitat
<i>Spermophilus spilosoma</i>	Spotted Groundsquirrel	Equally distributed

The kit fox (*Vulpes macrotis neomexicanus*) inhabits the marginal and interior dunes of the White Sands (Bison-M). These foxes prey on rodents, especially kangaroo rats, within the duneland; their ranges may extend approx. 3 km (1.9 miles) from their dens. New Mexico is regarded as one of the last strongholds for the mountain lion (*Felis concolor*) and, although its present status in the state is not well known, it appears to be demonstrably secure with a G5 NMNHP rank (Findley et al. 1975). The mountain lion occupies broken and mountainous country from the Pecos River west and commonly occurs within the San Andres and Oscura Mountains (Burkett and Kamees 1996; Bison-M 1997) west of Holloman AFB. Mountain lion scat was found within Holloman AFB in 1994, near the confluence of Malone and Ritas Draws. Mule deer (*Odocoileus hemionus*) and porcupine (*Erethizon dorsatum*) have been observed near the Boles Wells Wellfield facilities. Two subspecies of mule deer are reported to occur within this region; however it is likely the desert mule deer (*Odocoileus hemionus crooki*), with a range in the southern one-third of the state, is the sub-species of the southern Sacramento Mountains (Haussamen 1995). Porcupine are common in most habitat types and are occasionally observed on WSMR from grasslands and shrublands to higher elevation woodlands (Burkett and Kamees 1996); no observations have been made on the Main Base. The oryx (*Oryx gazella*), a non-native, introduced game animal is currently a resident of the base. Oryx range into most habitats found within Holloman AFB and consume the dominant plant types, e.g. mesa dropseed and alkali sacaton (*See Management Issues and Concerns - Exotic Plants and Animals*).

At least 230 bird species have been confirmed at Holloman Air Force Base ([Appendix D](#)). A substantial proportion of these, including grebes, herons, ducks, sandpipers, waders, gulls, and terns, were detected at the Holloman wetlands. A reasonably large number of species in the family Emberizidae (including warblers, towhees, sparrows, and blackbirds) was detected, especially considering the virtual absence of riparian or forested areas with permanent water. These species are usually seen primarily near the wetlands, and to a lesser extent during surveys of grassland habitats. Also detected on grassland surveys were nine species of sparrows and other typical grassland species such as Swainson's Hawk, Prairie Falcon, Eastern and Western Meadowlark, Scaled Quail, four species of wren, and three thrasher species.

The majority of species detected during surveys at cinetheodolite missile towers were residents (23), followed by long-distance migrants (20) or short-distance migrants (5) that breed or winter on Holloman (Johnson et al. 1997a). Similarly, the majority of grassland species detected during surveys were residents (23), followed by stopover migrants (15), winter residents (9), and migrant breeders (5, Mehlhop et al. 1998b). In contrast, the numbers of bird species and individuals at the wetlands peak during spring and fall migration, and there are few resident or breeding wetland species.

Several sensitive bird species occur in wetland habitats at Holloman (Holloman Wetlands MU). The Interior Least Tern (*Sterna antillarum athalassos*) is federally and state endangered and is a rare vagrant at the wetlands. The Peregrine Falcon (*Falco peregrinus*), an occasional migrant, is federally and state endangered. The White-faced Ibis (*Plegadis chihi*) is a federal species of concern observed regularly on migration. Another federal species of concern, the Western Snowy Plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) breeds in relatively small numbers on Stinky Playa and Lagoon G and is fairly abundant during migration (Freehling et al. 1998). The Bald Eagle (*Haliaeetus leucocephalus*), federally listed as threatened, and the Neotropic Cormorant (*Phalacrocorax brasilianus*), state endangered group 2, are potential visitors to the Holloman Wetlands complex, but to date neither has been observed there.

In grassland habitats, the most common sensitive bird species is the Western Burrowing Owl (*Athene cucularia hypugaea*). This federal species of concern is a common year-round resident and successful breeder. The Ferruginous Hawk (*Buteo regalis*) is a federal species of concern. Only one individual was detected during raptor surveys in 1994-95 (Mehlhop et al. 1997). Baird's sparrows (*Ammodramus bairdii*) occur in relatively undisturbed grasslands and are rarely reported in New Mexico. Only one incidental sighting has occurred on Holloman, and none was detected during surveys targeted at the species (NMNHP unpublished Baird's Sparrow report). A former category 2 species, Baird's sparrows now have no federal or state status. The Northern Aplomado Falcon (*Falco femoralis septentrionalis*) is a federally and state endangered species that has not been detected on Holloman. Finally, one state endangered group 1 species, the Common Ground Dove (*Columbina passerina*) is a potential shrubland inhabitant but has not been observed at Holloman. At least some of these grassland species occur in all management units except possibly the Duneland MU. All the above species are discussed in detail in the draft Endangered Species Management Plan for Holloman Air Force Base (Mehlhop et al. 1998a), and in this document under the specific management units in which they occur.

Herpetofauna species richness decreases southward in desert ecosystems; however, the percentage of lizard species doubles and frogs decline (Morafka 1977; Scott 1996). Structural complexity in plant communities is important to maintaining numbers of lizards in arid environments (Germano and Hungerford 1981). Two surveys, (1) along roads for the Texas horned lizard (*Phrynosoma cornutum*) (Mehlhop et al. 1998a), and another at (2) the cinetheodolite missile towers collected herpetofauna data (Johnson et al. 1997a). The Texas horned lizard survey was conducted on the Main Bases and the Boles Wells Water System Annex. The Texas horned lizard, formerly a Category 2

species for federal listing as endangered or threatened, was reclassified February 28, 1996 as a Species of Concern (Department of Interior 1996). This lizard appears to be abundant on Holloman AFB (Mehlhop et al. 1998a) and was found within the major plant community types on both the Main Base and Boles Wells Water System Annex. Other reptiles found during these surveys are listed below in Table 3.

Table 3. Holloman AFB Reptiles

Reptiles were observed and collected during surveys conducted along roads within the Main Base and Boles Wells Water System Annex (¹) and at cinetheodolite missile towers (²).

SCIENTIFIC NAME	COMMON NAME
<i>Cnemidophorus inornatus</i> ^{1,2}	Little striped whiptail
<i>Cnemidophorus neomexicanus</i> ²	New Mexico whiptail
<i>Cnemidophorus tesselatus</i> ¹	Checkered whiptail
<i>Crotaphytus collaris</i> ¹	Common collared lizard
<i>Gambelia wislizenii</i> ¹	Long-nosed leopard lizard
<i>Holbrookia maculata</i> ¹	Lesser earless lizard
<i>Masticophis flagellum</i> ¹	Coachwhip
<i>Phrynosoma cornutum</i> ¹	Texas horned lizard
<i>Phrynosoma modestum</i> ¹	Short-horned lizard
<i>Pituophis melanoleucus</i> ¹	Gopher snake
<i>Sceloporus magister</i> ¹	Desert spiny lizard
<i>Uta stansburiana</i> ^{1,2}	Side-blotched lizard

The White Sands pupfish (*Cyprinodon tularosa*) is endemic to the Tularosa Basin, with two naturally- occurring populations at Malpais Spring and Salt Creek within WSMR and two introduced populations at Mound Springs (WSMR) and Lost River within Holloman AFB. The White Sands pupfish is a Species of Concern (formerly a Category 2 species) and the responsibility of the Biological Resources Division of the U.S. Geological Survey. It has no legal protection under the Endangered Species Act, but could be listed under the act if the species fails to be managed properly under the Cooperative Agreement (1994). The introduction of other species of fish, degradation of water quality, physical barriers to stream flow, or illegal collection of these fish would negatively impact the population's viability ([Mehlhop et al. 1998a](#)).

Invertebrates are an important component of the desert ecosystem and little is known about their diversity in arid lands. Plant-feeding arthropods are beneficial pollinators, parasites, and predators as well as being efficient detritivores in plant decomposition and nutrient recycling (Ford and McPherson 1996; Lightfoot and Whitford 1990). Additionally, they are important prey for small mammals, reptiles and birds. To date there have been no basewide studies on Holloman AFB to determine arthropod species diversity. However, there have been studies on reptiles, birds and pupfish habitat that suggest the roles some of these invertebrates contribute to ecosystem function. The

preferred diet of the Texas horned lizard (*see* herptofauna discussion above) is harvester ants (*Pogonomyrmex spp.*); however it appeared that honeypot ants (*Myrmecocystus*) were more common throughout the base. On Boles Wells, harvester ant nests appeared to be abundant along roadsides (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Insects such as grasshoppers (*Orthoptera*), butterflies and moths (*Lepidoptera*), and beetles (*Coleoptera*) make up a large percentage of food items in Burrowing Owl (*Athene cunicularia hypugaea*) diets. Snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) fecal pellets collected in shoreline and saltflat habitats at Lake Holloman and Stinky Playa were found to contain large quantities of beetles (*Bledius spp.*), corixids (aquatic *Hemiptera*), ants, other beetles, and adult chironomids (*Diptera*) (Freehling et al. 1998). Pupfish populations located in Lost River and Malone Draw feed on mosquitoes, amphipods and annelid worms (Suminski 1977; Turner 1987).

Cultural Resources

Holloman AFB has a rich cultural history spanning over ten thousand years. From prehistoric hunting and gathering peoples to pre-puebloan subsistence agriculturalists, followed by early historic settlements, these societies have left their indelible mark on the landscape. Cultural resources are an important and often a permanent part of the landscape that require proper protection. Documenting past uses of the land assists in understanding current environmental conditions.

Much of the archeological work done in the Tularosa Basin, particularly resource inventory surveys, has been conducted on behalf of the military, due in part to their vast land holdings within the basin (Anschuetz et al. 1990). Cultural-historical reconstructions for sites inventoried and analyzed in the basin typically follow the classification sequence outlined by Lehmer (1948, *see* below). Prehistoric occupation within this region is termed the Jornada Mogollon District (Lehmer 1948).

Paleoindian period	11,000 - 8,000 BP ⁽¹⁾
Archaic period	8,000 - 1,600 BP(?)
Formative period:	
Mesilla Phase	1,600(?) - 900 BP
Doña Ana Phase	1,000 - 800 BP
El Paso Phase	800 - 600 BP

⁽¹⁾BP is Years Before Present.

The climate in the Tularosa Basin during the early Holocene was cooler and wetter than today, with extensive savanna or open woodland within the basin and heavily forested areas in the surrounding mountains (VanDevender 1977). Numerous lakes and permanent streams supported large game animals that were hunted by highly mobile Paleoindian populations (Carmichael 1985). Paleoindian sites within the Tularosa Basin appear to be scarce and difficult to find (Wimberly and Rogers 1977). No material traits

connected with Paleoindian activities were found within Holloman AFB or the Boles Wells Water System Annex.

Changing climatic conditions throughout the Archaic period produced a shift in plant types from mesic savanas and grasslands to more xeric species. Many of the dominant shrub types, e.g. mesquite, creosote bush, and ocotillo, characteristic of the region today began to increase throughout this period (VanDevender and Riskind 1979). Prehistoric human populations responded to the increased aridity by diversifying their utilization of natural resources to include a wider variety of plants and small-game animals (Carmichael 1986). Water sources within the basin were seasonal and scarce as evidenced by short-term use of small campsites (Carmichael 1986; Whalen 1978). However, there is some evidence, based on archeological surveys conducted on Holloman and WSMR, that basin sites were utilized for longer periods, perhaps for residential use (Doleman 1988). Most Paleoindian sites are distinguished by "fossil hearths" surrounded by cracked stone and various lithic scatter. Fossil hearths are particular to these gypsum dunes. Campfires followed by precipitation fuse the sands, creating more resistant surfaces that persist while surrounding sands are eroded by prevailing winds, exposing the archaic hearths. On Holloman AFB, these sites are found at the periphery of the dunes within the blowouts of parabolic dunes and some nearby eolian flats. Tularosa Peak was probably a raw material source for some of the lithic scatter, e.g. hearth stones and chipped and ground stone found throughout the base (Doleman 1988).

Cultural changes, rather than climatic conditions, distinguish the phases within the Formative period. The Mesilla phase marks the advent and wide use of ceramics. In addition to the use of ceramics, these societies utilized subsistence resources similar to the populations of the Archaic period (Carmichael 1985, 1986). Populations were clustered in small pithouse villages usually situated near a water resource such as a playa or major drainage. Artifacts found within the basin are believed to indicate the loci of varied hunting and gathering activities, as opposed to areas of population clusters (Carmichael 1985, 1986; Brethauer 1978). However, later studies conducted within Holloman AFB, uncovered evidence to the contrary (Doleman 1988). Within Holloman AFB, sites identified with the Formative period are predominantly along the periphery of the dunes and within the uplands near drainages. The Boles Wells Water System Annex also has numerous sites associated with the alluvial fan environment.

The human population within the Tularosa Basin increased substantially during the Doña Ana phase. Large sites inhabited for long periods were located on alluvial fans, while smaller campsites existed for seasonal occupation and short-term use within the basin (Carmichael 1986; Anschuetz et al. 1990). Agriculture was widely adopted, yet dependence on hunting and gathering persisted.

The El Paso phase is the best documented of prehistoric occupation in south-central New Mexico (Anschuetz et al. 1990). This phase shows transition from pithouses to the above-ground structures of the pueblo village, with an increasing dependence on agriculture. Cultivars such as beans, corn, and squash, along with subsistence gathering

of mesquite, yucca, acorns, and cacti, make up the plant diets of these populations. Large middens of rabbit bone are also found at these sites (Whalen 1980). Ninety-five percent of the documented villages were found at the base of alluvial fans and along the basin edge. Gathering was important, especially during late summer and early fall when large numbers of plants and animals were available (Anschuetz et al. 1990). Scattered throughout the basin environment are small, temporary sites that may have been used for special activities such as hunting and plant gathering (O'Laughlin 1980).

Late prehistoric and historic populations of Mescalero Apache (1500 AD? - 1870) inhabited large portions of the region between the Pecos and Rio Grande Rivers (Doleman 1988; Hawthorne 1994). The Apache were nomadic, subsisting mainly on wild plants and animals. An early Spanish explorer stated that they "change their location frequently in order to breathe new air and so that the site which they abandon might be purified" (Cortes 1799; Hawthorne 1994). This philosophy is reflected in both their seasonal migrations following buffalo and antelope and their use of teepees made of animal skins. Various conflicts arose between the Apache and non-native settlers to the region. One decisive battle ending in defeat for the Mescalero was in 1868 at Tularosa Peak, also known as Round Mountain (Doleman 1988). Surveys conducted on Holloman AFB (CES/CEV Archaeological Database), detected some evidence for the use of the area by Mescalero Apache, ie. teepee poles near Malone Draw.

The earliest non-native settlers to the Tularosa Basin (1860s) were Hispanics that moved from the flooded Rio Grande regions to the foothills of the Sacramentos (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997). Some of the first settlements were at the mouth of the Rio Tularosa and La Luz Creek. The early settlers were agriculturalists who developed drainage systems (acequias) to re-direct mountain runoff for irrigation purposes. In contrast, later settlers of Euro-American descent were predominantly cattle ranchers who homesteaded acreage within the basin, pursuant to the Homestead Act of 1862. By 1916, due to droughts, limited water resources, and poor crop returns, ninety percent of the homesteads were abandoned. The only Holloman AFB property to remain in continual use for farming purposes until condemnation by the government was the Boles Wells Well Field. The few long-term residents of the area tended to be ranchers.

Climatic factors within the Tularosa Basin have remained steady for the last 100 years; however, land use patterns have affected a change in water availability and native plant and faunal distributions. Prior to 1890, early settlers described "lush grasses" that stood "belly high to a horse" and foothill blue grama grass that grew "stirrup high" (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997). By 1934 the range was said to be "as bare as a rat's tail" (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997). Oral histories taken from previous landowners and lessees of Holloman lands recalled year-round springs near Tularosa (Tule) Peak and within Reagan and Sheep Camp Draws (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997). These springs dried up around 1952; residents blame the drilling of wells in Tularosa. In 1939, Grazing Service inspectors noted only minor encroachments of pickleweed (*Allenrolfea occidentalis*), within the wide draws that dissect the Main Base. This species is now widespread and common within the draws. Furthermore, in the 1920's saltgrass (*Disstichlis spicata*), now found in high densities within the wetlands south of the Cantonment Area, was widespread within the

drainages and a common forage for cattle (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997). Runoff is now reduced within these draws, possibly due to irrigation diversions at the mountain front (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997). Increase in mesquite within the basin may be due to multiple factors, including climatic and grazing practices (*see* Chapter 4 - Malone Draw).

Predator control programs initiated by the government in the 1920's targeted coyotes, jackrabbits, and kangaroo rats. These past management practices may have contributed to the slow recovery of these populations (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997). Other "pests," e.g. prairie dogs and rattlesnakes, were most often controlled by residents; today there is no evidence of prairie dogs within the base. Mountain lions inhabited areas within the foothills of the Sacramentos and moved between the Sacramento and Organ Mountains. There is some evidence of their past predation on cattle being grazed on summer forage in the Boles Wells Water System (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997).

In response to overgrazing of public domain lands, the Taylor Grazing Act of 1934 specified a state and federal lease permit system for grazing policy on public lands. Prior to that time, livestock had "free range" with no legally enforceable restrictions on grazing boundaries. The Act created grazing allotments, with first preference given to ranchers already using the lands for grazing. Under this system, and up to 1942 when the government took over lands now known as Holloman AFB, five grazing allotments overlapped these lands. The permittees had ranches on private lands, grazing allotments on federal lands, and leases on state lands. In comparison to other ranches throughout the Tularosa Basin, Holloman ranches were much smaller, but their proportion of federal range was much higher. For example, privately held lands amounted to roughly two percent of the area, while eight-two percent were federal allotments. Another difference between Holloman ranches and others within the basin was the production of supplemental feed. Dry farming techniques were used in Malone, Hay, and Carter Draws. Johnson grass hay and field corn were planted for livestock feed and small gardens occasionally were planted for personal use. Saltcedar (*Tamarix ramosissima*) was planted as a windbreak above Carter Draw and has since moved aggressively into the drainage bottoms and lowland depressions at the southern end of the base.

Holloman AFB was taken out of agricultural production in 1942. Several remnants of this historic period have been either destroyed by military personnel or deteriorated in the harsh desert environment. Fifty-eight historic sites, including remains of ranches, farms, irrigation systems, and refuse scatter, have been inventoried and documented (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997). These sites represent an important cultural and historic link to past lifestyles and occupants, particularly characteristic of the Tularosa Basin, and some are considered eligible for the National Register of Historic Places (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997).

CHAPTER 4 - MANAGEMENT UNITS AND ECOLOGICAL ASSOCIATIONS

The ecosystem management program at HAFB is a strategy based on conserving natural processes and maintaining suitable habitat for native plants and animals. Within the relatively small holdings of Holloman AFB, many natural ecosystems of the Tularosa Basin are represented providing essential habitat for migrating birds and overland corridors for desert mammals. To effectively manage these diverse natural systems, management units were developed based on similar properties of the physical landscape, sensitive plants and animals, and easily recognizable borders using roads and established landuse patterns consistent with mission guidelines. This chapter uses Management Units (MUs) as an administrative tool to describe the natural landscapes, identify critical habitat, relate natural processes, and establish links between Holloman's natural resources and its surrounding landscapes within the Tularosa Basin.

Organization of Management Units on HAFB

Holloman AFB is divided into six management units (MUs). Five fall within the main base: Dunelands, Test Track, Malone Draw, Cantonment, and Lake Holloman Wetlands. The Boles Wells Annex System is a single MU with two sub-units, the Boles Well Field and the Southern Well Fields (Douglas and San Andres)(Figure 9). The Dunelands MU borders the easternmost edge of the White Sands. The Test Track MU is sandwiched between the Dunelands to the west and Northern Shrublands to the east. Duneland, Test Track, and Northern Shrublands MUs are situated north of Douglas Road and collectively represent lands less impacted by military activities and base development. The Cantonment MU has the highest density of base development and roads, including the airfield, airfield operations, and base housing. The Lake Holloman Wetlands MU contains a complex of natural and constructed wetlands. The Boles Wells Annex System is geographically separated from the main base and located at the base of the Sacramento Mountains, south of Alamogordo. The Boles Well Field and the Douglas Well Field lie north of Oliver Reed State Park and the San Andres Well Field lies south of the state park.

The primary concept of the management unit is to develop a conceptual framework of ecologically similar communities within geographically defined boundaries. Management units are defined by the spatial contiguity of similar natural plant communities and established man-made features such as roads. In addition, elements of the military mission were taken into consideration to maximize efficacy of natural resource management. Management Units were organized in consideration of ecosystem processes, to protect biodiversity, and minimize the effort and cost of management.

An ecosystem can be defined at various spatial scales, but generally it is a collection of plants and animals, within a given area, and their abiotic environments (Tansley 1935; Odum 1971; Noss et al. 1995; Leslie et al. 1996). The ecosystem can be defined by one or a number of ecologically relevant factors, including vegetation type, plant association (or community type), habitat defined by floristics, natural process, or geography, to name a few. Our concept of the ecosystem is based on a hierarchy built from vegetation communities (*See* chapter 3 - Vegetation; Muldavin et al. 1998). Vegetation mapping units, made up of vegetation communities, are used to define and spatially delineate the ecosystem hierarchy. *See* [Muldavin et al. \(1998\)](#) for a comprehensive list of plant communities within Holloman AFB nested within mapping units.

The ecosystems represented on Holloman AFB, including the Boles Wells Wellfield, are part of more extensive systems extending beyond the borders of the base. Additionally, these ecosystems are influenced by adjacent systems; e.g. the Arroyo Riparian Ecosystem is influenced by the surrounding Upland Terrestrial Ecosystem. For the convenience of discussion, we group the vegetation mapping units into a higher level of the hierarchy and consider that Holloman contains four natural ecosystems and one man-made ecosystem (Table 4). The natural ecosystems are: Duneland, Arroyo Riparian, Playa and

Upland. The Constructed Wetland is a man-made ecosystem. A miscellaneous category is used to capture base facilities and the golf course.

The hierarchy used throughout this chapter is:

Ecosystem (6 classes - Table 4)

Vegetation Mapping Unit (23 classes - Table 4)

Plant Community (28 classes - See Chapter 3 - Vegetation)

Percent of total area covered by vegetation mapping unit within each ecosystem for the Main Base and the Boles Wells Wellfield are included in Table 5. Upland Ecosystem vegetation types dominate both the Main Base and the Wellfield.

Table 4. Ecosystem Hierarchy based on Vegetation Mapping Units

Vegetation mapping units are based on groupings of plant communities (discussed in Chapter 3-Vegetation). Mapping units are organized by physiographic features of the landscape to form surrogate ecosystems for the purposes of discussion.

UPLAND	DUNELAND	ARROYO- RIPARIAN	PLAYA	CONSTRUCTED WETLAND	MISC
Alkali Sacaton Grassland	Barren Duneland	Salt Cedar Woodland	Barren Alkaline Playa	Surface Water	Development/ Ground Disturbance/ Airfield Golf Course
Creosotebush Shrubland	Gyp Dropseed Grassland	Semi-riparian Alkali Sacaton Grassland	Pickleweed Shrubland	Wetland	
Fourwing Saltbush/ Alkali Sacaton Shrubland	Gyp Grama Interdune Grassland	Semi-riparian Honey Mesquite Shrubland			Urban Vegetation
Fourwing Saltbush/ Gyp Dropseed Shrubland	Rosemarymint Dune Shrubland				
Fourwing Saltbush Shrubland with Honey Mesquite					
Sparse Fourwing Saltbush Shrubland					
Honey Mesquite/ Feather Finger Grass Shrubland					
Honey Mesquite Shrubland					
Rock Outcrop					

Table 5. Total area represented by each Ecosystem Type

Table shows total area represented by ecosystem type for Holloman Main Base and the Boles Wells area.

Main Base					
UPLAND	DUNELAND	ARROYO- RIPARIAN	PLAYA	CONSTRUCTED WETLAND	MISC
44.41	32.73	5.64	4.75	0.66	11.81
Boles Wells					
93.49	0.00	0.40	0.00	0.35	5.66

Figure 9. Holloman AFB Management Units (MUs).

Holloman AFB and Boles Wells Water System Annex MUs with ephemeral streams, playas, and wetlands for reference. Wetland areas are shown in light blue, other bodies of water are in dark blue.

Cantonment

The Cantonment MU comprises 3,255 ha (8,045 acres) within the southern portion of the base (Figure 9). The landscape has been highly modified to accommodate the majority of functions conducted by the military, including base housing and personnel support facilities. Within this Upland Ecosystem, topography is relatively level with elevations ranging from 1258m (4127 feet) in the far northeast corner of the MU to 1232m (4042

feet) west of the airfield. Although the natural landscape has been fragmented by broad road networks and permanent structures, nearly 60% covered in native vegetation.

Holloman- Gypsum land-Yesum complex is the soil type for this management unit. These are highly calcareous, well-drained soils with areas of exposed gypsum, formed in eolian gypsiferous and alluvial sediments (Derr et al. 1981). Wind erosion is severe in exposed areas of this soil type (*See Chapter 3 - Soils and Geology*).

Changes in surface and sub-surface flow due to the diversion of drainages previously associated with Dillard Draw have increased wetlands within this MU (Figure 9). Ephemeral flats and vegetated wetlands have developed north of the golf course, as a result of the diversion of drainages associated with the construction of Highway 70/82 (United States Air Force 1996). In addition, the lower portion of Dillard Draw has been altered and channelized for the base stormwater drainage system, thereby creating a wetland east of housing.

The Cantonment MU contains the greatest total number of acres and continuous extent of alkali sacaton grasslands within Holloman AFB. These grasslands cover 24% (Figure 10) of the MU and are characterized by moderately dense grasslands within basin bottom alluvial flats (Muldavin et al. 1998). These grasslands dominate the area west of the north-south runway up to Douglas Road and extend into WSMR, forming an eccentric ring at the margins of the gypsum-dominated landscapes (Figure 7). They are nearly comparable in size to the most extensive alkali sacaton grassland within the Tularosa Basin, located on the alluvial flats of the Mockingbird Mountains within WSMR. These extensive grasslands in the Northern Jornada on WSMR also follow margins of a gypsum outcrop. Within the Chihuahuan Desert and Great Basin biomes, alkali sacaton grasslands occur in lowlands and swales, typically in depositional silts or clay soils (Muldavin et al. 1997). These grasslands probably formed at a time when intermittent flows deposited silts and increased the development of clays, as Dillard Draw emptied into a series of playas and lowland swales.

Figure 10. Cantonment MU Vegetation Mapping Units

Shrublands dominated by fourwing saltbush cover approximately 26% of the Cantonment MU. The mapping units include Fourwing Saltbush/Alkali Sacaton (15%), Sparse Fourwing Saltbush (7%), Fourwing Saltbush/Gyp Dropseed (2%) and Fourwing Saltbush with Honey Mesquite (2%). Fourwing saltbush/alkali sacaton, with inclusions of alkali sacaton grassland, dominates the landscape east of the north-south runway. Further east, this community grades into semi-coppicing honey mesquite/alkali sacaton communities. Sparse fourwing saltbush is associated with highly disturbed areas, concentrated near the airfield. This community is also associated with pickleweed shrublands within playas formerly part of the Dillard Draw desert riparian system. (Figure 9)

Pickleweed Shrubland and Gyp Dropseed Grassland make up the majority of the 'Other' category (9%, Figure 10). Pickleweed Shrubland includes 3 plant communities: pickleweed/sparse, pickleweed-Mojave seablite, and pickleweed/alkali sacaton. In 1939, Grazing Service inspectors noted only minor encroachments of pickleweed within the wide draws that dissect Holloman AFB (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997). These shrublands have increased within the draws in recent history (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997), due in part to more xeric conditions created by altering the natural flow of Dillard Draw. Near these communities, small occurrences of gyp dropseed-alkali sacaton or fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed occur at the margins of the playas and raised surfaces. Urban vegetation and the golf course make up nearly 2% of the land cover. Both urban vegetation and the golf course are comprised of non-native species that require large inputs of energy, chemicals, and water to maintain. In addition, undesirable pests such as mosquitoes increase creating a problem within the family housing sector (*See* Chapter 5 - Landscaping and Predator/Pest Control).

Grama grass cactus populations within the cantonment area are considered large enough to include within the proposed cactus conservation sites (Figure 21). The proposed site contains 278 ha (687 acres), protecting an average population density of 24 plants/ha. Ground-based training activities are no longer conducted in this area, thereby protecting the populations from trampling and other human-related disturbances.

The Marr cinetheodolite missile tower is located just north of runway 04-22. Along with two other towers within Holloman AFB, it was surveyed for biological resources in 1996. ([Johnson et al. 1997a](#)). In comparison to the other cinetheodolite sites, Marr Tower was consistently low on richness and abundance of birds, herpetofauna, and small mammals. Bird surveys detected no more than 2 species in any season at the Marr Tower. Species detected include: Horned Lark (*Eremophila alpestris*), Eastern Meadowlark (*Sturnella magna*), Chipping Sparrow (*Spizella pallida*), Loggerhead Shrike (*Lanius ludovicianus*), Western Kingbird (*Tyrannus verticalis*), and Northern Mockingbird (*Mimus polyglottos*). Traps captured one each of Couch's spadefoot toad (*Scaphiopus couchii*), Side-blotched lizard (*Uta stansburiana*), and Little striped whiptail (*Cnemidophorus inornatus*). Another survey for the Texas horned lizard (*Phrynosoma cornutum*) found 2 lizards along the Douglas Road survey (Mehlhop et al. 1998b). Small mammal surveys detected Deer mouse (*Peromyscus maniculatus*), Mearn's grasshopper mouse (*Onychomys arenicolor*) and an *Onychomys sp.* ([Johnson et al. 1997a](#)). Coyote tracks and scat were also seen during the tower survey.

Buildings within the cantonment area provide roosting and nesting habitat for owls and bats. Barn owl (*Tyto alba*) pairs use the borrow pit and buildings (#867 & #1020) for nesting and rearing young. A Great-horned Owl (*Bubo virginianus*) has also occupied Building #867 from Spring '96 to Summer '97. From January to March, 1997 a pair of Great-horned owls occupied Building #2428A. Another incidental sighting was a Golden Eagle (*Aquila chrysaetos*) near the soccer field. Silver-haired, pallid, and spotted bat have been observed roosting on buildings #824, #500, and #296, respectively.

Burrowing Owls inhabit the flat, nearly barren ground next to the runways (Figure 23). Owls forage on insects that accumulate in high numbers near lights, which may partially explain their attraction to the airfield. Fledging success in the cantonment area in 1996 was 60% with a 50% success rate in 1997 (Johnson et al. 1997b). There is concern at the airfield that owl burrows near runway lighting have a potential to flood and short out the lights (Johnson et al. 1997b, Mehlhop et al. 1998, See Chapter 6 - Sensitive Species).

Within the Cantonment MU, 18 sites with cultural significance have been inventoried. The majority of these sites (14) do not require any particular protection. Three of the sites contain lithic scatter and require protection from vehicular traffic or ground disturbance caused by digging. As long as vehicles stay on designated roads, these sites should remain intact. The Marr cinetheodolite missile tower requires protection from fire.

Dunelands

The Dunelands Management Unit comprises 6,028 ha (14,896 acres) and extends roughly from the test track facilities to the Holloman AFB western boundary. The striking natural features of this management unit are the constantly transforming white gypsum sand dunes. Factors such as vegetation, sand supply, seasonal winds, and soil moisture affect sand movement. Wind direction is the primary factor responsible for variation in dune morphology. These dunes have a complex morphology and have been interpreted to grade from dome, to transverse, to barchan, to parabolic (Fryberter, et. al. 1990). Barchan dunes within WSNM were observed to move at a rate of 12m (39.4 feet) per year (McKee 1966), while parabolic dune movement was found to move at a rate of 2 m (6.6 feet) per year (Patrick 1980). Because the White Sands are vegetated, they are unique in comparison to other large dune fields such as the Great Sand Dunes in the San Luis Valley of Colorado. The Duneland Ecosystem is defined primarily by duneland processes and associated vegetation community types (Table 4).

Three principal soil types dominate this MU: the Active dune land, the Dune land-Yesum association, and the Holloman-Gypsum land-Yesum complex (Neher and Bailey 1976; Derr et al. 1988). The active dune land soils are gypsum crystals redeposited by wind carried from Lake Lucero, a relict lakebed. These gypsum deposits are evaporites

from alluviated material brought into the lakebed from the surrounding mountains. Dune land soils becomes highly mobile during periods of high winds.

Depositional and soil-forming processes are characteristically similar for the Dune land-Yesum and Holloman-Gypsum land-Yesum complex are characteristically similar. The Yesum soils occur in the level areas between semi-stabilized dunes (Doleman 1988). These soils are formed in wind-laid deposits, high in gypsum content, and moderately permeable. Throughout the soil profile are fine to very fine gypsum crystals ranging from mildly to moderately alkaline. These soils are highly susceptible to winds and become hazardous at high velocities. Cryptogams are characteristic of Duneland-Yesum and Yesum-Holloman association soil groups (Neher and Bailey 1976) and are sparsely to densely distributed. Cryptogams may contribute to soil stabilization (Doleman 1988). The Dune land-Yesum association is 55 percent Dune land and 30 percent Yesum very fine sandy loam.

Yesum-Holloman association is the most widespread throughout the base. It is about 35 percent Yesum very fine sandy loam, 30 percent Holloman very fine sandy loam, and 20 percent Gypsum land, hummocky.

Hydrologic characteristics such as water-holding capacity of the dunes and underground water systems within the dunes are unknown; however, the dunes appear to have great capacity for retaining moisture (Doleman 1988). All of the draws that dissect the base, except Dillard Draw, terminate in the dunes. It is not known how far they extend under the dune field or to what extent the dunes may alter direction of the flows. In the case of Lost River, dunes are encroaching and covering portions of the drainage.

Five principal vegetation mapping units comprise nearly 92% of the vegetation communities found within this management unit (Figure 11). These include Rosemarymint Dune Shrubland (39.45%), Barren Duneland (16.32%), Gyp Grama Interdune Grassland (15.12%), Gyp Dropseed Grassland (10.6%), and Semi-riparian Alkali Sacaton Grassland (10.1%). Mapping units less than 3 hectares are combined into the 'other' category.

These mapping units contain specific plant associations that occur predominantly within the Duneland Ecosystem. The Rosemarymint Dune Shrubland occurs on slopes and summits of shifting and semi-stabilized gypsum dunes. Two community types (CT) dominate this mapping unit, the hoary rosemarymint/sandhill muhly CT and the hoary rosemarymint/ mesa dropseed CT. These CTs include other scattered shrubs such as soap tree yucca (*Yucca elata*), Torrey's jointfir (*Ephedra torreyana*) and skunkbush sumac (*Rhus trilobata*). Grasses are sparse, scattered, and dominated by sandhill muhly and mesa dropseed, with giant dropseed (*Sporobolus giganteus*) occurring near the duneland edges. Barren Duneland mapping unit contains non-vegetated, shifting gypsum dunes that may have inclusions of hoary rosemarymint/sandhill muhly on semi-stabilized portions of the dune field. Within the interdune, swale grasses, small shrubs (sub-shrubs), and forbs create a high diversity mosaic of gypsum-tolerant plants. The major community types are gyp grama associated with either New Mexico bluestem or hairy

coldenia and small inclusions of gyp dropseed with hairy coldenia occurring along the duneland periphery.

The Gyp Dropseed Grassland mapping unit borders the dunelands in a long narrow band and extends to broader regions at the far northwest corner of the base. These regions at the dune periphery are characterized by three CTs: gyp dropseed/hairy coldenia or gyp dropseed-alkali sacaton with inclusions of fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed. At the margins of the dunes in lowland swales, the periodically-flooded Semi-riparian Alkali Sacaton Grassland mapping unit occurs on very alkaline, gypic crusts. These low-lying depressions between dunes trap runoff, creating floristically dense communities dominated by alkali sacaton/James' seaheath.

Figure 11. Duneland MU Vegetation Mapping Units

Vegetation mapping units found within the Dunelands Management Unit.

Standing high above the sparsely vegetated dunes are stands of cottonwoods (*Populus* spp.). These impressive trees probably originated prior to the encroaching dunes at a time when a more reliable and permanent water source was available. Little is known of the habitat requirements or establishment history of these trees. After preliminary ground reconnaissance to some of the cottonwood sites, photo interpretive techniques were used to map their distribution within the dunes (Muldavain et al. 1998). These sites have not been ground truthed and are therefore preliminary. These stands could potentially hold fire and climate history for the basin, which is not available elsewhere. Proposals for further research are discussed in Chapter 6-Sensitive Natural Areas.

Dunelands provide a broad and elongated corridor for kit foxes connecting numerous reaches of the basin, including the San Andres Wildlife Refuge and south to the coppice dunes of Ft. Bliss. Swift fox range usually extends no more than 3 km of a den. They prefer loose, sandy soils to dig burrows and dens. Kit fox also inhabit desert shrub, shrub-grass and xeric riparian areas (Zoellick et al. 1989) and found within the coppice dune environments at Ft. Bliss. Kit fox dens and burrows are noticeable due to the mounds of dirt and sand they excavate from their burrows.

Rodent surveys conducted within Rosemarymint Dune Shrubland, Gyp Grama Interdune Grassland, and Fourwing Saltbush/Gyp Dropseed Shrubland habitats at the periphery of the dune found fourteen species of rodents (Table 2). The Ord's Kangaroo Rat (*Dipodomys ordii*), Desert Pocket Mouse (*Chaetodipus penicillatus*) and Plains Pocket Mouse (*Perognathus flavescens gypsi*) were found primarily within the dunes, while others were found equally distributed among habitats or in numbers too small to allow determination of habitat affinity.

The Western Burrowing Owl (*Athene cunicularia hypugaea*), a federal Species of Concern, is a common year-round resident and successful breeder on Holloman AFB ([Johnson et al. 1997b](#)). The Duneland MU contains the largest area of Gyp Dropseed Grasslands, the primary habitat type for Burrowing Owls, on Holloman. Eleven burrows were found within this MU in 1997 (63%). Two were natal burrows, one produced fledglings and one failed for unknown reasons. The rest were used as auxiliary burrows. A more detailed discussion of Burrowing Owls is included in Chapter 6-Sensitive Species.

A narrow ribbon of riparian vegetation in the westernmost reaches of the Lost River provides suitable habitat for one surviving population of the White Sands Pupfish (*Cyprinodon tularosa*). Three other populations originally observed in 1987 within this reach of the Dunelands MU were extinct during surveys conducted in 1995 (BCD 1998). This decline may be linked to encroachment by the surrounding dunefield. The pupfish is a Species of Concern and is managed under a cooperative agreement established in 1994 (Appendix B; [Mehlhop et al. 1998a](#)). Although not protected under the Endangered Species Act, it has an SCF federal listing, indicating evidence of vulnerability, but there are not enough data to support listing proposals at this time. The NMDGF considers the species "Endangered, group 2 (E2)", given to any species or subspecies whose prospects of survival or recruitment in New Mexico are likely to be in jeopardy within the foreseeable future. The White Sands Pupfish is considered critically imperiled and extremely rare (G1,S1) by the NMNHP.

The duneland MU provides a rich archaic history, with remnants of Paleoindian hearth sites and scattered lithic debris. Paleoindian sites are characterized by "fossil hearths" surrounded by cracked stone and various lithic scatter. Fossil hearths are particular to these gypsum dunes. Campfires followed by precipitation fuse the sands, creating more resistant surfaces that persist while surrounding sands are eroded by prevailing winds. On Holloman AFB, these sites are found at the periphery of the dunes within the blowouts of parabolic dunes and some nearby eolian flats. Tularosa Peak was probably a raw material source for some of the lithic scatter, e.g. hearth stones and chipped and ground stone found throughout the base (Doleman 1988). In addition, early non-native sites such as dug outs (homesites constructed partially below ground-level) and remnants of ranching operations are located within this management unit. Various cold war instrumentation sites such as a theodolite tower also exist in this MU.

With the exception of Test Track-related work, military activities in the area are limited. Test Track activities are usually conducted within 30 to 100 meters of the road marking

the eastern boundary of the MU. One other road that traverses the dunes north of Lost River provides access to sites on WSMR and is used principally for commuting and delivery purposes.

Northern Shrublands

This is the largest management unit, comprising 7,801 ha (19,278 acres). From this nearly level and moderately undulating topography, Tularosa Peak rises abruptly 300 m (984 feet) above the surrounding basin floor. Broad, deeply incised drainages move alluviated materials from upland reaches in the east westward into the dunes. This MU is a complex of Upland and Arroyo Riparian Ecosystems, creating a morphologically and biologically diverse ecological unit. With the exception of the Duneland MU, this area holds the greatest potential for natural resource recovery and conservation, because of its high plant and animal diversity and large areas currently unused for military or recreational purposes. Fragmentation by roads previously used for military purposes and continued access via these old roads may be the principal threat to conserving the ecosystems contained within this MU.

Two broadly-classified soil units are described for this area (Derr et al. 1988); they are the Mead silty clay loam (MEA) that occurs within the drainages, and the Holloman-Gypsum land-Yesum complex (HOB) that comprises the remaining upland areas. The MEA soils are flooded much of the year and have very slow permeability and low available water capacity (Derr et al. 1988). Overlying surfaces of the MEA are about 5 inches of reddish-brown silty clay loam and clay loam. The reddish brown clay substratum can reach depths of 48 inches and have a high salt content. Soil horizons extending to more than 60 inches are made of lacustrine material of variable texture and color. These soils are moderately calcareous throughout and strongly alkaline with a layer of salt that is more soluble than gypsum.

The topography within the upland reaches dominated by HOB is linear, northeast trending, and subtly undulating. This type of surface expression resembles linear dune morphology and may be the result of bi-directional wind regimes, as opposed to dunes created by winds from a single direction. These soils are formed in mixed eolian and alluvial gypsiferous sediments and can have horizons either well-drained, shallow or deep. They are calcareous throughout and mildly alkaline, having moderate permeability and available water capacity (*See* Chapter 3 - Soils and Geology). Tularosa Peak is described as Rock Land (Neher and Bailey 1976). This peak is an intrusive volcanic formation capped with limestone (Doleman 1988) comprised of sedimentary units of the Yeso Formation (Dane and Bachman 1965). This Permian Age unit is 35 percent rock outcrop, 30 percent colluvium, and about 20 to 25 percent shallow to very shallow soils. The remaining 10 to 15 percent of the unit are mixed alluvium and deeper soils found at further distances from the uplifted hill.

Deeply incised drainages are an important feature of this MU. The intermittent surface flows provide important desert riparian habitat for wildlife. Little is known about the

history of available water and water quality within the draws; however, at the turn of the century there was sufficient water to support enough saltgrass to provide forage for cattle (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997). Conditions within the draws have changed since the turn of the century, when dry farming techniques were used within Hay Draw to grow crops such as corn, small family gardens, and grass hay. Year-round springs were once common near Tularosa Peak and within Reagan and Sheep Camp Draws (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997). These springs dried up around 1952; residents at the time blamed the drilling of wells in Tularosa. Today these draws are more xeric and alkaline-tolerant shrubs such as fourwing saltbush and pickleweed dominate. Originally planted by previous landowners for erosion control, saltcedar, an invasive, Eurasian exotic tree is increasing within the wetland and riparian habitats within the base. This phreatophyte poses a threat to competing native species and can significantly alter the flow of streams (Malanson 1993) (See Chapter 6 - Exotic Plants and Animals).

Currently, surface and subsurface water availability on Holloman AFB is dependent on water recharge and runoff from the Sacramento Mountains. Diverting or mining this resource has affected water availability on Holloman AFB.

Figure 12. Northern Shrublands MU Vegetation Mapping Units
Vegetation Mapping Units found within Northern Shrublands Management Unit.

This MU is dominated by shrubland communities (61%) with extensive patches of grassland communities (20%). Base development, disturbance and roads cover about 8 percent of the management unit with the remaining communities associated with riparian habitat within the draws (10%) or rock outcrops on Tularosa Peak (1%).

Fourwing Saltbush/Alkali Sacaton Shrubland covers an extensive area within the central portion of the base (Figure 12). This mapping unit also covers extensive reaches within

the Tularosa Basin and is characterized by open canopies of fourwing saltbush with well-developed understories dominated by alkali sacaton (Muldavin et al. 1998). Adjacent to this vegetation mapping unit, fourwing saltbush forms an association with other plants. This may be due to the varying quantities of gypsum in the soils. Although the soil classification does not identify this change, these plant associations are good edaphic indicators. Westward toward the dunes, Fourwing Saltbush/Gyp Dropseed Shrubland mapping unit dominates and may have inclusions of gyp dropseed/hairy coldenia and gyp dropseed-alkali sacaton communities (Muldavin et al. 1998). This mapping unit contains more cryptogamic cover than all other community types (See Chapter 6 - Sensitive Natural Areas). In addition, this MU and the Test Track MU combined account for 93 percent of the total geographic distribution of this vegetation mapping unit. Easternmost shrublands are dominated by Fourwing Saltbush Shrubland with Honey Mesquite. The major community type for this mapping unit is fourwing saltbush/alkali sacaton with scattered honey mesquite throughout, as well as inclusions of honey mesquite/alkali sacaton communities. These communities lack a significant fourwing saltbush component. Two disjunct sites of alkali sacaton/monotypic with scattered honey mesquite are located north of Malone Draw at the far northeast corner and the other is west of Dillard Draw near Douglas Road. Creosote Shrubland, although only a small component of this MU (1.7 %) is found at higher elevations at the base of Tularosa Peak and on a short rise between upper Malone Draw and Carter Draw. Covering the limestone outcrops are high densities of Claret Cup Cactus (*Echinocerus triglochidiatus*). Claret Cup has a broad range from west Texas through central New Mexico and into northwestern Arizona and Colorado.

Although shrublands dominate the MU, patches and inclusions of grasslands add to the structural diversity of the area, providing a variation in habitat types that increase biodiversity. The two principal upland grassland mapping units are Gyp Dropseed Grassland and Alkali Sacaton Grassland. gyp dropseed/hairy coldenia community types within this management unit commonly occur in linear bands along the upland edges of the drainages and on gypsum mounds (outcrops) that form on the northeast trending raised surfaces (Muldavin et al. 1998). Inclusions of fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed communities may occur within the mapping unit and also are associated in nearby patches. Gyp dropseed-alkali sacaton communities are also included within this mapping unit. Alkali Sacaton Grassland mapping unit is comprised of monotypic alkali sacaton communities at varying densities from open to moderate and may include scattered fourwing saltbush. A large area of this grassland lies north of Hay Draw in the northeast corner of the base. These grasslands are often surrounded by fourwing saltbush/alkali sacaton communities.

The drainages within this MU are dominated by Arroyo Riparian Ecosystem species (4.5%): Semi-riparian Alkali Sacaton Grassland, Semi-riparian Honey Mesquite Shrubland, and Saltcedar Woodland. Pickleweed Shrubland has increased within the more playa-like depressions within Lost River, Malone Draw, Ritas Draw and at the confluence of Carter and upper Malone Draw (3.9%). Semi-riparian Alkali Sacaton Grasslands are dense monotypic grasslands throughout the more mesic reaches of the drainages; however, near the dune periphery alkali sacaton/James' seaheath communities

tend to increase. Semi-riparian Honey Mesquite Shrubland is open-to-closed stands of honey mesquite with dense understories of alkali sacaton. These shrublands are principally located within Hay Draw. Saltcedar Woodland may have sparse to moderate understories of alkali sacaton or saltgrass and occasionally be associated with fourwing saltbush or Mojave seablite (*Sueda moquinii*). These woodlands can be open or closed canopies and are located predominantly within the Malone Draw complex of drainages that include Lost River, Carter Draw and Ritas Draw.

The lichen *Biatorrella clauzadeana* is considered globally and regionally rare (G1,S1) and was the subject of brief searches by NMNHP on gypsum outcrops along river drainages within the main base (1994-95). Previous studies indicate that this lichen occurs on miniature "sandcastle" formations of weathered crystalline gypsum (Weber and Nash 1992; BCD 1998). The exposed layers of gypsum usually occur along the edge of drainages, such as Malone, Hay, Carter, Dillard and Sheep Camp draws on Holloman AFB (*See* Chapter 6 - Sensitive Species). Eight populations were found, seven of which are located within this MU. Highly precise field measurements using a Global Positioning System (GPS) were not used to attain these positions; therefore, it is difficult to determine if an association exists with a particular plant community or other environmental indicator.

Grama grass cactus populations are ubiquitous on Holloman AFB, with the highest densities occurring within the Northern Shrublands Management Unit. The grama grass cactus was downlisted to a Category 3 species based on its distribution, but also on the expectation that the large populations found on military bases, including Holloman AFB are relatively protected from disturbance (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Researchers do not consider the species likely to become endangered in the foreseeable future (Sivinski and Lightfoot 1994). Forty-five percent of the Holloman AFB populations are contained within seven areas in the Test Track, Northern Shrublands, and Cantonment MUs (Figure 21). These areas are under consideration for grama grass cactus conservation sites (*See* Chapter 6 - Sensitive Species)

Census data for animals within this MU are restricted to either near-road sampling for specific species such as the Texas Horned Lizard ([Mehlhop et al. 1998a](#)) data collected during surveys at the Malone Draw Cinetheodolite Missile Tower just north of upper Malone Draw ([Johnson et al. 1997a](#)). Surveys conducted in 1995 for the Texas Horned Lizard conducted in 1995 revealed low densities along Range Road 9 and Vandergrift Road. The tower study was conducted within an ecotone between riparian, shrubland and grassland plant communities.

In 1996-97 census data were collected for birds, bats, herpetofauna and small mammals (Johnson et al. 1997a). Seventeen bird species were detected in the fall, 15 in spring, 10 during raptor migration, 10 during breeding, and 4 in winter. The tower was used commonly as a night roost for small bats (probably small-footed myotis). Three species of lizard were identified: little striped whiptail, New Mexico whiptail and side-bloched lizard. Eight species of rodents were captured with deer mouse and merriam kangaroo rat most often captured. Studies at the dune periphery to identify rodents and their

respective habitats can be used to extrapolate to other portions of the base. For instance, rodents found within the fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed Shrubland (White Sands woodrat and house mouse) could potentially occur within the Northern Shrublands MU because this community type is represented in this MU. Short surveys conducted for the White Sands Woodrat in 1994 (HAFB in-house GIS layer) found a midden and female woodrat at the easternmost boundary within this MU. Incidental sightings such as mountain lion scat collected in 1994 north of Malone Draw indicate Holloman AFB is occasionally within the range of this species. The mountain lion commonly occurs within at least some portion of White Sands Missile Range, with substantial populations occurring in the San Andres and Oscura Mountains (Bison-M 1998).

The White Sands Pupfish is the most sensitive species identified within Holloman AFB ([Mehlhop et al. 1998a](#)). Pupfish habitat is clear, shallow, alkaline springs and streams. Non-native salt-cedar line the banks of much the dune segment of Lost River, with saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*) as a common ground cover. Pickleweed (*Allenrolfea occidentalis*) is common in the ephemeral wetted flats. Algae and pondweed (*Potamogeton* sp.) are common aquatic species, especially in the more lentic sites, and provide forage for the pupfish (Pittenger 1994, G. Harper and E. Muldavin, personal observation). Its habitat is protected under a cooperative agreement, the White Sands Pupfish Conservation Plan, between the U.S. Army (WSMR), U.S. Air Force (HAFB), National Park Service (WSNM), U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, and New Mexico Department of Game and Fish.

Four extant populations of pupfish exist within the basin; three are on WSMR and one on Holloman AFB. Two of the populations were introduced. The Mound Springs population is on WSMR, and the Holloman Lost River population of 30 individuals was introduced from Salt Creek in 1970 (Pittenger and Springer, 1996; Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Studies conducted on the introduced populations suggest that the Mound Springs and Lost River populations have undergone rapid evolution in response to local ecological conditions, presumably salinity differences. The Lost River population is distributed in three stream segments connected by water only at times of heavy rains (Figure 13): the Malone-Ritas Draw segment above Range Road 9, the trench segment between Range Road 9 and the Lost River Basin, and the dunes segment downstream from the basin (Pittenger and Springer 1996).

Figure 13. Pupfish Populations and Protected Habitat Zone

Protected habitat zone for the White Sands Pupfish is an area 200 meters on either side of the middle of the drainage.

Approximately 130 cultural sites have been identified within this management unit. These sites have been classified according to the type of disturbance that would adversely affect protection of the sites. There are over 90 sites that are sensitive to trampling and 14 sites that may be destroyed by fire. The remaining sites (27) are mostly cold war artifacts. Sites that are sensitive to trampling are concentrated within approximately 300 meters of the edge of Malone Draw, Ritas Draw, and Carter Draw. A buffer along these drainages to protect pupfish habitat (Figure 13) will function to protect some of these sites; however, sites at further distances north of Upper Malone Draw may be at risk for ground disturbance.

Test Track

The Test Track Management unit comprises 3,419 ha (8,448 acres) and is a complex area composed principally of Upland Ecosystem types (Figure 7). Its western boundary is an ecotone having elements of the duneland system and progressively grades eastward into the alluvial flat shrublands with gypsiferous soils. Most of the drainages that enter the base eventually dissect lands within this mapping unit.

Figure 14. Test Track MU Vegetation Mapping Units
Vegetation Mapping Units found within Test Track Management Unit.

Topography within this long and narrow MU is relatively flat, ranging in elevation from 1236-1260m (4055 - 4134 feet). Three soil units dominate: Holloman-Gypsum land-Yesum complex, Duneland Yesum Association, and Mead silty clay loam (Figure 5). The Holloman-Gypsum land-Yesum complex covers 91% of the MU with Duneland Yesum Association and Mead silty clay loam covering 6% and 3%, respectively. The Holloman-Gypsum land-Yesum Association are soils formed in mixed eolian and alluvial gypsiferous sediments. They can have horizons either well-drained, shallow or deep. They are calcareous throughout and mildly alkaline, having moderate permeability and available water capacity. The Duneland Yesum Association enters the western border of the MU above Hay Draw and extends approximately 900 meters into the MU. The Duneland-Yesum association is 55% Dune land and 30% Yesum very fine sandy loam. Cryptogams occur within the Duneland-Yesum and Yesum-Holloman association soil groups (Neher and Bailey 1976) and are sparsely to densely distributed. The Mead silty clay loam soil type occurs within the arroyo bottoms. It has a surface layer of reddish-brown silty clay or clay loam, underlain by clays high in salt. Beyond 48 inches deep, the subsoils are formed from lakebed sediments (*See Chapter 3 - Soils and Geology*).

Although the Test Track and Northern Shrublands MU are dominated by the same soil unit, differences in the vegetation communities between these units suggest edaphic differences. The Test Track MU is dominated by Fourwing Saltbush/Gyp Dropseed Shrubland, while the Northern Shrublands MU is dominated by Fourwing Saltbush/Alkali Sacaton Shrubland. Both MUs contain approximately 15% Gyp Dropseed Grassland. A more detailed soil survey would help define the soil properties that support one community over another and help explain the spatial distributions of the dominant plant communities.

Typically, gypsic environments are small outcrops, widely distributed in southern New Mexico to Texas, but are disjunct and appear as 'islands' among a vast landscape of more broadly distributed substrates (Hicks and Whitcomb 1996). In contrast, Holloman gypsic conditions are derived from eolian materials that create a gypsum crust over sedimentary units. Gypsophilous plant communities that are widespread on Holloman AFB also exist on these gypsic islands in Texas. These dominant plant communities are: fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed, gyp dropseed/hairy coldenia, and gyp dropseed-alkali sacaton, cover 51% of the area within the Test Track MU (Figure 14). Another 24 percent include alkaline-tolerant plant communities such as fourwing saltbush/sparse and fourwing saltbush/alkali sacaton. Other communities cover less than 3%. Development and other disturbance related primarily to Test Track activities encompass 12% of this MU. (Muldavin et al. 1998).

Shrublands dominate the Test Track MU. Fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed, the most common type, occupies swales and basin bottom flats in a mildly undulating surface, often between mounds hardened by gypsic crusts dominated by gyp dropseed/hairy coldenia (Figure 7). Other common shrub associates of fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed communities are: Christmas cactus (*Opuntia leptocaulis*), kingcup cactus (*Echinocereus triglochidiatus*), and Berlandier's wolfberry (*Lycium berlandieri*). Fourwing Saltbush/Alkali Sacaton Shrubland and Alkali Sacaton Grassland mapping units are within the upland regions bounded on the south by Sheep Camp Draw and the north by Guilez Draw near the northern extent of the MU. Common associates of fourwing saltbush/alkali sacaton are Tulip and purple pricklypear (*Opuntia phaeacantha* and *O. Macrantha*) and crucifix thorn (*Koeberlinia spinosa*). This area between the draws makes transition between Great Basin Shrublands and Chihuahuan Desert Scrub. Within the northern extent of the MU, Creosotebush Shrubland occurs on the piedmont and alluviated surfaces of Tularosa Peak. The Creosotebush Shrubland is either sparse or dominated by an understory of alkali sacaton grasslands. Sub-shrubs such as hairy coldenia and snakeweed may be present.

The Arroyo Riparian Ecosystem is an integral desert process. It contains and connects elements that affect the flows of energy, material, and species through the landscape (Malanson 1993). The plant composition of the arroyo has high potential for flux considering the disturbances caused by seasonal flooding. Three of the pervasive vegetation mapping units represented within the draws are Pickleweed Shrubland, Semi-riparian Alkali Sacaton Grassland, and Salt Cedar Woodland. Occasional wetland plants such as saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*) and mojave seablite (*Sueda moquinii*) are distributed within the reaches of the draw that receive more permanent ponding are situated closer to a high water table. Pickleweed often occurs with fourwing saltbush within the playa-like reaches of the arroyos. There is historical evidence indicating that pickleweed was less prolific than it is today (Hawthorne-Tagg 1997; See Chapter 4 - Northern Shrublands). Local extinction of some native plants and an increase of more xeric plants may have occurred due to overgrazing (Trammell 1995). Changes in plant communities and structure may also have affected native wildlife composition. Because the arroyos receive intermittent, seasonal flows, the size, density, and structure of semi-riparian alkali

sacaton communities are larger and more dense than adjacent upland communities of alkali sacaton.

The High Speed Test Track is second only to the Cantonment MU in terms of development and ground disturbance, with 12% of its area devoted to military purposes. The test track lies perpendicular to the east-west draws and in some cases, particularly within Hay Draw, Guilez, and Allen draws, alters the natural flow of these systems. Due to the nature of the testing involved with the High Speed Test Track, materials ejected from the track can impact at any location within the MU. Areas receiving the greatest impact and use are at the northern end of the track and the southern end near the north bank of Lost River.

Road surveys conducted by the NMNHP in 1995 for the Texas horned lizard (*Phrynosomum cornutum*) found the greatest number of species and individuals on the Camera Pad Road survey route (within this MU), while Boles Acres Road had the highest density (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). *P. cornutum* was the most abundant reptile found on Camera Pad Road. Lizard activity on HAFB is greatest in late May and early June, coincident with the mating season. In the summer of 1995, lizard activity peaked from 0730-1115 hrs. and again from 1725-2000 hrs., with ground surface temperatures ranging from 78°F to 100°F (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). A potential threat to the Texas horned lizard is the introduced fire ant (*Solenopsis invicta*). This species is spreading westward, but has not yet attained a high density in arid lands. The fire could swarm and sting the lizard to death or limit the potential prey of the lizard (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). On HAFB the arid climate and xeric vegetation communities probably will not support this ant in significant numbers (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Thus, HAFB potentially can offer a safe harbor for *P. cornutum* over the long term.

The Western Burrowing Owl is classified by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service as a Species of Concern (formerly Federal Candidate 2 species) and as an informal Species of Concern by the state of New Mexico (See Chapter 6 - Sensitive Species; Mehlhop et al. 1998a; Johnson et al. 1997b). The greatest density of occupied and nesting owl burrows is within the Test Track MU (Johnson et al. 1997b). Owl burrows were found primarily in sparsely vegetated areas dominated by gyp dropseed/alkali Sacaton grasslands. Populations of Burrowing Owls are declining in other states; New Mexico is ranked as the second most important over-wintering area (Johnson et al. 1997b).

Bat forage sites and maternity roots are located within the Test Track MU. The small wetlands that abut the High Speed Test Track at the mouth of Guilez Draw are known foraging sites for the pallid bat (*Antrozous pallidus*) and hoary bat (*Lasiurus cinereus*). Many of the pallid bat prey are flightless (O'Shea and Vaughan 1977), while the hoary bat feeds primarily on small moths (Black 1972). Two maternity roots for the pallid bat are within the High Speed Test Track buildings north of Lost River.

DNA tests in process will determine if the woodrats collected on Holloman AFB are a distinct subspecies. If tests determine subspecific level, the White Sands Woodrat (*Neotoma micropus leucophaea*) should be regarded as a species of concern (See

[Mehlhop et al. 1998a](#) for specifics on management recommendations). Nine White Sands Woodrats were captured at seven middens during NMNHP's surveys, June to November 1994, three within the Test Track MU and another three just outside the MU boundaries (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Six of the midden sites were within Fourwing Saltbush/Gyp Dropseed Shrubland, the dominant vegetation mapping unit of the Test Track MU. Middens were beneath honey mesquite (*Prosopis glandulosa*).

Little work has been done to document the insect fauna in gyp environments (Hicks and Whitcomb 1996). Research in low elevation areas of the Chihuahuan Desert in New Mexico and Texas identified three leafhopper specialists within grassland communities dominated by either gyp grama (*Bouteloua breviseta*), gyp dropseed (*Sporobolus nealleyi*), or inland saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*). These species are *Athysanella blockerii*, *A. stylosa*, and *A. pastora* (Hicks and Whitcomb 1996). *Athysanella blockerii* is a new species (Hicks and Whitcomb 1996). This study found leafhopper composition was explained almost entirely by the plant composition of the gyp communities. These plant communities are well represented on Holloman AFB and may host these endemic insect fauna.

Only twenty cultural sites have been identified within the Test Track MU. Of these, 9 need to be protected from vehicle traffic, 2 are sensitive to fire, and the remaining 9 are Cold War artifacts and do not require any particular protection. The sensitive sites are widely scattered and lie predominantly between the test track and Camera Pad Road.

Lake Holloman Wetlands

Lake Holloman Wetlands Management Unit comprises 715 ha (1,767 acres) north of highway 70 and 63 ha (131 acres) located south of the highway (Figure 9). The Holloman Lakes MU is in the southernmost part of the base, directly south of the Cantonment Management Unit. Prominent physical features within the unit are Lake Holloman and Stinky Playa, both former large alkali playa lakes. East of the playa lakes is a series of shallow depressions, lagoons, and intermittent drainages that were formerly part of the historic reaches of Dillard Draw (USAF 1996). Historic connections between the upper alluvial system and the basin lowland ecosystem, including Lake Holloman and Stinky Playa, have been interrupted by road development and military construction. In 1997, in cooperation with the USFWS, Holloman AFB built a system of berms, ditches, and control structures to create a constructed wetland. The wetland roughly encompasses the area containing and lying between Lagoon G and Lake Holloman (Figure 15). Prior to the establishment of the constructed wetland, surface water within this MU covered 90 ha (222 acres) and included the group of lagoons north of Lagoon G (Figure 7). With the constructed wetland, surface water may reach 140 ha (347 acres).

This management unit lies within the topographically flattest areas on the base. Elevations range from 1,224m (4,015.7 feet) to 1,235 m (4,051.8 feet). Although many structural modifications have been made in this area, it is a remnant of the naturally

occurring playa environment created by depositional processes. Dillard Draw, an ephemeral stream with its headwaters at the flanks of the Sacramento Mountains, combines downstream with various channels of the bajada and empties into naturally occurring playas located east of the primary housing area. Seasonal fluctuations in precipitation affect water availability into the naturally occurring playas.

Figure 15. Constructed Wetland Study Area

Constructed wetlands encompass the area between Lake Holloman and Lagoon G. Jurisdictional wetlands and Waters of the US were designated prior to construction of the wetland complex. Bird surveys and Snowy Plover nest sites are depicted on the map. All wetland bird survey sites were censused from 1994-1997 except those numbered 1-3. Survey site (1) 1996-97, (2) 1994-95, (3) 1996-97.

The constructed wetland was built to provide storage capacity for treated sewage effluent

for a new wastewater treatment plant. Originally, the wastewater from the old plant flowed into seven lagoons, including Lagoon G, then to Lake Holloman and Stinky Playa (Figure 7). All lagoons, except Lagoon G, were closed by the end of 1997. The treated wastewater from the new facility flows by gravity into Lake Holloman and then is pumped to the north end of Lagoon G where a series of berms and control structures direct water through the constructed wetland (Figure 15). The constructed wetland was completed and operational on November 21, 1997 when the surface ditch carrying water from the water treatment plant was opened (Freehling et al. 1997). Treated wastewater is used to create quality wildlife habitat, particularly for migrating and breeding shorebirds. The constructed wetland adds 40.5-50.6 ha. (100-125 acres) of mudflat, shallow water, and playa habitat to the existing mudflat, playa, and deep-water habitats present at the Holloman Lakes, producing the largest wetland in the Tularosa Basin. Because of the constructed wetland project, Holloman AFB was recognized by the Southwest Environmental Center in 1996 for their outstanding contribution to service for the environment in New Mexico.

Yesum-Holloman soils create an uneven mosaic of moderate to highly alkaline soils with flat to moderately undulating surfaces. The Yesum Series is a deep, well-drained soil derived from wind-deposited sediments, high in gypsum. These soils contain fine gypsum crystals; surfaces are nearly level with slightly undulating areas caused by changing wind deposition patterns. The Holloman series are shallow, well drained, and moderately alkaline. This moderately permeable soil is formed from loamy and sandy alluvium deposited over gypsum beds in old lake depressions. The underlying gypsum layers range from soft to hard and are 10 to 51 cm (4 to 20 inches) below the sandy loam. The Gypsum land soils in this mapping unit are partially stabilized and hummocky, derived from wind-blown gypsum crystals of relict lakebeds (see Chapter 3 - Soils and Geology).

Figure 16. Lake Holloman Wetlands Vegetation Mapping Units

Vegetation mapping units found within the Lake Holloman Wetlands Management Unit.

Fluctuating water levels, topographic variation, and proximity to military facilities have resulted in a diverse mix of natural and introduced vegetation types at the Lake Holloman Wetland MU. All ecosystems listed in Table 4 are represented in this MU. The Playa and Upland Ecosystem each contribute to approximately 30% of the variation in cover type, followed by Constructed Wetland with 16% (Figure 16). Arroyo Riparian Ecosystem, including salt cedar woodlands, cover 11% of the area. Development and disturbance cover 8%, and the remaining variation is gyp dropseed grasslands.

The Playa Ecosystem represented in this MU includes the vegetation mapping units of Pickleweed Shrubland and Barren Alkaline Playa (Table 4). The distribution of Pickleweed Shrubland, which contains the community types of pickleweed/sparse, pickleweed-Mojave seablite, and pickleweed/alkali sacaton, is an indicator of lowland depressions and periodically flooded areas (Figure 7). Most of these vegetation communities and barren alkaline playas are now included within the constructed wetland complex and comprise the majority of cover in the disjunct section below Hwy 70. Vegetation mapping units represented in the Upland Ecosystem type are: Alkali Sacaton Grassland, Fourwing Saltbush/Alkali Sacaton Shrubland, and Sparse Fourwing Saltbush Shrubland. The major community types included within these mapping units are: fourwing saltbush/alkali sacaton, fourwing saltbush/sparse, and alkali sacaton/monotypic. These communities occur within both upland and lowland depressions and are distributed east of Lake Holloman, north of the constructed wetlands, often surrounding lowland playas. Arroyo Riparian Ecosystem types include Semi-riparian Alkali Sacaton Grasslands and Saltcedar Woodland mapping units. Saltcedar woodlands surround Lake Holloman and Lagoon G and line ditches at the constructed wetland. The Constructed Wetland Ecosystem includes the Wetland mapping unit that occurs at the fringes of Lake Holloman, Stinky Playa, and Lagoon G (Figure 15). Other wetland sites, near Lagoon G and the constructed wetland control structures, have been enhanced due to diversion and channelization of stormwater drainages (USAF 1996). The dominant Wetland Ecosystem community type is inland saltgrass/monotypic and may also include: spreading alkaliweed (*Cressa truxillensis*), Mojave seablite (*Suaeda moquinii*), saltmarsh bullrush (*Scirpus maritimus*), seep willow (*Baccharis salicifolia*), smooth [desert] seepweed (*Suaeda suffrutescens*), and Transpecos sea-lavender (*Limonium limbatum*).

Wetlands absorb and filter a variety of sediments, nutrients and other natural and manmade pollutants that would otherwise degrade rivers, streams and lakes. Water flowing from uplands into water bodies often passes through wetlands, which maintain and improve water quality by filtering out nutrients and sediments before they reach the river or stream (USAF 1996). Wetlands hold the nutrients that contribute to their high rate of primary productivity that is measured in increased plant growth. Alkali sacaton grasses in periodically flooded areas grow larger than upland ecotypes. These plants provide a food source for invertebrates and microfauna, which support the diverse resident, over-wintering, and migratory bird populations at Holloman AFB.

Jurisdictional wetlands are based on three primary field indicators: hydrophytic vegetation, hydrology, and hydric soils (USAF 1996). The majority of Holloman AFB [jurisdictional](#)

[wetlands and waters of the U.S.](#) are concentrated within the Lake Holloman Wetlands MU. Natural recharge to this area has been altered by increased inflow from the wastewater treatment facility and stormwater drainage ditches.

The wetland complex provides habitat for mainly migrating, a few breeding, and very few over-wintering waterbird species. Within the Tularosa Basin, the Lake Holloman wetlands and Malpais Spring on WSMR are the largest wetlands in this large, arid region. The NMNHP conducted bird censuses at various survey sites at Lake Holloman, Stinky Playa, and Lagoon G between 1994 and 1998 (Figure 16). The majority of waterbirds recorded during these surveys used the wetland habitat at Holloman AFB as a migratory stopover (Mehlhop et al. 1998b). Census data taken at Lake Holloman, Stinky Playa, and Lagoon G, during 1994-95, show habitat use by waterbird species ([Species/Habitat Table](#)). Preliminary comparisons of shorebird species at Lake Holloman, Lagoon G, and the constructed wetland in April and May of 1997, indicated that there is a high similarity among the three sites in species use ([Freehling et al. 1997](#)).

In addition, foraging habitat surveys conducted at these waterbodies found that saturated mudflat and wet saltflat microhabitats had the highest species richness and abundance of foraging waterbirds ([Freehling et al. 1997](#)). Studies of the invertebrate community are currently in progress (Freehling et al., manuscript in preparation). Because of construction activities for the new wastewater treatment facility, higher water levels in Lake Holloman occurred throughout 1997. This resulted in a loss of most of these shallow water and mudflat habitats, increasing the importance of the habitats created within the constructed wetland complex to the continued presence of shorebirds.

[Snowy Plover](#) foraging and nesting habitat at Lake Holloman has also been diminished due to rising water levels. Suitable Snowy Plover habitat was incidentally created when Lagoon G was drained during 1997 construction of the new wetland. Fecal analysis of Snowy Plovers found *Bledius* spp. present in at least 30% of the pellets sampled. The ubiquity of *Bledius* spp. may prove to be an important indicator of the habitat quality for Snowy Plovers and other shorebirds within the Lake Holloman Wetlands ([Freehling et al. 1997](#), See Chapter 6 - Sensitive Species - Snowy Plover, [Mehlhop et al. 1998a](#)).

Other waterbird species of concern, such as the [Neotropic Cormorant](#) (*Phalacrocorax brasilianus*) and [Interior Least Tern](#) (*Sterna antillarum athalassos*) are protected under the North American Migratory Bird Treaty Act. They are rare vagrants to southern New Mexico wetlands and are accidental visitors to the Holloman wetlands (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). The Neotropic Cormorant is not federally protected but is a rare or uncommon breeder within New Mexico and therefore has a NMNHP rank of S3 for breeding and nesting status. It is ranked Endangered Group 2 within New Mexico, because its prospects of survival or recruitment in New Mexico are likely to be in jeopardy within the foreseeable future (NMGF Reg. 563). This species nests in dead snags or trees over or near water; therefore, newly flooded areas within the constructed wetlands that have dead salt cedar snags could provide suitable habitat for this species (Mehlhop et al. 1998a).

The Interior Least Tern was listed as Endangered on May 28, 1985 (Department of Interior 1994) and has a state Endangered, Group 1 status as of May 21, 1976 (NMGF Reg. 563 1988). The prospects of survival or recruitment in New Mexico are in jeopardy. Nesting habitat for the Interior Least Tern is similar to that of the Snowy Plover, where vegetation is sparse and playas are ephemerally inundated. Holloman AFB current management practices that support maintaining habitat for the Snowy Plover will also provide good habitat for the Interior Least Tern.

The [White-faced Ibis](#) (*Plegadis chihi*) was formerly a Federal Species of Concern, Category 2. It has no legal protection under the Endangered Species Act and is not protected by the state. The NMNHP lists the White-faced Ibis as a critically-imperiled breeder because of extreme rarity in the state (S1B), but it is apparently secure in the non-breeding season (S4N). The White-faced Ibis commonly uses mudflat and emergent vegetation at the wetlands on Holloman AFB (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Periodic flooding provides a continuous supply of invertebrate forage.

The wetland complex is also used by 22 species of ducks, 15 of which are frequent visitors. The most abundant, the Ruddy Duck, can be found throughout the year, followed by the Northern Shoveler, which becomes less abundant during the summer. The Canada Goose (*Branta canadensis*) and Snow Goose (*Chen caerulescens*) are occasional migrants. Ducks, geese, Scaled Quail (*Callipepla squamata*), and Mourning Dove (*Zenaidura macroura*) are hunted at Lake Holloman (See Chapter 6-Fish and Wildlife Management-Hunting).

The mosquitofish (*Gambusia affinis*) were apparently introduced by New Mexico Game and Fish into ditches, lagoons, and Lake Holloman to control mosquito populations. Exact population figures are unknown, but the populations are large due to the lack of natural predators. The best mosquito fish habitat is in stormwater runoff ditches due to good aeration. The population seems reasonably secure, even in the highly alkaline and saline waters of Lake Holloman and Lagoon G. Because the species is highly aggressive and bears its young live (avoiding the egg stage with its high predation rate), mosquito fish would likely eliminate any experimental pupfish populations introduced to Lake Holloman. Given that the constructed wetland receives treated effluent from Lagoon G, it is assumed the fish have entered the constructed wetlands.

It would be difficult to eliminate *Gambusia* from Lake Holloman because, under the Clean Water Act, mosquito fish are considered an “attained use”, and water quality must be maintained at standards protective to the fish, even if the fish are eliminated by some outside event. The water is too saline and alkaline to introduce other species of game fish.

Herpetofauna surveys, concentrating on the Texas horned lizard, were conducted along roads within Holloman AFB and the Boles Wells Water System Annex. Because these surveys were conducted along roads, the area within this MU was not represented in the survey. No data exist within the Holloman Lakes area for herpetofauna.

Only three cultural sites have been identified within this management unit. Two sites warrant protection from trampling and vehicle traffic while the other site requires no particular protection.

Boles Wells Water System Annex

The Boles Wells Water System Annex (Annex) is a geographically separated area comprising 2901.6 ha (6922.7 acres) that lies within the alluvial fans of the Sacramento Mountains, south of Alamogordo. The annex consists of 2 sections, the Boles Wells Well Field to the north and the Southern Well fields to the south (Figures 4 and 9). The principal use of the area is to provide potable water for Holloman AFB. After a water shortage in 1947, Holloman AFB entered into a contract with Luther Boles to develop and transport water to the base (Hawthorne 1994). Between 1947 and 1957 Holloman AFB drilled an additional 36 wells. In 1955 competition between the Air Force and local farmers and ranchers resulted in condemnation suits by the Air Force to acquire land and water rights from landowners (Public Land Orders 3434 and 4667). By 1960, all condemnation proceedings were completed. Boles and other landowners were subsequently compensated for land and water rights.

The wellfields receive groundwater recharge from six canyons: Lead Canyon, Muleshoe Canyon, Andres Canyon, Dog Canyon, Deadman Canyon, and Escondido Canyon. Depth to groundwater is approximately 82 m (270 feet); however, the last well was drilled to a depth of 396m (1300 feet). The depths of the wells are considered sufficient to prevent contamination by sewage effluent from adjacent residential communities. The only significant drawdowns for the aquifer were recorded during the drought of 1982.

Fourteen wells are in full operation a fifteenth needs repairs. The primary wells produce the following water flows:

- San Andres 100 gal/min
- Escondido 1250 gal/min, set at 1150 gal/min
- Frenchie I 1750 gal/min, set at 1650/min
- Frenchie II 650 gal/min
- Douglas IV 650-1000 gal/min

The wells pump sand mixed with water into a sand trap that separates the sands from the water, subsequently depositing water into the Boles Well tank. From the tank, pipelines carry the water to Holloman AFB. No pumping is required to deliver the water due to a mean elevation difference of 60m (197 feet).

Another water source for the base comes from the Bonito Pipeline. Holloman AFB owns 75 miles of the 90-mile pipeline, which conveys water from Bonito Lake, through Carrizozo to the City of Alamogordo. HAFB has rights to a portion of the water and obtains credits during periods when the water is not in use. In order to maintain those credits, the base must use some portion of water. When water use exceeds the credit

quantity, the base pays the city of Alamogordo for water. The city owns and operates the water treatment plant.

Holloman AFB uses City of Alamogordo water from the Bonito pipeline six months of the year, during the cooler months when water use is approximately 1.5 million gal/day. The Annex is used during the warmer months when water use ranges from 2.8 to 3.0 million gal/day. This schedule allows recharge of well aquifers during the cooler months and Bonito pipeline maintenance during the summer. Three consecutive years of non-use would jeopardize Holloman AFB water rights to the Bonito pipeline. In order to preserve water rights to the Bonito pipeline, Holloman AFB conducted repairs when the Bonito pipeline was out of operation between 1995-97. During this period of repair, the Annex was used year-round, and substantial drawdowns of the wellfield aquifers were not recorded.

Boles Wells Well Field

The Boles Wells Well Field (BWFF) comprises 645 ha (1,595 acres) within the alluvial flats of the Sacramento Mountains (Figures 4 and 9). The wellfield is characterized by nearly level topography dissected by natural ephemeral streams, channelized drainages, and excavated basins. Within these lowland areas, seasonal precipitation events create ponds in the saturated soils of swales and playas. [Jurisdictional waters of the U.S.](#) cover 2.2 ha (5.47 acres) and 8,409 m (27,589 linear feet) which include numerous ephemeral streams, occasionally flooded basins, and a permanently flooded impoundment ([United States Air Force 1996](#)). The Boles Wells pond (south of the Boles tank and east of US Highway 54) was formerly a ranch pond and has fresh water from overflow of the Boles Well tank. It is not known if fish inhabit the pond.

Prior to condemnation by the U.S. Air Force, beginning in the late 1800s, the BWFF was used for farming and livestock grazing (Hawthorne 1994). Much of the soil and native vegetation has been eroded and replaced by non-natives due to farming and grazing practices. Sparse vegetative cover and monsoonal precipitation events subject the area to extensive sheet erosion (Hawthorne 1994). Three soil types dominate the BWFF, they are: Largo-Ogral complex, Tome silt loam, and Mimbres-Tome association (*See Chapter 3 - Soils and Geology*). The soils form elongated bands that extend westward from the mountain front (Figure 6). The Largo-Ogral complex lies closest to the mountain front and consists of gently sloping pediments of very fine sandy loam. The Tome silt loam is located at the lower parts of the pediments, forming fan-shaped alluvium on nearly level to concave surfaces. These are dissected by small meandering drainages. This area is subject to flooding and, when surface soils are exposed, become susceptible to high wind erosion (Derr et al. 1981). The Tome silt loam is the major soil type for the BWFF. The Mimbres-Tome association lies at the fringes of the alluvial fan within the basin bottom. Having a moderately slow permeability, these soils are often flooded for short periods following intense rainstorms (Derr et al. 1981).

Figure 17. Boles Wells Well Field Vegetation Mapping Units

Vegetation Mapping Units found within the Boles Wells Well Field. A vegetation map for the southern portions of the BWWSA does not exist. These data cover only the BWWF.

Honey Mesquite Shrubland is the dominant vegetation cover in the BWWF, comprising 76.7% of the total vegetation cover (Figures 8 and 17). This shrubland is dominated by honey mesquite, but it may include other broad-leaf Chihuahuan Scrub, such as fourwing saltbush, tarbush, and lotebush (*Ziziphus obtusifolia*). This sparse shrubland is generally devoid of grasses, or grasses may be very scattered (Muldavin et al. 1998). This vegetation type is ubiquitous in the BWWF lower alluvials and basin flats. Honey Mesquite/Feather Fingergrass Shrubland occurs in shallow swales and drainages and covers 7.4% of vegetation cover within the BWWF. Feather fingergrass (*Chloris virgata*) exists within the understory of the honey mesquite, sometimes with scattered clumps of alkali sacaton (Muldavin et al. 1998) and is quick to colonize disturbed areas. Creosotebush Shrubland covers 9.4% of the area and occurs on the Largo-Ogral soil complex on the upper alluvials. The understory of this shrubland is typically sparse and may contain scattered occurrences of black grama (*Bouteloua eriopoda*) or mariola (*Parthenium incanum*). Several roads, buildings, and dump sites account for 5.3% of surface cover. Other types of cover make up 1.2% and include: urban vegetation, salt cedar, surface water, and wetlands.

There have been wildlife sightings of porcupine and mule deer (*Odocoileus hemionus*) near the facilities on BWWF. Other wildlife species common to the area include coyote (*Canis latrans*) and jackrabbit (*Lepus californicus*). The Texas horned lizard, a Species of Concern (Department of Interior 1996), is abundant throughout the BWWSA ([Mehlhop et al. 1998](#)). The silty loams and sparsely vegetated shrublands of the lower alluvial fans provide good burrowing habitat and provide an adequate food supply of

harvester ants (*Pogonomyrmex*). Wetlands located near the facilities within the BWFF provide good foraging habitat for several bats, including: pallid (*Antrozous pallidus*), big brown (*Eptesicus fuscus*), small-footed myotis (*Myotis ciliolabrum*), big free-tailed (*Nyctinomops macrotis*), Western pipistrelle (*Pipistrellus hesperus*), and Mexican free-tailed (*Tadarida brasiliensis*) bats. Common birds sighted of the BWFF are: Gambel's Quail (*Callipela gambelii*), Common Nighthawk (*Chordeiles acutipennis*), Common Poorwill (*Phalaenoptilus nuttallii*), White-throated Swift (*Aeronautes saxatalis*), Broad-tailed Hummingbird (*Selasphorus platycercus*), Bewick's Wren (*Thryomanes bewickii*), and Bronzed Cowbird (*Molothrus aeneus*). Electrocuting of Great Horned Owl and potentially of other raptor species at the electrical substation was apparently controlled by fencing the area, eliminating access by prey species, such as rabbits.

The BWFF has 27 cultural sites, primarily associated with historic events involving homestead activities early in the century. The majority of sites are sensitive to trampling, including vehicle traffic (25). Two of the sites are remnants of historic structures that could be destroyed by fire.

Southern Well Fields (Douglas and San Andres)

The Southern Well Fields (SWF) comprises 2,156 ha (5,327 acres) in two fields separated by private and state lands. The Oliver Reed State Park lies nearly half-way between the Douglas and San Andres Well Fields (Figures 1 and 9). These lands lie within the alluvial fan of the Sacramento Mountains and are heavily dissected by ephemeral drainages creating a rolling topography.

Soils are predominantly the Nickel-Tencee association (Figure 6) at the pediment toe slopes and upper portion of the alluvial fans. These gravelly sandy loams grade into the Tome silt loams and Mimbres-Tome association at lower elevations on the fan to basin bottom (See Chapter 3 - Soils and Geology). Areas not covered in the soil survey are shown in green (Figure 6).

Although neither vegetation surveys nor maps have been made, much of the area is dominated by various creosotebush communities. The fairly shallow and gravelly soils support creosotebush/sparse, creosotebush/mariola, and creosotebush/black grama. Creosotebush is poor forage for wildlife and some evidence suggests creosotebush inhibits the establishment of other shrub species (Mahall and Callaway 1991, Muldavin et al. 1997). The competitive advantage of creosotebush over other shrubs does not explain the lack of grasses. Nearby sites, such as those within the Oliver Reed State Park, share the same substrate type but have a greater plant diversity and vegetation cover. Past use of the area for grazing may explain the degradation of these sites.

Less than a kilometer to the east on BLM administered lands is habitat for four threatened and endangered plant species: Alamo Canyon beardtongue (*Penstemon alamosensis*), Villard's pincushion cactus (*Escobaria villardii*), button cactus (*Epithelantha micromeris*), and the Sacramento prickly poppy (*Argemone pleiacantha* ssp).

pinnatisecta). Surveys have been conducted by NMNHP in cooperation with the BLM to determine if these species occur on Holloman AFB lands or the adjacent Sacramento Mountain foothills. None of these species has been found to occur within Holloman AFB lands.

Within the southernmost extent of the BWWSA, an archaeological site, sensitive to destruction by fire, sits between two drainages on the alluvial fan. The site has historical importance to ranching in the Tularosa Basin and could be considered for the National Register (Hawthorne 1994). The area is currently grazed and has potential threats due to past vandalism.

Geographically Separated Units

Five geographically separated units (GSUs) are located on White Sands Missile Range and managed by Holloman AFB. These include the Red Rio Bombing Range (RRBR), Oscura Bombing Range (OBR), Radar Target Scatter Complex (RATSCAT), RATSCAT Advanced Measurement Site (RAMS), and Air Force Special Weapons Complex (AFSWC) - Weapons Impact Target (WIT).

Red Rio Bombing Range

Red Rio Bombing Range encompasses approximately 54,800 ha (135,400 acres) located in the far northeast portion of the range. The area is bounded on the northeast by NM State Highway 380, to the east by the eastern WSMR boundary, and to the south by the OBR. (Figure 18). To the west it includes the northern extent of the Oscura Mountains; access to the site is restricted by WSMR. The bombing range has been used for nearly thirty years as a target/impact area for inert bombs, rockets, cannon, and machine guns. Past military activities have been conducted throughout RRBR; however, current military firing operations occur within an 810 ha (2,000 acres) impact zone located within a safety area (Figure 18) of approximately 21,350 ha (52,750 acres). Since 1995, one target site within the impact zone has been used for live bomb practice.

The range is situated between two subsections of the Basin and Range physiographic province. It is located at the northern extent of the Tularosa Basin within the Mexican Highlands Section and at the eastern boundary of the Sacramento Section in the northern Jornada (Hawley 1986). The site has physiographic characteristics representative of both sections. Typical of the Mexican Highland Section are the Oscura Mountains, a block-faulted range that dips to the east. The Oscura range is capped with Pennsylvanian limestone underlain by Middle Proterozoic plutonic rocks (Anderson 1997). To the east are several uplifted, east-dipping cuestas and the Chupadera Mesa. This complex of uplifted cuestas and hills is dissected by narrow drainages that flow south into the Tularosa Basin. The cuesta-form mountains are representative of the Sacramento Section

and are predominantly capped by Permian Age limestone and sandstone with gypsum interbedded (Hawley 1986). Exposed sedimentary sequences include the red beds of the Abo and Bursum Formations, gypsic strata of the Yeso Formation, and the San Andres limestone and Glorieta sandstone. Alluviated materials from the mostly Pennsylvanian and Permian Age sediments accumulate as basin fill at the mouth of the drainages. The largest occurrences of these Quaternary deposits occur at the mouth of Red Canyon and the sub-basin on the east side of the Oscura Mountains.

A soil survey following the Soil Taxonomy, U.S. Department of Agriculture (Soil Survey Staff 1975) identified nineteen soil series and soil complexes. Shallow soils formed from alluvium, colluvium or eolian materials of sandstone or sandstone-shale facies include the Travesilla-Rock outcrop, Rock outcrop-Lithic Torriorthents, Rock outcrop-Lithic Ustic Torriorthents-Travesilla complex, and the Loarc-Bernal-Rock outcrop complex. Deep soils formed in alluvium from sandstone, limestone, and shale members comprised the La Fonda loam, Dean-Suwanee-La Fonda association, Manzano clay loam, Suwanee clay loam, and La Fonda-Tanbark-Deama complex. Soils derived from predominantly limestone and gypsum outcrops and formed in alluvium and eolian materials are the Deama very gravelly loam, La Fonda-Neotoma-Deama complex, Winona-Rock outcrop complex, Tortugas-Rock outcrop, Rock outcrop-Tanbark-Deama complex, Deama-Tortugas-Rock outcrop, and Cuate-Deama-Tanbark complex. Soils are generally stabilized where covered in natural vegetation. Sites disturbed by bombing have moderate to severe soil loss.

Drainages within the bombing range flow during seasonal monsoons into both the Tularosa and Jornada del Muerto basins. All streams found within these basins are ephemeral surface drainages (New Mexico Water Quality Commission 1994). Intermittent streams and arroyos within RRBR are classified as Riverine, Intermittent Streambed Systems ([Cowardin et. al. 1979](#)). Some jurisdictional waters of the United States exist within RRBR; however no priority wetland sites exist within WSMR (New Mexico Department of Energy, Minerals, and Natural Resources 1991). Both the Red Canyon Spring and the Red Canyon Drainage transect the center of the Primary Impact Area (PIA), which is the principal water source for this area. A survey for potential jurisdictional wetlands was conducted within the PIA; however, none were classified as jurisdictional wetlands (Holloman AFB 1996). However, because portions of RRBR were not surveyed, wetlands may exist in these areas.

This topographically complex area supports a high diversity of plant community types. Temperate montane shrublands cover the steep to moderate western and southern slopes of the Oscura range and nearby cuestas. Plant communities included in this map unit are mountain mahogany (*Cercocarpus montanus*), usually with grassy undergrowths of either sideoats grama (*Bouteloua curtipendula*) or blue grama (*Bouteloua gracilis*); and shrub live oak (*Quercus turbinella*), with either blue grama or black grama (*Bouteloua eriopoda*) grasslands. Gently dipping slopes and platform summits at higher elevations within the Oscura range and nearby cuestas with northerly aspects are dominated by pinyon pine woodlands. Community types most often encountered within this mapping unit are pinyon pine (*Pinus edulis*)/Scribner's needlegrass (*Stipa scribneri*), or pinyon

pine/wavyleaf oak (*Quercus undulata*). Juniper woodlands occur on drier, east-facing slopes of the Oscura range and Chupadera Mesa. One-seed juniper (*Juniperus monosperma*) is found with either New Mexico needlegrass (*Stipa neomexicana*), curlyleaf muhly (*Muhlenbergia setifolia*), or blue grama grasslands. Foothill Montane grasslands largely dominated by blue grama or New Mexico needlegrass cover the foothill slopes of the mountain-valley fans, particularly the northern Red Canyon Valley. Gypsum outcrops of the Yeso Formation at the western extent of Chupadera Mesa are largely covered with gyp dropseed (*Sporobolus nealleyi*)/hairy coldenia (*Tiquilia hispidissima*) foothill grasslands. Mixed foothill-piedmont grasslands occur at mid-to low-elevation slopes, foothills, and upper alluvial fan piedmonts that alternate and interfinger with mixed lowland desert scrub. Grama grasses, creosotebush (*Larrea tridentata*) and fourwing saltbush (*Atriplex canescens*) populate these areas in the southern portion of RRBR (Muldavin et al. 1997).

Holloman Air Force Base conducted surveys for candidate, threatened, and endangered plants within the PIA and made cursory observations along roads in other portions of the range (Holloman AFB 1996). Nineteen populations of pineapple cactus (*Neolloydia intertextata* var. *dasyacantha*) were identified within the PIA. Four populations were observed on Range Road 11, one population on Range Road 335, 12 populations on Range Road 337, and two populations on Range Road 9. Pineapple cactus is a state listed L4 species. It was considered for listing but was determined to be too common within in New Mexico to be listed.

There is high wildlife diversity in part due to the variability in elevation and diverse plant communities.. This region provides suitable habitat and extensive ranges for native American pronghorn (*Antilocapra americana*), mule deer (*Odocoileus hemionus*), coyote (*Canis latrans*), and bobcat (*Lynx rufus*). Non-native feral horses (*Equus caballus*) and Oryx (*Oryx gazella*) also inhabit the range. Small mammals such as desert cottontail (*Sylvilagus audubonii*), woodrat (*Neotoma sp.*), and chipmunk (*Tamias sp.*) are common. During surveys conducted in September, 1995, five snakes, 9 lizards, 1 skink and a turtle were identified (HAFB 1995). Desert sands and alluvial plains within the southern extent of RRBR are the preferred habitat of the Round-tailed Horned Lizard (*Phrynosoma modestum*), New Mexico whiptail (*Cnemidophorus neomexicanus*), and Lesser Earless Lizard (*Holbrookia maculata*). Desert Striped Whipsnake (*Masticophis taeniatus*), Mountain Patch-Nosed Snake (*Salvadora grahamii*), and Western Whiptail Lizard (*Cnemidophorus tigris*) exist in open and sparsely vegetated areas of the alluvial fans and rocky slopes (Williamson et al. 1994). The complex of cuernas dissected by drainages and large contiguous areas covered with natural grasses and lowland shrubs and occasional trees for perching makes this area particularly suitable habitat for birds such as hawks and owls (Hall et al. 1988; BISON-M 1997). There is a high availability of small mammals and reptiles in these xeric communities (HAFB 1995). Seventy-three species of birds were observed during surveys conducted from September 11-28, 1995 within the RRBR, including the PIA (HAFB 1995). Although no candidate, threatened, or endangered species were observed, some migrants and breeders identified in the survey are currently being tracked by TNC. Of these, the Great Horned Owl, Red-tailed Hawk,

Prairie Falcon, and Swainson's Hawk have G4-G5/S4-S5 ratings, meaning they are relatively secure within the state, but possibly declining in other portions of its range.

Archeological sites have been identified throughout the RRBR, particularly in the eastern and southeastern quadrants. No archeological sites were identified within the PIA, with the exception of three isolated sites. These sites represent human habitation from the Paleo-Indian Period through the recent Historic Period (Holloman AFB 1996).

Oscura Bombing Range

The Oscura Bombing Range, situated directly south of the Red Rio Bombing Range, WSMR, covers approximately 79,600 ha (196,700 acres). The range runs approximately 33 km (20.5 mi) south from the RRBR and 23 km (14 mi) east to the WSMR boundary (Figure 18). The safety impact area (SIA), approx. 14,200 ha (35,000 acres) and the target impact area (TIA), approx. 1,800 ha (4,400 ac) are situated within the Oscura Bombing Range. Military operations and activities include aircraft practice strafing and bombing runs. The TIA is impacted by weapons testing and firing.

The OBR lies within the northern extent of the Tularosa Basin at the base of the Oscura Mountains and Chupadera Mesa. The Tularosa Basin is within the Mexican Highlands Section of the Basin and Range Physiographic Province. Alluvial and eolian processes are the primary natural mechanisms reshaping the geophysical landscape within the range today. Beginning in the northern extent of the range, elevation drops gradually from the alluvial fans of the Ocuras and Chupadera Mesa into the alluvial flats and basin lowlands to the south, including portions of the Carrizozo Lava Flows. Alluvial fans within the range are derived from a composite of the limestone and sandstone members of the predominantly Permian Age formations. At increasingly larger distances from the piedmont slope, the incised drainages meet within the basin forming a mixture of alluviated Quaternary fill (Anderson et.al 1997). The topographically lowest unit within the basin holds undifferentiated quaternary fill, primarily from the exposed sedimentary units of the Abo, Bursum, Yeso, and San Andres formations. At the southern tip of the Oscura Mountains and along the eastern border of the alluvial fans of the San Andres Mountains, are mappable units of the Santa Fe Formation. The Carrizozo lava flow, located in the southeastern portion of the range is one of the youngest volcanic flows in the United States, estimated between 1,500-2,000 years old. The vent for the basalt lava flows is Little Black Peak; flows extend for forty-four miles, ranging from ½ to 5 miles wide, and are up to 49 meters (160') thick (Stoeser, et. al. 1989). The volcanic rock nearly covers the underlying Pennsylvanian, Permian, Triassic, and Cretaceous rock units, with the exception of some kipukas (Hawaiian term for an island of older rocks and surficial material surrounded by lava). Piedmont alluvial deposits occur on the eastern side of the volcanic flow, at the base of the Phillips Hills.

Representative vegetation mapping units within the OBR are Mixed Foothill-Piedmont Desert Grasslands, Creosotebush Shrubland, Mixed Lowland Desert Scrub, Fourwing Saltbush Shrubland, Lowland Basin Grasslands, and Malpais Lava Scrub (Muldavin et.al.

1997). Mixed Foothill-Piedmont Desert Grasslands found within this mapping unit occur within the northern extent of the range of the Oscura Mountain foothills and on the upper piedmont of the Phillips Hills. Major community types encountered in the OBR for this map unit are black grama-blue grama (*Bouteloua eriopoda*-*B. gracilis*), black grama-sideoats grama (*B. eriopoda*-*B. curtipendula*), and black grama-purple threeawn (*B. eriopoda*-*Aristida purpurea*). Continuing further downslope onto alluvial fan piedmonts, Creosotebush Shrublands and other Lowland Desert Scrub are prominent. Creosotebush-mariola (*Larrea tridentata*-*Parthenium incanum*) communities cover rocky surfaces while more gravelly surfaces will have creosotebush/bush muhly (*L. tridentata*/*Muhlenbergia porteri*) or creosotebush/alkali sacaton (*L. tridentata*/*Sporobolus airoides*) communities. Tarbush (*Flourensia cernua*) and Honey mesquite (*Prosopis glandulosa*) inclusions are found within the creosotebush shrublands and often at lower elevations within the alluvial plains or within drainages. Fourwing Saltbush Shrublands, dominated in this area by fourwing saltbush/alkali sacaton communities, occur on silty and clayey alluvial flats west of the lava flows adjacent to drainages. Within swales or broad drainages Lowland Basin Grasslands contain nearly monotypic stands of alkali sacaton or tobosagrass-alkali sacaton (*Hilaria mutica*-*Sporobolus airoides*) communities. Malpais Lava Scrub includes a high diversity of shrub and grass species, including creosotebush, honey mesquite, Wright's beebrush (*Aloysia wrightii*) and tarbush, along with black grama, sideoats grama, bush muhly (*Muhlenbergia porteri*), threeawn, and assorted annual forbs and grasses.

During a brief survey from 29 April – 9 May 1996, no candidate, threatened, or endangered species were identified within the TIA during surveys (Holloman AFB 1997). Wildlife, however, is abundant and diverse within the range, due to extensive, nearly contiguous natural grasslands and shrublands. Bird, mammal and reptile fauna are similar to those at the adjacent RRBR. Small mammals like the Black-tailed Jackrabbit (*Lepus californicus*) forage on grasses, sub-shrubs and cactus. Although the reptiles found within this region are quite common throughout New Mexico, lizards such as the Little Striped Whiptail (*Cnemidophorus inornatus*), Desert Grassland Whiptail (*Cnemidophorus uniparens*), and lesser earless lizard prefer the sparse desert grasslands typical of this area (Williamson et al. 1994). Thirty species of birds were identified during surveys conducted in May 1996 (HAFB 1996). A few differences between surveys here and at RRBR were found, (e.g., Chihuahuan raven (*Corvus cryptoleucus*) and Say's phoebe (Sayornis saya)), but these are probably due to timing of surveys. Lava flows support a variety of wildlife including deer, badgers, skunks, coyotes, ring-tailed cats and rattlesnakes.

Cultural resource surveys were conducted throughout the range, covering approximately 1,077 ha (2,660 acres) within the Bull Gap SW and Three Rivers NW, New Mexico, 7.5-min. USGS topographic maps (Holloman AFB 1997). Paleo-Indian sites through the recent Historic Periods (ca 10,000 B.P. to present) were encountered and mapped. Some of the sites are eligible for consideration for the National Register of Historical Places (NRHP) and are located in the proximity of the target areas.

Figure 18. Holloman AFB Geographically Separated Units (GSUs)

GSUs are within White Sands Missile Range. Three sites are designated by symbols and RRBR and OBR are shown with boundaries. RRBR Safety Area is also delineated.

Radar Target Scatter Complex

This test site located 13 miles (21 km) west of the HAFB boundary (Figure 18), comprises approximately 648 ha (1,600 acres). Primary access to this area via the east-west road from Holloman AFB, north of Lost River, is limited and controlled by WSMR. It was established in 1962 and has been operated since 1964 by the Air Forces Missile Development Center at Holloman AFB.

The site is used primarily as a radar backscatter measurement facility. It was chosen for radar testing because it is remote, providing a secure area to conduct radar backscatter testing, as well as topographically flat, to inhibit anomalous backscatter from objects not associated with the testing procedures.

The test area lies within an alkali flat basin bounded on the east by northeastward shifting gypsum dunes and to the west by the alluvial plains of the San Andres mountain range. Less than one mile to the south is the northern boundary of WSNM. Soils for this area consist of nearly level, low permeability gypsum deposits precipitated from an ancient lakebed. Groundwater level may be within 3 feet of the surface. Periods of rainfall often create extensive surfaces, sometimes covering many kilometers inundated with a few centimeters of water. This process of inundation in this arid region maintains the nearly flat topography.

This low lying area is sparsely vegetated and is dominated by pickleweed (*Allenrolfea occidentalis*), scattered salt-tolerant grasses such as alkali sacaton (*Sporobolus airoides*), and forbs such as the Transpecos sealavender (*Limonium limbatum*) and spreading alkaliweed (*Cressa truxillensis*). The plant communities associated with this soil type are similar to the pickleweed shrubland on HAFB located primarily in the wetlands management unit (Muldavin 1997).

No state or federally listed threatened or endangered species were found within the test area; however, viable populations of the White Sands pupfish (*Cyprinodon tularosa*) occur within .5 miles of the access road to the test site. Like these on Holloman, these populations are managed by the Cooperative Agreement for Protection and Maintenance of White Sands Pupfish between the U.S. Army (WSMR), U.S. Air Force (HAFB), National Park Service (WSNM), U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, and New Mexico Department of Game and Fish (1994).

RATSCAT Advanced Measurement Site

RAMS facility is south of Range Road 6 and northwest of the Rhodes Canyon Range Center at the eastern margin of the San Andres Mountains (Figure 18). Testing parameters are similar to RATSCAT, requiring nearly level surfaces. Therefore, the site was topographically modified by leveling the alluvial fan surface and enlarging a drainage to the south of the test ramp.

The site rests on an alluvial fan underlain by caliche and dissected by a fault scarp. The nearly level surface has sandy-loam soils with occasional limestone rock outcrops and is dissected by drainages. Vegetation cover is characterized by uniformly spaced creosotebush (*Larrea tridentata*) shrublands and may be associated with alkali sacaton (*Sporobolus airoides*) or bush muhly (*Muhlenbergia porteri*). Creosote shrubland communities are extensive at the mid-to lower portions of the San Andres alluvial fans and are occasionally dissected by drainages. These drainages have greater plant diversity, and harbor hillside, lower elevation, and desert riparian species. Drainages may contain assemblages of desert willow (*Chilopsis Linearis*), honey mesquite (*Prosopis glandulosa*), tarbush (*Flourenzia cernua*), ocotillo (*Foquieria splendens*), or soaptree yucca (*Yucca elata*).

Prior to construction of RAMS, the area was surveyed for Toden's pennyroyal (*Hedeoma todsenii*), which occurs at higher elevations (6,000'/ 1,829 m) within Rhodes Canyon. This species is rare statewide and globally and was not found at this site.

Deer are known to forage within the hillslope grasslands surrounding the site. Oryx are common at lower elevations. No threatened or endangered species were observed at the site.

Air Force Special Weapons Complex - Weapons Impact Target

The current program uses the AFSWC WIT site for both non-exploding (practice) warheads and AGM-65B Maverick air-to-ground live-fire testing. The 20th FS assigned to HAFB trains German Air Force (GAF) pilots in the employment of the Maverick missile. Pilots depart from HAFB to the WIT site on a northwest bearing and dislodge missiles at 46 m (150') intervals along a line to the center of the test site. The safety requirement for deployment of Maverick warheads is a 1,000m (32,000') safety zone surrounding the impact target. Firebreaks are arranged in concentric circles around the impact area to help control grass fires when they occur. Stallion Range Center Fire Department is approximately 12 miles to the north and can assist when fires are uncontrollable by on-site USAF personnel. HAFB explosive ordnance disposal (EOD) travel by vehicle to the site on established roads to remove exploded debris. Access to the site is west from Range Road 7 at the Pepper Site Junction, north of Government Road.

AFSWC WIT is located within a large depression in the northern Jornada Basin, northwest of the San Andres Mountains and directly west of the Oscura Mountains (Figure 18). Soils for the site are basin-fill deposits generally characterized as the Yesum-Holloman association (USDA 1976). Yesum-Holloman soils create an uneven mosaic of moderate to highly alkaline soils having flat to moderately undulating surfaces (See Chapter 3 - Soils and Geology)

Vegetation cover is dominated by lowland basin grasslands and Great Basin desert scrub. Where hummocks of gypsum land or undulating surfaces of gypsic crusts interrupt these flat lying areas, gypsophilous desert grasslands dominate. This lowland basin grassland and shrubland is similar in soil and plant community type to the Northern Shrublands Management Unit on HAFB (See Northern Shrublands above). Although much of the surface area within the impact site is highly disturbed, some viable communities and populations of sensitive plant species persist in this relatively small area. Major grassland community types are gyp dropseed/alkali sacaton (*Sporobolus nealleyi/Sporobolus airoides*), alkali sacaton/burrograss (*Sporobolus airoides/Scleropogon brevifolius*), gyp dropseed/hairy coldenia (*Sporobolus nealleyi/Tiquilia hispidissima*), and monotypic stands of alkali sacaton. Major shrubland community types are fourwing saltbush/alkali sacaton shrublands (*Atriplex canescens/Sporobolus airoides*) with some inclusions of sand sagebrush/alkali sacaton (*Artemisia filifolia/Sporobolus airoides*) (Muldavin et al. 1997).

The site was surveyed in July 1995 for federal and state listed endangered, threatened, and candidate species. Within the 1,000 meter safety radius of ground zero, 11 populations of grama grass cactus (*Toumeyia papyracantha*) were found along with a single population of Wright fishhook cactus (*Mammillaria Wrightii* var. *Wrightii*). The grama grass cactus has been downlisted to a state L4; its limited distribution within the state is within the Tularosa and Jordada del Muerto Basins, and some populations are known to reach into Arizona. Although it is more abundant than previously thought, it was principally downlisted because of the status of protection offered on military ranges within the Tularosa Basin. Wright fishhook cactus is a state L4 species that was considered but not included, because it is considered to be too common in New Mexico (Sivinski and Lightfoot 1994). Although wildlife species occurring on WSMR have been well documented (Burkett 1994; WSMR 1994), no wildlife surveys have been conducted within AFSWC WIT.

CHAPTER 5 - MISSION IMPACTS ON ENVIRONMENT

The Department of Defense has jurisdiction over vast areas of land, including large areas of substantial biological significance (Leslie et al. 1996). The military has been a steward of public lands since 1823 and has had an evolving policy that reflects changes in public policy. The largest expansion of military lands occurred during World War II, when lands were acquired for housing, training, and preparation for combat. As a result of early training exercises, soil erosion control measures were taken around 1942, marking the beginning of land management plans by the military.

Today, military natural resource management programs have begun incorporating new scientific and technological advances (Leslie et al. 1996), in an effort to prevent some of the adverse impacts caused by newer weapon systems. Modern military operations demand more diversified training areas that provide realistic natural settings. Environmental protection statutes such as the Endangered Species Act, National Environmental Policy Act, and Clean Water Act must be considered by military planners.

This chapter discusses some of the military impacts on natural resources within the geographic context of Holloman AFB. Activities that support the military operation, such as landscaping, pest control, and outdoor recreation are also discussed in terms of their impact on natural resources.

Introduction

Holloman AFB has an extensive and diversified military history that extends beyond its present boundaries within the Tularosa Basin (*See* Chapter 2 - History of Installation). Air Force mission impacts extend to large regions within the boundaries of WSMR and McGregor Range, Ft. Bliss. In the future, flight paths need to be considered when updating this plan. At present, the geographic extent of military impacts considered under the current INRMP is limited to the ground-based activities associated with military operations, training, and personnel support on Holloman AFB.

The impacts on natural resources of military training and operations are discussed below. Military training groups considered in this plan include the 49th Logistics Group, 49th Support Group, 49th Medical Group, and 49th Material Maintenance Group (*See* Installation Location and Facilities - Military Activities). Training activities are conducted primarily within the Northern Shrubland MU; however, numerous training and mission-related activities are conducted within the Test Track MU and Cantonment MU (Figure 19). Military operations include the 49th Fighter Wing Staff Agencies and 49th Operations Group. Operations occur within the Cantonment MU and at geographically separated units on White Sands Missile Range and McGregor Range on Ft. Bliss.

Other mission-related activities are performed by large numbers of military and civilian support personnel. Some of these activities include quality of life activities such as Grounds Maintenance and Outdoor Recreation. Natural Resource impacts resulting from support activities are also discussed below.

Major Impacts

Military Ground-Based Training

Military training activities are located principally within 3 MUs: Test Track, Northern Shrublands, and Cantonment (Figure 19). Fourteen organizations conduct field exercises that cover a variety of mission-essential training requirements (Table 6). In support of Holloman AFB military training objectives, a Programmatic Environmental Assessment (PEA) on ground-based field training and exercises was developed to provide the guidelines for environmentally sound long-term training (Holloman AFB 1998). "The PEA provides the opportunity for efficiently conducting military training in such a way that organizations work together when possible, do not disturb each other when required, meet their mission objectives, and protect the environment to meet legal requirements and maintain long-term use of training areas" (Holloman AFB 1998).

Figure 19. Ground-based Training Sites

Training sites are located within the Cantonment, Northern Shrubland, and Test Track Management Units. The ODELL ParaRescue Site is on White Sands Missile Range; however, it is considered within the Cantonment Management Unit.

The PEA document is an evaluation of all ground-based training and exercises conducted on seventeen different training sites by organizations at Holloman AFB (Table 7, Figure 19). The PEA evaluation of ground-based training, organized by training activity, includes (Holloman AFB 1998, Section 2.2):

- Purpose of training
- Description of training
- Frequency of training
- Terrain/facilities required for training
- Munitions used
- Location(s) of training

In addition, the PEA document outlines specific pre-exercise briefings on safety, natural resource protection issues, and mitigation measures for each training site (Holloman AFB 1998, Section 2.3). Several issues are addressed for each of the training sites, followed by mitigation measures designed to direct operational procedures for training and exercises. The impacted subject issues addressed in the PEA and requiring proposed action are:

- Grama grass cactus
- Burrowing Owl
- White Sands Pupfish
- Barn Owl
- Texas horned lizard
- Swainson's Hawk nesting habitat
- Spread of noxious weeds
- Soil erosion & soil disturbance plots
- Cultural and historical resources
- Visual quality and cleanliness
- Boundary issues
- Safety issues
- Avoiding utility lines

Mission impacts were excerpted from the PEA (Holloman AFB 1998, Section 2.3) and organized in Table 8 by Management Unit and Training Area Site. Although some impacted subject issues are the same for multiple training areas, the various activities conducted within training areas are diverse; therefore, impacts can vary. These differences are captured in the 'Impact Issue Description' column of table 8.

Table 6. Military training operations and responsible organization

Table is organized by office symbol. The type of training conducted by each organization is represented in the Training column. The Programmatic Environmental Assessment (PEA) Section relates to the chapter in the Programmatic Environmental Assessment Ground-Based Field Training and Exercises Combined with Integrated Ground-Based Field Training Management Plan (Holloman AFB 1998) to locate operational objectives.

Training	PEA Section	Responsible Organization	Office Symbol
Air Force Space Command Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	2.2.8	AF Space Command	4 SPSS
Air Force Mobile Space Surveillance, Communications, and Data Relay Systems Training	2.2.22	AF Space Command	4 SPSS/MAFX
Air Force Space Command Combat Readiness Training	2.2.23	AF Space Command	4 SPSS/MAFX
ParaRescue Squadron Training	2.2.21	48 Rescue Squadron	48 RQS
ParaRescue Squadron Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	2.2.7	ParaRescue Squadron	48 RQS
Explosive Ordnance ATV and HMMWV Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	2.2.10	EOD	49 CES/CED
Explosive Ordnance Disposal Proficiency Training	2.2.27	EOD	49 CES/CED
Fire Department On-Pavement and Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	2.2.9	Fire Department	49 CES/CEF
Fire Department Barrier Exercise Training	2.2.24	Fire Department	49 CES/CEF
Fire Department Egress Training	2.2.25	Fire Department	49 CES/CEF
Fire Department Vehicle Dispersal Training (Phase II ORE/ORI)	2.2.26	Fire Department	49 CES/CEF
Prime Beef Combat Readiness Training	2.2.15	Prime Beef	49 CES/CEX
Communications Squadron Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	2.2.5	Communications	49 CS
Communications Squadron Deployment Training	2.2.20	Communications	49 CS
Operational Readiness Exercises (OREs) and Operational Readiness Inspections (ORIs)	2.2.12	Wing Planning	49 FW/XP
TDY Deployment Units Ground Intercept Support (GCI)	2.2.28	Logistics	49 LSS
Roving Sands Support Training	2.2.29	Logistics	49 LSS

Training	PEA Section	Responsible Organization	Office Symbol
Medical Group Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	2.2.2	Medical Group	49 MDG
Field Hospital Training	2.2.16	Medical Group	49 MDG
Bare Base Heavy and Off-Pavement All-Terrain Vehicle and Equipment Training	2.2.3	Bare Base	49 MMG
Bare Base Structures Erection Training	2.2.17	Bare Base	49 MMG
Bare Base Generator Training	2.2.18	Bare Base	49 MMG
Security Forces Off-Pavement All-Terrain Vehicle Training	2.2.1	Security Forces	49 SFS/SFT
Security Forces Air Base Ground Defense Training	2.2.13	Security Forces	49 SFS/SFT
Security Forces Obstacle Course	2.2.14	Security Forces	49 SFS/SFT
Small Arms Firing Training	2.2.30	Security Forces	49 SFS/SFTC/CATM
Field Food Service Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	2.2.4	Services	49 SVS
Field Food Service Training	2.2.19	Services	49 SVS
Transportation Squadron Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	2.2.6	Transportation	49 TRNS
746 Test Squadron Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	2.2.11	Test Squadron	746 TS

Table 7. Military ground-based training sites

Table is arranged by management unit. There are 17 training areas. Organizations may operate in more than one training area.

Training Area	Management Unit	Organizations Using Training Area	Office Symbol
Balloon Launch Pad	Cantonment	Fire Department Logistics Medical Group	49 CES/CEF 49 LSS 49 MDG
Bare Base Compound	Cantonment	Bare Base Medical Group	49 MMG 49 MDG
Cantonment ORE/ORIs (Bldgs 855/805, 838, 847, and Westerner Dining/former Bldg 819)	Cantonment	Prime Beef Wing Planning Security Forces Squadron Communications Squadron Logistics Food Services	49 CES/CEX 49 FW/XP 49 SFS/SFT 49 CS 49 LSS 49 SVS
East of Bldg 1266	Cantonment	Communications Squadron Roving Sands Logistics Support	49 CS 49 LSS
Flightline	Cantonment	Fire Department	49 CES/CEF
Odell Site (WSMR)	Cantonment	ParaRescue Squadron Medical Group	49 RQS 49 MDG
Borrow Area	Northern Shrublands	Security Forces Squadron Medical Group Communications Squadron Explosive Ordnance Test Squadron Transportation Squadron Bare Base Fire Department Food Services Space Warning Squadron ParaRescue Squadron	49 SFS/SFT 49 MDG 49 CS 49 CES/CED 746 TS 49 TRNS 49 MMG 49 CES/CEF 49 SVS 4 SPSS 48 RQS
Explosive Ordnance Proficiency Range	Northern Shrublands	Explosive Ordnance	49 CES/CED
Hay Draw	Northern Shrublands	Security Forces Squadron Space Warning Squadron	49 SFS/SFT 4 SPSS
King 1	Northern Shrublands	Security Forces Squadron Space Warning Squadron ParaRescue Squadron	49 SFS/SFT 4 SPSS 48 RQS

Training Area	Management Unit	Organizations Using Training Area	Office Symbol
King 1 Loop Track	Northern Shrublands	Security Forces Squadron Medical Group Communications Squadron Explosive Ordnance Transportation Squadron Bare Base Fire Department Food Services Space Warning Squadron ParaRescue Squadron	49 SFS/SFT 49 MDG 49 CS 49 CES/CED 49 TRNS 49 MMG 49 CES/CEF 49 SVS 4 SPSS 48 RQS
La Luz Gate Balloon Pad	Northern Shrublands	Space Warning Squadron	4 SPSS
Obstacle Course	Northern Shrublands	Security Forces Squadron ParaRescue Squadron	49 SFS/SFT 48 RQS
Prime Beef Pit	Northern Shrublands	Security Forces Squadron Medical Group Prime Beef Communications Squadron Space Warning Squadron Logistics Squadron Wing Planning	49 SFS/SFT 49 MDG 49 CES/CEX 49 CS 4 SPSS 49 LSS 49 FW/XP
Prime Beef RRR	Northern Shrublands	Security Forces Squadron Medical Group Prime Beef Bare Base Explosive Ordnance	49 SFS/SFT 49 MDG 49 CES/CEX 49 MMG 49 CES/CED
Small Arms Firing Range	Northern Shrublands	All Base Squadrons	Managed by 49 SFS/SFT/CAT M
Test Track Pits and Berms	Test Track	Space Warning Squadron	4 SPSS

Table 8. Mission impacts by Management Unit and training site

The table is organized by Management Unit and Training Area. Training Areas excluded from this table had no significant impacts identified in the PEA.

Impacted Subject	Impact Issue Description
<i>Northern Shrubland Management Unit</i>	
<i>King 1 Training Area</i>	
Soil Disturbance Study Plot	The 2.5-acre soils disturbance test plot is located in the northeastern portion of the area. Air Base Ground Defense training and navigation training could create disturbances adversely impacting study results.
Soil Erosion	Based on soil type and preliminary indications from soil disturbance test plots, the soil surface is extremely sensitive to vehicle and foot traffic, and digging foxholes. All of these activities are components of the Air Base Ground Defense training. Loss of soil crusts (cryptogams) and vegetation cover occurs rapidly when disturbed. Soil stabilization, without further disturbance, takes over six months to recover. Digging foxholes removes all topsoil, soil crusts, and vegetation from the immediate area, which could cause wind and water erosion and decrease the viability of long-term use of the area for training. Restoration would be costly and difficult.
Grama Grass Cactus (<i>Toumeyia papyracanthus</i>) Populations	Grama grass cactus is a Federal Species of Concern. Semi-protected populations on military lands are considered crucial to the well-being of the species. The population on HAFB, in particular, is now the best-documented site to date. Three grama grass cactus populations are located within alkali sacaton grassland communities in the King 1 training area. Two relatively dense populations are located near the northern perimeter of the proposed training area. A third, smaller, population is located in the southeastern area. Because populations are sensitive to disturbance and plants are difficult to differentiate from the adjacent grasses, vehicle and foot traffic and digging associated with the Air Base Ground Defense training could adversely affect or eliminate any or all of the known populations within the training area.

Impacted Subject	Impact Issue Description
Historical Sites	This area was surveyed for cultural resources, documented in Air Base Ground Defense Exercise/Training Area (HAFB Report 1994-017). Three historical sites (Cold War Era) associated with an early missile launch area are located near the northeastern corner. These artifacts include small buildings and concrete pads. Ground disturbing activities within this buffered area would degrade the historical sites. [HILDY: unsure about treatment around this site]
White Sands Pupfish	The White Sands pupfish buffer boundary is contiguous with portions of the King 1 training area boundary. Without markers on the ground, the buffer boundary will not be evident to training participants, potentially resulting in training activities inadvertently occurring within the buffer.
Noxious Weeds: African Rue (<i>Peganum harmala</i>)	African rue is a highly persistent, rapidly spreading, noxious weed that is very resistant to herbicides. It is currently established along all paved and non-paved roads within the area and readily spreads into disturbed soils, such as along roads and any bladed or graded areas. Rue readily spreads wherever soil disturbance and loss of native vegetation occurs. Disturbance due to exercise activities (such as ATV trails and foxholes) might further spread the species into currently weed-free areas. Rue outcompetes native vegetation in disturbed areas, decreasing the value of the area for realistic training.
Training Debris and Trash	Repeated training exercises can result in substantial accumulation of debris and trash. Discarded brass, wire, wood, and other materials decrease the visual quality and realistic value of the training.
<i>Prime Beef Pit Training Area</i>	
Historic Characteristics	The berm is one of the few remaining Air Force WWII training sites constructed for moving target practice within a bermed area. The internal characteristics are not culturally significant and can therefore be modified. The berm itself must be protected from degradation (report for consideration as a potentially historic structure is in final stages for submittal to the State Historic Preservation Officer).
Damage to Utility Lines	Digging within the Prime Beef Pit could damage utility lines.

Impacted Subject	Impact Issue Description
Training Debris and Trash	Repeated training exercises can result in substantial accumulation of debris and trash. Discarded brass, wire, wood, and other materials decrease the visual quality and realistic value of the training.
<i>Prime Beef Rapid Runway Repair Area (RRR) Training Area</i>	
Underground Utilities	Underground water, optical cable, communication, and electrical lines are located between Douglas Road and the Prime Beef RRR site. The sewer line runs under the RRR site. Operation of a trencher, backhoe or other heavy equipment could rupture the lines.
Spills	Use of heavy equipment creates the potential for spills of fuel and other petroleum products. At this site, a spill would contaminate the soil and could drain into pupfish habitat in the Lost River drainage.
Noxious Weeds: African Rue (<i>Peganum harmala</i>) and Russian Thistle (<i>Salsola iberica</i>)	African rue is a highly persistent, rapidly spreading, noxious weed that is very resistant to herbicides. It is currently established along all paved roads and two-track roads in the area and readily spreads into disturbed areas. Further disturbance due to exercise activities such as digging and trenching might spread the species into currently weed-free areas. Rue outcompetes native vegetation in disturbed areas, decreasing the value of the area for realistic training.
Gravel Piles	Attempt to make old piles larger instead of creating new piles. Do not maneuver around puddles; this will increase the diameter of the disturbed area. Also, adding additional gravel adjacent to the piles instead of on top of the piles will increase the horizontal surface area of the pile.
<i>Hay Draw Training Area</i>	
Soil Erosion	Based on soil type and preliminary indications from the soils disturbance test plot, the soils throughout the training area are erosive when disturbed by vehicle or foot traffic or digging foxholes. All of these activities are components of the Air Base Ground Defense training, which could cause wind and water erosion and decrease the long-term viability of the area for training. Restoration would be costly and difficult.

Impacted Subject	Impact Issue Description
Burrowing Owl (<i>Speotyto culicularia</i>)	Burrowing Owl populations on Holloman AFB are considered a high conservation priority because of jeopardized populations elsewhere in its range. Three burrows that have been active in the past are located on the northern hillside, within the gyp dropseed grassland community. The burrows in Hay Draw were active in 1996, although they produced no fledglings. Nesting activity was not documented during the 1997 nesting season.
Grama Grass Cactus (<i>Toumeyia papyracanthus</i>) Populations	Grama grass cactus is a Federal Species of Concern. Semi-protected populations on military lands are considered crucial to the well-being of the species. The population on HAFB, in particular, is now the best-documented site to date. One grama grass cactus population (approximately 2 ha) is located within alkali sacaton grassland communities in the training area adjacent to the east-west road north of the draw. Two additional populations are located outside of the training area just to the east. Because populations are sensitive to disturbance and plants are difficult to differentiate from the adjacent grasses, vehicle and foot traffic and digging associated with the Air Base Ground Defense training could adversely affect or eliminate any or all of the known populations within the training area.
Swainson's Hawk Nest (<i>Buteo swainsoni</i>)	A Swainson's hawk nest is located in a large salt cedar tree to the west of Range Road 9, west of the Hay Draw training area boundary. Training activities in the western portion of the area during nesting season (which occurs between March and August) could disturb nesting.
Noxious Weeds: African Rue (<i>Peganum harmala</i>) and Russian Knapweed (<i>Acroptilon repens</i>)	African rue is a highly persistent rapidly spreading noxious weed that is very resistant to herbicides. It is currently located adjacent to and within the training area. Russian knapweed is also present in the bottom of the draw near the western boundary. No control of either species has been attempted in this area. Further disturbance due to exercise activities (such as ATV trails and foxholes) might further spread plants into currently weed-free areas.
Boundary of Training Area	Where roads do not form the actual training area boundary, especially on the eastern boundary, the delineation of the boundary needs to be marked to ensure all training is conducted within the appropriate area.

Impacted Subject	Impact Issue Description
Training Debris and Trash	Many used brass cartridges have been left near the roads, especially on the north side of the draw. An old burned conex, wood, brass, communication wire, and other debris and trash are within the bottom of the draw. This most likely would encourage further littering and decrease the reality of the training scenario.
Borrow Area Vehicle Training	
Barn Owl Nests	A Barn Owl pair has consistently nested in the caliche cliff in the southern portion of the Borrow Area. An additional twelve roost sites have also been identified in the southern portion of the Borrow Area. Active vehicle training in the southern portion could cause the owls to abandon the nest and the area. Barn Owls and their habitat (including nests) are protected under the Migratory Bird Treaty Act, which prohibits “taking” of birds and habitat without a permit from the US Fish and Wildlife Service.
Borrow Area Availability	Most units on Holloman AFB are currently not providing required off-road vehicle training because of lack of a suitable training area. The Borrow Area provides an excellent opportunity for training under varied conditions with a diversity of terrain and low level of impacts to soil, water, and other resources. However, this area will not be available until capping of the Lagoons and former landfill are completed.
Vehicle Training Course Design	Vehicle training requirements and types of vehicles vary among the units requesting use of the Borrow Area for training. Vehicles proposed for training include HMMWVs, large pickup trucks, ATVs, large diesel trucks, wreckers, and emergency response vehicles. Trainees need to gain expertise operating vehicles on inclines and uneven terrain, as well as speed. [HILDY: DOES THIS BELONG? IT'S NOT REALLY AN IMPACT?]
Soil Erosion	Soil erosion inside the Borrow Area is a concern only from a safety standpoint. Training instructors are responsible to ensure that safety is maintained at all times during training. However, any vehicle use on upland areas along the perimeter of the Borrow Area could cause erosion. Use of the southern entrance to the site, which is poorly drained, could also cause rutting and erosion.

Impacted Subject	Impact Issue Description
Unauthorized Dumping	Once the active removal of borrow material is completed, it is possible that unauthorized dumping could occur in the Borrow Area.
Conflicting Land Use	The Borrow Area has been requested for meeting recreational ATV requests for weekend use as a way to reduce unauthorized recreational ATV and motorcycle use elsewhere on base. Use of the Borrow Area for recreational purposes could cause damage to any course designed for military training requirements and potentially create a demand that could interfere with meeting military training requirements. Any recreational use of the site would have to be managed through a required registration at the Skeet Range and would require additional enforcement, especially during the week, by 49 SFS. The Security Forces Squadron does not have sufficient resources to conduct additional enforcement activities for controlling recreational ATV use of the Borrow Area.
<i>King 1 Loop Track Vehicle Training Area</i>	
Conflicting Land Use	The existing roads have light vehicular use with heaviest use on Douglas Road and near the horse stables. Other users, such as vehicles, walkers, and horseback riders, might conflict with training exercises, especially with inexperienced trainees. However, military use is not expected to create a traffic flow problem.
Soil Erosion	Some portions of the King1 Loop Track are not hardened and are subject to erosion, especially after rains.
Archaeological Sites	A lithic archaeological site is located either on or near the existing road on the northern end of the loop. [HILDY: unsure about treatment around this site?]
<i>Cantonment Management Unit</i>	
<i>Bare Base Compound</i>	
Explosive Arcs	The western half of the compound is located in an explosive arc.
<i>Balloon Launch Pad</i>	

Impacted Subject	Impact Issue Description
Noxious Weeds: African Rue (<i>Peganum harmala</i>) and Russian Thistle (<i>Salsola iberica</i>)	African rue is a highly persistent rapidly spreading noxious weed that is very resistant to herbicides. African rue and Russian thistle are established in the scraped area around the pad.
<i>Communications Deployment Training Site - West of Bldg 1266</i>	
Grama Grass Cactus (<i>Toumeyia papyracanthus</i>) Populations	Grama grass cactus is a Federal Species of Concern. Semi-protected populations on military lands are considered crucial to the well-being of the species. The population on HAFB, in particular, is now the best-documented site to date. Several low-density populations of grama grass cactus are found near the site, and it is likely that the cactus occurs in low densities on the site as well. Training activities such as digging foxholes and parking vehicles could disturb any plants on the site.
Noxious Weeds: African Rue (<i>Peganum harmala</i>)	African rue is a highly persistent rapidly spreading noxious weed that is very resistant to herbicides. Noxious weeds are known only from roadways in the area. Digging foxholes and driving vehicles could disturb the soil, causing noxious weeds to invade the area.
Soil Erosion	Digging foxholes, removing vegetation, and compacting soil while parking vehicles and setting up equipment could result in soil erosion.
Texas Horned Lizard (<i>Phrynosoma comutum</i>)	The Texas horned lizard, a Federal Species of Concern, has been identified near Vandergrift Road during field surveys and could probably be found in high densities near the area. No surveys for this species have been conducted at this site. Activities could potentially impact this species.
<i>La Luz Gate Balloon Pad</i>	
Land Use Conflicts	The site is in the drop zone for M60 rockets. The Balloon Pad could not be safely used during firing of this particular munition. Only the 49 SFS is allowed to fire this, and firing only occurs once or twice per year.

Impacted Subject	Impact Issue Description
Noxious Weeds: African Rue (<i>Peganum harmala</i>) and Russian Thistle (<i>Salsola iberica</i>)	African rue and Russian thistle are highly persistent, rapidly spreading, noxious weeds that are very resistant to herbicides. They are established along all paved and two-track roads, as well as the launch pad. Disturbance due to exercise activities might increase the spread of these species into currently weed-free areas. Rue outcompetes native vegetation in disturbed areas.
<i>Odell Training Site (on White Sands Missile Range)</i>	
Land Jurisdiction	The site is located on land under the direct jurisdiction of White Sands Missile Range. Use of the area was requested in writing by Holloman AFB on 10 March, 1993, but WSMR never responded.
<i>Explosive Ordnance Proficiency Range</i>	
Noxious Weeds: African Rue (<i>Peganum harmala</i>)	African rue is a highly persistent, rapidly spreading noxious weed that is very resistant to herbicides. It is currently located on the roadways and in the detonation area due to disturbed conditions. Disturbance due to exercise activities (such as ATV trails and foxholes) might further spread plants into currently weed-free areas.
<i>Small Arms Firing Range</i>	
Pupfish Habitat	<p>The septic tank violated the New Mexico Liquid Waste Disposal Regulations. It may have put sewage-related pollutants into the Malone Draw drainage, which is White Sands pupfish habitat. This could potentially increase the biological oxygen demand (BOD) during flooding in Ritas Draw. The septic tank was plugged in 1997, turning it into a holding tank.</p> <p>Lead from spent ammunition could also be contaminating the soil and water downstream in Malone Draw, affecting pupfish habitat.</p> <p>Spills from personal and military vehicles could potentially flow downstream into occupied pupfish habitat at the confluence of Malone and Ritas Draws.</p>
<i>Test Track Management Unit</i> <i>Test Track Pits and Berms</i>	

Impacted Subject	Impact Issue Description
Burrowing Owls	Burrowing Owls are located on both sides of the Test Track (mostly west of the track) near the southern site. Vehicle use and training activity could disturb the nesting owls. [HILDY: does everyone know what a southern site is?]
Historic Sites	The northern site is near a small mound which supported three camera stands and one concrete pad used as a military tracking station in the late 1940s. [HILDY: unclear about treatment around this site?]

Military Ground-Based Operations

The military activities covered in this section include operations associated with the fighter squadrons in the 49th Operations Group. The maintenance and operation of aircraft within the Cantonment MU have the potential to introduce contaminants into the environment. These issues have not been investigated in the PEA (Holloman Air Force 1998); therefore, only a preliminary list of concerns can be introduced here. Issues that address stormwater drainages within the industrial areas, including aircraft hangers, are discussed in Chapter 6 - Watershed Protection and the *Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan for Holloman Air Force Base* (in draft).

Aircraft Maintenance

The principal potential impact to the environment from aircraft maintenance activities is on Lake Holloman and the constructed wetlands complex. Soluble materials can be transported through the stormwater drainage system and introduced into the constructed wetlands and Lake Holloman. Fuel and chemicals for cleaning the aircraft and engine parts are potential risks (see Chapter 6 - Watershed Protection). No violations have been observed (Law Environmental, Inc. 1994); however, the list of pollutants covered under the Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan may not include soluble materials detrimental to wetland plants and animals.

Aircraft noise and low-level flights can disturb some nesting and foraging birds. Field studies show the Western Snowy Plover reacts to overhead flights. It has not been determined if noise levels associated with these flights adversely affect nesting, but foraging efficiency appears to be impacted (K. Johnson personal communication).

Air Quality

Air emissions at the base occur due to training exercises, aircraft refueling and maintenance, rocket firing activities, jet engine testing, fuel storing and distribution, aerospace ground equipment operations, corrosion control activities, emissions from aircraft and motor vehicle operations, boilers, emergency generators, grounds maintenance equipment, and an incinerator.

Holloman AFB and the surrounding area are currently in compliance with the New Mexico State Implementation Plan (SIP) and its requirements for National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS, Clean Air Act) for all “Criteria Air Pollutants” (carbon monoxide, lead, nitrogen oxides, PM-10 particulate matter, sulfur oxides, and volatile organic compounds). This places HAFB within an “Attainment Area”, requiring no detailed analysis for new projects.

Geographically Separated Units

A formal MOU has not been formalized between White Sands Missile Range NRES-E and Holloman AFB CES/CEV for the cooperative resource management of geographically separated units located on WSMR. The Air Combat Command (ACC) has implemented a natural and cultural resources management council for all bombing ranges where ACC operates. The goals of the council are to:

- 1) Maintain accessibility to ranges for military operations while sustaining the natural environment for future generations.
- 2) Increase range natural and cultural resources management effectiveness and capability, and provide ranges with a united voice on range natural and cultural resources matters.
- 3) Bring the natural/cultural range resource managers together with range operators to better coordinate their activities and better develop mutual understandings.

WSMR may need to interact with Holloman AFB resource management to comply with Air Force regulatory documents for range resource management of Red Rio Bombing Range, Oscura Bombing Range, RATSCAT, RAMS, and Maverick WIT (AFI 13-212, AFI 13-301, and 32-7064).

Bird Aircraft Hazard Strike Management (BASH)

The *49 FW Bird Aircraft Strike Hazard Plan* ([1998](#)) states that a minimal bird-aircraft strike hazard exists at Holloman AFB. The Holloman AFB BASH Working Group has bird-strike hazard advisories on low level military training routes.

Local flying procedures keep aircraft from direct overflights of the Holloman Lakes area, and no bird strikes with waterfowl have occurred. BASH incidents are so rare that no bird control has been needed near the runways. Closing the six wastewater lagoons

located within the runway clear zone at the end of the south runway will further reduce the potential for problems. Waterfowl and shorebirds using Holloman Lake, Stinky Playa, and Lagoon G are not found flocking near the airfield. Vegetation is periodically cut back 100 feet from the edges of each runway for safety reasons, and this appears to minimize rodent and bird activity near the airfield. The low stature of native grasslands in the infield also minimizes the number and diversity of birds using the area. The primary potential hazards to assigned aircraft are horned larks and migrating raptors (March - April and September - October). Army Air unit helicopters are reported to fly lower than necessary near Lagoon G, a shorebird and waterfowl habitat [HILDY: by whom?].

The wooded habitat in the "rainfield," where Hay Draw crosses the test track, attracts birds, oryx, deer, kit foxes, and coyotes. These animals create BASH problems with testing activities at the High Speed Test Track. The High Speed Test Track has experienced bird strikes on test vehicles during the summer, especially by doves, in the "rainfield" area where strikes have been sufficiently hard to knock the vehicle off the track. Test Track personnel do not keep a log of strikes, except as part of data collection for tests.

Grounds Maintenance

Landscaping

Holloman AFB is committed to adopting environmentally sound landscaping practices take climate and other local environmental conditions into consideration. Located within the Chihuahuan Desert Eco-region, a dry desert environment, Holloman AFB receives only about 20 cm (8 inches) of precipitation per year ([Appendix C](#)). The dry early-summer months of May and June are typically the hottest, with the majority of precipitation occurring between July and October. Precipitation events during the rainy season typically occur as afternoon thunderstorms. In addition to the harsh desert climate, the soils on Holloman AFB have a high gypsum and salt content that are typically considered very unproductive. The natural vegetation endemic to this area can tolerate these highly alkaline soils and seasonal monsoon thunderstorms.

Based on DoD and AF mandates (*see* Chapter 7 - Cantonment), Holloman AFB is required to implement native landscaping practices that benefit wildlife and at the same time reduce the use of pesticides and herbicides. Adopting environmentally sound landscape practices will help the installation meet the DoD measure of merit (MOM) number 2: "By the end of FY 2000, the amount of pesticides applied annually on Dod installations will be reduced by 50 percent from the FY93 baseline in pounds of active ingredient."

Benefits of landscaping with native plants include:

- **reduced use of pesticides, fertilizers and water.** Native plants are hardy because they have adapted to local conditions, the dry environment, and poorer soils. Once established, native plants do not need pesticides or fertilizers and require little or no watering. Potable water is one of the most precious natural resources in our dry desert environment.
- **improved air quality.** Native landscapes, including lawns of native, warm season grasses, do not need to be mowed. Thus native landscaping practices drastically reduce the need for lawn maintenance equipment (lawn mowers, weed edgers, leaf blowers, etc.), all of which are fueled by gasoline, electricity or batteries. All of these fuel types are associated with emissions of air pollutants such as carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxides (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and air toxins such as benzene. Gasoline lawn and garden equipment, on average, produces 5% of ozone-forming VOCs in areas with smog problems. The NO₂ and SO₂ released from lawn maintenance equipment can react with water in the atmosphere to form acid rain.
- **improved ecosystem health.** In conventional landscaping and grounds maintenance, pesticides are often applied incorrectly. Pesticides have the potential to cause serious human health problems when not handled properly or applied according to the label directions. Applications are only useful if applied to targeted insects when they are most vulnerable. Overuse and inappropriate use often kill beneficial insects. Additionally, many popular pesticides available at local stores are lethal to birds. These pesticides kill birds through direct contact and indirectly through contamination of their insect food and water. Less than 10% of all insects are harmful to plants.
- **improved water quality.** Eliminating the use of pesticides and fertilizers prevents these pollutants from running into streams, wetlands, or ground water. Run-off from fertilizers can lead to algal blooms in waterways, which cause loss of oxygen from lakes and streams, in turn killing fish and other aquatic organisms.
- **time and money savings.** Long term maintenance of native plants is extremely low. They require little to no soil preparation, mowing, weeding, or pruning. Natives usually grow to their mature form and stop growing, whereas ornamental or hybrid plants require frequent pruning. About 1/5 of landfill space is taken up by garden prunings.
- **enhanced biodiversity.** Landscaping with native wildflowers, shrubs, trees, groundcovers, and grasses provides habitat for native mammals, birds, reptiles, and insects, thus enhancing the biodiversity of the area. The below-ground ecology is just as important as that above ground. Environmentally sound landscaping practices restore beneficial soil bacteria, earthworms, and most importantly, mycorrhizae.

Mycorrhizae are soil fungi whereby plants derive nutrients and moisture from lean, dry soils. Standard practices which use herbicides, pesticides, and fertilizers destroy these below-ground organisms.

- **esthetic benefit.** The beauty of native wildflowers and grasses creates a sense of place, both at home and work. The native plants increase our connection to nature, help educate our neighbors, and provide a beautiful, peaceful place to relax. Whether for the backyard gardener or grounds maintenance people, restoring a patch of nature can be a rewarding activity.

Blading on either side of the road is the source of persistent disturbance within the cantonment area and around the airfield and promotes the establishment and spread of noxious and non-native plants. At this point, no viable alternative to blading exists for controlling vegetation growth along roadsides.

When trees and other plants require replacement, Chihuahuan Desert natives or regional native plants should be utilized. Care should be taken to select plants that do not create a traffic problem within the Cantonment area. An example of native landscaping on the base can be viewed at the Learning Center Project. A list of plants used is provided by the 49 CES/CEV in [Appendix E.1](#). Local plant nurseries and landscaping firms provide a variety of Chihuahuan Desert and regional native plants ([Appendix E.2](#)). The use of native plants should minimize, and eventually replace, use of non-native plants for landscaping on Holloman AFB. A comprehensive list of these more alkaline-tolerant plants is included in [Appendix E.2](#).

Current Air Force policy on Holloman AFB for Military Family Housing does not encourage the use of native landscaping and regulations create an impediment. Landscaping policies for Military Family Housing at HollomanAFB are contrary to DoD and Air Force guidance on reducing the use of pesticides and herbicides and replacing non-native landscaping with native species that require little chemical inputs (DUSD (S)/PP memo, 23 Sep 1994; ACC Wings/CC Memo, 29 Jun 1995; DoDD 4700.4; AFI 32-7064 Sec. 11.1-11.2). Memoranda from Holloman AFB Military Family Housing in 1996 and 1997 require that lawns, well-mown (1.5 to 2.5 inches high) and watered according to a schedule, be established and maintained at each military family housing unit. Grass seed, fertilizer, and some lawn care tools are made available at the Self-Help Store. The use of desert landscaping is allowed *only* after a serious, but failed attempt has been made to grow non-native vegetation. An inspector will check the area and inspect the ground where vegetation establishment was attempted. Any resident requesting desert landscaping must complete a comprehensive drawing, showing where the unit is located in reference to the proposed landscaping modifications. Measurements must accurately depict location and types of specific desert plants. Residents can order desert plants only with an approved request, and a separate AF Form 332 is required for use of rocks and other landscaping materials.

Pest Control

The primary objective of the pest management program is to ensure effective control of the identified pest species within the mission perspective. All control procedures are planned and accomplished consistent with current laws and regulations. The Department of Defense has set a goal which states: "By the end of FY2000, the amount of pesticides applied annually on DoD installations will be reduced by 50 percent from the FY93 base-line in pounds of active ingredients." Control procedures are compliant with the DoD Pest Management Program, with an emphasis on Integrated Pest Management (IPM).

IPM is a sustainable approach to managing pests by combining biological, cultural, physical and chemical tools in a way that minimizes economic, health and environmental risks. It is an applied ecology approach for protecting and improving human, animal, and plant health in a way that is sensitive to the environment and to sustaining natural resources. IPM involves the selection, integration, and implementation of control as determined by anticipated economic, ecological, and sociological consequences. IPM has become the standard method for protecting human valued resources from pests. The primary tools of IPM are host plant resistance, biological control, cultural control and a number of artificial interventions including chemical control. The practices of IPM require accumulating biological, ecological, and physiochemical information about the site before the program will be applied, then devising an ecologically, economically, and sociologically acceptable IPM program. This is an interdisciplinary endeavor requiring an understanding and collaboration among entomologists, plant and animal scientists, plant pathologists, soil and weather specialists, and a host of others including statisticians, economists, and sociologists, as well as producers, industry, and federal and state agencies. (Texas A&M University, Department of Entomology)

Guidance for pest management on Holloman AFB is contained in [AFI 32-1053](#), which implements AFPD 32-10, Installations and Facilities, and Department of Defense (DoD) Directive 4150.7, DoD Pest Management Program, October 24, 1983. The Pest Management program at Holloman AFB is comprised of four main components: integrated pest control, insecticides, rodenticides, and herbicides. (Figure 20).

Integrated pest management is conducted whenever possible. Measures often include mechanical treatment such as eliminating breeding sites for mosquitoes, removal of wasp nests, and electronic light traps for flies. Residents are expected to try self-help techniques for 30 days before calling Pest Management personnel.

Insects

The insecticide program covers control of mosquitoes, roaches, wasps, fleas, and nuisance pests. The Pest Management Shop (Shop) regularly conducts surveys in base housing and mission facilities, applying either corrective controls, as needed, or seasonal applications of insecticides. Treatment is usually based on mosquito trap counts and complaints received. Because of the absence of certified personnel at the golf course, Shop conducts all the spraying and mosquito fogging there. The insecticide program is conducted primarily in residential areas. Mosquitoes are controlled by fogging with chemicals within the cantonment area, use of mosquito fish and biological agents (cubes of *Bacillus thurengensis*) in larval breeding areas, and wet spraying of chemicals on the golf course and other turf areas.

Holloman AFB is implementing an aggressive mosquito control program that includes the following:

- *Gambusia* are maintained in Dillard Draw behind Military Family Housing, the constructed wetlands, stormwater runoff ditches, and golf course ponds.
- A biological larvacide, *Bacillus thurengiensis* (*B.t.*), in long-lasting form (three months) is placed in Dillard Draw behind the Military Family Housing, stormwater drainage ditches, and other stagnant water areas. The areas are inoculated with *B.t.* from February through September.
- *B.t.* will not be used near Lagoon G, Lake Holloman, Stinky Playa, or the constructed wetlands, because it is lethal to aquatic insects.
- Fogging will be conducted only when requested by Military Family Housing, the golf course, or airfield. Military Family Housing units, the golf course, and the flight line are fogged with Scourge, prior to business hours, to kill adult mosquitoes. Fogging is to occur only when wind conditions are sufficient to reduce drift. [HILDY: do you want to try to limit this further?]
- Aerial spraying of Dibrome is not recommended. Dibrome could be allowed in extreme cases, such as an outbreak of encephalitis. An AF Form 332 would be required before any aerial spraying could be conducted.
- Mosquito traps placed behind Military Family Housing in Dillard Draw would help monitor mosquito counts.
- A coincident program to decrease saltcedar will help decrease mosquitoes.
- A dialogue with 49 SPTG/CC will be begun regarding restriction of water use by residents of Military Family Housing.
- A dialogue with 49 SPTG/CC will be initiated to control the use of water on golf course greens.
- A dialogue with 49 SPTG/CC will be initiated regarding requiring residents to cut their grass shorter in Military Family Housing. Mosquitoes lodge at midday in the cool and moist grasses near the soil surface. Cutting the grass shorter would allow more aeration and a warmer environment.

- It is recommend that native grasses be substituted for non-natives. Native, drought-resistant grasses do not need as much water, and grass blades are thinner and more aerated, providing a warmer, drier environment less attractive to mosquitoes.

Rodents

The rodenticide program uses pesticides to control rats, mice, and pocket gophers. The Shop conducts daily rodent surveys during the colder months and monthly surveys during the summer for rats and mice. Year-round monthly surveys are conducted for pocket gophers. Alternatives to dangerous chemicals should be regularly investigated. For instance, zinc phosphide is an active ingredient in rodenticides and is toxic to wildlife and fish (USDA 1994; Johnson and Fagerstone 1994; Bison-M 1997). Phostoxin is currently used in gopher holes at the golf course; however, this method can kill non-target animals. An extensive Recurring Work Program (RWP) and aggressive customer education have eliminated all major rodent infestations. The rodenticide program is primarily conducted in residential areas. [HILDY: we don't have much on rodents... additional dangers of these poisons used in this program harmful to pets and wildlife? Should we encourage trapping vs. poison?]

Figure 20. Pest Management - Weed, Mosquito, and Vertebrate Control

Pets

Domestic species also fall under the jurisdiction of Pest Management. All pets must be vaccinated before they are permitted in Military Family Housing. No more than two pets are allowed by policy, although this policy is not strictly enforced. All domestic pets are to have identification tags and be leashed or under voice control when outdoors at all times. No poisonous pet (including tarantulas), ferrets, or wolf/dog hybrids are allowed on base.

Violators of HAFBI 48-4 are first warned; upon the second offense or the first incident of an unprovoked bite, the owner will reimburse Holloman AFB for expenses and be issued an appealable notification to remove the animal from HAFB within 10 days. The next violation is not appealable and will be enforced by the owner’s commander. All residents

of Military Family Housing are briefed on policies and provided a booklet before they move in. Any domestic/feral animals trapped by 49 SFS are given to Animal Control in Alamogordo and, if tagged, the owners are notified. Dead wild or untagged animals are disposed of by 49 CES/CEOHHE; disposal of dead pets is the responsibility of the owner. Security Police can shoot or trap stray animals when requested by Pest Management, especially if the animal has bitten a person. Generally, however, they call Animal Control in Alamogordo. The POC for reporting problems with wild, feral or domestic animals is 49 SFS/SPOX at 475-5037.

Other wild vertebrates

In addition to the standard pests managed under the Pest Management Plan, coyotes, jackrabbits, cottontails, bats, and snakes are common wildlife species on Holloman AFB. In dry years, these species increase in the housing area, runways, and High Speed Test Track. The "rainfield" area at the intersection of Hay Draw and the High Speed Test Track has consistent wildlife use.

In 1991, coyote populations were high and concentrated in the housing area and near the runways. A month-long program was initiated by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service in cooperation with Holloman AFB Pest Management to reduce coyote populations, using cyanide in M-44s. Since this time, studies indicate artificial controls such as those conducted in 1991 are ineffective in controlling reproduction rates. Therefore, offending animals are removed only when necessary. No current predator control programs are implemented at HAFB. The coyotes are important predators that control rabbits at the golf course.

Bats are located in culverts, aircraft hangers, and several abandoned and partially occupied buildings (Chapter 3 - Fauna, Chapter 4 - Cantonment, Chapter 4 - Northern Shrublands, Chapter 6 - Fish and Wildlife Management). Arousal from hibernation can cause fatal expenditure of energy reserves (Fenton 1970, Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Residents of Military Family Housing may be frightened of bats and often do not realize their beneficial impact on reducing nuisance insects. Calls received by the Shop for bats from Military Family Housing are reported to the 49 CES/CEV to determine method of removal, if necessary (*See* Chapter 7 - Cantonment (CT13) for procedures).

Snakes and skunks are often live-trapped by Pest Management personnel. After successful live-trapping, the animals are released on the western perimeter road north of the runway or south of the Odell site. Rattlesnakes are especially common near the High Speed Test Track during snake migration in the fall. The High Speed Test Track locations where rattlesnakes are most often encountered are the Salt Lakes and the Hay Draw intersection. Rattlesnakes are sometimes killed by Test Track personnel. A preferred alternative would be to contact Pest Management personnel. Currently, animals are not marked prior to release; therefore, there is no record to determine if they return.

Pest management procedures and chemicals used will differ between locations and especially in "environmentally sensitive areas." The proposed Pest Management Program should be aware of identified "environmentally sensitive areas" such as Lost

River and Malone Draw that provide essential habitat for the endemic White Sands pupfish. Lake Holloman, Stinky Playa and Lagoon G provide habitat for protected and sensitive waterfowl, shorebirds, and migratory birds. Additionally, the program should take into consideration the solubility of chemicals that translocate through surface and groundwater with particular emphasis in identified "environmentally sensitive areas". Other sensitive areas include Burrowing Owl habitat. Treating occupied burrows with fumigants could harm or kill the owls, which is a violation of the [Migratory Bird Treaty Act](#). Areas near active burrows should not be sprayed during the breeding season. The Pest Management Plan should make a thorough review and integrate the Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan with emphasis on Chapter 6 - Sensitive Natural Areas, Sensitive Species, and Wetlands to avoid endangering wildlife.

Outdoor Recreation

There are numerous outdoor recreation facilities at Holloman AFB that are available to military and government personnel and their families. Most of these facilities are within the Cantonment MU, while others, such as the horse stables and shooting range, are within the Northern Shrublands MU (Figure 21). Outdoor recreational activities that affect natural resources are addressed in this portion of the plan and include: sport centers, the golf course, parks and jogging paths, the FAMCAMP, sports range, and horseback riding. In addition, illegal recreational activities such as off-road vehicle use and fishing are also addressed. Hunting and birdwatching activities are covered in Chapter 6 - Fish and Wildlife Management.

Figure 21. Outdoor recreational sites on Holloman AFB

Sports Centers

The sports centers on Holloman AFB consist of the Youth and CDC Center, a soccer field, six ball fields, two tennis courts, a football and track field, and facilities associated with the airmen's and officers pools. Preliminary plans propose to expand outdoor recreational facilities (49 CES/SVS). The majority of these plans are proposed within the Cantonment area. Plans include renovation and new construction of a *Youth Center and Outdoor Education Facility*. The proposed expansion area is to be located behind the current Youth and CDC Centers. In addition to the expanded Center, a *Youth Sports 4-Plex* has been proposed for location adjacent to the golf course. The *Youth Sports 4-Plex* would include a bicycle and jogging trail network connecting the facility to the housing area. This would provide the opportunity for safe and non-motorized recreational activities. Another proposed recreational facility is the *Fitness Center Sports Complex*, a large construction proposal to include multipurpose facilities of sports fields connected by existing bicycle and jogging trails. The development of the *Youth Sports 4-Plex* and *Fitness Center Sports Complex* would increase water consumption and chemical inputs. [HILDY: COSTS, IS LAND AVAILABLE, IS THERE A NEED?]

Apache Mesa Golf Course

The golf course is a considerable luxury that imposes an enormous impact on water resources in this xeric environment. The golf course currently has 9-holes and is the single largest user of water and chemical inputs on the base. Approximately 5-6 million gallons of water are used monthly. The maintenance of the greens requires herbicides and fertilizers, non-point source pollutants that enter the drainage ditches and eventually empty into the constructed wetlands. The two ponds within the golf course constitute a sink for chemical pollutants originating within the golf course. Because the golf course is not considered an industrial source, it is not included within the Holloman AFB Stormwater Pollution Prevention Plan. Therefore, management of stormwater runoff from the golf course must be conducted independently of industrial sources. Programs have been implemented to reduce the use of water on the greens, saving approximately 3-7 million gallons/month. A review of natural resource impacts created at the golf course needs to be conducted regularly.

The golf course ponds are stocked with fish. These fish are non-edible due to toxic chemical contaminants within the ponds. 'No fishing' signs are posted at the ponds. Two to four Canada geese (*Branta canadensis*) live on the golf course ponds from October through January.

Maintenance vehicles currently use the playa shrublands west of the golf course for maintenance operations. The area is now rutted, resulting in soil erosion and disturbance to playa vegetation. Vehicle access needs to be controlled and an established route defined to allow the natural vegetation to reestablish. Golf course personnel find it inconvenient to drive to the base washrack located near Building 133 to wash down vehicles and equipment, and therefore they hose down the vehicles on-site. This procedure allows grease and oil to enter the stormwater drainage ditch that flows into the constructed wetland.

The base has submitted a proposal to increase the current nine holes to eighteen holes south of the existing course. This proposal includes construction of a "Tri-Club" near the site for the current clubhouse. Any consideration of the proposal would have to include the following logistical and management concerns:

- The reclamation agreement with the State of New Mexico prohibits the use of the capped lagoons as a golf course. Portions of the golf course could not be planned to cover this area.
- Holloman AFB should reduce water consumption, not increase it. Before new holes are added, water use on the existing course should be reduced. No additional water is available for nine more holes. Golf course design would need to be adjusted to include drought-tolerant and salt-tolerant grass species such as the native inland saltgrass. The inland saltgrass provides erosion control and is a nutrient filter for controlling fertilizer load in stormwater runoff. Additional xeriscaping designs will need to be implemented to further reduce water use.
- The existing grounds contract does not cover management of any new areas.
- Additional chemical impacts would need to be assessed, as well as consequence of the increased contaminant load into the constructed wetlands.
- A plan for the maintenance of vehicles is necessary to ensure that additional pollutants do not enter the system.

FamCamp RV Park

The FamCamp is situated partially within a floodplain containing barren alkaline playas. It is sparsely vegetated with grasses and shrubs characteristic of the Lake Holloman Wetlands.

FamCamp is located west of the main entrance and north of Hwy 70 (Figure 21).

The camp provides full hookups for 12 recreational camping vehicles. Stays are limited to 30 days and are available on a space-available basis.

A preliminary proposal and plan includes expanding the camp to 24 spaces and adding additional amenities to the camp. These include providing full service utility sites, a playground, and a pet exercise area. The proposed extension of the FamCamp has been designed and needs an Environmental Assessment (EA) compliant with NEPA and a Finding of No Practical Alternative (FONPA) compliant with EO 11988 (Protection of Floodplains). The EA should include removal of non-native plants (e.g. salt cedar) and landscaping with salt-tolerant xerotypic plants that are viable in floodplains.

Apache Sports Range

The Apache Sports Range offers skeet and trap shooting, sporting clay, archery, and a rifle and pistol range. The soil within the shooting range becomes heavily contaminated over time with an accumulation of lead shot. Birds normally pick up small pebbles to aid in digestion, and they can accidentally ingest the lead pellets. They also use nearby shrubs for perching. The lead is reclaimed every three years by a commercial contractor.

The method for removing the lead, by scraping the topsoil, supposedly removes the threat to neotropical migratory birds [HILDY: DO YOU HAVE A CITATION?]. Shrubs could be removed from the range to prevent the area from being attractive to the migratory birds. In addition, a study should be conducted to determine the extent to which birds ingest lead pellets and whether a 3-year interval is frequent enough to protect birds from lead poisoning.

Horseback Riding

The Flying "H" Equestrian Facility has a 40-stall capacity. The facilities include show, practice, and jumping arenas; an exercise pen; quarantine stalls; and hot walker. The programs associated with the equestrian facility offer horsemanship clinics, fun shows, trail rides and horse shows. The facility is located within the Malone Draw MU (Figure 21).

On Holloman AFB, the highest concentrations of non-native species tend to be within the cantonment area and at the horse stables. Many of the non-native species have been introduced in the grass hay and alfalfa feed used at the stables. Exotic seeds within the feed are either transported by air or disseminated in horse droppings. Trails that are repetitively used for horseback riding frequently show disturbances to the native composition of plants. Both trampling and the introduction of exotic species alter the natural vegetation composition. Because persistent disturbances were not part of the natural and evolutionary functioning of this arid landscape, many of the non-native plants out-compete the native species (Wedell 1996). Only certified "weed-free" horse feeds should be allowed on base.

There is no established system of trails. The horseback riders are allowed to create their own trails, known as "trailblazing". The practice of making new trails has further fragmented the landscape, caused soil compaction, trampled native plants, and destroyed cryptogamic crusts. Fragmentation creates a patchwork landscape of isolated natural areas that can separate species populations and prevent the flow of animals, materials, and energy among the patches (Leslie et al. 1996). Soil compaction creates an impervious surface that inhibits water filtration and promotes overland sheet flow preventing essential recharge to broad areas of the landscape. Trampling destroys the soil matrix so that cryptogamic crusts and native plants are destroyed. Cryptogamic crusts provide the greatest resistance to wind and sheet erosion (Belnap, personal communication) in this semi-arid landscape. Due to military training activities near the stables, the safety of the recreationist also is a concern. Trails should be carefully and judiciously planned, and rules against trailblazing should be strongly enforced.

Parks and Jogging Paths within the Cantonment Area

[HILDY: I NEED INFORMATION] The parks within Holloman AFB provide unique services for a diverse community of people. The Heritage Park The Steinhoff Park Thrasher Park

Steinhoff Park is visited by 25,000 to 45,000 people a year. A multipurpose pavilion for group activities has been suggested for the park. Hiking trails

Off-road vehicle use (ORV)

Recreational off-road vehicles and all-terrain vehicles (ATV) are not permitted to travel off existing roads within the base (Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3). Any off-road vehicle use must be justified following the criteria established in AFI 32-7064 (10.6):

Allow use of off-road vehicles only after thoroughly analyzing the resource base. Especially evaluate the impact on erodible soils and wildlife. Restrict use of off-road vehicles, including dirt bikes and all-terrain vehicles, to areas that can sustain their use without damage to natural or cultural resources. Make sure all off-road vehicles are licensed and insured. Close areas damaged from uncontrolled off-road vehicle use from future use. Undertake rehabilitation projects to restore the damage.

Unauthorized recreational ORV use has occurred on the base since 1975. Most of the current unauthorized ORV activity occurs in the drainage bottoms of Lost River, Malone Draw, the North Fork of Dillard Draw, and the more remote arroyos in the northern portion of the base.

Several potential recreational ORV areas were discussed at the INRMP scoping meetings. Two principal locations received consideration, the borrow pit (Figure 21) and a portion of the north fork of Dillard Draw (Figure 9). Due to mission-related demands, the borrow pit is currently a proposed site for ORV field training for the military. The borrow pit will not be considered for recreational use by off-road vehicles such as ATVs and motorcycles, because of potential damage to the course and scheduling conflicts (Lee 1998). Damage caused to the area due to recreational use could not be restored under the military program (Lee 1998). The proposed ORV area in the north fork of Dillard Draw is located on approximately 38.5 ha (95 acres) just south of the recently closed municipal landfill and east of the Fire Training Facility. The vertical relief of the sloping sides of the Dillard Draw arroyo provides challenging hill climbs; however, approximately 60% of this proposed site is within the 100-year floodplain. The area would require an extensive perimeter fence so that recreationists would not expand the ORV area to other sites such as the landfill remediation site nearby. If a recreational ORV/ATV area is established, safety and enforcement issues will need to be addressed.

Other types of ORVs include ATV such as motorcycles, quadrunners, and mountain bikes. Mountain biking will not be encouraged on base except during organized mountain biking events sponsored by the 49 SVS. The organized events are held approximately twice per year on weekends and occur only on existing roads in the Dillard Draw area. Off-road mountain biking will not be allowed either during these organized events or at any other time on base.

Fishing

Fishing is not allowed on Holloman AFB. The golf course ponds have been stocked with Tarpolean carp, which glean algae from the ponds, providing a biological control that maintains the esthetics of the ponds. Because the ponds are stagnant, they provide breeding grounds for mosquitoes; therefore, *Gambusia* are introduced to eat mosquito larvae. Non-native fish, particularly *Gambusia*, could potentially pose a threat to pupfish if they are accidentally introduced into pupfish habitat (Chapter 6 - Sensitive Species). These ponds are contaminated with DDT, other insecticides, fertilizer, and herbicides, which can move through the food chain into catfish and bluegills present in the ponds. Even if fish removal were not allowed as part of a fishing day, children who managed to take fish home could be at risk. For this reason, a children's fishing day is not recommended. The golf course ponds should be posted with signs warning of the dangers of swimming or fishing.

Off-base Recreation

During the internal scoping meetings, a proposal was discussed to establish an off-base camping area for Holloman AFB personnel use within the Lincoln National Forest. The interested participants suggested an agreement with the Lincoln National Forest to turn over management jurisdiction to Holloman AFB for an area within the western Sacramento Mountains. The informal proposal included constructing buildings and bringing in electrical and water utilities. The following management concerns and potential impacts are listed below:

- Abundant public facilities already exist within the Sacramento Mountains that provide this type of service. These facilities are already available to Holloman AFB personnel. Privately owned cabins can be rented, or, for more rustic conditions, camping sites are available through the U.S. Forest Service.
- The Lincoln National Forest is already overdeveloped, with numerous roads and buildings. This proposal would create more infrastructure and disruption to the environment.
- Building new facilities equipped with water and electricity for use only by the military within public lands could create poor public relations. The military already has sole access to many recreational facilities on base, including numerous quality of life amenities within the Tularosa Basin. Taking over more public lands in peacetime could also create public relations problems.
- The costs for construction and administration may be prohibitive due to shrinking federal budgets.

Potential Future Impacts

Military Training and Operations

Some training activities that were conducted in the past have had detrimental impacts on the environment. In particular, off-road vehicle training that was conducted along shoulders and within drainages, such as Malone Draw, Hay Draw and the wetlands south of the Bare Base compound, adversely affected soils and native plants. Due to the highly erodible soils and sensitive habitat areas for the federally protected pupfish, drainages such as Malone Draw will be excluded from training activities.

As long as all mitigation measures for proposed action items covered in the Programmatic Environmental Assessment (PEA) for ground-based training are implemented, there should be no foreseeable future actions that would have the potential for significant environmental impacts, individually or cumulatively (Holloman AFB 1998). No significant impact to a particular resource or cumulative impacts are predicted by long-term use of any of the training areas (Holloman AFB 1998).

Provisions for changes or additions to ground-based training are included in the ground-based training PEA. Any proposed ground-based training requirements will be evaluated by 49 CES/CEV against the training descriptions, mitigation measures, and predicted environmental impacts addressed in the PEA. If the proposed actions are consistent with the descriptions, mitigation measures, and impacts, and are not associated with extraordinary circumstances, then the actions can be categorically excluded under Categorical Exclusion A2.11 (AFI 32-7061) as documented on Form 813:

“Actions similar to other actions which have been determined to have an insignificant impact in a similar setting as established in an EIS or EA resulting in a FONSI. The EPF must document application of this CATEX on AF Form 813, specifically identifying the previous Air Force approved environmental document which provides the basis for this determination.”

If any future proposed ground-based field training has issues or extraordinary circumstances not evaluated in the PEA,

“...the proposed training cannot be categorically excluded under Categorical Exclusion A2.11. The proposed training activity will be evaluated in a supplement to the PEA (40 CFR 1502.9). Any supplement for a particular training will not effect the analysis of any other training/exercise evaluated in the PEA.” (Holloman AFB, 1998)

Grounds Maintenance

Current base landscaping practices take into consideration the arid climate and native plants when landscaping base general-use areas that surround buildings and medians. However, continued use of non-native, high water-use plants in base housing will jeopardize future water availability by drastically depleting this limited resource. In addition, the golf course is the largest water-user on base and is considering expanding to an additional 9 holes. The golf course green is planted in non-native grasses while native grasses found on Holloman AFB could provide a superior green that would require less water and pesticides input. There is a consensus among the environmental staff that expanding to an additional 9 holes and maintaining the current 9-holes would violate the DoD Measure of Merit number 2 that states: "By the end of FY 2000, the amount of pesticides and herbicides applied annually on Dod installations will be reduced by 50 percent from the FY93 baseline in pounds of active ingredient." [HILDY: are we quoting this properly? Or other regulation more pertinent?]

Recreation

Recreational pursuits that include off-road travel, using motorized vehicles and horseback riding, have resulted in degradation of easily erodible soils and sparse plant cover. If these types of activities are allowed to continue, especially in Malone and Ritas Draws, the White Sands pupfish habitat could be destroyed. Any expansion of off-road travel will further fragment the landscape and limit the movement of species throughout the landscape. Without specifically defined roads and trails for people to travel through the Northern Shrublands MU, the area could potentially develop into a landscape similar to the mesquite shrublands to the east. The mesquite shrublands are highly mobile, unstable sandsheets that creates visibility problems from blowing dust.

If management recommendations provided in Chapter 7 are adopted and reviewed annually to accommodate for changing environmental and mission related activities, there is no foreseeable impact that would require "major federal actions" pursuant to the National Environmental Policy Act.

CHAPTER 6 - MANAGEMENT ISSUES AND CONCERNS

This chapter focuses on the potential issues pertinent to managing the natural resources on Holloman AFB. These issues and concerns were assembled through the internal scoping meeting process of the INRMP. They are presented from the perspective that managing for diversity of functional groups, rather than individual species, is important in maintaining biodiversity (West 1993, Whitford 1997). In addition, abiotic factors need to be included in the assessment, to ensure that processes that support a variety of species are not inhibited or altered by human actions. Using this ecosystem approach, Holloman AFB recognizes local associations of interacting plants, animals, microbes, and fungi.

Introduction

This chapter focuses on management issues and concerns regarding various natural resources on Holloman AFB. These issues were compiled as a result of interdisciplinary presentations by subject matter experts from Holloman AFB, in association with the New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, University of New Mexico. Additional resources employed include GIS layers developed for the plan, various research and inventories previously conducted on base, component plans, Memoranda of Agreement, and the *Holloman AFB General Plan* (1996). These issues were considered in light of pertinent Department of Defense Instruction (DoDI), Air Force Instructions (AFI), Holloman AFB regulations, and best management practices (BMP).

Management issues and concerns are defined in the following sections. At the beginning of each sub-section, a summary list of the **Topics** and associated **Management Issues** are provided for quick reference. Below the list are presented in-depth discussions of the individual topics of concern. Recommended **Management Actions** and **BMP** relevant to each management issue are provided in the following chapter (Chapter 7).

Sensitive Natural Areas

Topic	Management Issue
<i>Cryptogamic Crusts:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Disturbance by trampling and fire● Re-establishment after disturbance
<i>Duneland Cottonwood Communities:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Research has not been conducted on this unique community● Groundwater flow has been altered due to High Speed Test Track activities

Cryptogamic Crusts

Cryptogamic soil crusts are living organisms composed of either algae (cyanobacteria), lichen, moss, fungi or liverworts. They may occur as a single taxa or in combinations (Ladyman and Muldavin 1996). These crusts provide stability to soils by reducing erosion and increase available nitrogen in nitrogen and carbon-deficient soils (Gottfried 1991). In desert and semi-desert ecosystems, cryptogamic crusts provide the majority of available nitrogen (West and Skujins 1977). They bind soil particles together into hydrophobic aggregates that can promote water retention in the soil and retard infiltration, thus to reducing nutrient loss (Ladyman and Muldavin 1996). Crusts of algae and lichen have been found to increase organic matter in soils in the Southwest United States

(Fletcher and Martin 1948). Crusts that develop on stabilized eolian flats with gypsic crusts may have a higher plant density than on substrates lacking cryptogams (Doleman 1988). Dark crusts (cyanobacteria) like those at Holloman AFB can increase soil temperature, and this may preferentially affect seed germination for some species. Hummocky microtopography of the crusts can be advantageous to seed germination by trapping water and sheltering seeds (Harper et al. 1965). Cryptogamic crusts aid in the mineral uptake of vascular plants, increasing total mineral content (Harper and Pendleton 1993), which in turn positively affect mineral availability for herbivores (Ladyman and Muldavin 1996).

A systematic field sampling procedure covering the Main Base (from the periphery of the dunes and to the east) reported that cryptogamic crusts varied from zero to 85 percent coverage (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). The geographic distribution of crusts with at least 60 percent cover lies predominantly within the Test Track and Northern Shrublands Management Units. GIS layers developed through the process of the INRMP suggest that these crusts may have associations with particular plant communities. Three vegetation mapping units combined held 85.06 percent of the lands containing greater than 80 percent cryptogam cover and 77.91 percent of the lands with at least 60 percent cover of cryptogams (Figure 22). These mapping units are: Fourwing Saltbush/Gyp Dropseed Shrubland, Gyp Dropseed Grassland, and Fourwing Saltbush/Alkali Sacaton Shrubland. Fourwing Saltbush/Gyp Dropseed Shrubland has the strongest association with cryptogam cover. High densities of cryptogam cover (60% and 80%) are dominated by Fourwing Saltbush/Gyp Dropseed Shrubland. This community type accounts for more than 46% of the total variation in cover type for high-density cryptogam cover. It is interesting to note that this vegetation community appears to be limited to areas with at least 23 percent cryptogam cover.

Three principal stages occur in the development of cryptogamic crusts on Holloman AFB. The first phase is the physical-chemical hardening of gypsum caused by rain and subsequent drying of the surface. The second phase is the development of cyanobacteria, followed by more complex organisms such as lichen and mosses. The primary natural erosional processes on Holloman AFB are wind, rain, and sheet erosion caused by overland flows during monsoonal storms. Cyanobacteria are the most widespread and abundant throughout the basin and provide the greatest resistance to wind and sheet erosion (Belnap, personal communication). Lichen and mosses, however, are most effective in protecting the soils from raindrop impact. Recovery rates for cryptogams on gypsum soils are usually rapid compared to other crusts in arid environments. Cryptogamic crusts on gypsum soils may return to pre-disturbance levels within ten years as compared to other arid regions that may take 200-250 years to re-establish to well developed levels (Belnap, personal conversation). Successful re-establishment of cryptogams in these soils is more likely if rainfall occurs soon after a disturbance event such as any ground military training exercise. The rainfall accelerates gypsic crust formation, thus protecting against wind erosion. Impediments to recovery would be continued use of an area and high winds following a disturbance.

Cryptogamic crusts are extremely sensitive to disturbance by trampling and fire (Ladyman and Muldavin 1996). Studies conducted in Arches National Monument found lower infiltration rates (up to 90% lower) and decreased species diversity in trampled areas (Ladyman and Muldavin 1996). Fire can destroy cryptogamic communities; post-fire activities help determine re-establishment rates that may differ depending on human activities and seasonal precipitation events (West and Hassan 1986; Johansen et al. 1982; Johansen and Rushforth 1985; Johansen et al. 1993). Since these crusts appear to be vital to maintaining the health of desert ecosystems, a decisive management plan to protect these habitats should be considered for all current and proposed military training areas as well as any future considerations for the introduction of fire management.

Duneland Cottonwood Communities

Cottonwood stands are found within dune fields in only two locations within the state, in the White Sands within the boundaries of WSNM, WSMR, and Holloman AFB and within the Mescalero Sands (managed by the BLM) east of Roswell. These unique communities have not been studied; therefore, little can be said about this habitat type and interactions or use by other organisms. This community represents the only species providing high vertical structure in these dunes. Research to determine ecosystem functions and processes will contribute to developing appropriate management strategies for the dunes.

It is likely the cottonwood stands were established prior to the dune encroachment (E. Muldavin, personal communication). Tree ring studies may offer clues to past climatic changes and fire occurrence history within this portion of the basin. Holocene climate history for the Chihuahuan Desert has been extrapolated from data collected primarily from packrat midden sites of the white-throated packrat (*Neotoma albigula*) (Betancourt et al. 1990). These data are collected at midden sites within the surrounding mountain ranges and exclude basinal information. Dendrochronology research on these cottonwoods may contribute to filling an important gap in climate and fire history for pre-settlement times. The possibility exists that older, preserved trees lie beneath the dunes and could provide even earlier data.

Cottonwoods require a permanent water source. A potential threat to this ecosystem is diminished groundwater flow. It is apparent from satellite images that the majority of these cottonwoods are located at the terminus of Hay Draw within the dunes. Changes in groundwater flows from either the headwaters of this drainage or diversions due to Test Track activities may imperil this unique community. Physical channel conditions are known to affect biotic composition (Cummins et al. 1984). Future research should include ground water data and water holding capacity of the dunes.

Figure 22. Cryptogam Cover by Vegetation Mapping Unit

Sensitive Species

Topic	Management Issue
Plants	
<i>B. clauzadeana:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Disturbance by trampling and vehicle traffic ● Disturbance during dry periods may destroy lichens
<i>Grama grass cactus:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Disturbance by trampling and vehicle traffic ● Removal of overstory nursery plants ● Conversion of grasslands to shrublands
Animals	
<i>White Sands Pupfish:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Introduction of non-native fish into pupfish habitat ● Dewatering of pupfish habitat ● Salt cedar and other phreatophyte exotics decrease water levels and concentrate salts ● Chemical treatments on exotic plants within pupfish habitat ● Potential break in sewer line that transects Lost River ● Potential threat of lead contamination from Small Arms Firing Range in Ritas Draw ● Off-road vehicle use in pupfish habitat ● Illegal collection of pupfish
<i>Western Burrowing Owl:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Predation by badgers ● Disturbance by trapping or frequent visits by humans ● Filling in burrows
<i>Western Snowy Plover:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Flooding of plover habitat ● Excessive drying of playa lakes ● Diminished food base ● Disturbance by human activities

Holloman lies within a region characterized by both Chihuahuan Desert and Great Basin plant species. This area has unique plant and animal assemblages specific to Holloman AFB and WSMR. No federally listed species, covered under the Endangered Species Act reside on Holloman AFB. However, four species have particular status; they are: a lichen (*B. clauzadeana*) proposed for rare and endangered listing with The World Conservation Union (Ladyman 1990, pers. comm.); the White Sands Pupfish, a state endangered, group 2 (threatened) species; the Western Burrowing Owl, a federal Species of Concern; and the Western Snowy Plover, a federal Species of Concern. The lichen receives no mandatory protection, while the pupfish could be listed under the ESA if protection

policies are not effectively carried out under the cooperative agreement (*See* Animals below). The grama grass cactus is included due to its former candidate status.

Refer to the *Holloman Air Force Base Sensitive Species Management Plan* (Mehlhop et al. 1998) for a comprehensive report on the threatened and endangered species found or likely to be found on Holloman AFB. The plan discusses the threats to individual species, defines conservation goals, and outlines research and monitoring needs to accomplish the conservation goals. A list is provided below of the species covered in the plan. Hyperlinks to the individual chapters covering the species is also provided.

<i>PLANTS:</i>	Neotropic Cormorant	Western Burrowing Owl
Sacramento Prickly Poppy	White-faced Ibis	Loggerhead Shrike
Grama Grass Cactus	Bald Eagle	Baird's Sparrow
Alamo Canyon Beardtongue	Ferruginous Hawk	Western Small-Footed Bat
Villard's Pincushion Cactus	Northern Aplomado Falcon	Occult Little Brown Bat
Button Cactus	Peregrine Falcon	Spotted Bat
<i>ANIMALS:</i>	Western Snowy Plover	Arizona Black-tailed Prairie Dog
White Sands Pupfish	Interior Least Tern	White Sands Woodrat
Texas Horned Lizard	Common Ground-Dove	New Mexico Jumping Mouse

Plants

B. clauzadeana

Lichens represent a symbiotic relationship between fungi and algae (Ladyman and Muldavin 1996). *Biatorrella clauzadeana* is a disjunct, tericolous (meaning it grows on soil) Mediterranean lichen species that occurs in the southwestern United States and Mexico. It is rare and currently under consideration by The World Conservation Union, [Species Survival Commission](#) (IUCN) for rare and endangered listing (pers. comm., Juanita Ladyman). The lichen is currently being tracked by the NMNHP and has Heritage rankings of G1 and S1. In New Mexico this lichen is restricted to gypsum "tiaras". These are vertical, concave, gypsum surfaces on the leeward side of small shrubs typically having a northwest aspect. These microhabitat distributions and their minute size make locating the lichen very difficult (Weber and Nash 1992). *B. clauzadeana* was found scattered and infrequent on Holloman AFB at the edge of escarpments along drainages, primarily within the Northern Shrublands MU (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). It occurs at only one other site within the state of New Mexico. At Bottomless Lakes, this lichen appears "sporadically" on gypsum outcrops on Comanche Hill (Weber and Nash 1992).

Lichens are easily disturbed by foot traffic. This may be somewhat advantageous during high precipitation events where the lichen fragment and can start new colonies. However, if fragmentation occurs during dry periods, it may lead to destruction of lichens (Pegau 1970; Harper and Marble 1988). Lichen is also highly susceptible to fire, even more so than the cryptogamic crusts predominant throughout this area of the base (*See* Chapter 6 - Sensitive Natural Areas). The lichens appear to occur on the knolls of

drainages. These surfaces are normally stabilized and protected if foot and automobile traffic are limited to maintained roads. Two of the lichen colonies are protected by the 200-meter buffer established around wetlands and Waters of the U.S. Protection of other sights does not warrant any action at this time, because lichen sites on Holloman AFB do not fall within current or proposed military training sites.

Grama grass cactus (*Toumeyia papyracantha*)

The grama grass cactus (*Toumeyia papyracantha*) was formerly a federal Category 2 candidate for listing as a threatened or endangered species. It was downlisted in 1995 to a Category 3 species, because it was found to be more abundant than previously recorded. The New Mexico State Natural Resources Division likewise removed the species from the review list for consideration. One of the important justifications for the downlisting was the presence of large ungrazed populations on military installations in New Mexico (Sivinski and Lightfoot 1994). These semi-protected populations are considered crucial to the well-being of the species. The population on HAFB, in particular, is now the best-documented site to date. This is the first population sampling large enough to allow a statistically confident estimation of plant numbers over a large area (Mehlhop et al. 1998a).

Grama grass cactus is notable for its tangled mass of grass-like spines that gives it the appearance of a small tuft of blue grama grass (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Grama grass cactus habitat on Holloman AFB is within communities dominated by *Sporobolus* grasslands. The cacti are found predominantly in sandy loam to sandy-clay loam soils, well drained, with little or no gravel. The highest densities are found within the Northern Shrublands and Cantonment MUs.

One of the high-density sites (26-44 cactus/ha) is located within the King I training area; an enclosure has been erected to protect this site from disturbance (Hildy Reiser, pers. comm.). Grazing has decimated populations of grama grass cactus by trampling, removing overstory nursery plants, and converting grasslands to shrublands (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Military ground-based activities could replicate some of these disturbances, potentially causing irreversible damage to the existing viable populations. Collection of the plant for ornamental use by commercial interests and private individuals has greatly reduced the size of numerous easily accessible populations (Mehlhop et al. 1998a).

Any new or proposed activities designated for Northern Shrublands or the Cantonment MUs should consider grama grass cactus distributions (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). NMNHP delineated seven areas of relatively high cactus density, representing approximately 45 percent of the total cactus population within Holloman AFB (Figure 23). These areas include 917 ha (2266 acres) covering 4.45 % of the base. Mehlhop et al. (1998) recommend a systematic, long-term monitoring plan be implemented by establishing monitoring plots within the grama grass cactus conservation areas.

Figure 23. Proposed grama grass cactus conservation areas

Seven proposed conservation areas for grama grass cactus protect 45 percent of the total population within Holloman AFB.

Animals

White Sands Pupfish (*Cyprinodon tularosa*)

The White Sands Pupfish is a Species of Concern (formerly a Category 2 species). Its protection is the responsibility of the Biological Resources Division of the U.S. Geological Survey. It has no legal protection under the Endangered Species Act, but it could be listed under the act if the species fails to be managed properly under the Cooperative Agreement (1994, Attachment 1). The species is classified as State Endangered, Group 2 (threatened) and was first listed on 24 January, 1975 (NMGF Reg. 563). This designation means that the species' prospects of survival or recruitment in the

state are likely to be in jeopardy within the near future. In addition, this species is considered a Species of Special Concern by the American Fisheries Society (Williams et al. 1989). It is listed in The Nature Conservancy's global ranking protocol as G1, meaning that it is critically imperiled globally because of extreme rarity or because of some factor(s) making it especially vulnerable to extinction. The New Mexico Natural Heritage Program ranks the White Sands Pupfish as S1, meaning that it is critically imperiled in New Mexico because of extreme rarity (Biological and Conservation Database 1994).

The White Sands pupfish is endemic to the Tularosa Basin (Figure 24). This fish inhabits clear, shallow, strongly alkaline pools and streams with fine mud-silt and sand bottoms. Prior to 1978, the causeway crossing Lost River was breached by Test Track personnel, introducing pupfish into the White Sands National Monument. On HAFB the Lost River population is distributed in three stream segments connected by water only at times of heavy rains (Figure 13): the Malone-Ritas Draw segment above Range Road 9, the trench segment between Range Road 9 and the Lost River Basin, and the dunes segment downstream from the basin (Pittenger and Springer 1996).

Figure 24. Pupfish sp.

A cooperative agreement for the management and protection of the pupfish was signed in mid-1994 by Holloman AFB, White Sands Missile Range, White Sands National Monument, US Fish and Wildlife Service, and Mew

Mexico Department of Game and Fish. The conservation goal of the team is to maintain a viable and genetically appropriate population of the White Sands pupfish in Malone Draw and Lost River as a replicate of the natural population in Salt Creek. If feasible, support additional replicate populations of the White Sands pupfish will be supported.

Essential habitat for the pupfish, designated under the cooperative agreement, includes “*all stream channels of Malone Draw and Lost River on HAFB and White Sands National Monument and a corridor 660 feet wide, extending 330 feet from either side of the center of the stream channel*” (MOU pg. 3). “Limited Use Areas” consist of all land within the topographic drainage basin of Malone Draw-Lost River, where activities must be managed to ensure that degradation of essential habitat does not occur through direct or indirect effects such as contaminated runoff or excessive soil erosion (Figure 13). All undertakings at Holloman AFB within Lost River and Malone Draw are closely monitored, and no projects, that would impound water or alter the natural landscape are allowed near known pupfish habitat.

Potential threats to the population of pupfish within Holloman AFB occur due to changes in the physical or biological environment. Other potentially destructive impacts are caused by human activities. The introduction of non-native fish into pupfish habitat, in particular the mosquitofish (*Gambusia affinis*) and the largemouth bass (*Micropterus*

salmoides) are potential threats ([Mehlhop et al. 1998a](#)). These fish have either reduced or eradicated native cyprinodonts in other habitats (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). The potential for dewatering of the pupfish habitat is a possibility because intensive groundwater pumping for agricultural uses nearby could potentially lower the water table, thereby affecting surface water availability within Malone Draw and Lost River (Pittenger and Springer 1996). Salt cedar, a non-native plant (*see* Chapter 6 - Exotics Plants and Animals) rapidly decreases water availability within desert arroyo-riparian ecosystems because of excessive evapotranspiration rates. The spread and increase of this species may pose a long-term threat to the stability of pupfish habitat ([Mehlhop et al. 1998](#)). Furthermore, chemical treatment for eradication of salt cedar along Lost River could cause water contamination (Pittenger 1996) and potentially disrupt the food chain of the pupfish by killing algae and other forage ([Mehlhop et al. 1998](#)). A break in the sewer line that crosses the river south of the Test Track could release as much as 2,000 gallons of raw sewage into the river. In addition, there is a potential threat of lead contamination from the Small Arms Firing Range in Ritas Draw. When water flows through the draw, it can carry lead from spent munitions into Malone Draw and Lost River. Unauthorized off-road vehicle use, particularly in the reach between the Malone-Ritas Draw confluence and Range Road 9 has been a chronic threat to that segment of the population (Pittenger 1996). Because that segment of the population is limited by low availability of water, the impact of vehicles could be substantial (Mehlhop et al. 1998). Finally, illegal collection of fish could imperil the populations, with the greatest impact occurring at the Malone-Ritas Draw segment (above Range Road 9) (Pittenger and Springer 1996; Mehlhop et al. 1998).

The following is a list of on-going research activities and projects with the White Sands pupfish and the sources for the methodologies used ([Mehlhop et al. 1998a](#)):

- Monitoring the population status of the pupfish at each of the sites over time (J. S. Pittenger, New Mexico Department of Game and Fish, Santa Fe; Pittenger and Springer 1996a).
- The genetic uniqueness and relatedness of the White Sands pupfish populations (C.A. Stockwell, North Dakota State University; Stockwell et al. submitted for publication).
- The relationship between White Sands pupfish morphometrics, genetics and habitat salinity (C.A. Stockwell, North Dakota State University; S. Schaeffer, New Mexico State University, Las Cruces (through 1998); S. Schaeffer, MS Thesis in preparation).
- The ecology of the White Sands pupfish in relation to a digenetic trematode that is present in two of the four populations (C.A. Stockwell, North Dakota State University).
- Methods to control salt cedar to maintain adequate amounts of surface water at pupfish sites (H. Reiser, Natural Resource Manager, Holloman Air Force Base).
- Completion of a study initiated by Holloman Air Force Base of the hydrology of the La Luz drainage, which supplies water to Lost River (H. Reiser, Natural Resource Manager, Holloman Air Force Base).
- ORV or ATV use within Malone Draw and Ritas Draws are limited to designated roads (H. Reiser, Natural Resource Manager, Holloman Air Force Base).

- GIS layer designating "Limited Use Areas," including "essential habitat corridors," were created using a 200-meter (656 feet) buffer from either side of the center of the stream channel (H. Reiser, Natural Resource Manager, Holloman Air Force Base).

Western Burrowing Owl (*Athene cunicularia hypugaea*)

The Western Burrowing Owl is classified by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service as a Species of Concern (formerly Federal Candidate 2 species) and as an informal Species of Concern by the state of New Mexico. New Mexico is the second most important wintering area for Burrowing Owls, following California (Draft: Partners in Flight State Conservation Plan 1997). With declining populations in other states, it is important that New Mexico populations be conserved (Johnson et al. 1997b).

Burrowing Owls typically inhabit flat, open areas surrounded by short grass or bare ground and use burrows constructed by other animals. These sites are often near areas of high human activity. On Holloman AFB, highest densities occur near the High Speed Test Track, with some scattered burrows near the airfield (Figure 25). Surveys conducted during the spring and summer of 1996-1997 reported a minimum of 42 fledglings from 32 nests (Johnson 1997). Although available burrows existed in less disturbed sites, such as the Northern Shrublands Management Unit, owls appear to prefer locations with relatively high human activity. Johnson et al. (1997) suggest owls may be avoiding predation by badgers that inhabit habitats with lower human impact. Burrows occur predominantly within gypgrass/alkali sacaton vegetation communities (57%). This plant community may also represent inclusions of gyp dropseed/hairy coldenia. Active owl burrows are also found in the following vegetation types: military disturbance on gyp crusts (26%), fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed (14%), and monotypic stands of alkali sacaton (0.01%).

Figure 25. Burrowing Owl Sites

Map shows Burrowing Owl burrows for surveys conducted in 1996 and 1997.

Burrowing Owls at HAFB may be taking advantage of the insects and possibly bats attracted to street and runway lights in the cantonment area. Informal observations of prey remains at burrows indicated that breeding owls consume several species of beetles, grasshoppers, lizards, small rodents, and passerine birds. There was also evidence that owls were foraging on toads in standing rainwater between the rails of the High Speed Test Track. Burrowing Owl activities near the runway and High Speed Test Track do not appear to adversely impact military missions. However, there is some concern regarding burrows near runway lights. Operations conducted at the airfield and within the High Speed Test Track area should incorporate operational procedures to avoid impacting owl

burrows (see Chapter 6 - Research and Monitoring; Chapter 7 - Cantonment and Northern Shrublands).

Trapping owls and human activities near active nests frequently result in abandonment. Therefore, where possible, owl nest sites should be avoided during training exercises, vehicle parking, or off-road travel. Owls nesting along the High Speed Test Track are threatened with direct disturbance from vehicles driving too close to the burrows (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). These and other activities with potential impact on Burrowing Owls should be conducted outside the breeding season (mid-March through July). Some owls overwinter at Holloman in nesting burrows. Pesticides are a direct threat to owl populations and should not be administered near owl burrows. Habitat use by winter owls should also be considered when planning for owl management. Because burrow availability does not appear to explain the distribution of owls on Holloman AFB, further research is needed to determine Burrowing Owl diet and foraging efficiency, predator impact, and nesting success in natural vs. human impact areas (Johnson et al. 1997b; [Mehlhop et al. 1998a](#)).

Western Snowy Plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*)

The Western Snowy Plover is a former Category 2 species and is presently a Species of Concern, except for the Pacific Coast population, which is designated as threatened. This subspecies breeds in the interior of the western U.S., including isolated locales in New Mexico. The New Mexico Natural Heritage Program ranks the Western Snowy Plover as S3B and S3N, meaning that it occurs as a breeder and a migrant in the state but that it is rare or uncommon (BCD 1998). Snowy Plovers arrive in New Mexico in late March, and breed in late April and May (possibly later if a second brood occurs). Numbers peak in April through early May, and again in August through early September (Freehling et al. 1998). Snowy Plovers are probably out of the state by November, although there are a few winter records in the southeast (Hubbard 1978).

Figure 26. Western Snowy Plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*)

In comparison to other shorebirds, the Plover tends to be compact, chunky, and short-necked with a very short bill (Figure 26). Snowy Plovers sprint along beaches and mud flats, stopping and starting abruptly. They forage at or just under the ground surface for small aquatic invertebrates, insects, worms, and small fish (Ehrlich et al. 1988).

Preliminary examination of fecal collections taken at Lake Stinky reveal at least 30% contain *Bledius* beetle remains, along with corixids (aquatic Hemiptera), ants, other beetles, and adult chironomids (Diptera, Freehling et al. 1998). *Bledius* spp. may be an important indicator of habitat quality for the Snowy Plover and other shorebirds at the Lake Holloman Wetlands (Freehling et al. 1998).

In New Mexico, the Snowy Plover breeds on barren alkali playas near water (Hubbard 1978). The mudflats within the Holloman Lakes Management Unit are a known breeding area for the species (Hubbard 1978). The species is most common at Stinky Playa on mudflats within close proximity to standing water and dense clumps of saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*). In addition to breeding birds, many Snowy Plovers use the area as a stopover during spring and fall migrations and occasionally during the winter (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Much of the optimal foraging habitat for the Snowy Plover around Lake Holloman was inundated during construction of the Lake Holloman Constructed Wetlands throughout 1997 and the number of Snowy Plover pairs nesting on Holloman was reduced. Birds apparently moved to Lagoon G, which had been drained as part of the construction (Mark Proctor, pers. comm.). The creation of mudflat mosaics within the Constructed Wetlands is important for the continued presence of shorebirds within the area (Freehling et al. 1998). Other limiting factors are maintaining a food base that includes *Bledius* beetles, aquatic Hemiptera, Diptera, ants, and other beetles that currently exist in the fluctuating natural playa environment within the wetlands area. Foot traffic and off-road vehicle-use disturb nesting Snowy Plovers. General and public access issues become important in considering maintaining optimal habitat and limit disturbances. Water contamination poses a threat to waterbird populations. Since the wetland system at Holloman AFB is primarily derived from processed effluents and stormwater drainages, pollution prevention controls recommended in the *Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan for Holloman AFB* should be followed.

Wetlands

Topic	Management Issue
Water quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Soluble toxic materials can enter the wetlands through wastewater effluents and stormwater drainages ● Toxic materials within wetlands are prone to biomagnification in ecological foodchains
Habitat disturbance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seasonal feeding, nesting, and migratory patterns of birds can be disrupted by human activities

Topic	Management Issue
Habitat quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Low flights of aircraft disrupt breeding birds ● Destruction of habitat by inundation ● Control flooding and drawdowns
Control the spread of salt cedar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Salt cedar alters water levels and imperils the wetland ecosystem ● Non-compliance issues within the flightline
Management for sensitive species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Management for Western Snowy Plover, Neotropic Cormorant, White-faced Ibis, Interior Least Tern, Bald Eagle, and Peregrine Falcon
Manage public use areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Manage the diverse public use recreational activities that include bird watching and hiking ● Access to other portions of the base by the public creates a security problem ● Off-road traffic imperils bird populations and the natural environment ● Resolve security issue created by hunters bearing firearms in the wetland area

In a time of declining wetlands and multiple water quality issues (Helmert 1993), Holloman AFB, in the midst of a desert ecosystem, has proactively enhanced a desert playa ecosystem to support breeding and migrating bird habitat (Davis et al. 1994).

Jurisdictional wetlands are a subcategory of waters of the U.S. and have been defined by the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers as areas that are inundated or saturated by surface or groundwater at a frequency and duration sufficient to support a prevalence of vegetation typically adapted for life in saturated soil conditions. There are approximately 48 ha. (119 acres) of jurisdictional wetlands on the main base and 0.3 ha. (0.72 acres) within the BWWSA (United States Air Force 1996). Depth and size of the wetlands vary across the base with Lake Holloman having the greatest depth and size. Maximum depth for Lake Holloman is 2-2.5m (6.6-8.2 feet) when water is near spillway height with an average depth of 1.4m (4.6 feet) (Cole et al. 1984). The most common wetlands on Holloman AFB are depressions within and adjacent to the ordinary high water mark of ephemeral streams and depressions flooded by runoff or saturated by high groundwater table (United States Air Force 1996). The majority of these wetlands fall within the Lake Holloman MU (32 ha./79 acres; Figure 9). Detailed physical and biological properties of the wetlands, including the constructed wetlands, within the Lake Holloman MU are discussed in "Chapter 4 - Lake Holloman Wetlands" and the United States Air Force Report (1996): [*Delineation of Jurisdictional Waters of the United States and Wetlands on*](#)

Holloman Air Force Base, New Mexico. The remaining wetlands are scattered throughout the base and include 6 ha. (15 acres) each within the Duneland and Cantonment MUs. The Malone Draw and Test Track MUs each contain 2 ha. (5 acres) of wetlands.

Many of the lowland depressions classified as wetland are the result of military impacts. Adjacent to the High Speed Test Track and within the northern portion of the Duneland and Test Track MUs are several depressional wetlands within blowouts or borrow pits (Figure 9). One wetland is situated in a missile crater within the dunes west of the track (United States Air Force 1996). Other small wetlands occur within the numerous systems of drainages. The Malone Draw MU contains two wetlands, one within upper Malone Draw and the other within Ritas Draw. The portion of Lost River that extends into the dunes within the Duneland MU is subject to intermittent flows and supports wetland vegetation (United States Air Force 1996). Wetlands within the Cantonment MU are located in 4 areas: (1) southeast of the north-south runway and just north of New Mexico Avenue, this wetland has been enhanced by diversion and channelization of the base stormwater drainage system; (2) vegetated wetlands north of the golf course, also due to channelization of the base stormwater drainage system; (3) depressional wetlands due to diversions of natural drainages from the construction of Highway 70/82; and (4) depressional wetlands associated with the southern reaches of Dillard Draw.

Many of the smaller wetlands, outside of the Lake Holloman MU, are important foraging areas for resident and migrating bats (Johnson et al. 1997a, Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Little is known about the use of these areas by wildlife. Their close proximity to military and testing activities, such as the High Speed Test Track are a concern. Contaminants entering these depressions, physical disturbance, and noise can negatively affect wildlife health (Helmers 1993). The effects of disturbances are variable, depending upon the species, type of disturbance, and time of year (Pfister et al. 1992).

The value of wetland habitat for wildlife is dependent on physical and biological characteristics such as vegetation communities, invertebrate communities, water chemistry, and depth (United States Air Force 1996). The constructed wetland should maintain both a vertical and horizontal diversity of habitats (Knight 1997). The vertical structure consists of a variety of canopy, subcanopy, and groundcover species. A diverse horizontal structure is maintained by a matrix of open water and microhabitats that range from dry to saturated soils on undulating topographic surfaces. A diversity of alkaline-adapted plant species providing diverse microhabitats is important for developing a broad food base for migrating bird populations and terrestrial and aquatic fauna. Water chemistry can change over time as chemical and biotic components respond to seasonal and anthropogenic impacts (Davis et al. 1997). A range of water depths in wetlands provide diverse niches and fulfill habitat requirements for terrestrial and aquatic fauna as well as avifauna. Animal diversity within wetlands and constructed wetlands typically includes microscopic invertebrates, macroinvertebrates, fish, reptiles, amphibians, birds, and mammals (Knight 1997).

Water quality is an important issue for all wetlands on Holloman AFB. Of these, the most susceptible to toxic pollutants are the constructed wetlands. The wetlands receive treated

effluent from the wastewater facility and input from industrial areas through the system of stormwater drainages (see Chapter 6 - Watershed Protection). Some toxic metals and organics have detrimental effects on the wetlands and are prone to biomagnification in ecological foodchains (Knight 1997).

Stinky Playa is the most alkaline and contains sodium chloride with a dissolved solids concentration of 23,000 mg/l (Davis et al. 1993). Stinky Playa is classified as eutrophic to hyper-eutrophic, based on phytoplankton community composition, total nitrogen, and total phosphorus (Davis et al. 1993). *Lyngbya lagerheimia* contributed to forty-six percent of the phytoplankton community composition for Stinky Playa (Davis et al. 1993).

Wetland plants have different adaptations to physical and chemical properties of the wetland. Obligate and facultative wetland plants on Holloman AFB consist of natives as well as exotics (Table 9). The most abundant native wetland plant is the inland saltgrass. The abundance of this species is partly due to the high alkalinity of soils within the wetlands. Moist-soil plants such as barnyard grass (*Echinochloa crusgalli*), a non-native found within the Holloman wetlands, provide more nutrition for migrating waterfowl than agricultural products such as corn (Haukos and Smith 1994). Barnyard grass, an important grain in the diets of migrating waterfowl (Haukos and Smith 1994) is a widespread exotic in temperate and tropical areas of the world and is high in amino acids (proteins) and minerals (e.g. calcium). Other native moist-soil plants, such as vine mesquite (*Panicum obtusum*), occur at the wetland edge within the arroyos on Holloman AFB. This plant may offer a native alternative to barnyard grass to provide nutrition for migrating waterfowl. Other invasive non-natives such as the salt cedar can significantly alter the water levels at the wetlands and imperil the wetland ecosystem (see Chapter 6 - Exotic Plants and Animals). Height restrictions exist within the flightline of the airfield and some of the salt cedars are a hazard to operations due to their location and height within the flightline.

Table 9. Wetland Plants at Holloman AFB

SCIENTIFIC NAME	COMMON	FAMILY	STATUS
Monocotyledon			
<i>Scirpus maritimus</i>	Alkali bulrush	Cyperaceae	OBL
<i>Juncus mexicanus</i>	Mexican rush	Juncaceae	FACW
<i>Distichlis spicata</i> var. <i>stricta</i>	Inland saltgrass	Poaceae	FACW
<i>Echinochloa crusgalli</i>	Barnyard grass ^e	Poaceae	FACW-
<i>Hordeum jubatum</i>	Foxtail barley ^e	Poaceae	FACW-
<i>Phragmites australis</i>	Common reed	Poaceae	FACW+
<i>Polypogon monspeliensis</i>	Rabbitfoot polypogon ^e	Poaceae	FACW+
<i>Typha angustifolia</i>	Narrowleaf cattail	Typhaceae	OBL
<i>Typha latifolia</i>	Common cattail	Typhaceae	OBL
Dicotyledon			
<i>Baccharis salicifolia</i>	Seepwillow	Asteraceae	FACW
<i>Heliotropium curassavicum</i>	Heliotrope	Boraginaceae	FACW*
<i>Allenrolfea occidentalis</i>	Pickleweed	Chenopodiaceae	FACW
<i>Bassia hyssopifolia</i>	Smotherweed	Chenopodiaceae	FACW-
<i>Sarcocornia utahensis</i> = <i>Salicornia utahensis</i>	Utah samphire	Chenopodiaceae	FACW
<i>Suaeda nigrescens</i> var. <i>glabra</i>	Smooth seepweed	Chenopodiaceae	OBL
<i>Cressa truxillensis</i>	Silky cressa	Convolvulaceae	FACW-

Legend:

- OBL - Obligate Wetland Plant
- FACW - Facultative Wetland Plant
- +/- - More/Less affinity for wetland conditions
- * - pers. comm. with Jim Wood,
USACE, Albuquerque
- ^e - exotic species

Excerpt from United States Air Force (1996).

Table 10. Phytoplankton community composition of Stinky Playa

TAXA	PERCENT
<i>Lyngbya lagerheimia</i>	46
<i>Spirulina</i>	1
<i>Chlamydomonas</i>	5
<i>Crucigenia</i>	11
<i>Staurastrum</i>	1
<i>Cosmarium</i>	1
<i>Euastrum</i>	1
<i>Phytodiniaceae</i>	3
<i>Cryptomonas</i>	31

Measurements taken April 7, 1993 (Davis et al. 1993).

The complex of constructed wetlands within the Lake Holloman MU provides important bird habitat. Bird censuses are ongoing at Holloman AFB ([Freehling et al. 1998](#)) and a complete list of birds is found in [Appendix D](#). Species management plans (Mehlhop et al. 1998a) for birds that have been sighted or could potentially be sighted at the wetlands have been developed for some of the more imperiled species such as the [Neotropic](#)

[Cormorant](#), [White-faced Ibis](#), [Interior Least Tern](#), [Western Snowy Plover](#), [Bald Eagle](#), and [Peregrine Falcon](#). Waterbird species richness and abundance were measured for Lake Holloman and Stinky Playa within four microhabitats (Freehling et al. 1998). Niche specialization for the various foraging guilds of birds range from wading and shorebirds that are dependent on the relatively shallow water edges and mudflats to ducks and grebes that forage in deeper water. The saturated soil habitat held the greatest richness and abundance across all guilds. A survey conducted at Lake Holloman, Lagoon G, and the constructed wetland, before the constructed wetland ponds were completely filled, reported bird species diversity at the constructed wetlands comparable to those at the other established, and larger waterbodies (Freehling et al. 1998).

Shorebirds are the group of birds of primary conservation concern at the Holloman wetlands. Shorebirds are found in vegetation cover ranging from 0-75%; however, most species use sites with less than 25% cover and prefer vegetation heights to be less than half their body height (Helmers 1993). Shorebirds forage on wet and drying mudflats and at water depths ranging from 0-7 inches (0-18cm). Their principal diet is macroinvertebrates. Diversity and biomass of macroinvertebrates at Holloman wetlands is apparently sufficient for shorebirds at present. Macroinvertebrates have been sampled within the constructed wetland, Lake Holloman and Stinky Playa (Davis et al. 1993, [Freehling et al. 1998](#)). Soil samples of wet to moist mudflat habitat at the constructed wetland, Lake Holloman, and Stinky Playa show that 75-90% of invertebrate composition is Diptera (primarily chironomids and ceratopogonids), followed by ostracods (5-20%, Freehling, personal communication). In contrast, a small and limited sampling at Stinky Playa found 91% of the macroinvertebrate species were Ostracoda (Davis et al. 1993, Table 11). Corixids are the predominant component of the open water habitats and shallower areas of the wetlands, i.e., in the water column (Freehling, personal communication).

Table 11. Macroinvertebrate abundances at Stinky Playa

TAXA	#m ²
<i>Ephydriidae Hydroporus nr cinerea</i>	6
<i>Chironomidae</i>	4
<i>Corixidae</i>	1
<i>Ostracoda</i>	117

Measurements taken April 7, 1993 (Davis et al. 1993).

Peak spring migrations for shorebirds generally occur from March through May, and summer/autumn migrations occur from July through September (Helmers 1993). Stopover areas with an abundance of food and resting sites free from human disturbance are particularly important during shorebirds spring migration (Eldridge 1992).

The Western Snowy Plover, a federal Species of Concern (see Chapter 6 - Sensitive Species), is a breeder and migrant at the Lake Holloman Wetlands. Management of these wetlands for the Snowy Plover would include mudflats within close proximity to standing

water and dense clumps of inland saltgrass ([Mehlhop et al. 1998a](#)). In addition, *Bledius* beetles may be an important indicator of habitat quality for Snowy Plovers (Freehling et al. 1998).

Section 2345 of the National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 1995 transferred jurisdiction of land in the Holloman Lakes area and south of Highway 70 to Holloman AFB, Department of Defense. These lands were formerly under the jurisdiction of the Bureau of Land Management, Department of Interior. The survey of the transferred land was completed in FY 98, allowing for formal management and posting of the land. The transferred lands have not been posted or fenced, which creates a security problem for the base. Access to these lands from Highway 70 remains open to the public and the area is currently used for hunting, birdwatching and hiking. Security issues associated with this area should receive high priority. In addition, off-road vehicle traffic is currently travelling from the main base into the wetlands area. This creates a hazard for bird and animal populations, destroys natural vegetation, and increases soil erosion.

Holloman AFB would like to continue public recreational activities at Lake Holloman. The other wetlands, including the constructed wetlands, are off-limits for recreational use. At Lake Holloman, there are no established policies or regulations to control public access. Until jurisdictional and legal access issues are resolved, there will be no way to enforce compliance with regulations established to protect these natural resources. In addition, trails, interpretive signage, and observation towers or blinds cannot be constructed without taking into consideration legal (*See* Chapter 6 - Fish and Wildlife Management - [Hunting](#)) and ecological management issues that protect wildlife habitat.

Holloman AFB is an active participant in the National Watchable Wildlife Program, a nationwide cooperative effort to combine wildlife conservation with America's growing interest in wildlife-related outdoor recreation. The ultimate goal of the program is to help maintain viable populations of all native animal species by creating well-informed public support for conservation. Defenders of Wildlife initiated the idea and have been instrumental in developing the program. The following organizations have a memorandum of understanding to support Watchable Wildlife sites: Bureau of Land Management, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, National Park Service, Bureau of Reclamation, U.S. Forest Service, Army (two offices), Navy, Air Force, International Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies, Defenders of Wildlife, Izaak Walton League, National Audubon Society, and National Wildlife Federation. Holloman AFB CES/CEV is also a member of the state of New Mexico Wetlands Task Force.

Information on population trends of shorebirds throughout interior flyways are limited (Helmert 1993); therefore Holloman AFB will have an excellent opportunity to contribute valuable research in important nationwide conservation efforts such as the Watchable Wildlife Program and the North American Waterfowl Management Plan (NAWMP). In addition, Holloman AFB, Natural Resource Manager, Hildy Reiser, is a member of the State of New Mexico Wetlands Task Force and the White Sands Pupfish Conservation Team.

Watershed Protection

Topic	Management Issue
Discharge of pollutants	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Unauthorized storm water discharge● Industrial pollutants into storm water drainage● Unregulated non-point source pollutants into storm water drainage
La Luz watershed	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Protect the La Luz watershed for the pupfish and duneland cottonwood communities

Elevations are nearly level, ranging from 1,224 m (4,015 feet) at the extreme southern tip of Stinky Playa to 1,320 m (4,330 feet) at Tularosa Peak. Average elevation is 1,240 m (4,086 feet). Groundwater table is within 3 m (10 feet) of the surface.

The junction of five hydrologic unit boundaries (HUBs) lie within Holloman AFB: Tularosa, La Luz, White Sands, Garten Wells, and Alamo (Figure 26). The Cantonment and Lake Holloman Management Units lie principally within the Garten Wells and Alamo HUBs. The La Luz and Tularosa HUBs cover much of the alluviated portions of the base and the White Sands HUB contains the area dominated by duneland processes. Recharge to aquifers on Holloman AFB originate from the Sacramento Mountain front and topography tilts gradually to the southwest.

Nine major drainages cross the base and receive intermittent flows from higher elevations to the east, as well as surface runoff in channelized ditches that are part of the system of storm water drainages (Chapter 3 - Hydrology). La Luz Creek originates in the Lincoln National Forest and is the principal source of surface drainage for Malone Draw and Lost River. Malone Draw and Lost River provide important habitat for the White Sands pupfish (*See* Chapter 6 - Sensitive Species). Dewatering has been identified as a major threat to the Holloman AFB pupfish population. To address this need, a study of the hydrology of the La Luz drainage is currently underway (Mehlhop et al. 1998). The Laborcita Arroyo of La Luz Creek drains into Little Hay Draw and eventually into Hay Draw. These drainages potentially provide groundwater for the duneland cottonwood communities (*See* Chapter 6 - Sensitive Natural Areas). The La Luz watershed encompasses the Hay Draw, Malone Draw, and Lost River drainages. Protection of this watershed would protect the White Sands pupfish population and potentially the duneland cottonwood community.

Holloman AFB lies within the Tularosa Basin watershed, a closed surface-water basin (*See* Chapter 3 - Topography and Geomorphology). Some underground water sources

may move to adjacent basins (West and Broadhurst 1975). The basin-fill on Holloman AFB originates from both alluvial and lake deposits. The lake deposits consist of silt, clay, and evaporites, principally gypsum. Evaporites are the principal source of high salinity in ground water within the Tularosa Basin (West and Broadhurst 1975). Ground water with a dissolved-solids content of more than 3,000 mg/l is considered saline. The concentration of dissolved solids within the Tularosa Basin ranges from 200 mg/l to more than 100,000 mg/l. Holloman AFB lies near the center of the basin where groundwater is more saline; therefore, potable water for Holloman AFB is piped from the alluvial fill at the base of the Sacramento Mountains (*See Chapter 4 - Boles Wells Water System Annex*).

In addition to natural runoff, the stormwater drainages receive discharge from industrial and non-industrial base activities. Drainage for the developed portions of the base is provided by a system of above-ground and under-ground ditches and culverts that discharge to various outfall areas and ultimately, in some cases, to the stormwater drainage canal. Water in the canal flows through the constructed wetlands and into Lake Holloman.

Under the Water Quality Act of 1987, the discharge of any pollutants to Waters of the United States from a point source is not permitted. Any discharge from an industrial source must be authorized using a National Pollution Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) Storm Water Multi-Sector General Permit (SWMSGP), which is regulated by the USEPA (USEPA 1992). Under the Multi-Sector General Permit (September 29, 1995 Federal Register 60 FR 50804), non-stormwater discharges are not allowed, with some exceptions in the areas of base housing, commercial facilities and administrative offices. In particular, authorized non-stormwater discharges include: fire fighting activities, fire hydrant flushings, potable water sources including waterline flushings, irrigation drainage, lawn watering, routine exterior building washings that do not use detergents or other compounds, pavement wash waters where spills or leaks of toxic or hazardous materials have not occurred and where detergents were not used, air conditioning condensate, uncontaminated springs, uncontaminated groundwater, and foundation or footing drains where flows are not contaminated with process materials such as solvents.

Unauthorized non-storm water discharges attributable to industrial activities were identified in Outfall Areas 001, 002, and 008. The non-storm water discharges are summarized below. (Law Environmental, Inc. 1998)

<u>Drainage Area</u>	<u>Building Number</u>	<u>Unauthorized Non-Storm Water Discharge</u>
001	281	Potable cooling water from welder discharges to ground surface outside of facility.
001	306	Fire trucks periodically washed outside Fire Station, wash water flows to storm drain. Fire trucks periodically washed outside Fire Station, wash water flows to storm drain.
002	Washrack near 54	Uncovered washrack potentially can overflow to surrounding ground surface during rainfall event.
002	55	Potable cooling water from welder discharges to ground surface outside of facility.
002	55	Metal-quenching sink discharges to ground surface outside of facility.
002	Washrack near 137	Covered washrack occasionally overflows, wash water flows to storm drain.
002	195	Rinse water from glass belt sander discharges to ground surface outside of facility.
008	Test Track	Potable water (also containing methanol if ambient temperature is below freezing) used to slow Test Track sled discharges to desert surface.
008	1176	Potable water from rain simulation bay and wash water from vehicle wash rack bay discharge to ground surface outside of facility.
008	1185	Potable cooling water from welder discharges to ground surface outside of facility.

Storm water discharge permit regulations covering industrial activities are specified in 40 CFR 122.26(b)(14)(I)-(xi) (Law Environmental, Inc. 1994). Holloman AFB conducts industrial activities that warrant being subject to NPDES regulations. In compliance with

the Multi-Sector General Permit, Holloman AFB is in the process of finalizing a revised SWPPP. Under this plan, Holloman AFB has identified 13 outfall areas of the base containing discharge industrial activities (Figure 26; Law Environmental, Inc. 1994, 1988). Eleven of these outfall areas contribute "distinct" discharges from the base to designated waters of the United States (Law Environmental, Inc. 1994, 1988). The two remaining outfall areas discharge to depressions in the ground (located on base) where storm water evaporates or percolates into the ground (Law Environmental, Inc. 1994, 1988).

"Waters of the United States that receive discharges from outfall areas include Lake Holloman (Outfall Areas 001, 010, and 011), Dillard Draw (Outfall Areas 002, 003, and 007), Lost River (Outfall Area 008), Ritas Draw (Outfall Area 013), and three unnamed wetlands (Outfall Areas 004, 006, and 009) (Figure 27; Law Environmental, Inc. 1998). In Outfall Area 008, storm water flows both by sheet flow and through an outfall to the Lost River. Dillard Draw and Ritas Draw do not discharge to other water bodies; storm water that flows to these ditches either ponds, percolates into the ground, and/or evaporates." (Law Environmental, Inc. 1998). Automatic samplers were placed in outfall areas 001, 002, 003, 004, 006, 009, and 011 in 1997 to improve the effectiveness of sampling and monitoring required under the SWPPP.

On-site examinations of all industrial areas were conducted to assess potential sources of storm water pollution at Holloman AFB (Law Environmental, Inc. 1998). Although no violations were observed, some potential problems were noted:

- Loading and unloading of fuels, oils, and waste liquids at above ground storage tanks, underground storage tanks, and portable bowsers.
- Waste and material transfer operations at various facilities throughout the base.
- Outdoor storage of aerospace ground equipment and other miscellaneous equipment.
- Outdoor storage or maintenance of aircraft, vehicles, and other mechanized equipment.
- Outdoor storage of materials.
- Above ground storage tanks without secondary containment berms.

As of May 1994, Holloman AFB identified 257 hazardous waste sites that are a result of past waste and resource management practices. Of these, 50 are currently in some stage of remediation by the Installation Restoration Program (IRP). To effectively respond to potential solid waste issues, a Management Action Plan (MAP) was prepared by Holloman AFB. The MAP is a regularly updated document that summarizes the status of the base's environmental restoration and environmental compliance programs. It proposes strategies to implement response actions to protect human health and the environment. Potential spread of contamination from these sites due to erosional processes is unlikely, due to the relatively level surfaces and measures taken to avoid runoff. (Law Environmental, Inc. 1998)

The greatest pollutant risks identified at Holloman AFB are improper connections to the storm sewer system from oil/water separators and industrial area trench drains (Law Environmental, Inc. 1998). Other potential risks include non-storm water and storm water discharge from industrial activities, as described above. The pollution risks from industrial activities are well documented in the Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan (SWPPP) and include management responsibilities and monitoring schedules that provide sufficient controls to enforce pollution prevention guidelines to protect human health and the wetland desert ecosystem at Holloman AFB.

Potential pollution sources from unregulated non-point source pollution such as the base housing area and golf course are of particular concern. Herbicides and fertilizers used on lawns are currently uncontrolled and eventually reach the storm water drainage system. The seasonally large inputs of these chemicals into the storm water drainage system can adversely affect the aquatic ecosystem within the Lake Holloman Wetlands (*See* Chapter 5 - Landscaping and Chapter 6 - Wetlands).

Holloman AFB is recognized by the U.S. EPA, State of New Mexico, and DoD for its proactive conservation and pollution control initiatives. The [U.S. EPA](#) has recognized Holloman AFB for its Hazardous Material Pharmacy (HAZMART) for "dramatically" decreasing the stock of hazardous materials in work centers on the base. The State of New Mexico presented Holloman AFB with the Environmental Initiative Award in 1992, and Brigadier General Lloyd W. Newton, former 49th Fighter Wing Commander at Holloman, received the Environmental Leadership Award from the New Mexico Environmental Department in July 1993. The DoD recognized the excellence of Holloman AFB's proactive installation-wide approach to preserving the environment by including the base in a group of only five Air Combat Command (ACC) bases participating in the Accelerated Cleanup Program (ACP).

Figure 27. Storm Water and Non-Storm Water Discharge Areas

Fish and Wildlife Management

The topics discussed in this chapter are Fish and Wildlife Management issues that have not been reviewed in other chapters, such as Sensitive Species where the Pupfish is covered in detail.

Topic	Management Issue
<i>American pronghorn:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Holloman AFB may not be within the historical range of the pronghorn ● Potential conflict with military training and operations ● Native vegetation on HAFB is more suited to the diet of Mexican pronghorn ● Adequate fresh water source to maintain pronghorn
<i>Grassland birds:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National declines ● Support of the Partnership in Flight Initiative ● Lack of information on Holloman AFB of habitat use by grassland birds
<i>Bats</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pesticides can cause mortality ● Disturbance during hibernation can cause mortality
<i>Hunting</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Finalize a cooperative agreement with USFWS to comply with 16 USC 670a ● Oryx depredation hunts conducted by NMGFD ● Establish regulations and policies for managing Lake Holloman hunting and wildlife viewing ● Designate hunting and waterfowl refuge areas ● Establish regulations and policies in reference to hunting activities within the BWWSA

American pronghorn (*Antilocapra americana americana*):

The American pronghorn is considered "demonstrably secure" in New Mexico, according to the New Mexico Natural Heritage Program ranking process (G5T5). In 1988, the pronghorn was listed as a game mammal in New Mexico. Genetic mixing between populations of the American and Mexican pronghorn (*Antilocapra americana mexicana*) have occurred in southern New Mexico (Lee et al. 1994), due to natural proximity and perhaps restocking programs that have occurred in the past. Although southern New Mexico is a natural intergrade zone between two sub-species of pronghorn, efforts should be made to maintain genetic integrity (Lee et al. 1994). The Mexican pronghorn was listed in Arizona as a USFWS Sensitive Species in 1990 (Bison-M 1997).

American pronghorn typically inhabit open short-grass prairies with scattered shrubs. Their average home range extends 100 mi² over rolling or dissected hills and mesas. They graze on forbs and succulent grasses in the spring and summer; winter forage consists of Great Basin shrubs like rabbitbrush (*Chrysothamnus sp.*), sagebrush (*Artemisia sp.*), and winterfat (*Krascheninnikovia lanata*) (Bison-M 1997). Water is important particularly when new growth on grasses is limited. In Arizona, reintroduced Mexican pronghorn consumed alkali sacaton and browsed on saltbush in overgrazed plains (Hoffmeister 1986).

Although there is no historic or recent evidence that Holloman AFB is within the native range of pronghorn, their populations are quite stable throughout WSMR. Introduction of this native ungulate to Holloman has been considered. Pronghorn are primarily browsers and their addition to the upland ecosystem may enhance biodiversity. However, since it is unknown whether they are historically a part of the natural ecosystem, further research is required before introduction is possible. In addition, free water sources are needed to sustain these populations and the reliable source would be Lake Holloman and the constructed wetland complex that lies south of the airfield. A conflict with mission activities on the airfield and test track may also prohibit the introduction of this large ungulate.

Grassland Birds

Grassland bird populations are declining, and their habitat is recognized by many as possibly the most imperiled ecosystem worldwide (USGS 1998; Whitford 1997; Department of Interior 1996). Grassland bird populations have shown steeper, more consistent, and more geographically widespread declines than any other guild of North American bird species. Breeding Bird Survey (BBS) data from 1966-1993 indicate that almost 70% of the 29 grassland bird species adequately surveyed by the BBS had negative population trends. Because most grassland birds that breed in North America winter on the continent (USGS 1998), declines in grassland birds are principally attributed to changes in North American ecosystems.

Grasslands comprise approximately 22.6% of vegetation cover on Holloman AFB. Four vegetation mapping units are dominated by four distinct grassland communities. These mapping units are: Gyp Dropseed Grassland, Alkali Sacaton Grassland, Gyp Grama Interdune Grassland, and Semi-Riparian Alkali Sacaton Grasslands. A grassland bird survey conducted from September 1994 to April 1995 sampled a relatively large region dominated by two of the 4 communities present on Holloman AFB, fourwing saltbush/alkali sacaton and fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed communities (Mehlhop et al. 1998b). Numbers of individuals along a transect were recorded, along with some habitat use information.

These surveys, conducted during spring and fall migrations, revealed a total of [52 species](#) and 2,918 individuals (Mehlhop et al. 1998b). Of particular interest is the Baird's Sparrow, due in part to its significant decline over the past 25 years (Breeding Bird Survey, National Biological Service). There were no sightings made during the survey; however, surveyors sighted one individual while making vegetation measurements (Mehlhop et al. 1998b). Migrant species such as the Yellow-rumped Warbler (*Dendroica coronata*), Green-tailed Towhee (*Pipilo chlorurus*) and Wilson's Warbler (*Wilsonia pusilla*) preferred sites with mesquite. Other species often identified with Chihuahuan desert scrub habitat were also found in mesquite sites: Curve-billed Thrasher (*Toxostoma curvirostre*), Crissal Thrasher (*Toxostoma dorsale*), Cactus Wren (*Campylorhynchus brunneicapillus*), Ladder-backed Woodpecker (*Picoides scalaris*), Verdin (*Auriparus flaviceps*), Say's Phoebe (*Sayornis saya*), and Black-throated Sparrow (*Amphispiza bilineata*). Species that were most often found within grasslands were the Horned Lark (*Eremophila alpestris*), Chestnut-collared Longspur (*Calcarius ornatus*) and Lark Bunting (*Calamospiza melanocorys*).

Although sometimes a minor component within grasslands, shrubs provide important nesting habitats for many grassland birds (Ford and McPherson 1996). Sparsely distributed desert shrubs such as Torrey yucca (*Yucca torreyi*), soaptree yucca (*Yucca elata*), and little-leaf sumac (*Rhus microphylla*) are frequently used for nesting (Kozma and Mathews 1997; Whitford 1997). In a study on arroyo riparian ecosystems, they were found to have higher nest densities than upland grassland habitats (Kozma and Mathews 1997). On Holloman AFB, arroyo riparian areas with salt cedar attracted migrants such as MacGillivray's Warbler (*Oporornis tolmiei*), Orange-crowned Warbler (*Vermivora*

celata), and Ruby-crowned Kinglet (*Regulus calendula*). On Holloman AFB, survey sites that contained honey mesquite (*Prosopis glandulosa*) had a greater number of species and higher diversity than other similar areas without mesquite (Mehlhop et al. 1998b). Additionally, variation in bird species richness in grassland and shrub habitats at cintheodolite missile towers appeared to be related primarily to the diversity of habitat types present (Johnson et al. 1997a).

The following grassland avian species are discussed in the sensitive species plan (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Only the Loggerhead Shrike was detected on grassland surveys:

[Bald Eagle](#)

[Ferruginous Hawk](#)

[Northern Aplomado Falcon](#)

[Peregrine Falcon](#)

[Common Ground Dove](#)

[Western Burrowing Owl](#) (also Chapter 6 - Sensitive Species)

[Loggerhead Shrike](#)

[Baird's Sparrow](#)

As a DoD cooperator in Partners in Flight, Holloman AFB could substantially contribute to the knowledge base of both neotropical migrants and resident grassland birds. The Partners in Flight - Priority Bird Species List for New Mexico is currently in revision. The national program currently lists 49 New Mexico priority species. Of these, 12 use upland habitats within Holloman AFB ([HAFB Grassland Bird List](#)). While extensive monitoring of birds within the wetland habitats at Holloman AFB is ongoing, little is known of habitat use on the base by grassland birds.

Bats

Bats roost during the day and forage at night. Roosting and foraging areas within Holloman are found within the Test Track, Northern Shrubland, and Cantonment Management Units. Bat roost locations within Holloman AFB are usually found in undisturbed or abandoned buildings and in culverts. These sites are typically near foraging areas, such as open water or night light sources ([Mehlhop et al. 1998a](#)). On the Boles Wells Well Field, bat foraging occurs near the pond and other water impoundments. Recorded sightings of bats found within these areas are: pallid (*Antrozous pallidus*), big brown (*Eptesicus fuscus*), small-footed myotis ([Myotis ciliolabrum](#)), big free-tailed (*Nyctinomops macrotis*), Western pipistrelle (*Pipistrellus hesperus*), and Mexican free-tailed (*Tadarida brasiliensis*).

Bats produce one young per year in the late spring or early summer (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Bats are typically active from early spring until October or November when they hibernate for the remaining period. Monitoring should be carried out during the breeding and migration periods for bats, which typically fall within June and July (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). During this period, the young bats are also active.

The major threats to bats on Holloman AFB are pesticides and disturbance during hibernation. Direct and indirect exposure to pesticides, such as when bats consume insects containing pesticides, can lead to mortality. When bats are aroused during hibernation, they expend their energy reserves and may die (Fenton 1970, Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Entering buildings where bats are hibernating can create enough noise to arouse the bats.

Research priorities should first concentrate on determining specific habitat use and identifying roost and hibernacula for foraging bats (Mehlhop et al. 1998a). Due to bat mortality from disturbance during hibernation, determining the location of these sites and subsequently protecting them from disturbance is important in maintaining bat populations. In addition, tracking the distances that bats travel to a local water source is important in understanding local bat ecology. A monitoring strategy based on these initial goals will contribute to developing an adaptive management strategy.

Hunting

For compliance with the Sikes Act (16 USC 670a), Holloman AFB and the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service have a drafted a cooperative agreement for protecting, conserving, and managing fish and wildlife resources. This agreement must address each agency's responsibilities, wildlife law enforcement, access to the installation for agency representatives, user fee rate schedule for hunting, fishing, and trapping, and BASH programs.

Hunting programs, with the exception of Oryx depredation hunts, are limited due to the lack of game animals on Holloman AFB (*See* Chapter 6 - Exotic Plants and Animals - Oryx). The Game and Fish Department directs oryx depredation hunts, using its depredation permit list to select hunters for the once-in-a-lifetime permit hunt. Each oryx hunter is escorted by Holloman AFB personnel. The funds collected from the hunting permits are used to cover Game and Fish Department expenses.

Section 2345 of the National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 1995 transferred jurisdiction of land in the Holloman Lakes area and south of Highway 70 to Holloman AFB, Department of Defense. These lands were formerly under the jurisdiction of the Bureau of Land Management, Department of Interior. The original intent of the transfer was to provide for the "construction of new evaporation ponds to support a wastewater treatment plant" (National Defense Authorization Act). Responsibility for remediation of any existing and subsequent hazardous release under the Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation, and Liability Act of 1980 (CERCLA) was transferred to the Department of the Air Force, and the Air Force "shall ensure the continuation of valid, existing rights under the mining laws and the mineral leasing and geothermal laws of the United States" under Department of Defense policies regarding mineral exploration. The survey of the transferred land was completed in FY 98, allowing for formal management and posting of the land.

Lands transferred from the Bureau of Land must remain open, to some degree, to public access and use. Currently, bird-watching is very popular because of the high biodiversity and density of birds. In addition, waterfowl, dove, and quail hunting is currently allowed at Lake Holloman without Air Force management. Lagoon G, outside of these transferred lands, is closed to hunting and should be established as a waterfowl refuge.

Public access to the transferred lands is stated in the law as follows:

- “The Secretary of the Air Force shall permit public access to the lands transferred”, except the Secretary of the Air Force “may not permit public access to the immediate area affected by the construction of the wastewater treatment facility in the area with the legal description of T17S R8E Section 22, except that the Secretary of the Air Force shall permit public access on an adjoining unfenced parcel of land - located along the west boundary of such an area; and that is 50 feet in width.”
- The Secretary of the Air Force shall permit on the lands transferred (except for on the lands excepted above) “public uses that are consistent with the public uses on adjacent lands under the jurisdiction of the Secretary of the Interior.”
- “The Secretary of the Air Force may not require a permit for access...to the lands transferred...”
- “The Secretary of the Air Force shall ensure that the entry gate to the lands transferred...that is located along United States Highway 70 shall be open to the public.”

Legal interpretation of the Federal law by Holloman AFB counsel is that,

while the Air Force must permit the same kinds of activities as on BLM lands, the Air Force is not required to permit identical activities, nor the same amount of access to Air Force land, as long as management and protection activities follow established Air Force, DoD, and other relevant Federal and state laws and regulations.

Reasons of safety or military necessity may preclude the same level of access or the same activities on military land as on BLM land. The entry gate at Highway 70 may be closed for reasons of safety, security, protection of Federal property (especially the water control structures), and military necessity. During those times when the Air Force allows hunting, fishing and other outdoor activities that are “consistent with” activities on BLM land, the Air Force may not impose additional requirements on members of the public wishing to participate in those activities. However, if the base decides to charge a user fee, with the rates consistent with DoD policy, that same fee must be charged to all users, including federal employees and military personnel.

Because the Air Force apparently has proprietary jurisdiction over the transferred land, the state of New Mexico has criminal jurisdiction, unless the action falls under federal law, such as the Endangered Species Act. 49 SFS may detain individuals for commission of criminal offenses of which they are aware, but may not arrest individuals nor issue citations. They may, however, investigate those offenses for the purposes of taking administrative action such as barment against the offenders.

Hunting within the Boles Wells Water System Annex is not currently managed by Holloman AFB. Relatively substantial recreational off-road vehicle use, some limited hunting, and substantial artifact scavenging occurred in the past in the Douglas Well Field area (Figure 9). Water is a vital resource to maintaining military mission activities, and therefore the integrity of the BWWSA is a primary security issue. Although the question of hunting in this area has been discussed, overriding security issues preclude serious consideration of hunting at BWWSA in the near future (*See* Chapter 7-BWWSA).

Fire Management

Topic	Management Issue
Fire occurrence in desert ecosystems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Historical fire frequency is unknown but considering low fuel loads was probably low.
Fire effects on cryptogamic crusts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● May imperil these populations; recovery rates are unknown.
Fire effects on gypsum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Gypsum may fuse and inhibit filtration, causing an increase in surface runoff. Less water will be available to plants.
Fire effects on plant and animal populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fire effects on plant and animal populations and recovery rates should be considered in planning for fire management.

Fire is an important force in maintaining grassland ecosystems. During the past 150 years, many of the desert grasslands of North America have been converted to shrublands (Buffington and Herbel 1965, Bahre and Shelton 1993, Bahre 1995, Whitford 1995, Whitford 1997). by fire suppression and grazing. This result is a change in composition structure from grass-shrub to primarily shrub (Humphrey 1974, Whitfield and Anderson 1938, Dick-Peddie 1993). In the absence of grazing pressures, York and Dick-Peddie (1969) found that shrubs did not increase within a 100-year period on desert grasslands.

Holloman AFB is no exception to the trend toward decreasing grass and increasing shrubs (See Chapter Chapter 3 - Cultural Resources).

The occurrence of fire is directly correlated with the amount of fuel available to sustain a fire; therefore, the prevalence of fire in desert ecosystems is generally lower than in areas of greater precipitation and higher fuel loads (Humphrey 1974). To date, there is no record of fire history in the lowland basins of southern New Mexico. Fire frequency may have been very low (Humphrey 1974); a review of early accounts in southern New Mexico by Buffington and Herbel (1965) reveals no reports at all. In addition, little has been reported concerning the effects of fire on vegetation within the Chihuahuan Desert (Humphrey 1974, Ahlstrand 1982).

Past fire history may have little relevance in desert environments today due to the "profound" physical and biological changes that have taken place (Ford and McPherson 1996). In the past 150 years, undesirable non-natives have replaced many of the native species and often are the early colonizers that take advantage of burned sites (Ahlstrand 1982). Although grasses are considered early colonizers and are an important component in the development and origin of grasslands (Vogl 1974), extensive fires may result in an increase in shrubs and forbs if a sufficient seed bank of native grasses is absent (Cornelius 1988).

Plant structure and composition play an important role in the movement and intensity of fire in desert shrublands and grasslands. A structurally diverse cover of grasses, interspersed within shrublands, will tend to carry a fire; however, a lack of grasses within the understory of shrubs will tend to inhibit the spread of a fire (Humphrey 1974). Fourwing saltbush, a dominant shrub on Holloman AFB, is a fire-tolerant sprouter, which typically recovers fully within 2 or 3 years after a burn (Shantz and Piemeisel 1924). Fourwing saltbush has been characterized as "fire resistant" because of its unusually low volatilization rate (Ho 1987, USDA Forest Service IFSL 1995). Alkali sacaton is the most common grass within the base and is tolerant of fire. Recovery time is 2 to 4 years. Within 2 years alkali sacaton will attain pre-fire basal area, but reaching only 54% of its pre-fire height (Wright and Bailey 1982, USDA Forest Service IFSL 1995). The rhizomes of saltgrass, another common grass within the wetland areas and draws on Holloman AFB, are deep within the soil and are protected from the heat of most fires (Smith and Kadlec 1985a, USDA Forest Service IFSL 1995). Saltgrass seeds within the soil also remain viable after a fire (Smith and Kadlec 1985b, USDA Forest Service IFSL 1995). Fire causes high cactus mortality (Humphrey 1974) and therefore could endanger the grama grass cactus populations on the base.

Cryptogams are damaged by fire. Recovery rates depend on the original cryptogam community and life form (Ladyman and Muldavin 1996, *See* Chapter 6 - Sensitive Natural Areas - Cryptogamic Crusts). The first to recover are algae, and moss and lichen have slower recovery rates (Ladyman and Muldavin 1996). Recovery rates have not been determined for Chihuahuan Desert grasslands. Recolonization rates in other arid environments range from 2 to 5 years, often with substantial changes in species

composition and cryptogamic biomass (Ladyman and Muldavin 1996). Increased fire frequencies could reduce and imperil Holloman AFB cryptogam populations.

Herpetofaunal response to burning grasslands has "scarcely been studied" (Scott 1996). Arthropods appear to recolonize an area quickly after fire in short-grass prairies (Ford and McPherson 1996). Recovery typically occurs from 6 months to 3 years after temporary declines (Ford and McPherson 1996), depending on precipitation and recovery of native vegetation.

The timing of fire can have broad effects on ground-nesting birds. A fire occurring at an appropriate stage of development can lower the number of avian insect parasites (Lyon et al. 1978, Kramp et al. 1983, Ford and McPherson 1996). Alternatively, a fire during the nesting and fledging period of ground-nesting birds can devastate their populations and food sources (Ford and McPherson 1996). The Baird's Sparrow ([Mehlhop et al. 1998](#)), a Species of Concern, is absent from unburned prairie (Madden 1995) but is a migrant to areas of frequent burns. This species was seen once during a fall vegetation survey on Holloman AFB ([Mehlhop et al. 1998](#), See Chapter 6 - Fish and Wildlife Management - Grassland Birds). Burrowing Owls suffer declines on grasslands with increased in litter cover and could therefore benefit from fire (Ford and McPherson 1996).

After a fire, mammals dependent on invertebrates within the litter layer will suffer negative effects. However, some mice and rodent populations may increase after a fire due to an abundance of forb seeds and insects (Lyon et al. 1978). Some Holloman AFB rodent species that benefit from the effects of fire are: white-footed mouse, deer mouse, Merriam's kangaroo rat, Ord's Kangaroo Rat, and Mearn's Grasshopper Mouse (Ford and McPherson 1996).

After gypsum in the soil has been exposed to campfire heat and precipitation, it fuses over time. This creates a very resistive surface that inhibits water infiltration and to some extent wind erosion, sometimes referred to as plaster of paris. This process has created hard, pedestal-shaped surfaces called hearths. Surface soils at Holloman AFB are mantled by gypsum or underlay eolian sediments and can be up to several inches thick. Introducing fire into this system may pose a serious problem due to the high gypsum content within the soils. Fire, followed by a precipitation event, may fuse the gypsum crystals and create an impenetrable surface that could cause sheet wash. An example is provided by Blank et al. (1994) control fire study conducted in a Nevada sagebrush community on coarse-textured granitic soils. The fire created hydrophobic compounds that considerably inhibited water infiltration. The residual effects of the fire on soil filtration lasted until the following summer (Blank et al. 1994).

In summary, frequent fires are probably not historically a part of Holloman AFB ecosystems. Although occasional fires may have occurred, there is no evidence to support the assumption that fire is an important ecological force here. The dominant plants on Holloman AFB are fire-tolerant with recovery rates estimated at 2 to 3 years, depending on precipitation. Grama grass cactus populations could also be negatively impacted by a fire. Animals respond in various ways, but no research exists to document

actual recovery rates. Cryptogams are an important component of the ecosystem on Holloman AFB and fire adversely affects their survival and recovery. Some cultural resources on Holloman AFB should be protected from wildfire. In light of available information, there does not appear to be any reason to begin prescribed burning, and every effort should be made to control wildfires.

Exotic Plants and Animals

Topic	Management Issue
Plants	
<i>Salt Cedar:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adoption of ecologically 'friendly' control practices ● Timely control measures to prevent further alteration of arroyo riparian and playa ecosystems
<i>African Rue, Russian Knapweed & Russian Thistle:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adoption of ecologically 'friendly' control practices ● Replaces and outcompetes native vegetation ● No natural enemies to limit its distribution
Animals	
<i>Oryx:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Depredation hunts ● Threat to military activities at the Test Track ● Preventing access to the base

Geographic isolation has contributed to the diverse assemblage of species throughout the world. Species have evolved gradually in response to physical and biological changes in their respective environments. Humans have radically altered these associations by introducing exotics that often result in the displacement of native species. Exotic species are able to invade and often dominate in new habitats in the absence of natural predators. Exotics may have an advantage over natives in areas of high human activity causing unusual environmental conditions. This may be the reason the highest concentrations of exotic species are often found in environments that have been disturbed. Exotic species are considered the most serious threat facing the biota of the United States park system (Primack 1993). Ignoring exotics make it increasingly difficult and expensive to remove them because they become entwined within the community.

Exotic Plants

Over 2,800 acres of Holloman AFB, including approximately 700 acres of disturbed roadsides, have established populations of noxious weeds. Four species of introduced noxious weeds have been exceptionally problematic in the Tularosa Basin and on Holloman's Main Base: Salt Cedar (*Tamarix ramosissima*), African rue (*Peganum harmala L.*), Russian knapweed (*Acroptilon repens* or *Centaurea repens*), and Russian thistle (*Salsola kali L.*).

Salt Cedar (*Tamarix ramosissima*)

Salt Cedar (*Tamarix ramosissima*) is an invasive Eurasian phreatophyte that was planted originally as a windbreak above Carter Draw and has since moved aggressively into the drainage bottoms and lowland depressions at the southern end of the base. It is a multiple-branched tree with feathery, needle-like leaves and numerous small, pink flowers at the ends of the branches. It is well adapted to conditions in the Southwest and spreads rapidly by seed, root, trunk or branch sprouts. During the spring, it can grow as much as one foot per month.

Phreatophytes can significantly alter the flow of streams and increase evapotranspiration rates (Malanson 1993). Estimated transpiration rates in this species may total as much as 2.1 cubic meters/square meter (Carmen and Brotherson 1982). In addition, salt cedar aggressively competes with native species such as the willow and cottonwood. In drainages with intermittent flows, salt cedar can out-compete native plants and severely limit available water for other plants. It has a high tolerance for salty soils and can increase the salinity of soils by shedding its leaves, which are high in excess salts.

Studies on wildlife use of habitats dominated by salt cedar differ. Anderson et al. (1983) reported finding fewer bird species using salt cedar than native trees, with negative effects on riparian bird species. Another study, conducted within the Grand Canyon National Park, along the Colorado River, found the diets of several neotropical migrants were highly specific and depended on terrestrial insects over aquatic insects (Yard 1998). They concluded salt cedar plays an important role in the community structure of the birds by structuring their feeding habits. Considering Holloman AFB wetlands has only Salt Cedar, this tree may be important for neotropical migrants.

Without significant control measures, salt cedar can take over entire desert riparian areas, thereby decreasing levels of biodiversity. Well-established communities can lower the water table in the soil (Brotherson et al. 1984). The result is an overall drying out of the habitat, with more xeric plant species establishing within the understory of salt cedar stands. At the Bosque del Apache National Wildlife Refuge, salt cedar is effectively being cleared and replanted with cottonwood, black willow, and understory plants, to restore the native bosque habitat. At Death Valley National Park, when Salt cedar was eradicated and native species allowed to grow, water returned to wetland areas. The

method employed was persistent cutting and systemic-herbicide stump applications continued for ten years.

Efforts to eradicate and control the spread of salt cedar on Holloman AFB have been limited. Both mechanical and chemical methods have been used within the draws and the wetlands area. Biological control agents are not yet commercially available (Ladyman 1997). Fire is very often ineffective with re-sprouting taking place soon after the fire (Ladyman 1997). Intensive and continued efforts are necessary to suppress established stands of tamarisk. Methods used to control the growth of salt cedar are:

- Mechanical uprooting of trees and replacement by native trees and shrubs. This method causes excessive disturbance to the soil, changing the soil structure and may lower fertility and plant growth for planted species (Ladyman 1997).
- Mechanical removal of small seedlings when the soils is soft. This is time consuming and constantly monitored. Old growth trees are unaffected.
- Foliar applications also affect non-target species and may have detrimental effects on amphibians and invertebrates. However, an experimental approach for seedlings, using Scythe (from Mycogen), a short chain fatty acid found naturally in fruit skins, has a half life of a few hours and may be effective if followed by willow pole planting. Shade provided by the pole plant may adversely affect germination of the tamarisk during the following germination season (Ladyman 1997).
- Herbicides such as Arsenal or Garlon4 on the stump of a tree cut to within 1 inch of the ground surface and applied to branches of young saplings. The herbicide should be applied within a few minutes after cutting. This method is quite costly but the environmental impact to surrounding plants and animals is minimized. Arsenal is effective on Salt cedar and has a relatively low animal toxicity and short residual life in the soil (7 months or less). Once in the soil, there is little lateral or vertical movement of the compound. Garlon is more much more toxic to animals than Arsenal and toxic to fish (Ladyman 1997). Both products are not to be used in ponds or streams and should not be directly applied to water or wetlands.

African Rue (*Peganum harmala L.*)

African rue (also known as Syrian Rue, *Peganum harmala L.*) is native to northern Africa, the Middle East, and Asia. The plant is a bright green, succulent perennial with many branching stems and narrow leaves (Figure 28). The flowers are white with five petals. The fruits are leathery capsules with 45-60 seeds (Figure 28) (Parker and Reiser 1997). African rue was introduced into the United States near Deming, New Mexico, in 1928. A farmer cultivated the plant in order to harvest the seed to produce a dye called "Turkish Red" (Parker and Reiser 1997). Since then, the plant has increased its range and has become a significant weed problem in Otero County and on Holloman AFB. This noxious weed has spread east into Texas and reaches west into Arizona, California,

Nevada, Idaho, Oregon, and Washington. Rue invades highly disturbed areas where native plants have been removed, such as roadsides and heavily grazed desert rangelands.

Figure 28. African rue plant and seeds

African rue spreads by seeds but may also sprout from roots or root fragments (Parker and M. Hildegard Reiser 1997). It can tolerate alkaline soils and extreme drought conditions, and its roots can reach depths of 20 feet. There are several reasons that African rue maintains a competitive advantage over native plants such as saltbush and desert grasses: (1) seedling establishment probably occurs during droughts when native seed establishment is suppressed; (2) most parts of the plant contain allelopathic chemicals that retard or prevent the growth of other vegetation; (3) plant growth begins early in the spring before native plants; and (4) there are no insects or diseases to control its spread (Parker and Reiser 1997).

There are no laws or regulations to prevent the spread of this plant in New Mexico; however, in 1996 Otero County initiated a voluntary noxious plant control program and placed African rue on the primary noxious weed list. The seeds are dispersed when mixed with hay or other seeds, can attach to vehicles and equipment. High densities of African rue have been found along all road right-of-ways, the High Speed Test Track, Space Command testing area, 46 Test Group office area, and many portions of the flightline infield. Although colonization begins in disturbed areas, it is rapidly spreading into the native grass and shrublands.

Mowing and blading of roadside infestations have done little to impede the spread of this plant on Holloman AFB and may actually transport the seed to other areas. In Asia, successful reduction of this weed has been accomplished by repeated cultivation to a depth of 8 to 10 inches, followed by seeding perennial grasses. Holloman used trial plots to test different foliar sprays on African rue. The recommended treatments should be applied in the fall from late September through October before the first killing frost (see Parker and Reiser 1997, for ingredients, mixtures and equipment). The foliar spray is only about 80 percent effective, but multiple applications for several years may be effective in reducing infestations to a level low enough to allow the growth of desirable vegetation.

Russian Knapweed (*Acroptilon repens* or *Centaurea repens*)

Russian knapweed is a native of Mongolia, western Turkestan, Iran, Turkish Armenia, and Asia Minor (Moore and Frankton 1974 in Watson 1980; Zimmerman 1996), but it has now spread to every continent (Rosenthal 1995; Figure 29). Russian knapweed is reported to have been introduced into the United States several times near the turn of the century in shipments of impure Turkestan alfalfa and possibly sugarbeet seed (Watson 1980; Zimmerman 1996). It is considered a restricted noxious weed in Arizona, a designated undesirable species in Colorado, a candidate species for the New Mexico noxious weed list, and a designated weed species in Utah (Zimmerman 1996). On Holloman AFB it occurs near near Hay Draw, west of RR9, and west of the highspeed Test Track.

Figure 29. Russian knapweed

This weed disperses in much the same way as African rue, attaching to machinery and vehicles and mixing with unpure hay. It is not a prolific seed producer; however, it can spread vegetatively, making it difficult to control (Lacey et al. 1995). Seeds appear to be viable for long periods, possibly increasing germination success in older seeds (Zimmerman 1996). This species is highly toxic to horses and carries allelopathic effects that may prevent establishment of desirable, native species (Watson 1980; Zimmerman 1996).

There are currently no insect biocontrol agents for Russian knapweed in the United States (Rosenthal 1995). The following biocontrol agents are currently being studied for the control of this species, the first two are insects and the other is a fungus: *Aceria acroptiloni*, *Aulacida acroptilonica* and *Puccinia acroptili* (Watson 1980, Rosenthal 1995). Mechanical treatment using deep tillage techniques, followed by planting of natives is an option. However, since this species spreads vegetatively, supplemental

applications of herbicides may be needed. Suppression treatments using herbicides followed by grass seeding of perennials was found to be more effective than suppression treatments alone (Beck 1998). Information on chemical control of this species can be obtained from the Weed Management Library @ 1-800 554-WEED or from the New Mexico State Weed Specialist, Dr. Richard Lee, New Mexico State University (505) 646-2888.

Russian Thistle (*Salsola sp.*)

Russian thistle is a self-seeding annual, producing as many as 200,000 seeds per plant (Allred 1998). Originally from the steppe and grasslands of Russia, the plant was introduced to the United States about 1873. It was first discovered in South Dakota. Within 20 years the weed had reached New Mexico and was first identified as Russian thistle by Professor E.O. Wooton, an Agricultural Experiment Station botanist in Las Cruces. Wooton's advice was to "immediately pull it up as soon as you see it." The same advice applies today, according to Richard Lee, a weed scientist with NMSU Cooperative Extension Service.

Russian thistle displaces native plants and reduces valuable soil moisture. By displacing native vegetation, plant diversity lowers and consequently changes the availability of food or shelter for native animals accustomed to a different set of organisms. This weed's lack of natural enemies poses a threat to natural areas within Holloman AFB. It is called "tumbleweed," because it breaks off at the base of the stem during winter and rolls across the fields, spreading seed as it goes. Some Agricultural Extension Services have erroneously encouraged the increase of this plant by promoting the young plants as an emergency forage crop during drought (North Dakota State University Extension Service). It is also accidentally harvested and distributed with hay.

Russian thistle has increased within the High Speed Test Track area, but major infestations occur in the northern portion of the Boles Wells Water System Annex. No control efforts have targeted this noxious weed. The weed germinates in the spring, the best time for active control measures. Some herbicides recommended for Russian thistle by CPM Magazine On-line are: Ally, Amber, Harmony Extra or Express. Banvel/SGF, 2,4-D, Buctril, and Tordon plus 2,4-D at 0.75 pt/A also give good Russian thistle control. MCPA is not as effective as 2,4-D in controlling this weed. The esters of 2,4-D generally are more effective than the amines for both weeds.

Exotic Animals

Oryx (*Oryx gazella*)

The Oryx is an African antelope brought from the Kalahari Desert to an experimental range at Red Rock, New Mexico. Oryx are highly adapted to desert life and can go for 30

days without water (Figure 30). They eat desert grasses, yucca, buffalo gourds, mesquite bean pods, and tumbleweeds. Offspring from this original stock were introduced onto White Sands Missile Range as a game animal, between 1969 and 1977, and annual hunts have been conducted since 1974. Ninety-three oryx were released onto the Range, and numbers have increased to about 1,000. Population estimates on HAFB are between 24 and 36 animals. Reproduction averages one fawn per doe, which indicates a healthy growing population on base.

Figure 30. Oryx

Oryx access to the base from White Sands National Monument is controlled through an existing fence near the western boundary. The fence was specially designed by the national park to prevent oryx from gaining access in the southern and western portions of the Monument. Holloman AFB granted an easement to the White Sands National Monument to extend their oryx control fence across Lost River basin in the spring of 1995. Although the fence prevents oryx from passing through, it may be restricting movement of mammals such as fox and coyote, because it was constructed upside down for portions its length. Where the fence was constructed across Holloman AFB, it was properly installed to ensure movement of small mammals through the fence.

Oryx tend to concentrate in the northern shrublands area and the “rainfields” and Hay Draw area near the Test Track. Oryx wandering near the runways and the Test Track are chased off by operational personnel. Depredation hunts, managed by New Mexico Department of Game and Fish, were conducted on HAFB in 1991, 1992, 1994, and 1996. Generally, one to six oryx are harvested during depredation hunts. The oryx are considered a hazard to operation of the High Speed Test Track and aircraft operations.

Decisive management procedures for the oryx are necessary. There is a strong argument for removing the oryx from the base, because they pose a threat to military operations, primarily in the vicinity of the Test Track and airfield. This non-native species also eats the centers of the native yucca plants, thereby destroying them. The yucca provides habitat and food for native wildlife. Existing fences should be surveyed to determine

where the oryx are gaining access to the base. Depredation hunts and permanent exclusion measures are being considered.

Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

Topic	Management Issue
<i>GIS:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Develop an intranet for sharing GIS data ● Develop an accessible metadata website for in-house GIS coverages ● Develop detailed soil map ● Update road coverages and add road names ● Develop coverages for all utility networks ● Map storm water drainages ● Coverage over New Mexico of the 49th Air Space ● Ownership of contiguous properties ● Vegetation map of southern well field ● Recreational maps

A GIS is a computer-based tool for mapping and analyzing features and events that occur on earth. GIS technology integrates common database operations such as query and statistical analysis with the unique visualization and geographic analysis offered by maps. These abilities distinguish GIS from other information systems for explaining events, predicting outcomes, and planning strategies. (Environmental Systems Research Institute, Inc. 1998).

The GIS has been an integral part of the development of the Holloman AFB INRMP. In the early stages of the development of the plan, GIS coverages were created to show distributions of military activities, infrastructure such as roads and buildings, biological elements such as sensitive species, and physical characteristics such as soils and hydrology. During the process of the INRMP, 48 separate GIS coverages were created (Table 12). Other coverages were developed from existing geographically based digital data from the 49 CES/CECP Base Planning archives and the Installation Restoration Program (IRP).

Table 12. List of GIS Coverages

The following list is arranged by Entity Set (Tri-Services Standards, July 1995) in alphabetical order of the coverage name within the Holloman AFB GIS. The metadata for the GIS coverages are maintained by the 49 CES/CEV GIS Department.

Coverage	Topology	Description
<i>Fauna</i>		
bat	point	Bat sightings, maternity sites, and feeding areas. NMNHP bat survey 1994-95
grass_birds	line	Area where grassland bird study was conducted
lizard	point	Texas horned lizard numbers observed at survey points
lizrds	line	Road segments surveyed for Texas horned lizard
oryx	polygon	Oryx habitat and management areas
owl_auditory	polygon	Areas represent extent of Burrowing Owl surveys conducted using auditory (broadcast) survey techniques
owl_burrow	point	Burrowing Owl burrow sites identified in the 1996-97 surveys
owl_transect	line	Transects followed for 1996-97 Burrowing Owl studies
owl_visual	polygon	Areas represent extent of Burrowing Owl surveys conducted using visual survey techniques
plover_nest	point	Western Snowy Plover nest site locations
pup	point	White Sands pupfish sights
rodents	polygon	Potential habitat for various rodents
wet_bird1	point	Wetland bird survey sites
wet_bird2	polygon	Delineation of three survey sites for wetland bird surveys conducted by NMNHP
wildlife	point	Wildlife sightings independent of formal studies
woodrat	point	Locations for White Sands woodrat
<i>Flora</i>		
cactus	point	Distribution of grama grass cactus and field survey notes 1994-95
cottonwood	point	Cottonwood tress in duneland area of the base
lichen	point	Lichen distribution
plant_sacs	point	Sensitive plant species east of the BWWSA
revegetation	polygon	Areas reclaimed for revegetation - also delineates burned regions
veg_wet	grid	Vegetation classification for HAFB including wetland classification designated by Geomarine
wellveg	grid	Vegetation classification for northern portion of the well field area
<i>Hydrology</i>		
hydro	line	Surface hydrology
wet200m	polygon	200 meter buffer area around Waters of the U.S. and jurisdictional wetlands
wetbuff	polygon	Revised 200 meter buffer area around Waters of the U.S. and jurisdictional wetlands to provide connectivity in upper reaches of draws
<i>Military</i>		

Coverage	Topology	Description
boundary	polygon	HAFB main base boundary
boundary_2	polygon	HAFB main base boundary, included is the state land easement
boundary_bliss	polygon	Boundary of Ft. Bliss
boundary_wellfield	polygon	Boundary of HAFB BWWSA
boundary_wsmr	polygon	Boundary of White Sands Missile Range (includes portions of HAFB)
easements	polygon	Easements contiguous to main base HAFB
easmnt_state	polygon	State easement within the boundaries of HAFB
railroad	line	Railroad
recreation	polygon	Outdoor recreational areas
rr_buffer	polygon	Jurisdictional boundary surrounding railroad
training	polygon	Training sites
Miscellaneous		
archbuf	polygon	Area of largest extent of cultural resource-areas may or may not meet official status
archsited	point	Archaeology sites
borrow_pit	polygon	Existing and proposed borrow pit
landfill	polygon	Landfill area as of 1997
mgmtunits	polygon	HAFB management units
nmstate	polygon	State of New Mexico
opindex	polygon	Ortho-photo index for color-IR digital photography
Soils		
quat_main	polygon	Quaternary geology of main base
quat_wellfield	polygon	Quaternary geology of the BWWSA
scs_main	polygon	Soil Conservation Service (now NRCS) soils for HAFB
scs_wellfield	polygon	Soil Conservation Service (now NRCS) soils for BWWSA

The GIS coverages were developed from various data sources, including: USGS digital data, digitizing of hard copy maps, on-screen digitizing using photo mosaics as a backdrop, data reports from field surveys, digital data sources from field surveys, and GPS-generated field data. These coverages provided accurate locational data that assisted in identifying potential sources of conflict and developing precise management recommendations.

Following the NEPA process, internal scoping meetings were conducted throughout 1997. Representatives of the 49th Fighter Wing for each Group and Squadron were systematically briefed on the INRMP process, goals, and compliance requirements. These representatives were interviewed to determine if any natural resource constraints might interfere with their respective Squadron compliance regulations. In addition, representatives were asked to present to the CES/CEV normal logistical operating procedures and geographical areas for those operations. During these meetings the GIS was used interactively to identify potential conflicts between natural resource issues, such as sensitive habitat, and various mission-related activities. Depending upon technical resources available, either paper maps or real-time computer displays were used. The two methods in combination provided the most flexibility for the largest number of participants.

Geographic analyses, using combinations of GIS coverages and statistical procedures, were applied to produce maps and management prescriptions for the INRMP report. This involved creating derivative GIS coverages that often represented a subset of the original data, based on either geographic, statistical, or topological constraints. Some examples of these are graphically represented in Chapter 6 - Management Issues, where specific issues were sometimes better understood in a geographical context. GIS data are useful for defining management direction at scales ranging from small, such as owl burrows, to regional, such as flight lines. In addition, maps can be created with combinations of GIS coverages and shared with other Holloman AFB directives and military groups to show restricted areas and operational procedures. GIS maps will help the user of the INRMP in long-range planning, particularly when it involves on-the-ground activities.

Although the GIS is a key component of this plan and allowed the planning process to be efficient and comprehensive, some coverages have not been available. To efficiently and accurately produce proactive and dynamic management prescriptions, it is important to continually update and create additional GIS coverages. Updated coverages will aid in tracking biophysical changes in the environment and integrate infrastructure modifications.

The existing soil map (Neher et al. 1976; Derr et al. 1981) does not meet the needs of the environmental scientist or engineers at Holloman AFB, primarily because of the lack of detail and the limited number of mapping units employed. The soil map was digitized using two separate soil surveys that necessitated interpreting between two separate classifications. The soil map should be equal in scale to the vegetation map that was produced at the community level, that would equate to the series level of the soil classification system. Greater detail and accuracy in a soil map would enhance research and management for soil erosion, soil stability, watershed protection, and storm water, to name a few.

Cooperative efforts within the CES group to develop GIS coverages of infrastructure components within Holloman AFB would benefit military and civilian group activities. Developing priorities based on consensus of management and compliance needs would potentially necessitate GIS coverages such as: (1) update of road coverages with road names; (2) map utility networks; (3) map stormwater drainages; (4) 49th air space for New Mexico; (5) detailed land ownership on contiguous properties; (6) vegetation map of the southern well field; and recreational maps.

Communication between civilian and military personnel would be enhanced using shared GIS coverages in an **intranet** environment. A continued effort to create a shared environment of digital data should be encouraged to enhance operational efficiency. The development of an intranet for shared GIS data would be beneficial base-wide.

In summary, GIS is an indispensable tool for natural resource planning. Updated and improved coverages should continue to be employed in the implementation of the Holloman AFB INRMP.

Research and Monitoring

Topic	Management Issue
<i>Soils:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Effect of training activities on soil erosion ● Recovery of disturbed soils
<i>Western Burrowing Owl:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Population and breeding success ● Predator impact ● Owl diet and foraging efficiency ● Owl activity and seasonal patterns ● Human activity affecting owl reproductive success
<i>White Sands Pupfish:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● See Sensitive Species

Soils

Holloman AFB (49 CES/CEV) has implemented a long-term soil disturbance research project to determine the erodibility of various soils types. Plots have been established to determine the effects of different types of disturbance on soil crust communities. Two of the study plots are located in the Northern Shrublands Management Unit and the other is within the Dunelands Management Unit.

The Northern Shrubland plots differ in the soil types and vegetation communities. The plot located in the King 1 Training Area has shallow soils with high gypsum content on vegetation mapping units dominated by fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed or gyp dropseed grasslands. The other Northern Shrubland plot is on deep soils with low gypsum content dominated by fourwing saltbush/alkali sacaton plant communities. The plot within the Dunelands Management Unit is located just west of the Test Track on deep soils with high gypsum content dominated by fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed plant communities.

Each plot is disturbed using horses, vehicles, and military personnel on foot to determine how different types of disturbance affect the degree of soil erosion and impacts to the soil crust community. Preliminary observations indicate that soils are relatively less erodible within the plant communities dominated by fourwing saltbush/alkali sacaton. The soils with a higher gypsum content within vegetation units dominated by fourwing saltbush/gyp dropseed or gyp dropseed grasslands may be more susceptible disturbance causing greater erosion of the soil crust communities (communication with Hildy Reiser, 49 CES/CEV).

Western Burrowing Owl

Research should continue to focus on monitoring Western Burrowing Owl populations and protecting their nesting and wintering burrows from disturbance. Creating partnerships with personnel operating in high use areas of Burrowing owl habitat are crucial to the success of maintaining healthy populations of Burrowing owls. To accomplish this, two principal Groups, the High Speed Test Track operators and Airfield personnel/maintenance needs to coordinate with HAFB biologists.

- A system of reporting observations of Burrowing Owls to HAFB biologists should be developed so that biologists can be kept aware of new nesting locations and post signs accordingly each year.
- A consistent monitoring program should be developed in coordination with airfield personnel/maintenance and HAFB biologists. This would include regular reconnaissance of airfield locations near utility lights by airfield personnel/maintenance to fill-in holes at these critical locations. If holes have become inhabited by Burrowing Owls, HAFB biologist will need to visit the site to determine the best action to be taken.

Four principal research and monitoring directions are discussed in Mehlhop (1998) that include:

- Population and breeding success
- Predator impact
- Owl diet and foraging efficiency
- Owl activity and seasonal patterns
- Human activity affecting owl reproductive success

CHAPTER 7 - MANAGEMENT GOALS GUIDELINES AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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Holloman Air Force Base is working in partnership with other government agencies and DoD facilities within the Tularosa Basin to support national policy for natural and cultural resource management of federal lands. Holloman AFB is committed to implementing Best Management Practices (BMP) that include compliance with federal, state, and local laws, as well as base-wide initiatives to create a safer and cleaner natural environment.

This chapter is organized by Management Unit. A matrix of training groups and their Management Unit (MU, associated geographic operations area) is indexed by office symbol to provide an efficient method of locating guidelines for ground-based activities on Holloman AFB.

Introduction

An important goal in ecosystem management is to restore or maintain natural ecosystems to ensure the viability of native species. If a system is functioning under normal processes, with its complete complement of living and nonliving components, the system will require little human input and potentially self-maintaining (Leslie et al. 1996). Because we do not fully understand the manner and extent to which organisms interact, it is important to maintain or restore them and to retain biodiversity within ecological communities (Noss et al. 1995).

Holloman proactively manages their valuable natural resources and implements Holloman AFB "Best Management Practices" (BMPs) to reduce adverse impacts to the environment. Implementation of Holloman AFB BMPs will effectively maintain and enhance these ecosystems, providing for long term sustainable use.

In this section, a matrix is presented in which Squadrons are paired with the Management Units where they conduct ground-based activities. Users can locate their Office Symbols and appropriate Training Activities by corresponding Management Unit. Squadrons are responsible for understanding all issues within their Management Units. The mitigation measures addressed in the Programmatic Environmental Assessment Ground-Based Field Training and Exercises Combined with Integrated Ground-Based Field Training Management Plan (Holloman AFB 1998, Section 2.3) should be used in conjunction with the INRMP management recommendations of this chapter.

At the beginning of each MU section, a table summarizes the **GOALS, HOLLOWAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES, and MANAGEMENT ACTION**.

Management action is represented by alpha-numerics covered in detail below the table. On occasion, management actions are consistent across more than one management unit. In these cases, the alpha-numeric character may reference another management unit. For instance, within the Northern Shrubland section, the management action may include DL01, which would refer to Duneland management action 01. The alpha-numeric characters for the management units are:

Cantonment	CT
Dunelands	DL
Northern Shrublands	NS
Test Track	TT
Lake Holloman Wetlands	LH
Boles Wells Water System Annex	BW
GSUs:	
Red Rio Bombing Range	RR
Oscura Bombing Range	OBR
Radar Target Scatter Complex	RAT
RATSCAT Advanced Measurement Site	RAM
Air Force Special Weapons Complex - Weapons Impact Target	WIT

Matrix of Ground-Based Training by Management Unit (MU)

Table 13. Matrix of Ground-Based Training by Management Unit

Table is organized in Alpha-numeric order by OfficeSymbol. The following sub-sections are arranged by Management Unit (MU). Training groups are to use the following table to identify MUs where training activities have been identified. Refer to the MU section. In addition, a Programmatic Environmental Assessment covers ground-based training activities (see Chapter 5 - Military Ground-based training; see Holloman AFB 1998).

Training	MU	Responsible Organization	Office Symbol
Air Force Space Command Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	AF Space Command	4 SPSS
Air Force Space Command Readiness Training	Northern Shrublands/ Test Track	AF Space Command	4 SPSS/MAFX
Air Force Mobile space Surveillance, Communications, and Data Relay Systems Training	Northern Shrublands/ Test Track	AF Space Command	4 SPSS/MAFX
ParaRescue Squadron Training	Cantonment	48 Rescue Squadron	48 RQS
ParaRescue Squadron Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	48 Rescue Squadron	48 RQS
Explosive Ordnance Disposal Proficiency Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands/ Test Track	EOD	49 CES/CED
Explosive Ordnance ATV and HMMWV Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	EOD	49 CES/CED
Fire Department On-Pavement and Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	Fire Department	49 CES/CEF
Fire Department Barrier Exercise Training	Cantonment	Fire Department	49 CES/CEF
Fire Department Egress Training	Cantonment	Fire Department	49 CES/CEF
Fire Department Vehicle Dispersal Training (Phase II ORE/ORI)	Cantonment	Fire Department	49 CES/CEF
Prime Beef Combat Readiness Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	Prime Beef	49 CES/CEX
Communications Squadron Deployment Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	Communications	49 CS
Communications Squadron Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	Communications	49 CS

Training	MU	Responsible Organization	Office Symbol
Operational Readiness Exercises (OREs) and Operational Readiness Inspections (ORIs)	Cantonment	Wing Planning	49 FW/XP
TDY Deployment Units Ground Intercept Support (GCI)	Cantonment	Logistics	49 LSS
Roving Sands Support Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	Logistics	49 LSS
Field Hospital Training	Cantonment	Medical Group	49 MDG
Medical Group Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	Medical Group	49 MDG
Bare Base Structures Erection Training	Cantonment	Bare Base	49 MMG
Bare Base Generator Training	Cantonment	Bare Base	49 MMG
Bare Base Heavy and Off-Pavement All-Terrain Vehicle Tand Equipment Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	Bare Base	49 MMG
Security Forces Air Base Ground Defense Training	Northern Shrublands	Security Forces	49 SFS/SFT
Security Forces Off-Pavement All-terrain Vehicle Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	Security Forces	49 SFS/SFT
Security Forces Obstacle Course	Cantonment	Security Forces	49 SFS/SFT
Small Arms Firing Training	Northern Shrublands	Special Forces	49 SFS/SFTC/ CATM
Field Food Service Training	Cantonment	Services	49 SVS
Field Food Service Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	Services	49 SVS
Transportation Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrublands	Transportation	49 TRNS
746 Test Squadron Off-Pavement Vehicle Training	Cantonment/ Northern Shrubland	Test Squadron	746 TS

The following text is arranged by Management Unit in the following order: Cantonment, Dunelands, Northern Shrublands, Test Track, Lake Holloman Wetlands, Boles Wells Water System Annex (Northern Well Field, Southern Well Field), Geographically Separated Units (Red Rio Bombing Range, Oscura Bombing Range, Radar Target Scatter Complex, RATSCAT Advanced Measurement Site, Air Force Special Weapons Complex-Weapons Impact Target). All Management Units begin with a summary table that briefly presents the Goal, Holloman Best Management Practices, and Management Action. Following the table are the Management Actions organized by the alpha-numeric character. Occasionally, the Management Action will refer the reader to a Management Action for another Management Unit. All Management Actions stated in the summary table are pertinent.

Cantonment

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Increase public awareness on natural and cultural resources of HAFB	Historic Preservation Plan; Archaeological Resources Protection Act	CT01
Increase use of native plants. Restrict use of non-natives.	DUSD (S)/PP memo, 23 Sep 1994; ACC Wings/CC Memo, 29 Jun 1995; DoDD 4700.4; AFI 32-7064 Sec. 11.1-11.2;	CT02
Control the spread of noxious weeds.		CT03, NS04, NS05
Decrease use of pesticides, herbicides, and water	DoD (MOM) number 2	CT04, NS04, NS05, CT14
Protect Burrowing Owl habitat		CT05
Eliminate off-road vehicle traffic	Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3; AFI 32 (Section 6.1.1)	CT06
Survey grassland bird use of habitats	DoD Initiative for Partners in Flight	CT07
Compliance with the SWPPP	Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan (SWPPP); Clean Water Act, Section 404; AFI 32-7064, Chapters 3 and 4, Section 11.6-11.7	CT08
Compliance with clear zones around airfield		CT09
Enhance quality of life for military personnel and families		CT10, CT14
Support BASH initiatives		CT11
Maintain the natural balance of predator-prey relationships on Holloman AFB		CT12

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Maintain and manage bat populations on base		CT13
Use integrated pest management procedures when possible		CT15
Maintain wetland ecosystems		NS12
Air Quality - Open Burning Permits	Environmental Improvement Act, NMSA 1978, Section 74-1-8(A)(4) and (7); Air Quality Control Act, NMSA 1978, Sections 74-2-1 et seq., Section 740205(A),(B) and (C); 20NMAC2.60	NS13

CT01:

Increase public awareness concerning the cultural and natural heritage of Holloman AFB and develop informational materials and natural sites to increase appreciation and understanding of the surrounding natural landscapes.

- Enhance public education concerning the role of Holloman AFB as a missile development installation and early contributor to U.S. space initiatives. Three sites have potential as archaeological sites for public interpretation showing the role of Holloman AFB as a principal research installation for national defense projects and contributions to the 'Man in Space' programs. These are the MTSA (Northern Shrublands MU near King I Training Area), Able 51 (WSMR), and the Mart site located within the cantonment area. Interpretive trails with wayside exhibits and signs could be created, with an interpretive loop drive between the sites (Mattson and Tagg 1995; [Kammer 1997](#)).
- Enhance the trail system within the cantonment area by adding interpretive signs at natural and cultural sites. Signs could identify native plants and could include information on the use of these areas by native wildlife.
- Bats and avifauna, such as the Barn Owl and Great Horned Owl, nest and roost outside buildings. Holloman AFB residents may be concerned about the potential for transmitting disease; therefore, the 49 CES/CEV need to provide educational materials and information upon request on these species. Materials would include the benefits for rodent control.
- Provide educational materials and briefings to residents of Military Family Housing to discourage children from capturing lizards as pets.
- Incorporate information prohibiting collection of specimens into base educational materials for base and Test Track personnel and residents of Military Family Housing.
- Develop a brochure for Self Help with information about planting native and xeriscaping plants for landscaping around buildings and in Military Family Housing

areas. Brochure will be based on demonstration area constructed in Thrasher Park.
CEV AND 49 CES/CEOM

- A brochure on the native animals and plants would include biologically sensitive areas.

CT02:

Increase use of native plants in landscaping throughout the cantonment area. Restrict use of non-native plants and distribute a list of unacceptable plants.

- The use of native plants in new construction projects, medians, and along walkways are consistent with HAFB Best Management Practices. Take into consideration the growth of the plant so that it does not grow to obstruct motorist's vision.
 - 49 FW/SE will map landscaping that interferes with traffic/pedestrian safety and identify appropriate actions for implementation. 49 CES/CEO/HHG will be notified of appropriate actions, such as removing/transplanting offending plants through AF Form 332/AF Form 103, with appropriate coordination.
- Non-native ornamental plants such as salt cedar and Russian olive are not permitted on base, including FamCamp and Military Family Housing (MFH). Work with 49 SPTG/CC to develop policies for Military Family Housing for use of xeriscaping to reduce water use, herbicide and fertilizer use, and mosquitoes. Continue to update the MFH literature to show lists of acceptable and non-acceptable plants. In addition, revise the Base Landscape Plan, in coordination with 49 CES/CECP, to show lists of acceptable and unacceptable plants for use in landscape design.
- When trees and other plants require replacement, Chihuahuan Desert natives or regional native plants should be utilized. Care should be taken to select plants that do not create a traffic problem within the Cantonment area. An example of native landscaping on the base can be viewed at the Learning Center Project. A list of plants used is provided by the 49 CES/CEV in [Appendix E.1](#). Local plant nurseries and landscaping firms provide a variety of Chihuahuan Desert and regional native plants ([Appendix E.2](#)). The use of native plants should minimize, and eventually replace, use of non-native plants for landscaping on Holloman AFB. A comprehensive list of these more alkaline-tolerant plants is included in [Appendix E.2](#).
- Lawn replacements in housing, park areas, and office areas should be converted to buffalo-blue grama grass lawns.
- The golf course should be provided guidance to strongly consider converting existing water-intensive grasses to native Holloman grasses such as inland saltgrass for use in roughs.
- Guidance for facility managers and other personnel will be made available by 49 CES/CEVN. Educational materials will be made available to base personnel in Military Family Housing through 49 CES/CEOM (Self-Help stores), and 49 CES/CEH (Family Housing). Articles on native landscapes and plant care will be submitted to 49 FW/PA (Public Affairs Office) for publication in the base newspaper.

Create outdoor demonstrations that incorporate native plants, pollution prevention, and water conservation techniques.

- Annual training to 49 CES/CEOE (Maintenance Engineering) on native landscaping will be provided by CES/CEVN. In turn, 49 CES/CEOE will serve as the central point of contact for base facility managers on proper maintenance of native landscaped facilities.
- Prevent pollution by reducing fertilizer and pesticide use. Implement Integrated Pest Management (IPM) techniques, recycle green waste, and minimize runoff.
- Implement water efficient practices, such as using mulches, efficiently irrigating, recycling or reclaiming water, and selecting plant species that conserve water and control erosion.

CT03:

Control the spread of noxious weeds. "Strategies for eliminating exotic species must be devised on a case-by-case basis"(Leslie et al. 1996). Control of noxious weeds is a high priority on Holloman AFB. A funding request has been submitted for a 5-year survey, assessment, implementation, and monitoring program to control the spread of noxious weeds. If approved, the program will initiate in FY99.

The grounds maintenance contract provides for herbicide use and mowing within the Cantonment area, including the runway and infield, and the industrial facilities south of the Test Track. This contract does not include areas north of Douglas Road or the Boles Wells Water System Annex. A list of approved herbicides, compiled by 49 CES/CEV for use by grounds contractors operating on Holloman AFB, has been submitted to 49 CESCEOE and 49 CEOHHG.

- 49 CES/CEV, 49 CES/CEOE, 49 FW/HEO, and 49 CES/CEOHHE will meet to develop collaboratively an effective strategy for herbicide/pesticide use by the contractor. The objective will be to find the most effective way to comply with the Air Force policy of reduction of herbicide and pesticide use. The results may require a contract modification.
 - 49 CES/CEOHHE will research any Otero County weed management ordinances and determine how they apply to HAFB.
 - 49 CES/CEVN (Natural Resources Manager) will survey adjacent federal land managers (White Sands Missile Range, Ft. Bliss, USDA Forest Service, BLM, and White Sands National Monument) to examine their noxious weed management programs and evaluate methods applicable to HAFB.
- Any herbicide use near the airfield will be coordinated with 49 OSS/OSAA so that the grounds contractor can be safely escorted.
- Prevent the introduction and spread of noxious weeds. All feed fed to horses must be certified as "weed-free" (See NS14).

CT04:

Decrease use of pesticides, herbicides, and water.

- Alternatives to dangerous chemicals should be regularly investigated. For instance, zinc phosphide is an active ingredient in rodenticides and is toxic to wildlife and fish (USDA 1994; Johnson and Fagerstone 1994; Bison-M 1997). Phostoxin is currently used in gopher holes at the golf course; however, this method can kill non-target animals. Use gopher bait and traps rather than phostoxin.
- Revise current practices on lawn maintenance to conform to regulations that dictate decreasing all forms of pollution.
- Standing water within the Dillard Draw playa next to the housing area is too ephemeral to support a population of *Gambusia*. An alternative method for treating the mosquito problem, already in practice, is to place *Bacillus thuringus* in the area. The bacteria releases when wet and kills mosquito larvae.
- Monitor stormwater drainages that receive flow from the golf course for levels of herbicides, fertilizers, and pesticides.
- Golf course ponds serve as a sink for some of the chemical inputs into the golf course. Biomonitoring of fish and benthic soils, as appropriate, could help determine pesticide load.
- Assess water use and chemical inputs at the golf course. Determine methods to decrease water and chemical consumption. This may include:
 - Increasing xeric landscaping
 - Experimental plots with native, drought- and salt-tolerant turf grasses (inland saltgrass) to replace sections of poorly functioning turf.
 - Current practices for watering the fairways are coordinated with weather station data to adjust water use to actual need, rather than regular saturation. This practice has reduced water use, increased the health of fairway grasses, and reduced the mosquito problem. Continued monitoring of the effectiveness of this program is advised. A regularly scheduled assessment of the effectiveness of the program should be arranged between 49 CES/CEV and golf course grounds maintenance.
 - An Environmental Impact Statement or Environmental Assessment will need to be prepared if additional fairways are to be considered. The following issues will need to be addressed:
 - ◆ The scope of the NEPA document shall include management of the existing nine holes with actions requiring lower water use (implement xeriscaping), and the impacts of expansion to 18 holes.
 - ◆ Approximately 5-6 million gallons of water are used monthly (down from a peak of 13 million/month). A proposed additional 9 holes could not be allocated any additional water.

- ◆ Ensure that any landscaping efforts do not create BASH problems by providing bird roosting sites.
- ◆ A complete redesign of the golf course to use xeriscaping and salt- and drought tolerant grass species, such as inland saltgrass.
- ◆ Consider using wastewater from the water treatment plant, with redesign and implementation of larger pipes to carry sufficient water for irrigation.
- ◆ Redesign the ditch that flows into Lagoon G to increase its capability to hold stormwater surges, angle the culvert, and clean out excess vegetation. NEPA compliance would require signatory authority at SAF/MIQ because of wetlands Executive Order.
- ◆ Remove existing cottonwood and salt cedar trees that are creating a hazard for air operations because of unauthorized height. Use drought tolerant trees that attain a maximum height of 40 feet.
- ◆ Develop an authorized transportation network for the golf course and provide a briefing of the networks to all golf course personnel. Where necessary, harden the network with asphalt millings.
- ◆ Control gophers, ground squirrels, and rabbits through xeriscaping practices rather than poisoning. Use gopher bait and traps rather than phostoxin to minimize harm to non-target organisms.

CT05:

Protect Burrowing Owl habitat.

A system of reporting observations of Burrowing Owls to HAFB biologists should be developed so that biologists can be kept aware of new nesting locations and post signs accordingly each year.

- Surveys have been conducted for Burrowing Owl nests for only two years, which is not sufficient for determining trends in habitat use and numbers. 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager) will survey all areas of known Burrowing Owl burrows linked to mission activities at the airfield for activity every year and breeding/fledging success every three years.
- 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager) will survey, identify, and flag occupied burrows along Dezonía Road and any other major thoroughfares during breeding season (mid-March through July) and maintain those signs.
 - Soils may be artificially loosened within appropriate areas along 49er Road, Vandergrift Road and/or along Dezonía Road near the obstacle course to encourage any displaced owls to use that area. Artificial burrows may also be used in these areas. 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager) would be responsible.

- 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager) will incorporate educational materials regarding Burrowing Owls into natural resources brochures, cards, and handouts.

Airfield maintenance will monitor holes near utility lights and fill-in the holes near the runway to prevent use by wildlife. May need to coordinate with HAFB biologists to relocate some owls. Owl relocation will not be undertaken during breeding season (mid-March through July).

- 49 CES/CEOE will evaluate if any shorting of runway lights has ever occurred due to Burrowing Owls, and how lights are wired to determine how many would go out if shorting were to occur.
 - If the evaluation identifies a concern along the runway, conduct appropriate and consistent maintenance along the runways, including filling in conduit trenches, collapsed burrows, and burrows not used by Burrowing Owls, within 50 feet of the edge of the runway by the end of February to discourage use of the soft soils by Burrowing Owls. Burrows located in such areas are not stable over the long-term. 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager) will conduct surveys, 49 CES/CEO will conduct maintenance within 24 hours of the survey.
 - A permit from the US Fish and Wildlife Service under the North American Migratory Bird Treaty Act may be needed to cover “incidental take” occurring due to filling in burrows along the runway, or in the case of an aircraft accident destroying an active burrow. Applying for this permit would be the responsibility of 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager).
 - Burrows of resident owls living along the runway would be marked by 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager) using a stick or flag agreeable to the mowing crew and airfield operations personnel.
 - The burrow located near Bong Street and at least 50 feet from the edge of the runway (outside the mowing area) does not present a concern with airfield management and would not be disturbed.
 - Based on reproductive success and degree of consistent activity, noise is apparently not a problem at either the Test Track or the airfield. However, 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resource Manager) and 746 TG personnel will evaluate test data, to determine potential impacts.

CT06:

Eliminate off-road vehicle travel. Guidelines and recommendations provided below are pertinent to all management units. Guidelines and recommendations that have particular restrictions within a management unit are identified below under its respective management unit.

All Management Units

- Drive only on established roads. No off-road travel is allowed on base (Holloman AFB regulation 125-3). This includes all forms of ORV/ATV vehicles, such as four-wheelers, three-wheelers, dune buggies, motorcycles, and mountain bikes.
 - Develop a new Holloman AFB regulation or revise the existing regulations restricting all mission- and nonmission-related vehicle use to designated roads (except for emergency circumstances), and prohibiting and enforcing all nonauthorized use, using “Commanders’ inherent authority.”
- Encourage the Commanding General to prepare and distribute a letter supporting a 'designated road use' regulation applicable to all Holloman AFB personnel and families. A letter prior to enactment of the regulation would provide enforcement rationale for unauthorized road use. 49 CES/CEV, 49 SF
- Develop a plan, using GIS, to propose road closures and limited use roads. Make annotated road maps with names for all primary and secondary roads available to all personnel.
- Identify areas of heavy human and vehicle use, and harden with asphalt millings.
- Any ground disturbing activities and off-road vehicle use must be coordinated via an AF Form 332 to identify and avoid impacts to archaeological, historical, and natural resources.
- Range Road 9 may be temporarily closed to all non-test-related vehicle activity during certain tests. A sign will be placed at the King 1 facility and the road will be patrolled by Test Track personnel.
- The gate to Range Road 10 is currently locked on weekends, nights, and weekdays during tests, and the White Sands Missile Range guard station is manned at these times to regulate unauthorized vehicle use. WSMR also has range riders, some on horseback, patrolling west of the Test Track.

Cantonment

- Develop an authorized transportation network for the airfield infield and where necessary, harden authorized roads with asphalt millings to prevent dust and protect vegetation. Provide a briefing to all airfield personnel.
- Identify and harden all necessary access roads on the landfill cap.
- Close unauthorized roads in the Military Family Housing area near NE Mesquite Street to minimize erosion and allow the area to revegetate. In areas with existing soil erosion, put rock and gravel. In areas with potential for restoration, consider

using biosolids from the wastewater treatment plant on soil that has been prepared by ripping.

CT07:

Grassland bird populations are declining and their habitat is recognized by many as possibly the most imperiled ecosystem worldwide.

Conduct additional grassland bird surveys to capture habitat use, number of species, and species diversity. Previous studies determined fairly open grasslands characterized optimal avian habitat (Johnson et al. 1997a, Mehlhop et al. 1998b). Initiate research on habitat use by grassland birds within the 4 grassland vegetation types on Holloman AFB. Using the Holloman AFB vegetation map, transects should be established to census birds and monitor trends.

CT08:

Compliance with issues addressed in the Holloman AFB Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan.

- Ensure that all grass clippings are brought to recycle center to avoid creating/using unauthorized roads for on-site dumping. Alternatively, use a site west of the southern pond for reuse as mulch.
- Remove salt cedar from runoff ditch to eliminate any BASH problems at the end of Runway 16-34 and eliminate clogging of the ditch. Do not remove the inland saltgrass and bulrushes because they slow down the water and are natural contaminant filters.
- Do not disturb the existing DDT in the sediment at the bottom of the ditch, south of 49er Road. It is stabilized and will degrade at a faster rate under the existing anaerobic conditions.
- Place Vortex units in ditches directly adjacent to the golf course to sample water from the first flush of rainstorms. Test the water in the stormwater collection ditch at the golf course and upstream of the wetlands for contamination, especially fertilizer and pesticides. Place Vortex stormwater sampling units, submitted under the Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan, to be located near the:
 - wastewater treatment plant
 - POL yard
 - Bare Base compound near the road intersection
 - recycling center
 - outfall 2
 - across from the 48 RQS building
- Golf course personnel find it inconvenient to drive to the base washrack located near Building 133 to wash down vehicles and equipment. Current practice is to hose down the vehicles and grounds equipment on-site. As a result, wastewater with grease and

oil enters the stormwater drainage ditch and flows into the constructed wetlands. Buying a zero-discharge recycling wash unit is recommended.

- Require a berm around the golf course maintenance yard to control stormwater flows. Ensure that all “significant materials”, including fertilizers and herbicides, be placed on pallets and covered.
- Identify location where golf course vehicles and equipment are fueled and evaluate the potential for spills.
- Outdoor storage and maintenance of vehicles and other mechanical equipment at the aircraft hangers are potential sources for pollutants to enter the stormwater drainage system. Ensure sampling units are placed in outfall areas to capture this potential source pollutant and monitor regularly.

CT09:

The airfield is required to maintain a 75' (22.9 meters) clear zone around the perimeter of the airfield. No permanent structures with vertical height are allowed within this zone. From the centerline of the airfield, a 1,000' (304.8 meter) area must be clear from vegetation that can attain a height of 52' (15.8 meters).

- Exceptions to this regulation must be approved.
- Some trees within the golf course violate this regulation. Survey the clear zone and bring the area into compliance.
- Any additional trees added to the constructed wetlands or golf course within the airfield clear zone must comply with the height and distance regulation.

CT10:

Air Force guidance gives Natural Resource Managers the opportunity to develop programs in cooperation with Moral, Welfare, Recreation and Services (MWRS) to enhance the quality of life for servicemen and their families. Activities that include Watchable Wildlife Programs, Arbor Day, and hiking are a few that are compatible with the military mission. Below is a list of programs that would meet "quality of life" goals at Holloman AFB.

- The playa at the base of Dillard Draw, situated east of the Military Family Housing is infested with undesirable and exotic species such as salt cedar. The area is also often plagued with mosquitos. To make the area more aesthetically pleasing and also attract songbirds, the salt cedars could be treated and removed (Chapter 6 - Exotic Plants and Animals) and replaced with native willows. Benches and educational signs could be added after the area has been returned to its natural playa environment.
- Connect the existing parks with a system of bike and walking trails.

- Develop a formal jogging route along existing roads in the Cantonment area with maps, solar lights for night jogging, and signs cautioning drivers to watch for joggers. The exception to night jogging will be the airfield. The signs will also identify the authorized path for joggers. 49 CES/CEV, 49 CES/CECP, 49 SVSSVRO
- Formalize the jogging/biking path around the airfield and the vicinity of 4 SPSS building with signs and maps. Lights would not be allowed for nighttime jogging due to interference with airfield operations. 49 CES/CEV, 49 CES/CECP, 49 SVSSVRO
- Develop an outdoor site at the Heritage Park that teaches about the Chihuahuan Desert ecosystem. A walking tour through Chihuahuan native plant communities would have educational signage. Additional educational materials would link the physical and biological components of the ecosystem to include animals, climate, soils, and geology.
- Steinhoff Park has between 25,000 and 45,000 visitors a year. An expansion of this popular park, connecting it with the existing jogging trail, would help to alleviate some of the pressures on this popular park. A multipurpose pavillion for group activities has been suggested for the park. The expansion to the jogging trail would require an expanded vegetated zone that would have to be developed with native plants so as not to increase use of water resources.
- A Fitness Center Sports Complex has been proposed that would include multipurpose facilities and sports fields. The existing bicycle and jogging trail would be integrated into the complex. Holloman's eight ball fields would either have to be integrated into the new ball fields or be replaced. Ball fields require intensive use of water resources in this arid climate; Holloman cannot afford to increase water or chemical inputs. An environmental assessment would be required before proceeding in the development of this complex. Increasing the use of water would not be recommended under this plan.
- The extension of the FamCamp RV park has been designed and needs an Environmental Assessment (EA) compliant with NEPA and a Finding of No Practical Alternative (FONPA) compliant with EO 11988 (Protection of Floodplains). The EA should include the removal of existing non-native plants and salt-tolerant xeriscaping within floodplains. The Statement of Work for all design and construction activities on Holloman AFB requires xeriscaping.

CT11:

The Bird Aircraft Hazard Strike Plan (1996) is aimed at minimizing collisions between military aircraft and birds. Stay current on [information and management techniques](#) to prevent bird strike hazards on Holloman AFB. In support of the BASH initiatives on Holloman AFB, the following list should be prioritized by the BASH Working Group.

Base-wide

- Through the BASH program, develop a communication network and process to effectively disseminate information on BASH procedures, monitoring results, and

management techniques to the following groups: 49 CES/CEOHHE, 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager), 46 TG, 49 SVS (golf course), 49 FW/SE, High Speed Test Track.

- Finalize maps of BASH 'Areas of Concern' by species, activity, and season for Holloman AFB.

Airfield - Golf Course

- Evaluate the erosion control plantings and mulches on IRP sites at the lagoons and old landfill to determine if the vegetation attracts birds that could create a BASH problem at the airfield.
- To reduce BASH hazard either remove trees or cut out small branches in trees providing bird roost habitat at the golf course and in stormwater drainage ditches.
- Request a bid from the grounds contractor to trim salt cedar trees at the end of Runway 1-6 at 49er Road; modify the grounds contract. [HILDY: regular trimming?]
- Determine if blackbird flocking seasons at the golf course creates a potential BASH problem.

CT12:

Maintain the natural balance of predator-prey relationships on Holloman AFB. No current predator control programs are implemented at HAFB. Coyotes are important predators that help control the populations of rabbits and rodents.

- Coyotes are known to occur at the airfield, housing units, and test track. If coyotes become a problem, either 49 CES/CEOHHE can live trap offending animals, or USDA APHIS Animal Damage Control or New Mexico Department of Game and Fish could be consulted for corrective measures. Currently, coyotes are not a problem, and will only be controlled if they increase in numbers within heavy use areas.
- Residents should not leave food outside to attract coyotes, raccoons, skunks, snakes, and other animals into the housing area and should not feed any animal that they do not own.

CT13:

Maintain and manage bat populations on base. Bats are important elements in the ecosystem and their populations can be impacted by diverse human activities. The major threats to bats on Holloman AFB are pesticides and disturbance during hibernation.

Because fear of bats is common, educational materials should be published to eliminate those fears. Although the potential for Histoplasmosis fungus transmission from bat guano has not been reported west of the Mississippi, some precautions can be taken to

remove unwanted bat guano. If guano must be disturbed, soak first with 5% bleach solution, and use a filter mask when removing, or try the enzyme material that digests the guano, followed by hand washing. [HILDY: Should we include this if it doesn't occur out here?]

- If bats create a pest management problem in Building 1169, evaluate the quality of the colony against colonies using historic buildings at the Test Track to determine how this population should be managed.
- 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager and Archaeologist) will conduct a survey of historic buildings supporting bats to determine numbers using the buildings, limiting factors, and concerns. They will post signs and determine how they should be managed.
- 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager) will provide a list of pesticides and herbicides that can be used at or near bat foraging and roosting areas that would not be toxic to bats, insects, or aquatic life.
- Install “bat friendly” grating on east side of the culvert at Malone Draw to keep people out of the culvert. 49 CES/CEO cannot repair or conduct maintenance on the culvert crossing Malone Draw without coordinating with 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager) first.
- Develop educational materials on bat management and protection and appropriate actions regarding human-bat encounters for Military Family Housing residents and Holloman and Test Track personnel.
- No bat houses will be placed in residential areas.
- Bat guano in Building 1169 at the Test Track will not be disturbed, unless requested to do so by Test Track personnel. Information about bats will be included in all “Right Start” briefings for personnel and housing residents.
- If a bat is acting abnormally, such as not trying to escape when approached, call Pest Management.
- Before demolishing or modifying a structure, conduct a bat survey both inside and outside the building (some locations have bats living behind circuit breaker boxes). If bats are present, which will be rare except near the Test Track, coordinate with 49 CES/CEOHHE and 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager) through AF Form 332 to ensure that bats are not present and the demolition occurs between the fall and spring. If bats are present, 49 CES/CEV will determine best removal technique.

CT14:

Manage the ponds at the golf course to enhance the use of biological controls and provide esthetic value.

- The Tarpolean carp eat algae in the pond, thereby eliminating the need for pond herbicides. The ponds are stagnant and can be a breeding ground for mosquito larvae.

Gambusia placed into the ponds eat mosquito larvae, providing a safe biological control. Management needs to ensure that no mechanism exists for either of these exotic species to be transported to existing or potential pupfish habitat on or off the base.

- Biomonitor fish and benthic soils, as appropriate, to determine their pesticide load as an indicator of the pesticide load in the pond sediments.
 - Children's fishing programs at the ponds are currently the primary concern for (1) potential consumption of contaminated fish, and (2) risk of transporting exotic fish to pupfish habitat on or off the base.
 - Children's fishing day is therefore not recommended.
 - Signs warning against swimming and fishing due to toxins in water should be posted.
 - Ponds may need to be fenced to prevent unauthorized fishing.
 - Consider filling in the ponds.

CT15:

Use Integrated Pest Management (IPM) procedures whenever possible.

- Roosting birds, such as pigeons can be a nuisance inside buildings. Pest Management (49 CES/CEOHHE) and 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager) should cooperate to test and evaluate the effectiveness of organic fogger to repel roosting birds. Other avifauna, such as the Barn Owl and Great Horned Owl, nest and roost outside buildings. This wildlife falls under the jurisdiction of the 49 CES/CEV. A permit from the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, under the North American Migratory Bird Treaty Act, is required to capture or harass raptors.
- 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager) will provide to 49 CES/CEOHHE (Pest Management) regularly updated lists of pesticides that are not toxic to reptiles or insects to maintain raptor and lizard prey populations.
- Current release sites for pests, such as rattlesnakes and skunks should be evaluated for their effectiveness. Current release sites and potential new locations should be identified.
- *B.thurengiensis* cubes will be placed in any draws, ditches, and depressions within Military Family Housing where mosquito larvae are observed and could become a pest, except from Lagoon G west to Lake Holloman.
- Two permanent mosquito traps are planned behind the 2500 area in Military Family Housing and near the driving range at the golf course. These traps will be used to determine appropriate management prescriptions for managing mosquitoes.
- 49 CES/CEV will continue to publish articles in the base newspaper to educate Military Family Housing occupants about effective mosquito control procedures.

- Residents should not leave food outside to attract coyotes, raccoons, skunks, snakes, and other animals into the housing area. Residents should not feed any animal that they do not own.
- Gophers at the golf course can be managed through xeriscaping. Traps and sonar devices should also be considered. Gopher bait can be used where necessary. Phostoxin is currently used; this method can kill nontarget animals in the gopher holes and it is therefore not recommended.

Dunelands

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Protect cultural resources	Historic Preservation Plan; Archaeological Resources Protection Act	DL01
Maintain functioning ecosystems	AFI 32-7064, Chapters 3 and 4, Section 11.6-11.7;	DL02, NS12
Eliminate off-road vehicle traffic	Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3; AFI 32 (Section 6.1.1)	DL03
Designate Special Natural Areas	DoD Instruction 4715.3	DL04
Management of oryx		NS06, NS07
Research on fire history for the Tularosa Basin		NS10
Air Quality - Open Burning Permits	Environmental Improvement Act, NMSA 1978, Section 74-1-8(A)(4) and (7); Air Quality Control Act, NMSA 1978, Sections 74-2-1 et seq., Section 740205(A),(B) and (C); 20NMAC2.60	NS13
Minimize impact to wildlife and their habitat		TT04

DL01:

Protect cultural sites. 49 SFS law enforcement personnel will be trained periodically on legal requirements under Archaeological Resources Protection Act (ARPA) by 49 CES/CEV. 49 SFS routinely stops people in unauthorized places and asks them their business, especially after dark. If a person is caught damaging a protected archaeological site, 49 SFS will turn them over to the FBI.

- Archaeological sites are both numerous and very sensitive in the Dunelands/Test Track and will be managed in the following ways:
 - ❑ All vehicular use shall stay on existing roads as designated.
 - ❑ Any digging shall have AF Form 103 coordination.
 - ❑ No horse or foot traffic will be allowed off existing roads within the dunes.
 - ❑ Brief any researchers conducting activities in the dune area not to pick up any artifacts (violation of Archaeological Resources Protection Act).

- ❑ Any blading for sand removal will be no more than the existing right-of-way and must be preceded by an AF Form 332.
- ❑ Blading around the Test Track will not be allowed, except for Camera Pad Road and the sand dune removal area.

DL02:

The duneland complex on Holloman AFB is an ecotone rich in biodiversity that creates habitat for avifauna, mammals, reptiles, and aquatic life. Shifting dunes are a dynamic environment of geologic processes that provide a challenge to living organisms. Many of the organisms that have adapted to this harsh environment are endemics associated with gypsiferous sediments. Little intervention is required to maintain this ecosystem; however, the opportunities for research are numerous. Below are some recommended research topics:

- Direction and movement of the dunes: The dunes are encroaching on pupfish habitat in the lower reaches of Lost River and portions of the High Speed Test Track. Long-range planning for the pupfish and test track activities would require knowledge of dunefield movement.
- Duneland cottonwood community: This area is proposed as a 'special natural area' for this INRMP. No information exists on how this community was established and how it is maintained. The catchment at Hay Draw may pose a significant threat to the health of this unique community.

DL03:

Eliminate off-road vehicle travel. Guidelines and recommendations provided below are pertinent to all management units. Guidelines and recommendations that have particular restrictions within a management unit are identified below under its respective management unit. No recreational activity is allowed within the dunelands.

All Management Units

- Drive only on established roads. No off-road travel is allowed on base (Holloman AFB regulation 125-3). This includes all forms of ORV/ATV vehicles, such as four-wheelers, three-wheelers, dune buggies, motorcycles, and mountain bikes.
 - ❑ Develop a new Holloman AFB regulation or revise the existing regulations restricting all mission- and nonmission-related vehicle use to designated roads (except for emergency circumstances), and prohibiting and enforcing all nonauthorized use, using “Commanders’ inherent authority.”
- Encourage the Commanding General to prepare and distribute a letter supporting a 'designated road use' regulation applicable to all Holloman AFB personnel and families. A letter prior to enactment of the regulation would provide enforcement rationale for unauthorized road use. 49 CES/CEV, 49 SF

- Develop a plan, using GIS, to propose road closures and limited use roads. Make annotated road maps with names for all primary and secondary roads available to all personnel.
- Identify areas of heavy human and vehicle use, and harden with asphalt millings.
- Any ground disturbing activities and off-road vehicle use must be coordinated via an AF Form 332 to identify and avoid impacts to archaeological, historical, and natural resources.
- Range Road 9 may be temporarily closed to all non-test-related vehicle activity during certain tests. A sign will be placed at the King 1 facility and the road will be patrolled by Test Track personnel.
- The gate to Range Road 10 is currently locked on weekends, nights, and weekdays during tests, and the White Sands Missile Range guard station is manned at these times to regulate unauthorized vehicle use. WSMR also has range riders, some on horseback, patrolling west of the Test Track.

Dunelands

- No recreational use of the dunesfield area will be allowed or encouraged because of the sensitive ecology, difficulty in enforcement and management, potential conflicts with operation of the test track, and the availability of quality duneland recreation in the White Sands National Monument.

DL04:

Areas on AF installations containing natural resources that warrant special conservation efforts may, after appropriate study and coordination, be designated as special natural areas. Special natural areas include botanical areas, ecological reserve areas, geological areas, natural resources areas, riparian areas, scenic areas, zoological areas, "Watchable Wildlife" areas, and traditional cultural places having officially recognized species, qualities, or attributes (DoD Instruction 4715, p. 11, section 7.e). Potential special natural areas on Holloman AFB may include:

- Duneland cottonwood community and associated wildlife
- Lake Holloman Wetlands as a "Watchable Wildlife" area

Northern Shrublands

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Maintain and manage bat populations on base		CT13
Stabilize Soils		NS01
Protect Sensitive Species		NS02, NS03, NS08

Eliminate noxious weeds and non-native plants		NS04, NS05, CT03,
Boundary fence repair and construction		NS06
Management of oryx		NS07
Maintain the proper functioning of arroyo riparian systems	Clean Water Act, Section 404; EO 11988; EO 11990; AFI 32-7064, Chapters 3 and 4, Section 11.6-11.7;	NS09
Research on fire history for the Tularosa Basin	AFI 32-7064 Sections 10.5, 8.7 and 11.2	NS10
Control wildfire	AFI 32-7064 Sections 10.5, 8.7 and 11.2;	NS11
Maintain wetland ecosystems	AFI 32-7064; EO 11990;	NS12
Air Quality - Open Burning Permits	Environmental Improvement Act, NMSA 1978, Section 74-1-8(A)(4) and (7); Air Quality Control Act, NMSA 1978, Sections 74-2-1 et seq., Section 740205(A),(B) and (C); 20NMAC2.60	NS13
Minimize environmental impact from recreational activities - horse stables		NS14
Prevent adverse affects to wildlife from recreational and military activities		NS15
Protect cultural sites		NS16
Eliminate off-road vehicle traffic	Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3; AFI 32 (Section 6.1.1)	NS17

NS01:

Cryptogamic crusts are integral to the prevention of soil erosion and aid in plant establishment. The following guidelines should be considered in planning military training exercises or recreational activities.

- Confine off-road activities such as ground training exercises to designated training areas, thereby avoiding disturbance of cryptogams. Cryptogam re-establishment can take at least ten years to recover to pre-disturbance levels. Any ground disturbing activities and off-road vehicle use must be coordinated via an AF Form 332 to identify and avoid impacts to archaeological and historical resources.
- Training exercises during spring are not recommended, because rainfall is sparse and winds are high.
- Exercises should be avoided during rainfall events and windy periods. Because climate varies from year to year, local climate predictions should be consulted to choose appropriate days to schedule training exercises, particularly on sensitive areas (Figure 13, Figure 23). April through June ground exercises should be avoided because the highest mean wind velocities occur during this period. Late July and

August should be avoided because precipitation is high and sheet erosion is common during monsoon events.

NS02:

Biatorella clauzadeana, a rare lichen (G1,S1), occurs on Holloman AFB and in only one other location within the state. Its preferred habitat is at the edge of escarpments along drainages. The following guidelines should be considered in planning military training exercises or recreational activities.

- Whenever possible, conduct activities at least 100 meters from the edge of all drainages. This has a two-fold effect: (1) protecting lichen colonies and (2) preventing erosion at the drainage escarpments or banks.
- Do not disturb or trample these colonies. No information exists to determine recovery rates or if these colonies can reestablish after disturbance.
- Create a buffer of 100 meters wide beginning at the drainage escarpment to exclude future activities for all drainages.

NS03:

White Sands pupfish (Cyprinodon tularosa) is a Species of Concern and State Endangered Species protected under the Cooperative Agreement for Protection and Maintenance of White Sands Pupfish between U.S. Army (WSMR), U.S. Air Force (HAFB), National Park Service (WSNM), U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, New Mexico Department of Game and Fish, July 21, 1994. In concordance with this agreement, the following guidelines should be followed.

- Protect, manage and enhance habitats of the White Sands pupfish within Limited Use Areas.
- Assist in research and monitoring of habitats and populations.
- Prohibit the transport of any live non-native aquatic organisms to or near habitats occupied by pupfish.
- Coordinate all non-classified activities proposed within Limited Use Areas with the signatory agencies to prevent negative impacts.
- Evaluate all classified activities to ensure no negative impacts occur.
- Develop and implement incident response programs for accidental chemical spills, impacts from airborne debris, vehicle accidents and the like.
- Allow unescorted Conservation Team access to designated Essential Habitat.

The following recommendations would satisfy HAFB compliance with the Cooperative Agreement:

- Work with the Interagency Committee to:
 - identify other locales to create habitat for pupfish, i.e. Tule Peak or Camera Pad ponds.
 - determine if dunes moving into pupfish habitat in lower Lost River drainage pose a problem and determine how they should be managed.
 - create a HAFB regulation for enforcing pupfish Interagency Agreement under “Commanders inherent authority.”
 - create a contingency plan for pupfish in case of prolonged drought. Consider adding “instant ocean” to pools and/or conduct a massive trapping program to maintain pupfish in stocktanks for release after the drought is over.
- Develop HAFB regulation to:
 - manage unauthorized off-road vehicle travel in pupfish buffers
 - require that any ground disturbing activities and off-road vehicle use must be coordinated via an AF Form 332 to identify and avoid impacts to archaeological and historical resources.
 - prohibit introduction of fish or other aquatic organisms into known pupfish habitat.
- Eliminate access to pupfish habitat through unauthorized road networks within Malone Draw, Ritas Draw, and Lost River (Figure 13).
 - Identify appropriate road/trail closure methods for each road.
 - Develop a GIS layer and map for distribution to show road closures.
 - For authorized road closures, tank traps, boulders, or gates could be used to close off unauthorized traffic.
 - Put signs at roads closed in pupfish habitat with POC phone numbers and notify 49 SFS law enforcement that the roads are closed (*see* Section 5.1.4 for complete road closure plan).
- Prioritize research activities to be conducted for the pupfish.
- Ensure that the pest management plan continues to enforce the requirement that *Gambusia* only be introduced south of the delineated line south of Douglas Road.
- Do not introduce pupfish into Lake Holloman wetlands because *Gambusia* living there would eat them
- 49 CES/CEOI will evaluate all utility lines running near or under the Lost River drainage to determine condition and repairs needed. Utility lines include sewage, water and gas. Develop a contingency plan to avoid rupture or repair without degrading water quality.
 - Develop processes for remote detection of leaks.
 - Develop process for damming up the culvert downstream to protect pupfish.
- Evaluate lead contamination and sewage in runoff from Small Arms Range within Ritas Draw using an ISCO sampling unit. Test soils above and below the Small Arms Range. Consider testing lead loads in pupfish.

NS04:

Eliminate and control the spread of African rue and Russian knapweed. Contractors are used for grounds maintenance and a list of chemicals that are not permitted on the base has been provided to the contractor. Efforts should be made to continue to update and deliver the list of prohibited chemicals.

Explore the cost effectiveness and environmental consequences of the following methods for controlling the spread of African rue:

- Mechanical methods include repeated cultivation depth of 8 to 10 inches in infested area and follow with seeding of perennials. This would be effective in areas near roads.
- Evaluate grounds contract and modify mowing techniques to decrease the spread of African rue. This may include steam cleaning mowing equipment prior to mowing on Holloman AFB and additionally between infested and non-infested areas of the base.
 - 49 CES/CEOHHE will spray selected infestations of African rue several weeks prior to mowing by the contractor. Applications will extend to 6 meters (20 feet) from the road edge, both sides of the road.
- Use foliar spray technique developed at Holloman AFB and commit to 2-3 year program until effective control is obtained. Treatments include Garlon 4, Stalker, and Trichlopyr. Spot applications will have to continue in off-road areas. Evaluate the results of preliminary studies of the herbicide treatment.
 - 49 CES/CEVN (Natural Resources Manager) will contact Departments of Transportation in Arizona, Texas, Colorado, and Utah to review their programs to eliminate African rue.
 - Monitor and evaluate the existing herbicide program throughout the base.
 - Develop a plan to suppress/eradicate African rue, including setting priorities for treatment areas. Surveys would be required to identify and prioritize treatment sites by 49 CES/CEVN (Natural Resources Manager). Consider putting in a test treatment plot in a peripheral area near La Luz/Tule Peak wetlands to test herbicides. Any tests must consider the possibility of conflicting with the grounds management contract.
- A biological control recently identified by the Agricultural Research Station in Temple, TX requires further study. A beetle, native to Turkmenistan, where African rue is found, effectively kills the rue by burrowing through the stems. Minimal funding of \$4,000/year would fund a program by ARS, Temple, TX station to determine efficacy of this beetle and other insects as biological control agents. The program would take 3 to 5 years. This program could also be cooperatively funded with other signatories through an Otero County Memorandum of Understanding on noxious weed control. The other participants include, Otero County, U.S. Forest Service, Natural Resources Conservation Service, Bureau of Land Management, and New Mexico Highway Department.

- Test Scythe, a naturally occurring fatty acid based, non-selective, contact herbicide. It rapidly degrades into the environment. Treated areas can be sown or planted as soon as desirable levels of weed control are obtained.
- Non-commercial Sale of African rue. A market exists for the seeds as a dye in the manufacture of Persian rugs and as an herb in ethnobotanical and heritage seed catalogues. The seeds would be harvested, preventing their spread and possibly over time eliminated.
- Integrate the control of Russian knapweed with the management recommendations for developing control strategies with the African rue program, mentioned above. Specific management prescriptions for this noxious weed should take the following information into consideration.
- There are currently no insect biocontrol agents for Russian knapweed in the United States (Rosenthal 1995). The following biocontrol agents are currently being studied for the control of this species, the first two insects and the other a fungus: *Aceria acroptiloni*, *Aulacida acroptilonica* and *Puccinia acroptili* (Watson 1980, Rosenthal 1995). Mechanical treatment using deep tillage techniques, followed by planting of natives, is an option. However, because this species spreads vegetatively, supplemental applications of herbicides may be needed. Suppression treatments using herbicides [Tordon 22K] followed by grass seeding of perennials was found to be more effective than suppression treatments alone (Beck 1998). Information on chemical control of this species can be obtained from the Weed Management Library @ 1-800 554-WEED or from the New Mexico State Weed Specialist, Dr. Richard Lee, New Mexico State University (505) 646-2888.

NS05:

Control the spread of Salt Cedar.

Collaboratively develop (49 CES/CEVN (Natural Resources Manager), 46 TG, 49 SVS, and 49 OSS/OSAA) a plan for systematically identifying and prioritizing salt cedar management areas, including:

- FamCamp and other cantonment locations
- Hay Draw
- Lost River Basin
- Cantonment area stormwater ditches
- Airfield
- Salt Lakes
- Lake Holloman - (1) outfall pipe located at the north end of the Lake, (2) constructed wetlands, and (3) Lagoon G.

Treatments using herbicides should be applied by an experienced applicator-person and all labeling directions strictly followed. Herbicides affect most plant and some animal forms; therefore, disturbance of native vegetation and soils must be minimized. Use the

methods below to control the spread of salt cedar (also see Chapter 6 - Exotic Plants and Animals):

- Treatments on smooth bark or young branches of salt cedar - use oil-based Garlon 4 herbicide (or any other vegetable-based oil product with surfactant) in a backpack sprayer. Plant willow poles or other native vegetation to shade young seedlings that have been chemically treated.
- Treatments in the constructed wetlands - flood communities for extended periods. Plant native plants to compete with salt cedar after inundation. Coordinate with a Holloman AFB Biologist before using chemicals in wetland areas and Lost River, Malone Draw and Ritas Draw.
- Mechanical treatments - hand-pull young sprouts and seedlings; cut down individual trees within 1 inch of the ground surface and apply a systemic herbicide within a few minutes after cutting. The entire surface of the stump should be covered. Treatments may need to be repeated for several years.

Monitoring is essential after remediation/restoration treatments. Before, and preferably, immediately after, treatment, photographs should be taken and photo points established. It is best to mark the site from where the picture was taken, and the view in the photograph, by labeled rebars so that the changes in vegetation, channel morphology and widths of the riparian areas can be documented. Age class and composition of tree species and grass, rush, and forb species and abundances should also be recorded. The condition of adjacent upland regions is also important to note. Stream profile and vegetative cover can be assessed using transects. The data collected during monitoring can be used to update activity plans. (Ladyman 1997).

NS06:

Repair and construction of boundary fences to exclude cattle and deter oryx. Ensure the mobility of small mammals through boundary enclosures.

A survey of boundary fences needs to be conducted. The results would determine the repairs and new constructions needed to exclude cattle and create a deterrent for oryx.

- Coordinate with White Sands National Monument to ensure movement of small to moderate sized mammals through the existing oryx fence. Encourage the Monument to create occasional, larger openings in the fence for coyote-sized mammals.
- Repair the boundary fence in the northern perimeter of the Northern Shrublands MU and close all gates near Tule Peak to exclude cattle.

NS07:*Management of oryx populations.*

- Coordinate with NM Game and Fish Department to minimize or eliminate oryx on HAFB using fall or winter depredation hunts to reduce the herd. Use trained military/G&F sharpshooters to remove the remaining animals. The heads would be NMGFD property; the meat would be given to charity. Compliance with NEPA will be required for a program of population elimination or control.

NS08:

Grama grass cactus is formerly a federal Category 2 candidate for listing as a threatened and endangered species and was downlisted in 1995 to a Category 3 species, because it was found to be more abundant than previously recorded. One of the important justifications for the downlisting was the presence of large ungrazed populations on military installations in New Mexico (Sivinski and Lightfoot 1994). Holloman AFB has an abundance of suitable habitat for this cactus and is committed to conserving this natural resource.

The following recommendations are taken from the *Holloman Air Force Base Sensitive Species Management Plan* (Mehlhop et al. 1998):

- Within the proposed "high quality cactus areas" (Figure 23), ground-based disturbances are restricted. Before unauthorized activities take place, Holloman AFB biologists need to assess potential impact.
- Limit vehicle traffic to authorized roads.
- Establish long-term monitoring plots in high-density cactus areas. Document changes on Holloman site and compare to other site(s) in grazed areas, holding other conditions equal.
- Clayton (1989) noted that the habitat and nurse plant associations of grama grass cactus appeared to be quite different in the southern part of its range, near the White Sands dunes complex, than have been reported from other parts of its range. Recommended research on the ecological requirements of the species in southern New Mexico would include: soil requirements, nurse plant and mycorrhizal associations, seed dispersal mechanisms, and animal utilization.
- Do not mark locations of individual plants or populations to prevent collecting.

NS09:

Arroyo riparian systems play an important role in desert ecosystems. Holloman AFB must maintain, enhance, and restore the natural functioning of the numerous drainages that dissect the base.

Jurisdictional waters of the U.S., including wetlands, are protected under federal guidelines outlined by the Clean Water Act (CWA; Sections 401 and 404), Executive Order (E.O.) 11988 (Floodplain Management), and E.O. 11990 (Protection of Wetlands) and by the review process of the NMED surface water quality board (New Mexico Water Quality Control Commission [NMWQCC] 1994).

- Construction and military activities within and adjacent to wetlands and other waters of the U.S. should be avoided to the extent possible. However, if activities are necessary which would impact jurisdictional habitats, 49th CES/CEV natural resource managers should be notified (United States Air Force 1996).
- Draws that transect the base harbor diverse plant communities and provide water for area wildlife. The draws with intermittent streams (i.e., Dillard, Lost River, Malone, Ritas) support wetland plant communities, including uncommon species such as Utah sapphire (*Sarcocornia utahensis*), gypsumwort (*Pseudocappia arenaria*), and sea lavender (*Limonium limbatum*). Additionally, draws without extensive jurisdictional habitats support similar riparian communities. Although Carter Draw did not meet criteria to be considered a jurisdictional wetland, portions of the draw supported uncommon wetland plants such as New Mexico sida (*Sida neomexicana*) and Mexican rush (*Juncus mexicanus*). Although not protected under CWA Section 404, these non-jurisdictional habitats should also be avoided, to limit direct impacts by construction and military activities (United States Air Force 1996).

NS10:

Fire is considered a natural and historical component of desert grasslands. Fire suppression has led to the invasion of shrubs into grasslands. The historical frequency of fire within the Tularosa Basin is unknown. Because Holloman AFB has remained ungrazed for over 50 years, the density and volume of grasses may have increased to pre-settlement conditions. In order to determine pre-settlement fire history, the following recommendations may help guide research:

- Cooperative research with White Sands Missile Range and White Sands National Monument on desert grassland fires. Of particular interest to Holloman AFB are the alkali sacaton/fourwing saltbush grasslands.
 - Conduct a thorough literature search on the role of fire in the Chihuahuan Desert.
 - Determine effect on soils with high concentrations of gypsum (*See Chapter 6 - Fire Management*). Experimental plots could be used to analyze affects.
 - Determine local fire history. Studies would include playa sediment cores to examine charcoal fragments (Umbanhowar 1996) and tree core samples from the

duneland cottonwoods (*See Chapter 6 - Sensitive Natural Areas - Duneland Cottonwood Communities*).

- At this time, prescribed burns are not recommended for Holloman AFB.

NS11:

Unimproved grounds, whether forests, brushlands, grasslands, or other land forms, must be protected from damage by fire even if the resources have no commercial value. The natural resources manager must participate in fire management planning and execution to ensure ecosystem management requirements are met. Personnel executing fire management plans must be properly trained and equipped to the generally accepted professional standards as outlined in the Federal Wildland Fire Management Policy and Program Review of 1995 and the current standards established by the National Wildfire Coordinating Group.

Holloman AFB natural resource manager (CES/CEV) and fire department personnel (CES/CEF) will coordinate activities and develop guidelines to protect the natural and cultural resources in case of a wildfire. The guidelines will cover the associated training activities and include the following recommendations:

- Determine how wildfire can be controlled to avoid or minimize effects on wildlife and sensitive plants.
- Protect Burrowing Owl habitat from wildfire and fire fighting activities. The base Fire Department will be notified of the location of active burrows each year so that fire trucks are not inadvertently parked on or near active burrows or that fire lines are not constructed through active burrow areas.
- GPS all sensitive sites on base to include sensitive natural areas, special natural areas, wildlife sites, and archaeological sites. Develop maps for these sites, along with a list of POCs and phone numbers to coordinate activities within these sensitive areas.
- Develop a GIS road coverage that includes primary and secondary roads. Develop maps that include roads and sensitive natural and cultural areas. These maps will include data that prioritize risk to fire and/or trampling. Distribute maps to all Fire Department and 49 CES/CEOH personnel. Information on sensitive areas shall be briefed at Right Start briefings and reviewed as part of development of AF Form 332 for all projects.
- Coordinate with the county volunteer fire departments to identify and create appropriate fire lines and fire breaks. The use of existing roads may be sufficient. Determine effective strategies to control fires that originate at the urban interface.

NS12:

Little is known about the function and wildlife use of the small wetlands scattered throughout the base, excluding the Lake Holloman Wetlands. Specific guidelines must be met to protect these environments, especially those designated as jurisdictional wetlands.

- Determine and develop management and monitoring strategies that are appropriate for the various wetlands created by human activities.
- Determine and develop management and monitoring strategies that are appropriate for isolated playa-like wetlands such as Salt Lake. Salt Lake is situated within the Duneland MU and provides roosting and foraging habitat for Barn Owls and Great Horned Owls. Salt cedars are used for roosting. An appropriate strategy to maintain habitat use and reduction of salt cedars needs to be considered.
- Determine and develop management and monitoring strategies that are appropriate for the riparian wetlands within Dillard Draw, Malone Draw, Ritas Draw and Lost River.
- Establish BMP to avoid construction or military activities within the wetlands and floodplain path adjacent to the wetlands. Any construction or activities proposed for wetlands or floodplains must be documented on an AF Form 332 with a site plan and an AF Form 813 for environmental evaluation. No such action can be categorically excluded under the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) and must comply with either Executive Order 11988 (Floodplains) or EO 11990 (Wetlands) with a Finding of No Practicable Alternatives (FONPA) signed by SAF/MIQ as appropriate.

NS13:

An Open-Burning Permit must be obtained from the New Mexico Environmental Department (NMED) for: weed abatement; prevention of fire hazards; disposal of dangerous materials; instruction and training of bona fide fire-fighting and fire-rescue personnel; civil defense; conservation; game management; disease and pest control; land clearance for highway construction; forestry management; control of vegetation in irrigation ditches and canals; clearance and maintenance of watercourses and flood control channels to eliminate flood hazards; disposal of hydrocarbons spilled or lost from pipeline breaks or other transport failure; and other special circumstances.

- Blank applications and submittals for an Open-Burning Permit can be obtained from the 49 CES/CEV.

NS14:

Minimize environmental impacts created by the horse stables and associated activities.

- Establish a system of riding trails. Trails should be well marked to avoid the possibility of the recreationist accidentally encountering dangerous mission related activities.

- Establishing trails would increase safety. Military training activities that include the King1 Loop Track (Figure 19) are conducted near the stables and on riding trails used in the past. The King1 Loop Track is used for vehicle training exercises. Horseback riding in this area would be dangerous to both the recreationist and military trainees.
- A system of trails would also protect the natural habitat, preventing "trailblazing" activities. Delineate "restricted zones" such as pupfish habitat in Malone Draw and Lost River.
- Establish strict rules for trail riding that would include a map of the system of horseback riding trails. Maps should be made available to the horseback rider that would include, at a minimum, horse trails, restricted areas, and topographic relief.
 - No trails have been formally designated for use and riders usually ride east of the stables area.
- Prevent the introduction and spread of noxious weeds. All feed fed to horses must be certified as "weed-free". Weed -free hay would be required after 01 Jan 99. 49 CES/CEV will provide list of sources of certified hay to 49 SVS.
 - Consider developing a Memorandum of Agreement with adjacent federal agencies regarding weed-free policy.
 - Let area hay suppliers know about any weed-free hay policies on base and ask them how they will self-certify.
 - The horses maintained at the stables are fed hay and pellets and are not grazed on the base. At least seven species of non-native/noxious weeds have been spread from hay, manure and horsehair. Actions to minimize the spread include cleaning horses hooves, manes and tails.
 - Conduct survey of policies from White Sands Missile Range and Fort Bliss regarding use of weed-free hay.
- 40 CES/SVS should provide for reclamation of unofficial trails and other lands damaged by trailblazing.

NS15:

Prevent adverse affects to wildlife from recreational and military activities.

- The Apache Sports Range accumulates a considerable amount of lead shot on the ground. Shrubs could be removed from the range to prevent the area from being attractive to the migratory birds.
- A study should be conducted to determine whether a 3-year interval to scrape the topsoil and remove lead is frequent enough to protect birds from lead poisoning.
- To minimize raptor electrocutions, coordinate with 49 CES/CEOIE and the electric company to replace existing transformers with fully insulated transformers and construct vertical protrusions on crossarms to discourage perching.

- Consider constructing nesting structures on utility poles in the Northern Shrublands MU to encourage raptor nesting. [HILDY: Is this contradictory? Discourage perching, but encourage nesting?]

NS16:

Protect cultural sites. 49 SFS law enforcement personnel will be trained periodically on legal requirements under Archaeological Resources Protection Act (ARPA) by 49 CES/CEV. 49 SFS routinely stops people in unauthorized places and asks them their business, especially after dark. If a person is caught damaging a protected archaeological site, 49 SFS will turn them over to the FBI.

- Closing non-maintained roads that are not necessary for base mission would be valuable in protecting cultural resources. In particular, gating the road into Carter Draw island and the road near the La Luz gate.

NS17:

Eliminate off-road vehicle travel. Guidelines and recommendations provided below are pertinent to all management units. Guidelines and recommendations that have particular restrictions within a management unit are identified below under its respective management unit.

All Management Units

- Drive only on established roads. No off-road travel is allowed on base (Holloman AFB regulation 125-3). This includes all forms of ORV/ATV vehicles, such as four-wheelers, three-wheelers, dune buggies, motorcycles, and mountain bikes.
 - Develop a new Holloman AFB regulation or revise the existing regulations restricting all mission- and nonmission-related vehicle use to designated roads (except for emergency circumstances), and prohibiting and enforcing all nonauthorized use, using “Commanders’ inherent authority.”
- Encourage the Commanding General to prepare and distribute a letter supporting a 'designated road use' regulation applicable to all Holloman AFB personnel and families. A letter prior to enactment of the regulation would provide enforcement rationale for unauthorized road use. 49 CES/CEV, 49 SF
- Develop a plan, using GIS, to propose road closures and limited use roads. Make annotated road maps with names for all primary and secondary roads available to all personnel.
- Identify areas of heavy human and vehicle use, and harden with asphalt millings.
- Any ground disturbing activities and off-road vehicle use must be coordinated via an AF Form 332 to identify and avoid impacts to archaeological, historical, and natural resources.

- Range Road 9 may be temporarily closed to all non-test-related vehicle activity during certain tests. A sign will be placed at the King 1 facility and the road will be patrolled by Test Track personnel.
- The gate to Range Road 10 is currently locked on weekends, nights, and weekdays during tests, and the White Sands Missile Range guard station is manned at these times to regulate unauthorized vehicle use. WSMR also has range riders, some on horseback, patrolling west of the Test Track.

Northern Shrublands

- The development of a recreational ORV site, currently considered within the north-fork of Dillard Draw, will need to undergo an evaluation based on requirements in AFI 32-7064. The proposed area lies within the 100-year floodplain and is designated a Waters of the U.S. and will therefore need to comply with regulations governing activities in these waters. If authorization is granted for use of this area for ATV activity, the playa must be fully fenced to exclude use within the floodplain. All breaks in the existing fences will be repaired and maintained on a regular schedule.
- Develop an authorized transportation network for the Lost River/Malone Draw/Ritas Draw drainage, identifying roads to be left open and those to be closed. Where necessary, harden roads with asphalt millings.
- Close unauthorized roads south of 4 SPSS and fire training facility - It is near the IRP site for closure of the old fire training facility and no unauthorized vehicle use needs to be there.
- Put guardrails on Range Road 9 where it crosses the Lost River to protect the environment and users.

Test Track

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Control the spread of noxious weeds		CT03, NS04, NS05
Maintain the natural balance of predator-prey relationships on Holloman AFB		CT12
Maintain and manage bat populations on base		CT13
Protect cultural sites	Historic Preservation Plan; Archaeological Resources Protection Act	DL01
Protect Sensitive Species		NS08, TT03

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Air Quality - Open Burning Permits	Environmental Improvement Act, NMSA 1978, Section 74-1-8(A)(4) and (7); Air Quality Control Act, NMSA 1978, Sections 74-2-1 et seq., Section 740205(A),(B) and (C); 20NMAC2.60	NS13
Protect Burrowing Owl habitat		TT01
Maintain functioning ecosystems	Executive Order 11990	TT02, NS12
Minimize impact to wildlife and their habitat		TT04
Management of dune and riparian interface at the test track		TT05
Eliminate off-road vehicle traffic	Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3; AFI 32 (Section 6.1.1)	TT06
Support BASH initiatives		TT07

TT01:

Protect Burrowing Owl habitat. Within Holloman AFB, this Management Unit holds the largest populations of Burrowing Owls.

- The base Fire Department will be notified of active burrow locations each year so that fire trucks are not inadvertently parked on or near active burrows or that fire lines are not constructed through active burrow areas.
- No herbicides or pesticides will be sprayed in Burrowing Owl areas (Figure 25) during the breeding season. Any herbicides or pesticides used within this management unit will be recommended by 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager) to avoid adversely impacting reptiles and insects, primary prey for Burrowing Owls. Treating occupied burrows with fumigants could harm or kill the owls, which is a violation of the [Migratory Bird Treaty Act](#).
- Driving near Burrowing Owls and operation of test trailers will be recommended to occur only on existing designated roads (49 CES/CEV and 746 TG).
- Educational briefing will be provided to the Commander and top staff of 846 TS and 746 TG at next Commanders Call by 49 CES/CEV, USFWS, 49 FW/JAV, and 49 FW/JAG regarding protection requirements and penalties for violation of Migratory Bird Treaty Act and management of Burrowing Owls while meeting test requirements.

TT02:

Maintain functioning ecosystems. The cottonwood populations within the dunelands are probably partially maintained by the underground water that flows from Hay Draw into the dunes. There is only one other population of cottonwoods that grows within dunes in the state. This habitat is unique.

Test Track activities may adversely affect the viability of this unique ecosystem. Control structures to prevent the movement of water within Hay Draw may limit the water resource that is critical to phreatophytes like the cottonwood. A research project should be initiated to determine groundwater flows that affect the dune cottonwood populations, focusing on areas of highest density, located directly west of Hay Draw. Other recommendations concerning the cottonwood populations are covered in Chapter 7 - Dunelands (DL02, DL04).

TT03:

Protect sensitive species such as the Texas Horned Lizard.

- The spread of fire ants (*Solenopsis invicta*) should be monitored due to the potential threat to horned lizards (Mehlhop et al. 1998a).
- Populations of ants that serve as food for horned lizards should be periodically surveyed in good lizard habitat.

TT04:

Minimize impacts to wildlife and their habitat.

- Unless a snake is directly threatening personnel, Pest Management will be called to relocate any snakes identified as pests.
- Personnel operating in known snake areas shall wear protective high top boots when in the field.
- 49 MDG and Pest Management will provide a briefing and first aid course to Test Track, 4 SPSS, and other squadrons regarding snakebite and other pest management health concerns, as requested.
- 46 TG personnel will call 49 CES/CEOHHE to trap and relocate kit foxes. Provide educational materials and briefing to discourage 746 TG personnel from feeding kit foxes.
- 49 CES/CEOHHE will purchase and use glue-based snake traps.
- 49 CES/CEOHHE will provide glue-based snake traps to 46 TG. 46 TG will record snake locations and the date of sightings. This information will help to determine habitat and seasonality of snake problems.

- Place all exposed “significant materials” associated with the Test Track, such as missile parts with explosive residues and scrap metal, on pallets at the existing storage area. Attempt to sell all the old rocket casings containing asbestos stored here and close out this storage site. Move the storage site farther away from the Lost River Drainage adjacent to Building 1185 to comply with the stormwater management plan and reduce non-point discharges to the Lost River basin. Consider berming the area to control runoff.

TT05:

The High Speed Test Track lies at the interface of the duneland and riparian ecosystems. In order to maintain the proper functioning of these diverse systems, test track personnel must comply with the following procedures.

- Portions of the test track become covered with sand from the dunelands to the west of the track. These sands are mechanically removed approximately three times per year for several weeks at a time. These areas need to be identified and mapped in the GIS. In addition, a permanent area or areas need to be selected for placement of the the sand that is removed from these sites. These procedure may require NEPA compliance.
- Vegetation stabilizes the dunes. Areas on the eastern edge of the dunefields that are vegetated will not be disturbed.
- In accordance with the Clean Water Act, man-made ordnance craters that collect water cannot be dredged or filled in without a Section 404 permit. This includes dumping waste sand or removing borrow material.

TT06:

Eliminate off-road vehicle travel. Guidelines and recommendations provided below are pertinent to all management units. Guidelines and recommendations that have particular restrictions within a management unit are identified below under its respective management unit.

All Management Units

- Drive only on established roads. No off-road travel is allowed on base (Holloman AFB regulation 125-3). This includes all forms of ORV/ATV vehicles, such as four-wheelers, three-wheelers, dune buggies, motorcycles, and mountain bikes.
 - Develop a new Holloman AFB regulation or revise the existing regulations restricting all mission- and nonmission-related vehicle use to designated roads (except for emergency circumstances), and prohibiting and enforcing all nonauthorized use, using “Commanders’ inherent authority.”
- Encourage the Commanding General to prepare and distribute a letter supporting a 'designated road use' regulation applicable to all Holloman AFB personnel and

families. A letter prior to enactment of the regulation would provide enforcement rationale for unauthorized road use. 49 CES/CEV, 49 SF

- Develop a plan, using GIS, to propose road closures and limited use roads. Make annotated road maps with names for all primary and secondary roads available to all personnel.
- Identify areas of heavy human and vehicle use, and harden with asphalt millings.
- Any ground disturbing activities and off-road vehicle use must be coordinated via an AF Form 332 to identify and avoid impacts to archaeological, historical, and natural resources.
- Range Road 9 may be temporarily closed to all non-test-related vehicle activity during certain tests. A sign will be placed at the King 1 facility and the road will be patrolled by Test Track personnel.
- The gate to Range Road 10 is currently locked on weekends, nights, and weekdays during tests, and the White Sands Missile Range guard station is manned at these times to regulate unauthorized vehicle use. WSMR also has range riders, some on horseback, patrolling west of the Test Track.

Test Track Management Unit

- Develop an authorized transportation network for the Test Track and where necessary, harden authorized roads with asphalt millings to prevent dust and protect vegetation. Provide a briefing to all Test Track related personnel through a Commander's Call. All vehicle use will be on authorized roads.
- Identify the POC for WSMR personnel associated with use west of the Test Track (mostly for the Missile Theodilite towers) and coordinate to ensure that all personnel stay on existing roads.
- Organized activities conducted by the 49 SVS must remain on established roads. No off-road use will be allowed.
- Construct a gate on the road existing Range Road 10 south of the Test Track just west of the causeway and north of the mouth of the Lost River to protect isolated playas and small riparian habitats.

TT07:

The Bird Aircraft Hazard Strike Plan (1996) is aimed at minimizing collisions between military aircraft and birds. Stay current on [information and management techniques](#) to prevent bird strike hazards on Holloman AFB. In support of the BASH initiatives on Holloman AFB, the following list should be prioritized by the BASH Working Group.

Base-wide

- Through the BASH program, develop a communication network and process to effectively disseminate information on BASH procedures, monitoring results, and

management techniques to the following groups: 49 CES/CEOHHE, 49 CES/CEV (Natural Resources Manager), 46 TG, 49 SVS (golf course), 49 FW/SE, High Speed Test Track.

- Finalize maps of BASH 'Areas of Concern' by species, activity, and season for Holloman AFB.

High Speed Test Track

- Suggest the BASH committee incorporate management for BASH hazards created by coyotes and other mammals into the BASH plan.
- Include High Speed Test Track personnel in the BASH Working Group.
- Modify BASH forms to incorporate High Speed Test Track information.
- Have High Speed Test Track keep a log on BASH strikes to include the date, species, and problem/damage caused.
- 46 TG will contact Eglin AFB to determine if that base has a BASH problem at the High Speed Test Track. If so, what management procedures do they have in-place?
- Consider fencing the track at the "rainfield" where it crosses Hay Draw, to keep mammals away from the track.
- Eliminate salt cedar in the "rainfield" area to reduce habitat quality for doves and mammals.
- Evaluate effectiveness of the organic bird repellent at the "rainfield" where the track crosses Hay Draw.
- Do not encourage raptor nesting in the Cantonment area and along the Test Track, to avoid BASH concerns.

Lake Holloman Wetlands

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Compliance with clear zones around airfield		CT09
Support BASH initiatives		CT11
Maintain and manage bat populations on base		CT13
Designate Special Natural Areas	DoD Instruction 4715.3	DL04
Maintain breeding populations of Snowy Plover		LH01, LH05

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Proactive management of the Constructed Wetlands	Clean Water Act Section 404; Executive Order 11990; AFI 32-7064, Chapters 3 and 4, Section 11.6-11.7	LH02
Prevent pollutants from entering Constructed Wetlands & prevent soil erosion	SWPPP; Executive Order 11990; AFI 32-7064, Chapters 3 and 4, Section 11.6-11.7	LH03
Compliance with INRMP guidelines for wetlands	AFI 32-7064; EO 11990;	LH04
Manage public use areas	AFI 48-136;	LH06
Protect cultural resources	Historic Preservation Plan; Archaeological Resources Protection Act	LH07
Eliminate off-road vehicle traffic	Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3; AFI 32 (Section 6.1.1)	LH08
Control the infestation non-native plants		LH09
Eliminate noxious weeds and non-native plants		NS04, NS05
Air Quality - Open Burning Permits	Environmental Improvement Act, NMSA 1978, Section 74-1-8(A)(4) and (7); Air Quality Control Act, NMSA 1978, Sections 74-2-1 et seq., Section 740205(A),(B) and (C); 20NMAC2.60	NS13

LH01:

To maintain a breeding source population of Snowy Plover at Holloman Air Force Base and provide suitable stopover habitat for individuals during the spring and fall migrations.

- Monitor breeding and migrating populations of Snowy Plovers.
- Investigate habitat use and foraging behavior of breeding and migrating Snowy Plovers in the Constructed Wetlands.
- Describe the role of Holloman plovers in a possible metapopulation of Plovers in New Mexico.
- Investigate the effect of aircraft noise on breeding bird populations. Do low-level flights affect breeding or foraging habits?
- Army air unit helicopters were reported to fly too low over Lagoon G (INRMP scoping meetings). Ensure this unit is provided with the BASH Plan.

LH02:

New shorebird habitat consisting of a mosaic of ponds and mudflats surrounded by diverse wetland plants and associated invertebrate fauna is developing within the

Constructed Wetlands. Proactive management strategies must be developed to maintain optimal breeding and migrating shorebird habitats.

- Document the development of the wetland vegetation communities using remote sensing and GIS technologies.
- Monitor colonization by invertebrate species.
- Monitor bird species use of habitats.
- Develop long-term monitoring and research objectives. Establish monitoring plots and develop a seasonal monitoring protocol for the plots to include: water levels, vegetation composition, invertebrate samples, and bird use.

LH03:

Storm water drainages eventually flow into the Lake Holloman Wetlands complex aquatic systems. These include permanent water sources such as Lake Holloman and the series of ephemerally wet playas and depressions throughout the Constructed Wetland complex. Under the Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan (SWPPP), industrial discharges are regulated and monitored; however, non-point source runoff and discharges to the storm water drainages are not regulated. These receive herbicides and fertilizers from base housing lawns and the golf course. A proactive management strategy should be developed to monitor these inputs into the wetland system.

- Automatic samplers, currently in place at outfall areas 001, 002, 003, 004, 006, 009, and 011 should be monitored for the seasonal input of chemicals associated with lawn and golf course maintenance.
- Add additional samplers to specifically monitor inputs from known non-source pollutants such as the golf course.
- Outfalls that collect for the aircraft maintenance hangers should be tested for pollutants that are harmful to wetland plants and animals. Place Vortex units where necessary.
- Maintain gabions at the outfall for the wastewater treatment plant to control erosion.
- Do not use mosquito control chemicals within the constructed wetlands. Use biological controls such as *Gambusia*.
- Compile lists from the EPA and USFWS of chemicals which endanger birds and other wildlife, and regularly test wetland waters for the presence of these chemicals.
- 49 CES/CEV will continue to attempt to revegetate the five steep soil berms connected with the water control structures. Revegetation measures include seeding with fourwing saltbush, use of riprap, and/or hydroplanting, or other effective measure.
- Watch for ecological indicators of DDT contamination in organisms using the Lake Holloman area (DDT contamination last sampled in 1995).

- 49 CES/CEV and the WWTP contractor will biomonitor the wastewater effluent for aquatic organisms such as *Daphnia* and flathead minnows, as part of the permit requirement.

LH04:

As part of the INRMP, AFI 32-7064 requires long-term monitoring of trends in habitat values, plans for restoration and enhancement of wetland habitats, and establishment of a permanent database or inventory of wetlands at each installation. Holloman AFB has established a permanent database and GIS and conducted an inventory of wetlands (USAF 1996). Habitat monitoring and enhancement are ongoing at Holloman AFB. As part of the long-term monitoring process, the following research projects are recommended:

- Continue to document the development of the wetland vegetation communities, using remote sensing and GIS technology
- Monitor colonization by invertebrate species
- Follow increasing use by wetland birds
- Develop proper management methods, including proactive control of exotic invading plant species
- Determine potential benefits to introducing other wetland plants such as willow and cottonwood, to enhance constructed wetland habitat.
- Establish BMP to avoid construction or military activities within the wetlands and floodplain path adjacent to the wetlands. Any construction or activities proposed for wetlands or floodplains must be documented on an AF Form 332 with a site plan and an AF Form 813 for environmental evaluation. No such action can be categorically excluded under the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) and must comply with either Executive Order 11988 (Floodplains) or EO 11990 (Wetlands) with a Finding of No Practicable Alternatives (FONPA) signed by SAF/MIQ as appropriate.

LH05:

Freehling et al. (1998) recommend the creation and management of a "saturated soil" or mudflat mosaic to serve as shorebird habitat. Much of this type of habitat has been lost due to the high water levels at Lake Holloman. Eldridge (1992) outlined a management regime to control seasonal water levels and thereby produce shorebird habitat in wetlands. The management scheme maintains chironomid habitat for migrating shorebirds in the Midwest. Freehling et al. (1997) found chironomids (blood worms) and ceratopogonids (biting midges) were predominant colonizers within the constructed wetland on Holloman AFB. Eldridge (1992) proposed maintenance through manipulation of water levels for five categories of wetland: Temporary Wetland (Moist Soil Unit)-Winter Drawdown, Temporary Wetland (Moist Soil Unit)-Summer Drawdown,

Temporary Wetland (Moist Soil Unit)-Disking and Flooding, Semipermanent Wetland-Upland Flooding, and Semipermanent Wetland-Periodic Drawdown. Due to the arrangement of control structures at the constructed wetland, some of these regimes could be modified to create a diversity of habitats. Extensive trials and existing research need to be considered to adapt the regime to situations within Holloman AFB that includes wastewater release schedules, timing of seed dispersal, seedling establishment of salt cedar and other potential weedy or undesirable plant species.

- Develop a management strategy to manipulate water levels similar to Eldrige's plan. The plan must address the topography, hydrology, vegetation, invertebrates, and birds specific to the Holloman constructed wetland.

LH06:

Lake Holloman water is not safe for swimming, boating, or fishing. These activities are not allowed in Lake Holloman, Stinky Playa, Lagoon G, the constructed wetlands, or any waterbodies within Holloman AFB. These waters, as well as the others within the Lake Holloman MU receive effluent from the wastewater treatment plant and are highly alkaline. The sediment is contaminated with pesticides and other chemicals. Game fish cannot survive in these saline to hyper-saline conditions. Hunting, birdwatching, and hiking are currently allowed but pose varying security risks that should be addressed.

- Lake Holloman wetland complex will not be opened for swimming, boating, or fishing.
- Access and ground safety concerns will be periodically conducted by 49 CES/CEV, 49 FW/SE, 49 SFS, 49 SVS, and 49 JA. Recommendations will be prioritized and implemented through proper channels.
 - Restrict public access to the base and airfield through Observatory Road by replacing the wire gate with a locked gate.
- Waterfowl, quail, and dove hunting should not be allowed unless a permit program and Air Force management procedures are developed to address security issues. See the legal interpretation for hunting within the Lake Holloman wetlands in Chapter 6 - Fish and Wildlife Management - [Hunting](#).
 - Develop waterfowl hunting regulations and procedures for the Holloman Lakes MU consistent with federal and state law, incorporating the following considerations as appropriate:
 - ◆ Use volunteer Conservation Officers in uniform, trained by NM Fish and Game.
 - ◆ Modify the Air Force Explorers program (a children's training program to involve children in conservation law enforcement) to train adults.
 - ◆ Make any waterfowl hunting regulations consistent with or more restrictive than Federal regulations, including only allowing hunting between ½ hour before sunrise to 1300 hrs and allowing only steel shot.
 - ◆ Incorporate hunting regulations into NM state regulations.

- ◆ Develop HAFB pass/permit for hunting/nonconsumptive use/ with or without use fee (based on Federal requirements) through 49 SVS. This permitting system would include issuing a permit to hunt on base only after showing proof of hunter education and appropriate state/federal license. When the individual wishes to actually hunt, the visitors center would issue a badge upon surrender of the permit, on a first come-first serve basis, regardless of affiliation.
 - ◆ The number of waterfowl hunters would be managed through construction of no more than five blinds, and a pass system would be used to manage use of those blinds (no more than two hunters/blind) during hunting season. Considering the Americans with Disabilities Act, the base should consider having at least one blind accessible by road, designed in such a way that it could be easily converted to wheelchair accessibility.
 - ◆ Waterfowl hunting would be managed according to USFWS regulations.
 - ◆ Regulate type of hunting weapons allowed, to specify no rifles allowed and explicit use of steel shot. 49 SFS can stop any person anywhere on base carrying a rifle based on “cause”. Encourage 49 SFS to patrol periodically during hunting season.
 - ◆ Post signs with list of prohibitions, such as no boating, swimming, camping, target shooting, fishing, use of steel shot only, hunting only from existing blinds, “carry in-carry out”, no dumping, etc. in English, German, Spanish and/or international symbols.
 - ◆ Implement volunteer “clean up” days to periodically clean the area of trash and litter.
- Birdwatching, hiking, and cycling will continue to be allowed; however, a management program needs to be instituted to establish trails and construct signage to protect the natural resources and minimize disturbance to the wildlife. Development of the area for recreational viewing should be planned to consider wildlife spatial and temporal use.
 - 49 CES/CERR will contact the BLM for any data on past grazing use, history and status of allotment and permits, carrying capacity, season of use, and permittees. Legal requirements will be fulfilled.
 - If agreement can not be reached during the development of a grazing permit for the area south of Highway 70, Holloman AFB will fence the entire playa for protection of the federal species of concern, Western Snowy Plover.

LH07:

Protect cultural resources. 49 SFS law enforcement personnel will be trained periodically on legal requirements under Archaeological Resources Protection Act (ARPA) by 49 CES/CEV. 49 SFS routinely stops people in unauthorized places and asks them their business, especially after dark. If a person is caught damaging a protected archaeological site, 49 SFS will detain them for the FBI.

- The one known significant archaeological site in the Lake Holloman MU is located on Observatory Road near the gauging station. The site will remain protected if blading, which widens the road is not conducted.

LH08:

Eliminate off-road vehicle travel. Guidelines and recommendations provided below are pertinent to all management units. Guidelines and recommendations that have particular restrictions within a management unit are identified below under its respective management unit.

All Management Units

- Drive only on established roads. No off-road travel is allowed on base (Holloman AFB regulation 125-3). This includes all forms of ORV/ATV vehicles, such as four-wheelers, three-wheelers, dune buggies, motorcycles, and mountain bikes.
 - Develop a new Holloman AFB regulation or revise the existing regulations restricting all mission- and nonmission-related vehicle use to designated roads (except for emergency circumstances), and prohibiting and enforcing all nonauthorized use, using “Commanders’ inherent authority.”
- Encourage the Commanding General to prepare and distribute a letter supporting a 'designated road use' regulation applicable to all Holloman AFB personnel and families. A letter prior to enactment of the regulation would provide enforcement rationale for unauthorized road use. 49 CES/CEV, 49 SF
- Develop a plan, using GIS, to propose road closures and limited use roads. Make annotated road maps with names for all primary and secondary roads available to all personnel.
- Identify areas of heavy human and vehicle use, and harden with asphalt millings.
- Any ground disturbing activities and off-road vehicle use must be coordinated via an AF Form 332 to identify and avoid impacts to archaeological, historical, and natural resources.
- Range Road 9 may be temporarily closed to all non-test-related vehicle activity during certain tests. A sign will be placed at the King 1 facility and the road will be patrolled by Test Track personnel.
- The gate to Range Road 10 is currently locked on weekends, nights, and weekdays during tests, and the White Sands Missile Range guard station is manned at these times to regulate unauthorized vehicle use. WSMR also has range riders, some on horseback, patrolling west of the Test Track.

Lake Holloman Wetlands Management Unit

- Add post to gate for road closure at the large dike near the first control structure at Holloman Lake.

- Place a new gate with a sign at the north end of Observatory Road at Holloman Lake to control western boundary access and unauthorized ATV use coming from either the wetland to the north or from the east.
- Install offset fence to prohibit vehicular and horse access to Lagoon G, allowing only foot travel.
- Add additional metal posts at other gates in the Holloman Lakes area to keep vehicles from going around the road closure gates.

LH09:

Control the infestation of non-native plants.

- [HILDY: We are going to add more here when we get an update from Mike Freehling]

Boles Wells Water System Annex

Northern (Boles Wells) Well Field

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Maintain natural biotic diversity	Executive Order 11990; AFI 32-7064, Chapters 3 and 4, Section 11.6-11.7;	BW01
Establish regulations and policy for recreational activities		BW02
Review fire suppression and control measures		BW03, NS11
Control erosion		BW04
Avoid damage to water lines and wells		BW05
Protect cultural resources	Archaeological Resources Protection Act	BW06
Control the spread of noxious weeds and exotics		BW07, NS04, NS05
Eliminate off-road vehicle traffic	Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3; AFI 32 (Section 6.1.1)	CT06
Maintain and manage bat populations on base		CT13
Air Quality - Open Burning Permits	Environmental Improvement Act, NMSA 1978, Section 74-1-8(A)(4) and (7); Air Quality Control Act, NMSA 1978, Sections 74-2-1 et seq., Section 740205(A),(B) and (C); 20NMAC2.60	NS13

BW01:

Maintain the natural biotic diversity of the lower alluvial fan of the Sacramento Mountains. Increased encroachment of rural housing developments creates habitat fragmentation that poses a threat to native wildlife such as the Texas horned lizard.

- Holloman AFB can limit further development of these lands, thereby maintaining natural corridors and foothill to basin-bottom habitat for native wildlife and plants.
- Past utilization of these lands for agriculture and grazing have introduced non-natives and probably destroyed much of the soil matrix that supports native plants. Limiting further disturbances, such as off-road travel, would help to restore natural biotas. Any ground disturbing activities and off-road vehicle use must be coordinated via an AF Form 332 to identify and avoid impacts to archaeological and historical resources.
- Wetland habitats are scarce in this region, making those within the BWWF important to native wildlife. Limiting human access to these wetlands will help support native wildlife utilization.
- Consider installing raptor nest structures and placing crossbars on electrical poles to prevent raptor electrocutions.
- Consider conducting surveys for population trends, season of use, and habitat use by shrubland birds in the center of the Boles Wells section of the Annex area.
- Consider conducting surveys of Texas horned lizards and ant colonies every three to five years to monitor population trends and habitat use.

BW02:

The BWWSA provides a vital resource to the operation and security of the Holloman AFB military mission. Regulations and policies need to be established to prevent public access for recreational activities. Because of limited use and isolation of the BWWSA, only activities related to the maintenance of the water systems occur.

- Holloman AFB Security Police have no authority to enforce any activities in the BWWSA because Holloman AFB does not have exclusive legislative jurisdiction, and no mission-related ground based training is conducted there. Any law enforcement is handled by the County Sheriff's Department. Because of limited enforcement presence, any legal controls implemented in the BWWSA would be difficult to control.
- Remove the "makeshift" diving board at the Boles Wells pond and post "no swimming" signs to discourage swimming and reduce liability. The water quality has not been tested for human use and swimming could not be managed or controlled. Consider having 49 AMDS/SGPB conduct water and sediment sampling for coliform organisms.
- Do not allow hunting anywhere in the Annex because the base does not have the authority or capability of managing hunting. Hunting would also create hazards with

the encroaching urban interface and potential damage to the water tanks. All gates are locked and allowing hunting would encourage unauthorized vehicular use and damage to fences and gates.

- Place frequent signs on the fences around the Boles Wells and Douglas Wells portion of the Annex stating “No trespassing” and “No hunting, fishing, or swimming.
- 49 CES/CERR will contact local realtors and notify them of areas under Air Force control and the limitations on use. Many realtors are under the impression that the BLM controls the area and that use is unrestricted.
- Encourage 49 SFS to spend more time at the Well Fields Annex area to identify vandalism to water well infrastructure and archaeological sites. A greater presence of the 49 SFS would discourage unauthorized use.

BW03:

A review of the fire suppression and control methods is important for security and cultural resource issues.

- Fire control is conducted by the County volunteer fire departments with cooperative assistance by Holloman AFB 49 CES/CEF when needed under a mutual aid agreement. The volunteer fire departments are mainly concerned with protecting the wellfield infrastructure, not archaeological or cultural resources.

BW04:

Control soil erosion.

- Restore or stabilize areas experiencing severe soil erosion. Potential remedial management practices may include any combination of the following:
 - application of sewage sludge followed by reseeding with native plants
 - reseeding with native plants
 - construction of gabion structures or other features (water bars, settling ponds, etc.)

BW05:

Avoid damage to water lines and wells. Ensure maintenance activities do not cause unnecessary disturbances to surrounding natural environment.

- The wells, numerous seeps, and man-made pipelines which leak have created intermittent semi-riparian habitats. Such leaks are illegal and will be repaired.

BW06:

Protect cultural resources. Archaeological property shall be avoided and preserved in place whenever possible.

- Any ground disturbing activities and off-road vehicle use must be coordinated via an AF Form 332 to identify and avoid impacts to archaeological and historical resources.
- Identify and gate any non-mission essential roads on the San Andres Well Field to protect sites.
- 49 CES/CEV will make buffers around known archaeological and historical sites more location-specific on the GIS layer.

BW07:

Control the spread of noxious weeds and exotic species.

- 49 CES/CEOHHE will check with Otero County to determine how the new noxious weed program will affect the current Holloman AFB program of not treating noxious weeds on the Well Fields Annex.
- Aquatic or surface herbicides will not be used at the Well Fields Annex, to avoid contamination of ground water.
- Spot treatment of African rue can be conducted with herbicides along roadsides to control early establishment.
- Management and control of honey mesquite/feather fingergrass communities may follow any combination of the below mentioned management practices:
 - Eliminate the honey mesquite and encourage the establishment of fourwing saltbush and native grasses.
 - Conduct any control measures near the edges of the community where higher vegetative diversity exists to enable a higher potential for success.
 - Cut one-half acre clearcuts in dense mesquite stands to encourage community diversity.
 - Check the herbarium collection to identify any data gaps in plant species collected on the Well Fields Annex.
 - Control salt cedar at the Boles Well pond and plant with native shrubs and grasses.
 - Spot control of honey mesquite can be considered to increase vegetative diversity.

Southern Well Field

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Establish regulations and policy for recreational activities		BW02
Review fire suppression and control measures		BW03
Control erosion		BW04
Avoid damage to water lines and wells		BW05
Protect cultural resources	Archaeological Resources Protection Act	BW06
Eliminate off-road vehicle traffic	Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3; AFI 32 (Section 6.1.1)	CT06
Air Quality - Open Burning Permits	Environmental Improvement Act, NMSA 1978, Section 74-1-8(A)(4) and (7); Air Quality Control Act, NMSA 1978, Sections 74-2-1 et seq., Section 740205(A),(B) and (C); 20NMAC2.60	NS13
Protect federally and state listed plant species		SWF01

SWF01:

Holloman AFB is committed to protecting threatened and endangered plant species. Although no populations of federally or state listed species have been found within the Southern Well Field, Holloman will strive to maintain management practices that will not threaten nearby federally and state listed plant populations.

- U.S. Forest Service and BLM lands nearby have protected plant species. A potential threat to these populations are illegal collection. Holloman AFB will not divulge the location of these species. If these species (Chapter 4 - Southern Well Fields) are found within the wellfield boundaries, individuals will contact the biologists at the CES/CEV.

Geographically Separated Units (GSUs)

Red Rio Bombing Range

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Eliminate off-road vehicle traffic	Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3; AFI 32 (Section 6.1.1)	CT06
Air Quality - Open Burning Permits	Environmental Improvement Act, NMSA 1978, Section 74-1-8(A)(4) and (7); Air Quality Control Act, NMSA 1978, Sections 74-2-1 et seq., Section 740205(A),(B) and (C); 20NMAC2.60	NS13
Protect wetlands and Waters of the US	Clean Water Act - Sec. 404 & Sec. 401; AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	RR01
Protect cultural sites	AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	RR02
Coordinate with WSMR on range management	AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	RR03

RR01:

Protect areas delineated as Waters of the United States and wetlands.

Activities within Waters of the US are regulated under Section 404 of the Clean Water Act (CWA). Projects and construction activities within boundaries of Waters of the United States, including wetlands, should be avoided to the extent practicable (Holloman AFB 1996). Surface water quality certification in accordance with Section 401 of the CWA must be obtained from the NMED prior to initiation of the proposed project in areas associated with Waters of the US. Projects impacting less than one acre (cumulative) may be conducted without prior notification; otherwise projects impacting under ten acres need to submit a Section 404 Nationwide Permit and notify the USACE district regulatory officer.

RR02:

Protect cultural sites from potential destruction or disturbance.

Potential threats to cultural resources within the primary impact area are three sites that represent human habitation from the Paleo-Indian Period through the recent Historic Period (Holloman AFB 1996).

RR03:

Holloman Air Force Base and White Sands Missile Range will need to formalize a MOU for coordinating activities on all geographically separated units of Holloman AFB that lie within the boundary of WSMR.

In accordance with AFI 13-212, AFI 13-301, and 32-7064, operational and natural resource management issues need to be coordinated between Holloman AFB and WSMR for Red Rio Bombing Range, Oscura Bombing Range, RATSCAT, RAMS, and Maverick WIT. An Air Combat Command Range Natural and Cultural Resources Management Council, recently implemented by the ACC, could provide the means to discuss natural resource and operational issues for these sites.

Oscura Bombing Range

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Eliminate off-road vehicle traffic	Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3; AFI 32 (Section 6.1.1)	CT06
Air Quality - Open Burning Permits	Environmental Improvement Act, NMSA 1978, Section 74-1-8(A)(4) and (7); Air Quality Control Act, NMSA 1978, Sections 74-2-1 et seq., Section 740205(A),(B) and (C); 20NMAC2.60	NS13
Protect cultural sites	AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	OBR01
Coordinate with WSMR on range management	AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	RR03

OBR01:

Cultural sites within the Oscura Bombing Range need to be protected, where possible, from bombing and recovery activities.

- The difficult terrain of the Malpais lava flows create a problem for recovery of missiles within this area. Ground access is not possible for missile recovery because of the deep crevasses within the flows and brittle volcanic crusts which can give way under heavy weight of a vehicle or person. Therefore, missile recovery within the lava beds are accomplished by helicopter.
- Cultural resource surveys conducted between October and November, 1995 and again in April and December of 1996 indicated the need for further investigation of some of the sites within the target areas (Holloman AFB 1997). Some of the sites within the target area are considered eligible for inclusion in the National Register of Historic Places (NRHP). Recommendations for three sites located in the proximity of the target areas suggest they be marked on the ground and monitored or inspected on a periodic basis (every 3-6 months) in order to evaluate avoidance procedures. These sites need to be re-evaluated to ensure sufficient documentation is present and accurate; however, the ground is littered with practice bombs and munitions and may prevent safe evaluation of the sites. Maintenance procedures for blading within the lead-in line one mile south of Range Road 8 have been adopted to ensure the safety of four archeological sites. Range activities such as blading will take place north of metal fence posts constructed to protect the sites.

Radar Target Scatter Complex (RATSCAT)

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Eliminate off-road vehicle traffic	Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3; AFI 32 (Section 6.1.1)	CT06
Air Quality - Open Burning Permits	Environmental Improvement Act, NMSA 1978, Section 74-1-8(A)(4) and (7); Air Quality Control Act, NMSA 1978, Sections 74-2-1 et seq., Section 740205(A),(B) and (C); 20NMAC2.60	NS13
Conduct biological and cultural inventories	AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	RAT01
Prevent transport of contaminants	AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	RAT02
Protect cultural resource sites	AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	RAT03
Coordinate with WSMR on range management	AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	RR03

RAT01:

Conduct biological and cultural inventories for the Radar Target Scatter Complex to fulfill responsible stewardship accountability consistent with Air Force and DoD Instruction.

RATSCAT comprises 648 ha (1,600 acres) and lies within a large alkali flat covering approximately 24,300 ha (60,000 acres). This flat also encompasses a large part of the western extent of WSNM. No ecological studies or biological inventories have been performed by Holloman AFB for this site since the FY-87 RATSCAT Modernization (EA 833 CSG/DEV, 33-0-3) documentation. Coordination with WSMR and WSNM to conduct biological and cultural inventories or research for this larger ecosystem would be consistent with the guidelines set by DoD for managing lands based on an ecosystem approach and developing cooperative partnerships with stakeholders such as the National Park Service.

RAT02:

Conduct an assessment of potential transport of pollutants from the Radar Target Scatter Complex into Lake Lucero.

RATSCAT lies within this relatively large, vegetatively homogeneous ecosystem at the lowest point of the Tularosa Basin. Military activities cause the alluvial transport of materials that may affect ecosystem functions at Lake Lucero. Periodic and seasonal monsoonal rainfall inundates the flat, providing a mechanism for transport of materials by overland sheet flows. Point source materials from RATSCAT may accumulate within the Lake Lucero area, as well as at any point along the 16-mile basin. Coordinate with WSMR and WSNM to address research need for the alkali flat and Lake Lucero area.

RAT03:*Protect cultural resource sites.*

Historic cultural sites are protected within the Lake Lucero area at the southern extent of this flat, located within WSNM. Pleistocene mammal trackways have been found within this flat north of WSNM. Obtain locational information on the trackways to delineate spatial extent and investigate the possibility of protecting these trackways from natural and human disturbance.

RATSCAT Advanced Measurement Site (RAMS)

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Eliminate off-road vehicle traffic	Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3; AFI 32 (Section 6.1.1)	CT06
Air Quality - Open Burning Permits	Environmental Improvement Act, NMSA 1978, Section 74-1-8(A)(4) and (7); Air Quality Control Act, NMSA 1978, Sections 74-2-1 et seq., Section 740205(A),(B) and (C); 20NMAC2.60	NS13
Reseed with native grasses when reseeding is necessary	AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	RAM01
Coordinate with WSMR on range management	AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	RR03

RAM01:*When reseeding is necessary, reseed with native grasses.*

RAMS EA (1982) suggested Lehmann and Boer lovegrass (*Eragrostis lehmanniana* and *E. chloromelas*) may be used to prevent wind or water erosion if soil destabilization becomes a problem. These plants were suggested because they are both low-growing (less than 6 inches) and drought-tolerant perennial grasses. However, these plants are invasive non-natives and can compete with native species. If seeding were required to stabilize the soil within this area, recommended alternatives would be black or blue grama grasses (*Bouteloua eriopoda* or *B. gracilis*). These grasses occur on surrounding hillslopes and nearby drainages and without assisted watering will maintain heights comparable to the lovegrasses previously mentioned.

Air Force Special Weapons Complex (AFSWC) - Weapons Impact Target (WIT)

GOAL	HOLLOMAN BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES	MANAGEMENT ACTION
Eliminate off-road vehicle traffic	Executive Order 11989; US Army Corp of Engineers 1992; HAFB regulation 125-3; AFI 32 (Section 6.1.1)	CT06
Air Quality - Open Burning Permits	Environmental Improvement Act, NMSA 1978, Section 74-1-8(A)(4) and (7); Air Quality Control Act, NMSA 1978, Sections 74-2-1 et seq., Section 740205(A),(B) and (C); 20NMAC2.60	NS13
Coordinate with WSMR on range management	AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	RR03
Protect natural elements of the landscape	AFI 13-212; AFI 13-3-1; AFI 32-7064	WIT01

WIT01:

Protect natural elements of the landscape and control fires.

Military activities at this site include live-missile impacts, litter of exploded debris, and vehicle traffic. Most of the disturbance to the natural landscape has been confined within the 1,000 meter safety area. Two principal concerns as a result of these activities are grass fires and accelerated wind erosion from defoliated areas. Site disturbance by military activities expose the underlying gypsum deposits and de-stabilize gypsic crusts. Additionally, two state L4 species, the grama grass cactus and Wright fishhook cactus were identified within the safety zone.

- Begin to document and map fire occurrences
- Establish fire monitoring plots within an area outside the control rings of the safety zone
- Monitor Wright fishhook cactus populations periodically

Timeline for Management Objectives

[Timeline to be organized by MU with priorities set by HILDY]

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Agricultural Outleasing	The use of DoD lands under a lease to an agency, organization, or person for growing crops or grazing animals.
Alluvial Fan	A semiconical, or fan-shaped landform built of loose rock material deposited by a stream at the place where it issues from a narrow mountain valley upon a plain or broad valley. It is steepest near the mouth of the valley and slopes gently and convexly outward with gradually decreasing gradient.
Bajada	Individual alluvial fans along a mountain front that grow laterally to the extent that they coalesce to form a continuous piedmont sedimentary apron.
Biological Diversity	The variety of life forms, the ecological roles they perform, and the genetic variability they contain within any defined time and space.
Cooperative Agreement	A written agreement between an AF installation and one or more outside agencies (Federal, state, or local) that coordinates planning strategies. It is a vehicle for obtaining assistance in developing natural resources programs.
Critical Habitat	Any air, land, or water area (excluding existing synthetic structures or settlements that are not necessary to the survival and recovery of a listed species) and constituents thereof that the USFWS has designated as essential to the survival and recovery of an endangered or threatened species or a distinct segment of its population.
Cuesta	A hill or ridge with a gentle slope on one side and a steep slope on the other.
Ecosystem Management	An approach to natural resources management that focuses on the interrelationships of ecological processes linking soils, plants, animals, minerals, climate, water, and topography. Managers view such processes as a living system that affects and responds to human activity beyond traditional commodity and amenity uses. They also acknowledge the importance of ecosystem services such as water conservation, oxygen recharge, and nutrient recycling.

Edaphic	Ecological effects resulting from or influenced by local conditions of the soil or substrate; most likely soil characteristics that affect plant growth.
Endangered Species	Any plant or animal listed as endangered by the Federal Government.
Evapotranspiration	The combined evaporation from soil surface moisture and transpiration from plants.
Exotic Species	Any plant or animal not native to a region, state, or country. (This definition excludes certain game species that have become established, such as pheasants.)
Faculative Wetland	An organism that can exist independently from the wetland, but may under certain circumstances exist in a wetland
Federal Endangered	Any species that is in danger of extinction throughout all or a significant portion of its range.
Federal species of concern	Any species whose population numbers are declining or whose range is diminishing to the point where it may become threatened in the near future
Federal Threatened	Any species that is likely to become endangered within the foreseeable future throughout all or a significant portion of its range.
Fish	Fresh and salt water fin-fish, other aquatic vertebrate organisms, and crustaceans and mollusks.
Floodplains	Lowland or flat areas adjoining inland and coastal waters, including areas on offshore islands, that are prone to flooding.
Game	Any species of fish or wildlife for which state or federal laws and regulations prescribe hunting seasons and bag or creel limits.
Grazing Land	Land with vegetative cover that consists of grasses, herbs, and shrubs valuable as forage.
Grazing Systems	Specialized methods of grazing management (the manipulation of livestock grazing to accomplish a desired result) that define systematically recurring periods of grazing and deferment for pastures or management units.

Habitat	An area that provides the environmental elements of air, water, food, cover, and space necessary for a given species to survive and reproduce.
Highly Erodible Soils	Soils that, because of their physical properties or slope, the US Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service, identifies as being highly susceptible to wind or water erosion.
Improved Grounds	Grounds on which personnel annually plan and perform intensive maintenance activities. These are developed areas of an installation that have lawns and landscape plantings that require intensive maintenance. They usually include the cantonment, parade grounds, drill fields, athletic areas, golf courses (excluding roughs), cemeteries, and housing areas.
Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP)	A natural resources management plan based on ecosystem management that shows the interrelationships of the individual component plans as well as mission and land use activities affecting the basic land management plans.
Integrated Pest Management (IPM)	A planned program incorporating continuous monitoring, education, record-keeping, and communication to prevent pests and disease vectors from causing unacceptable damage to operations, people, property, materiel, or the environment. IPM includes methods such as habitat modification, biological control, genetic control, cultural methods, mechanical control, physical control, regulatory control, and the judicious use of least-hazardous pesticides.
Intranet	An intranet is a network that is contained within an enterprise. It may consist of many interlinked local area networks and also use leased-lines in the wide-area network. It may or may not include connections through one or more gateways to the outside Internet. The main purpose of an intranet is usually to share company information and computing resources among employees. An intranet can also be used to facilitate working in groups and for teleconferences.

Land Management Unit	The smallest land management division that planners use in developing specific strategies to accomplish natural resources management goals. Land management units may correspond to grazing units on agricultural outleased lands, stands or compartments on commercial forest lands, various types of improved grounds (for example, athletic fields, parks, yards in family housing, or landscaped areas around administrative buildings), or identifiable semi-improved grounds (for example, airfield areas, utility rights-of-way, or roadside areas).
Land-Use Regulation	A document that prescribes the specific technical actions or land use and restrictions with which lessees, permittees, or contractors must comply. It derives from the grazing or cropland management plan and forms a part of all outleases, land use permits, and other contracts.
Livestock	Domestic animals kept or raised for food, by-products, work, transportation, or recreation.
Multiple-Use	The integrated, coordinated, and compatible use of various natural resources to derive the best benefit while perpetuating and protecting those resources.
Multiple-Use and Sustained Yield Management	The care and use of natural resources so as to best serve the present and future needs of the United States and its people without impairing the productivity of the land and water.
Natural Resources Management Professional	A person with a degree in the natural sciences who manages natural resources on a regular basis and receives periodic training to maintain proficiency in that job.
No Funds Service Contract	An agreement by which a party performs a land management service for a consideration other than funds. Such a contract exists, for example, when a party hired to establish, control, or remove vegetative cover or growth agrees to take payment for the service in the form of the growth that results.
Non commercial Forest Land	Land not capable of yielding forest products of at least 20 cubic feet per acre a year because of adverse site conditions. The classification also includes productive forest land on which mission requirements, accessibility, or non-compatible uses preclude forest management activities.
Obligate	Restricted to a specified condition of life, as an obligate wetland species.

Orogenic	Mountain building processes.
Outdoor Interpretation	Observing and explaining the history, development, and significance of our natural heritage and natural resources.
Outdoor Recreation	Recreation that relates directly to and occurs in natural, outdoor environments.
Outdoor Recreation Resources	Land and water areas and associated natural resources that provide, or have the potential to provide, opportunities for outdoor recreation for present and future generations.
Outfall	The point, location, or structure where wastewater or drainage discharges from a sewer pipe, ditch, or other conveyance to a receiving body of water.
Phreatophyte	A type of plant with very long, extensive root systems which draws its water from the water table or other permanent groundwater supplies. Example is saltcedar.
Piedmont	Lying or formed at the base of a mountain or mountain range.
Rangeland	Land on which the native vegetation is predominantly grasses, grass-like plants, herbs, or shrubs suitable for grazing or browsing use. It includes lands re-vegetated naturally or artificially to provide a forage cover that is managed like native vegetation. It also includes natural grasslands, savannas, shrubland, most deserts, tundra, alpine communities, coastal marshes, and wet meadows.
Recreation Carrying Capacity	The level of recreational use that an area can sustain without damage to the environment.
Reforestation	The renewal or regeneration of a forest by natural or artificial means.
Semi-Improved Grounds	Grounds where personnel perform periodic maintenance primarily for operational and aesthetic reasons (such as erosion and dust control, bird control, and visual clear zones). These usually include grounds adjacent to runways, taxiways, and aprons; runway clear zones; lateral safety zones; rifle and pistol ranges; picnic areas; ammunition storage areas; antenna facilities; and golf course roughs.

Special Natural Areas	Special natural areas include botanical areas, ecological reserve areas, geological areas, natural resources areas, riparian areas, scenic areas, zoological areas, “Watchable Wildlife” areas, and traditional cultural places having officially recognized species qualities or attributes.
Species of Local Concern	Any species known to exist or potentially exist within the proximity of Los Alamos National Laboratory lands and surrounding areas that are rare in numbers and/or occurrences and whose habitat requirements are very specific, rare to this area, or threatened in any way.
State Endangered	Any species listed in the New Mexico state endangered list because it is rare in numbers and/or occurrences and, without protection, its further existence in the state is in serious jeopardy.
State Threatened	Any species whose prospects of survival or recruitment within the state are likely to become jeopardized in the near future.
Stewardship	The management of a resources base with the goal of maintaining or increasing the resources' ' value indefinitely into the future.
Threatened Species	Those federally listed species of flora and fauna that are likely to become endangered within the foreseeable future throughout all or a significant portion of their range and that have been designated for special protection and management pursuant to the Endangered Species Act.
Unimproved Grounds	Grounds normally managed by the natural resources staff on an installation or in firing ranges or annexes in support of the AF mission and to achieve integrated resources goals defined in the INRMP. All grounds not expressly defined as improved or semi-improved are unimproved. Unimproved grounds include weapons firing and bombing ranges; forest lands; croplands and grazing lands; grasslands or ranges; lakes, ponds, and wetlands; and areas in the airfield beyond the safety zones.
Urban Forests	Planted or remnant native tree species existing within urbanized areas such as parks, tree-lined residential streets, scattered tracts of undisturbed woodlands, and cantonment areas.

**Watchable Wildlife
Areas**

Areas identified under the Watchable Wildlife Program as suitable for passive recreational uses such as bird watching, nature study, and other non-consumptive uses of wildlife resources.

Wetlands

Areas inundated or saturated by surface or ground water at a frequency and a duration to support, and that under normal circumstances do support, a prevalence of vegetation typically adapted for life in saturated soil conditions.

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SCIENCE/NATURAL RESOURCE ABBREVIATIONS

3A*	Taxa for which the USFWS has persuasive evidence of extinction. Federal endangerment listing determined by U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service.
3B*	Names that, on the basis of current taxonomic understanding, do not represent distinct taxa. Federal endangerment listing determined by U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service.
3C*	Taxa that have proven to be more abundant or widespread than previously believed and/or those that are not subject to any identifiable threat. Federal endangerment listing determined by U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service.
C	Candidate taxa for which the USFWS has on file enough substantial information on biological vulnerability and threat(s) to support proposals to list them as endangered or threatened species. Federal endangerment listing determined by U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service.
D	"Plant Species Considered, But Not Included"; taxa considered, but not included on above lists; or taxa delisted from previous lists. State status of endangerment determined by Energy, Minerals and Natural Resources Department.
dB	decibels
E1	"Endangered, group 1," any species or subspecies whose prospects of survival or recruitment in New Mexico are in jeopardy. Status of endangerment determined by NM Department of Game and Fish.
E2	"Endangered, group 2," any species or subspecies whose prospects of survival or recruitment in New Mexico are likely to be in jeopardy within the foreseeable future. Status of endangerment determined by NM Department of Game and Fish.
E	"Endangered Plant Species," any plant species whose prospects of survival within the state are in jeopardy or are likely, within the foreseeable future, to become jeopardized. State status of endangerment determined by Energy, Minerals and Natural Resources Department.
EA	Environmental Assessment
e.g.	exempli gratia (for example)
ESA	Endangered Species Act
et al.	et al.ii (and others)
et seq.	et sequens (and the following)
etc.	et cetera (and so forth)
ft	feet (or foot)
G1	<i>See</i> GRANK. Critically imperiled globally because of extreme rarity or because of some factor(s) making it especially vulnerable to extinction. Typically 5 or fewer occurrences or very few remaining individuals or acres.

G2	<i>See</i> GRANK. Imperiled globally because of rarity or because of some factor(s) making it very vulnerable to extinction throughout its range. 6 to 20 occurrences or few remaining individuals or acres.
G3	<i>See</i> GRANK. Either very rare and local throughout its range or found locally (even abundantly at some of its locations) in a restricted range (e.g., a single western state, a physiographic region in the east) or because of other factors making it vulnerable to extinction throughout its range. 21 to 100 occurrences.
G4	Widespread, abundant, and apparently secure globally, though it may be quite rare in parts of its range, especially at the periphery. Thus, the Element is of long-term concern. Usually more than 100 occurrences.
G5	Demonstrably widespread, abundant and secure globally, though it may be quite rare in parts of its range, especially at the periphery.
GH	<i>See</i> GRANK. Of historical occurrence throughout its range, i.e., formerly part of the established biota, with the expectation that it may be rediscovered (i.e., Bachman's Warbler)
GRANK	A numeric rank (G1 through G5) of relative endangerment based primarily on the number of occurrences of the Element globally. Ranking established by The Nature Conservancy. . http://www.nmnhp.unm.edu/ranks.html
GU	<i>See</i> GRANK. Possibly in peril range-wide but status uncertain; need more information.
GX	<i>See</i> GRANK. Believed to be extinct throughout range (i.e., Passenger Pigeon) with virtually no likelihood that it will be rediscovered.
ha	hectare
HUB	Hydrologic Unit Boundary
i.e.	id est (that is)
L1	Plant species endangered in New Mexico. State status of endangerment determined by Energy, Minerals and Natural Resources Department. http://www.emnrd.state.nm.us/forestry/endplntlist.htm
L2	New Mexico rare and sensitive plant species. State status of endangerment determined by Energy, Minerals and Natural Resources Department. http://www.emnrd.state.nm.us/forestry/endplntlist.htm
L3	New Mexico rare plant review list. State status of endangerment determined by Energy, Minerals and Natural Resources Department. http://www.emnrd.state.nm.us/forestry/endplntlist.htm
L4	Plant species considered, but not included. State status of endangerment determined by Energy, Minerals and Natural Resources Department. http://www.emnrd.state.nm.us/forestry/endplntlist.htm
LE	Endangered. Federal endangerment listing determined by U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service.
LCTA	land condition trend analysis
LT	Threatened. Federal endangerment listing determined by U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service.

MSL	mean sea level
MU(s)	management unit(s)
NAWMP	North American Waterfowl Management Plan
PE	Taxa proposed to be listed as endangered. Federal endangerment listing determined by U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service.
PT	Taxa proposed to be listed as threatened. Federal endangerment listing determined by U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service.
R	"Review List"; any plant taxon about which more information is needed. The species is either taxonomically questionable or poorly understood as to distribution or endangerment. State status of endangerment determined by Energy, Minerals and Natural Resources Department.
R-E-D Code	The three components are rarity, endangerment and distribution which together form the R-E-D Code. Each element in the code is divided into three classes or degrees of concern, represented by the number 1, 2 or 3. In each case, the higher the number, the more critical the concern. State status of endangerment determined by Energy, Minerals and Natural Resources Department.
S1	<i>See</i> SRANK. Critically imperiled in state because of extreme rarity (5 or fewer occurrences or very few remaining individuals or acres) or because of some factor(s) making it especially vulnerable to extirpation from the state.
S2	<i>See</i> SRANK. Imperiled in state because of rarity (6 to 20 occurrences or few remaining individuals or acres) or because of some factor(s) making it very vulnerable to extirpation from the state.
S3	<i>See</i> SRANK. Rare or uncommon in state (on the order of 21 to 100 occurrences)
S4	<i>See</i> SRANK. Apparently secure in state, with many occurrences.
S5	<i>See</i> SRANK. Demonstrably secure in state and essentially ineradicable under present conditions.
S	"Sensitive Plant"; any plant taxon that is considered to be rare because of restricted distribution or low numerical density. State status of endangerment determined by Energy, Minerals and Natural Resources Department.
SA	<i>See</i> SRANK. Accidental in NM, including species (usually birds or butterflies) recorded once or twice or only at very great intervals.
SB	<i>See</i> SRANK. Migratory species that breeds in the state.
SC	Taxa for which there is some evidence of vulnerability (USFWS Species of Concern), but for which there are not enough data to support listing proposals at this time, and for which there is no legal documentation. Federal endangerment listing determined by U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service.
SCF	Taxa for which there is some evidence of vulnerability, but for which there are not enough data to support listing proposals at this time. USFWS Species of Concern. Former Candidate 2 (C2) species. Federal endangerment listing determined by U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service.

SE	<i>See</i> SRANK. An exotic established in state; may be native elsewhere in North America; includes fish native to NM but introduced into watersheds where the species is non-native.
SH	<i>See</i> SRANK. Of historical occurrence in state, perhaps having not been verified in the past 20 years, and suspected to be still extant, or if occurrence known to be destroyed or extensively and unsuccessfully looked for. SB = Breeds in the state.
SN	<i>See</i> SRANK. Regularly occurring, usually migratory and typically nonbreeding.
sp.	species
SR	<i>See</i> SRANK. Reported from the NM, but without persuasive documentation which would provide a basis for either accepting or rejecting (ie, misidentified specimen) the report.
SRANK	A numeric rank (G1 through G5) of relative endangerment based primarily on the number of occurrences of the Element globally. Ranking established by The Nature Conservancy. http://www.nmnhp.unm.edu/ranks.html
ssp.	subspecies
SU	<i>See</i> SRANK. Possibly in peril in NM but status uncertain; need more information
SX	<i>See</i> SRANK. Apparently extirpated from New Mexico.
SXC	<i>See</i> SRANK. Apparently extirpated from its natural habitat in the state, but being held in captivity.
var.	variety

MILITARY/GOVERNMENT ABBREVIATIONS

ACC	Air Combat Command
ACP	Accelerated Cleanup Program
AFB	Air Force Base
AFI	Air Force Instruction
AFR	Air Force Regulation
AFSWC	Air Force Special Weapons Complex
CAA	Clean Air Act
CFR	Code of Federal Regulations
DoD	Department of Defense
EA	Environmental Assessment
EOD	explosive ordnance disposal
ESA	Endangered Species Act
FS	Fighter Squadron
GAF	German Air Force
HAFB	Holloman Air Force Base
HAZMART	Hazardous Material Pharmacy
IRP	Installation Restoration Program
LCTA	Land Condition Trend Analysis
MAP	Management Action Plan
MU(s)	Management Unit(s)
NAAQS	National Ambient Air Quality Standards
NEPA	National Environmental Policy Act
NMDGF	New Mexico Department of Game and Fish
NPDES	National Pollution Discharge Elimination System
NPS	National Park Service
NWR	National Wildlife Refuge
OBR	Oscura Bombing Range
PL	Public Law
POC	Point of Contact
RAMS	RATSCAT Advanced Measurement Site
RATSCAT	Radar Target Scatter Complex
RRBR	Red Rio Bombing Range
SHPO	State Historic Preservation Officer
SWPPP	Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan
U.S.	United States
USAF	U.S. Air Force
U.S.C.	U.S. Code
USFWS	U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
USGS	U.S. Geological Survey
WIT	Weapons Impact Target
WSMR	White Sands Missile Range
WSNM	White Sands National Monument

APPENDIX A LIST OF NATURAL RESOURCES LEGISLATION AND REQUIREMENTS

An excellent Search Engine for these data listed below is provided on the website -- [DENIX](#).

Animal Damage Control Act (7 USC 426-426b; 47 Stat. 1468)
Bald Eagle Act of 1940 (16 USC 668-668d; 54 Stat. 250)
Clean Water Act (CWA) of 1977 (P.L. 95-217 as amended)
Coastal Barrier Resources Act (16 USC 3501 et seq)
Coastal Zone Management Act (16 USC 1451 et seq)
[DoD Directive Instruction 4715.3](#), "Environmental Conservation Program"
[DoD Directive Instruction 4700.4](#), "Natural Resources Management Program"
Endangered Species Act (16 USC 1531 et seq)
Estuary Protection Act (16 USC 1221-1226; 82 Stat. 625)
Executive Order 11514, Protection and Enhancement of Environmental Quality
Executive Order 11988, Flood plains Management
Executive Order 11989, Off-Road Vehicles on Public Lands
Executive Order 11990, Wetlands Management
Farmland Protection Act (7 USC 4201 et seq)
Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act
Federal Land Policy and Management Act of 1976 (43 USC 1701)
Federal Noxious Weed Act of 1974 (7 USC 2809 et seq)
Federal Water Pollution Control Act of 1977
Fish and Wildlife Conservation Act (P.L. 96-366, 16 USC 2901)
Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act (16 USC 661 et seq)
Forest and Rangeland Renewable Resources Planning Act of 1974 (P.L. 93-378, 16 USC 1601 et seq)
FY91 Defense Appropriations Act
Lacey Act of 1900 (16 USC 701, 702; 31 Stat. 187, 32 Stat. 285)
Marine Mammal Protection Act of 1972 (P.L. 92-533)
Migratory Bird Conservation Act (P.L. 89-699, 16 USC 715)
Multiple Use Sustained Yield Act of 1960 (16 USC 528 et seq)
National Environmental Policy Act (42 USC 4341)
National Forest Management Act of 1976 (P.L. 94-588, 16 USC 1600 et seq)
National Trails Systems Act (16 USC 1241-1249)
Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899 (33 USC 401 et seq)
Secretary of the Air Force Order 780.1, Wetlands
Secretary of the Air Force Order 790.1, Floodplains
Sikes Act (16 USC 670 et seq) "Conservation Programs on Military Reservations"
Soil and Water Conservation Act (P.L. 95-193, 16 USC 2001)
Taylor Grazing Act (P.L. 73-482, 43 USC 315 et seq)
Title 10 USC 2665: Forest Management
Wild and Scenic Rivers Act (16 USC 1274 et seq)
Wild Horses and Burros Act (16 USC 1331-1340; 85 Stat. 649)

Wilderness Act of 1964 (16 USC 1131-1136); 78 Stat. 890; PL 88-577)

APPENDIX B. SELECTED COOPERATIVE AGREEMENTS AND MEMORANDUMS OF UNDERSTANDING

- Cooperative Agreement for Protection and Maintenance of White Sands Pupfish between U.S. Army (WSMR), U.S. Air Force (HAFB), National Park Service (WSNM), U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, New Mexico Department of Game and Fish, July 21, 1994
- New Mexico Cooperative Agreement [HILDY] - Pat has electronic format

APPENDIX C. CLIMATE DATA

Tables compiled from United States Air Force Environmental Technical Applications Center, 1994. Surface observations Climatic Summaries for Holloman Air Force Base/Alamogordo, New Mexico. USAFETAC, Asheville, North Carolina.

- C.1. [Climate Brief](#) – Average, Mean, Minimum, Maximum Data (1942-1995)
- C.2. [Snowfall](#) – Monthly Averages and Maximums by Year (1946-1995)
- C.3. [Winds](#) - Percent Frequency of Peak Wind Speeds by Month (1946-1995)

APPENDIX D. BIRD LIST HOLLOMAN AFB

The [bird checklist](#) was compiled by the New Mexico Natural Heritage Program and Mesilla Valley Audubon Society for Holloman Air Force Base, including the Boles Wells Well Field Area.

The Holloman AFB bird checklist is also published on the [web](#) and shows species abundance and periods of occurrence on Holloman and the Boles Wells Well Field Area.

APPENDIX E. LANDSCAPING

- E.1. [Recommended Landscaping Plants Used in Learning Center Project](#)
- E.2. [Holloman AFB Native Plants List and Local Nurseries](#)

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Ahlstrand, Gary M., 1982. Response of Chihuahuan Desert mountain shrub to burning, *Journal of Range Management*, 35(1)82-85.
- Allred, Karen, 1996. Tumbleweed season hits New Mexico, *In: a News Release from New Mexico State University, New Mexico State University Agricultural Experiment Station, New Mexico State University, April 25, 1996.*
- Anderson, B.W., R.D. Ohmart and J. Rice. 1983. Avian and vegetation community structure and their seasonal relationships in the lower Colorado River valley. *Condor* 85:392-405.
- Anderson, O.J., G.E. Jones, and G.N. Green, 1997. *Geology Map of New Mexico*, USGS Open-File Report OF-97-52, unpublished map, digital format.
- Anschuetz, Kurt F., William H. Doleman and Richard C. Chapman, 1990. *Landscape Archeology in the Southern Tularosa Basin*, Volume 1, Small Site Distributions and Geomorphology, WSMR Archeological Research Report No. 90-7, OCA/UNM Report No. 185-324D, Office of Contract Archeology, University of New Meico.
- Bahre, C.J., 1995. Human impacts on the grasslands of southeastern Arizona, *In: McClaran, M.P. and Van Devender, T.R., (ed.)s, The Desert Grassland*, pp. 230-264, Tucson: The University of Arizona Press, 346 pp.
- Bahre, C.J. and M.L. Shelton, 1993. Historic vegetation change, mesquite increases, and climate in southeastern Arizona, *Journal of Biogeography*, 20:489-504.
- Beck, K. George, 1998. A management system to reclaim Russian knapweed infested range land, *Colorado Weed Management Association Newsletter*, vol. 9, no. 4, Colorado State University.
- Belnap, Jane, 1998. U.S.G.S. Biological Research Division, Moab, Utah, personal communication.
- Bennett, Iven, 1986. Wind, *In: New Mexico in Maps*, 2nd edition, (ed.) Jerry L. Williams, University of New Mexico Press, Albuquerque, New Mexico.
- Betancourt, Julio L., Thomas R. Vandevender, and Paul S. Martin, 1990. *Packrat Middens the Last 40,000 Years of Biotic Change*, University of Arizona Press.
- Biological Conservation Database (BCD), 1998. New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, Biology Department, University of New Mexico.

Biota Information System of New Mexico (BISON-M), 1997. Version 9/97, September 20, 1997, New Mexico Department of Game and Fish, Santa Fe, NM 87503.

Blair, W. Frank, 1941. Annotated list of mammals of the Tularosa Basin, New Mexico, *The American Midland Naturalist*, p. 218-227.

Black, Hal L. 1972. Differential exploitation of moths by the bats *Eptesicus fuscus* and *Lasiurus cinereus*, *Journal of Mammology*, Vol. 53, No. 3:598-601.

Blair, Terence C., Jeffrey S. Clark and Stephen G. Wells, 1990. Quaternary continental stratigraphy, landscape evolution, and application to Archeology: Jarilla piedmont and Tularosa graben floor, White Sands Missile Range, New Mexico, *Geological Society of America Bulletin*, v. 102, p. 749-759.

Blank, R.R., Allen, F., Young, J.A., 1995. The soil beneath shrubs before and after wildfire: implications for revegetation, In: Proceedings: wildland shrub and arid land restoration symposium, editors: Roundy, B.A., McArthur, E.D., Haley, J.S., Mann, D.K., 1993 October 19-21, Las Vegas, NV, Gen. Tech. Rep INT-GTR-315, Ogden, UT: U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Intermountain Research Station.

Brethauer, Douglas 1978. *Archeological Investigations at Site LA 15330, Dona Ana County, New Mexico*, Cultural Resource Management Division Report No. 250, New Mexico State University, Las Cruces.

Brotherson, J. D., J. G. Carman, and L. A. Szyska, 1984. Stem-diameter age relationships of *Tamarix ramosissima* in central Utah, *J. Range Manage.* 37:362-364

Brown, D.E. and C.H. Lowe, 1979. *Biotic Communities of the Southwest*, USDA Forest Service General Technical Report RM-78, 1 page map.

Buffington, L.C. and C.H. Herbel, 1965. Vegetational changes on a semidesert grassland range from 1858 to 1963, *Ecological Monographs*, 35:139-164.

Burkett, D.W., 1994. Herpetofauna of White Sands Missile Range, Cortez III Environmental Services, White Sands Missile Range, New Mexico, 13 p.

Bury, R.B., R.A. Luckenbach, and S.D. Busack, 1977. *Effects of off-road vehicles on vertebrates in the California Desert*, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Wildlife Research Report 8:1-23.

Burkett, Doug and Larry Kamees, 1996. *Mammals of White Sands Missile Range, New Mexico*, New Mexico State University and Cortez III Environmental Services, NM, May, 1996.

Carmen, J.G. and J.D. Brotherson. 1982. Comparisons of sites infested and not infested with salt cedar (*Tamarix pentandra*) and Russian olive (*Elaeagnus angustifolia*), *Weed Science* 30:360-364.

Carmichael, David L. 1985. *Archeological Excavations at Two Prehistoric Campsites near Keystone Dam*, El Paso, Texas, Occasional Papers No. 14, New Mexico State University, University Museum, Las Cruces.

Carmichael, David L. 1986. *Archeological Survey in the Southern Tularosa Basin, New Mexico*, Publications in Anthropology No. 10, El Paso Centennial Museum, University of Texas at El Paso.

Chung-MacCoubrey, Alice L., 1996. Grassland bats and land management in the Southwest, In: *Ecosystem Disturbance and Wildlife Conservation in Western Grasslands*, (ed.) Deborah M. Finch, USDA Forest Service, General Technical Report RM-GTR-285, September 1996.

Clayton, P. 1989. Preliminary distribution study for grama grass cactus, *Toumeyia papyracantha*, in Otero County, New Mexico. Report to BLM, Las Cruces, New Mexico.

Cole, R.A., D.L. Weigmann, and M.C., Hayes. 1984. Limnology of a shallow, brackish, hypereutrophic reservoir in southern New Mexico, NM State Univ. Agricultural Experiment Station Bull. 709.

Cornelius, J.M. 1988. *Fire effects on vegetation of a northern Chihuahuan desert grassland*. Dissertatin, New Mexico State University, Las Cruces.

Cortes, Jose, 1799. *Report on the Northern Provinces of New Spain*, (ed.) Elizabeth A.H. Johns, Trans. John Wheat, Norman, Oklahoma, University of Oklahoma Press, 1989.

Cowardin, L.M., V. Carter, F.C. Golet, and E.T. LaRoe, 1979. *Classification of Wetlands and Deepwater Habitats of the United States*, U.S. Department of the Interior, FWS/OBS-79/31, Washington, D.C., 131 p.

Cummins, K.W., G.W. Minshall, J.R. Sedell, C.E. Cushing, and R.C. Petersen, 1984. Stream ecosystem theory, *Verh. Internat. Verein. Limnol.*, 22:1818-1827, Stuttgart, December 1984.

Davis, Danny R., J. Scott Hopkins, and Seva J. Joseph, 1993. Lake Water Quality Assessment Surveys - Playa Lakes, 1993, New Mexico Environment Department, Surveillance and Standards Section Surface Water Quality Bureau, NMED/SWQ-95/2, February 1995.

Davis, Danny R., J. Scott Hopkins, and Seva J. Joseph, 1994. Lake Water Quality Assessment Surveys - Playa Lakes, 1994, New Mexico Environment Department,

Surveillance and Standards Section Surface Water Quality Bureau, NMED/SWQ-96/3, December 1996.

Department of Interior, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, 1994. Endangered and threatened wildlife and plants 50 CFR 17.11 and 17.12. Available from: Publication Unit, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, 130-WEBB, Washington, D.C. 20240.

Department of Interior Grassland and Bird Working Group, 1996. Declining birds in grassland ecosystems: A Department of the Interior Conservation Strategy, Report from Department of the Interior Grassland Bird Working Group, December 11-12, 1996, Fort Collins, Colorado.

Derr, Phillip S., James T. Bayer, M. Kaplan, R.C. Perkins, J.F. Ragus, J. Walker, 1981. *Soil survey of Otero area, New Mexico, Parts of Otero, Eddy, and Chaves Counties*, USDA Soil Conservation Service and Forest Service, in cooperation with the New Mexico State University Agricultural Experiment Station.

Dick-Peddie, W.A., 1993. *New Mexico Vegetation, Past, Present and Future*. University of New Mexico Press, Albuquerque.

Doleman, William H., 1988. *The Holloman Test Track Impact Area Archeological Survey*, Office of Contract Archeology, University of New Mexico.

Donart G.B., D.D. Sylvester and W.C. Hickey, 1978. *A vegetation classification system for New Mexico*, U.S.A. Proceedings of the First International Rangeland Congress, 498-500.

Driscoll, R.S., D.L. Merkel, D.L. Radloff, D.E. Snyder, and J.S. Hagihara, 1984. *An Ecological Land Classification Framework for the United States*, USDA Forest Service Mexc. Pub. 1439, Washington, D.C.

Ehrlich, P.R., D.S. Dobkin, and D. Wheye, 1988. *The birders handbook: A field guide to the natural histories of North American birds*, New York: Simon and Schuster.

Eidenbach, Peter L., 1981. *Two Prehistoric Solstice Observatories in the Sacramento Mountain, Southern New Mexico*, Tularosa, NM: Human Systems Research, p. 27 In: *We Develop Missiles, Not Air! The Legacy of Early Missile, Rocket, Instrumentation, and Aeromedical Research Development at Holloman Air Force Base* by Wayne O. Mattson and Martyn D. Tagg, Holloman Air Force Base, Cultural Resources Publication No. 2, June 1995.

Eldridge, Jan 1992. Management of habitat for breeding and migrating shorebirds in the Midwest, In *Waterfowl Management Handbook*, Fish and Wildlife Leaflet 13.2.14, 5 pp.

Environmental Systems Research Institute, Inc. (ESRI), July 1998,
<http://www.esri.com/library/gis/index.html>

Federal Register, September 29, 1995, Vol 60, No. 189. Final National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System Storm Water Multi-Sector General Permit for Industrial Activities, FRL-5298-3, pp. 50804-51319, United States Government Printing Office, Washington, D.C.

Fenton, M.B. 1970. Population studies of *Myotis lucifugus* (Chiroptera:Vespertilionidae) in Ontario, Royal Ontario Museum, 77:1-34.

Findley, J.S., A.H. Harris, D.E. Wilson, and C. Jones, 1975. *Mammals of New Mexico*, University of New Mexico Press, Albuquerque, New Mexico.

Fletcher, J.E. and W.P. Martin, 1948. Some effects of algae and molds in the rain-crust of desert soils, *Ecology*, 29(1):95-100.

Ford, Paulette L. and Guy R. McPherson, 1996. Ecology of fire in shortgrass prairie of the southern Great Plains, In: *Ecosystem Disturbance and Wildlife Conservation in Western Grasslands*, editor Deborah M. Finch, USDA Forest Service, General Technical Report RM-GTR-285, September 1996.

Freehling, Michael, Kristine Johnson, and Linda DeLay, 1998. Foraging ecology of wetland birds at Holloman Air Force Base: Summary of Progress, 1997, New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, Biology Department, University of New Mexico, January 12, 1998.

Frey, Jennifer K. and Terry L. Yates, 1996. Mammalian Diversity in New Mexico, *New Mexico Journal of Science*, Vol.36:4-37.

Fryberger, Steven G., Lee F. Krystinik, Christopher J. Schenk, 1990. *Modern and ancient eolian deposits: petroleum exploration and production*, Rocky Mountain Section, S.E.P.M.

Garza, S. and J.S. McLean, 1977. *Freshwater Resources in the Southeastern Part of the Tularosa Basin*, New Mexico State Engineer's Office Technical Report No. 40, Santa Fe.

Germano, D.J. and C.R. Hungerford, 1981. Reptile population changes with manipulation of Sonoran Desert shrub, *Great Basin Naturalist* 41:129-138.

Gottfried, G.J., 1991. New perspectives and forest service research for the Southwestern pinyon-juniper woodlands. General Technical Report RM 216. Hayes, D.C.; Bumstead, J.S.; Richards, M.T. (eds.). U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Forest and Range Station Experiment Station: 37-44.

- Hall, R.S., R.L. Glinski, D.H. Ellis, J.M. Ramakka, and D.L. Base, 1988. Ferruginous Hawk. In: Glinski et al., (eds.), *Proceedings of the Southwest raptor management symposium and workshop*, Washington, D.C.: National Wildlife Federation, Series 11:111-118.
- Harper, J.L., J.T. Williams, G.R. Sanger, 1965. The behavior of seed in soil. I. The heterogeneity of soil surfaces and its role in determining the establishment of plants, *Journal of Ecology*, 53:272-286.
- Harper, K.T. and J.R. Marble 1988. A role for non-vascular plants in management of semiarid rangelands. In: *Vegetation science applications for rangeland analysis and management*, Tueller, P.T. (ed.), Kluwer Academic Publishers, London: 135:169.
- Harper, K.T. and R.L. Pendleton 1993. Cyanobacteria and cyanolichens: Can they enhance availability of essential minerals for higher plants, *Great Basin Naturalist*, 53(1):50-72.
- Haukos, David A. and Loren M. Smith, 1994. The importance of playa wetlands to biodiversity of the Southern High Plains, *Landscape and Urban Planning* 28:83-98.
- Haussamen, Wally, 1995. *Mule Deer and Their Management in New Mexico*, New Mexico Department of Game and Fish, Santa Fe, NM, December, 1995.
- Hawley, John W., 1986. Physiographic provinces II In: *New Mexico in Maps*, 2nd edition, (ed.) Jerry L. Williams, University of New Mexico Press, Albuquerque, New Mexico.
- Hawley, John W., 1994. *Quaternary geology of New Mexico*, New Mexico Bureau of Mines and Mineral Resources, New Mexico Tech, Albuquerque Office, unpublished map.
- Hawthorne, Lori S., 1994. *I Never Left a Place that I Didn't Clean Up*, Cultural Resources Publication No. 1, Holloman Air Force Base, New Mexico.
- Hawthorne-Tagg, Lori S., 1997. *A Life Like No Other: Ranch life on lands now administered by Holloman Air Force Base*, Cultural Resources Publication No. 4, Holloman Air Force Base, New Mexico.
- Helmets, Douglas L. 1993. Enhancing the management of wetlands for migrant shorebirds, in *Management of Wetlands for Migrating Shorebirds*, Trans. 58th N.a. Wildl. and Natur. Res. Conf. (1993).
- Hicks, Andrew and Robert F. Whitcomb, 1996. Diversity of the leafhopper (Homoptera:Cicadellidae) fauna of Northern Chihuahuan Grasslands, with emphasis on gypsum grasslands and description of a new species of *Athysanella* (Cicadellidae: Deltocephalinae), *Proc. Entomol. Soc. Wash*, 98(1), pp. 145-157.

Ho, Iwan, 1987. Vesicular-arbuscular mycorrhizae of halophytic grasses in the Alvord Desert of Oregon, *Northwest Science*, 61(3):148-151.

Hoffmeister, D.F. 1986. *Mammals of Arizona*, The University of Arizona Press and the Arizona Game and Fish Dept., 602pp.

Holloman AFB, 1996. Environmental attributes analysis for Red Rio Bombing Range, White Sands Missile Range, New Mexico, Final, Volume III, Soil, Natural, Water, Cultural and GIS Resources, November 27, 1996.

Holloman AFB, 1997. Environmental attributes analysis for Oscura Range, White Sands Missile Range, New Mexico, Final, Volume III, Soil, Natural, Water, Cultural and GIS Resources, January 30, 1997.

Holloman AFB, 1998. Programmatic Environmental Assessment Ground-Based Field Training and Exercises Combined with Integrated Ground-Based Field Training Management Plan Holloman Air Force Base, New Mexico, June 1998.

Hubbard, J.P., 1978. Revised check-list of the birds of New Mexico, New Mexico Ornithological Society, Publication No. 6.

Humphrey, Robert R. 1974. Fire in the deserts and desert grassland of North America, ed. T.T. Kozlowski, *In: Fire and Ecosystems*, Academic Press, Inc., 365-400.

Johansen, J.R. and S.R. Rushforth 1985. Cryptogamic soil crusts: seasonal variation in algal populations in the Tintic Mountains, Juab County, Utah, *Great Basin Naturalist*, 46(4):14-21.

Johansen, J.R., A. Javakul, S.R. Rushforth, 1982. Effects of burning on the algal communities of a high desert soil near Wallsburg, Utah, *Journal of Range Management*, 35(5):598-600.

Johansen, J.R., J. Ashley, W.R. Rayburn, 1993. Effects of range fire on soil algal crusts in semi-arid shrub-steppe of the lower Columbia Basin and their subsequent recovery, *Great Basin Naturalist*, 53(1):73-88.

Johnson, G.D. and K.A. Fagerstone, 1994. Primary and Secondary Hazards of Zinc Phosphide to Non target Wildlife - A Review of the Literature. USDA-APHIS, DWRC Research Report No. 11-55-005.

Johnson, Kristine, Kim Score, Sarah Berckman, J. Scott Altenbach, and Patricia Mehlhop, 1997a. *A survey of biological resources at the Cinetheodolite Missile Towers on Holloman Air Force Base and White Sands Missile Range, New Mexico*, New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, Biology Department, University of New Mexico, Albuquerque, New Mexico, November 7, 1997.

Johnson, Kristine, Linda DeLay, Patricia Mehlhop, and Kimberly Score, 1997b. *Distribution, Habitat, and Reproductive Success of Burrowing Owls on Holloman Air Force Base, New Mexico*, New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, Biology Department, University of New Mexico, July 31, 1997.

Kamees, Larry and Doug Burkett, 1996. A Checklist of Birds for White Sands Missile Range New Mexico (Updated).

Kammer, David, 1997. Historical significance of the Askania Cinetheodolite Towers located on Holloman Air Force Base and White Sands Missile Range, New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, unpublished.

Knight, R.L. 1997. Wildlife habitat and public use benefits of treatment wetlands, *Wat. Sci. Tech.*, Vol. 35, No. 5:35-43.

Kozma, J.M. and N.E. Mathews, 1997. Breeding bird communities and nest plant-selection in Chihuahuan Desert habitats in South-Central New Mexico, *Wilson Bulletin*, v. 109(3), 424-436.

Kramp, B.E., Patton, D.R., Brady, W.W., 1983. The effects of fire on wildlife habitat and species, *Run Wild Wildlife/Habitat Relationships*, USDA Forest Service Wildlife Unit Technical Report, 29 pp.

Lacey, C.A., J.R. Lacey, P.K. Fay, J.M. Story, and D.L. Zamora. 1995. Controlling knapweed on Montana Rangeland. Montana State University Extension Service, Bozeman, Montana. Circular 311, 17 p.

Ladyman, Juanita A.R., 1997. Tamarisk - Removal and Re-establishment of Native Vegetation, unpublished.

Ladyman, Juanita A.R., 1998. Personal conversation with Juanita Ladyman, Botanist, New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, University of New Mexico, Albuquerque, New Mexico.

Ladyman, Juanita A.R. and Esteban Muldavin, 1996. *Terrestrial cryptogams of Pinyon-Juniper woodlands in the southwestern United States: A review*, New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, Department of Biology, University of New Mexico, U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service General Technical Report RM-GTR-280, July 1996.

Law Environmental, Inc., 1994. Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan for Holloman AFB, Basic Contract No. F33615-90-D-4008.

Law Environmental, Inc., 1998. Draft Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan for Holloman AFB.

Lee, Judith, 1998. Draft Programmatic Environmental Assessment for Ground-Based Field Training and Exercises, Holloman AFB, NM, Environmental Planning Strategies, May 1998.

Lee, Thomas E., et al. 1994. Mitochondrial DNA and Allozyme Analysis of North American Pronghorn Populations, *Journal of Wildlife Management* 58(2):1994. pp. 307-318.

Lehmer, D.J. 1948. *The Jornada Branch of the Mogollon*, Social Science Bulletin 17, University of Arizona, Tucson.

Leslie, Michele, Gary K. Meffe, Jeffrey L. Hardesty, and Diane L. Adams, 1996. *Conserving Biodiversity on Military Lands: A Handbook for Natural Resource Managers*, The Nature Conservancy, Arlington, VA.

Lightfoot, D.C. and W.G. Whitford, 1990. Phytophagous insects enhance nitrogen flux in a desert creosote community, *Oecologia* 82:18-25.

Lyon, L.J., Crawford, H.S., Czuhai, E., Fredriksen, R.L., Harlen, R.F., Metz, L.J. Pearson, H.A., 1978. *Effects of fire on fauna: A state-of-knowledge review*, USDA Forest Service General Technical Report WO-6, 22 p.

Madden, L., 1995. Ecological effects of prescribed fire on prairie songbird communities, Abstract: International Conference and Training Workshop on Conservation and Ecology of Grassland Birds and 1995 Annual Meeting of the Association of Field Ornithologists, 26-28 October 1995, Tulsa, OK.

Mahall, B.E. and R.M. Callaway, 1991. Root communication among desert shrubs, *Ecology* 88:874-876.

Malanson, George P., 1993. *Riparian Landscapes*, Cambridge University Press, 296 p.

Mattson, Wayne O. and Martyn D. Tagg, 1995. *We Develop Missiles, Not Air! The Legacy of Early Missile, Rocket, Instrumentation, and Aeromedical Research Development at Holloman Air Force Base*, Cultural Resources Publication No. 2, June 1995.

McKee, E.D., 1966. Structure of dunes at White Sands National Monument, New Mexico, *Sedimentology* 7:1-69.

Mehlhop, P., N.M. Runyan, E. DeBruin and J.M. Brown-Ellington, 1998a. *Holloman Air Force Base Sensitive Species Management Plan*, Report to Holloman Air Force Base, NM, New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, Biology Department, University of New Mexico, unpublished.

- Mehlhop, P., N. M. Runyan, E. DeBruin and J.M. Brown-Ellington. 1998b. *Sensitive species status assessment for Holloman Air Force Base, New Mexico*. Draft Report to Holloman Air Force Base, NM, New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, Biology Department, University of New Mexico, Albuquerque, New Mexico, unpublished.
- Meinzer, O.E., and Hare, R.F., 1915. *Geology and water resources of Tularosa Basin, New Mexico*: U.S. Geological Survey Water Supply Paper 343, 317 p.
- Miller, B.C., C. Wemmer, D. Biggins, and R. Reading, 1990. A proposal to conserve black-footed ferrets and the prairie dog ecosystem, *Environmental Management* 14:763-769.
- Miller, B.C., G. Ceballos, and R. Reading, 1994. The prairie dog and biotic diversity, *Conservation Biology* 8:677-681.
- Moore R.J. and C. Frankton, 1974. The thistles of Canada. Canadian Department of Agriculture Monograph No. 10, Information Canada, Ottawa, Ontario. 111 p.
- Morafka, D.J. 1977. A biogeographical analysis of the Chihuahuan Desert through its herpetofauna, *Biogeographica* 9:1-313.
- Muldavin, Esteban H. and Patricia Mehlhop, 1992. A test of 6-band satellite imagery and mapping of the vegetation of White Sands Missile Range and San Andres National Wildlife Refuge, New Mexico. Final report to the Environmental Office, White Sands Missile Range, NM. New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, Albuquerque, NM.
- Muldavin, Esteban, Glenn Harper, Paul Neville, Yvonne Chauvin, and Patricia Mehlhop, 1997. *A Vegetation Classification and map for White Sands Missile Range and San Andres National Wildlife Refuge, New Mexico*, Final Report, Volume II, New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, unpublished.
- Muldavin, Esteban, Glenn Harper, Paul Neville, Teri Bennett, and Kris Johnson, 1998. *A vegetation classification map for Holloman Air Force Base, New Mexico*, Final Report, New Mexico Natural Heritage Program, unpublished. [Link to report](#)
- National Defense Authorization Act, 1994. National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 1995, Report 103-701, Section 2345, 12 Aug 1994.
- Neher, Raymond E. and Oran F. Bailey, 1976. *Soil survey of White Sands Missile Range, New Mexico, Parts of Dona Ana, Lincoln, Otero, Sierra, and Socorro Counties*, USDA Soil Conservation Service in cooperation with US Department of the Army, White Sands Missile Range, and the New Mexico Agricultural Experiment Station.
- New Mexico Department of Energy, Minerals, and Natural Resources, 1991. *Statewide Comprehensive Outdoor Recreation Plan for New Mexico, New Mexico, Wetlands* (addendum). State of New Mexico, Santa Fe, NM. 57 p.

New Mexico Partners in Flight, 1997. *Draft Bird Conservation Plan for New Mexico*.

New Mexico Water Quality Control Commission , 1994. *Water Quality and Water Pollution Control in New Mexico*, State of New Mexico Water Quality Control Commission, Santa Fe, 243 p. plus appendices, NMED/SWQ-94/4.

Noss, Reed F., Edward T. Laroe III, J. Michael Scott, 1995. *Endangered ecosystems of the United States: A preliminary assessment of loss and degradation*. Biological Report 28, February 1995, U.S. Department of the Interior, National Biological Service, Washington, D.C. 20240.

Noyes, Peter T. and Matthew F. Schmader, 1988. Environmental Overview. In: *The Border Star 85 Survey: Toward an Archeology of Landscapes* (ed.) T.J. Seaman, W.H. Doleman, and R.C. Chapman, pp. 19-26. Office of Contract Archeology, University of New Mexico, Albuquerque.

Odum, E.P., 1971. *Fundamentals of Ecology*, third edition, Saunders, Philadelphia, Pa.

O'Laughlin, Thomas C. 1980. *The Keystone Dam Site and other Archaic and Formative Sites in Northwest El Paso, Texas*, Publications in Anthropology No. 8, El Paso Centennial Museum, University of Texas at El Paso.

O'Shea, Thomas J. and Terry A. Vaughan, 1977. Nocturnal and seasonal activities of the pallid bat, *Antrozous pallidus*, *Journal of Mammology*, Vol. 58, No. 3:269-284.

Parker, Doug and M. Hildegard Reiser, 1997. *Low-impact, selective herbicide application for control of African Rue, a Preliminary Field Guide*, U.S.D.A., Forest Service, Southwestern Region, June 1997.

Patrick, Gail R., 1980. Succession behind the parabolic dunes, In: *Final Report: White Sands National Monument Natural Resources and Ecosystem Analysis*, Volume 1, CX 702900001, William H. Reid, Projector Director, Laboratory for Environmental Biology, Research Report Number 12, October 1980, The University of Texas at El Paso.

Pegau, R.E., 1970. Effect of Reindeer trampling and grazing on lichens, *Journal of Range Management*, 23:95-97.

Peterson, Frederick F., 1981. *Landforms of the Basin and Range Province*, Technical Bulletin 28, Nevada Agricultural Experiment Station, University of Nevada, Reno, Nevada, 52 p.

Pfister, C., B.A. Harrington, and M. Lavine, 1992. The impact of human disturbance on shorebirds at a migration staging area, *Biol. Conserv.* 60:115-126.

- Pittenger, J.S. 1994. White Sands pupfish conservation *plan*. Conservation Services Division, New Mexico Department of Game and Fish, Santa Fe, New Mexico 87503.
- Pittenger, J.S. 1996. White Sands Pupfish Conservation Team meeting summary. Unpubl. report available from NM Department of Game and Fish, Santa Fe. 11p.
- Pittenger, J.S. and C.L. Springer, 1996. *White Sands pupfish status report: 1995*. Unpubl. report to White Sands Pupfish Conservation Team, NM Department of Game and Fish, Santa Fe & U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Albuquerque, NM. 30p.
- Primack, Richard B. 1993. *Essentials of Conservation Biology*, Sinauer Associates, Inc., Sunderland, Mass., 564 p.
- Rosenthal, S.S. 1995. Russian knapweed *Acroptilon repens* sunflower family- Asteraceae In: Rees, N.E., P.C. Quimby Jr., G.L. Piper, E.M. Coombs, C.E. Turner, N.R. Spencer, and L.V. Knutson (eds.) 1995. *Biological Control of Weeds in the West*. Western Society of Weed Science in cooperation with USDA Agricultural Research Service, Montana Department of Agriculture, and Montana State University.
- Ross, A. 1967. Ecological aspects of the food habits of insectivorous bats, *Proceedings of the Western Foundation of Vertebrate Zoology*, 1:205-264.
- Schmidt, R.H., 1986. Chihuahuan climate in the *Second Symposium on Resources of the Chihuahuan Desert Region, United States and Mexico*, (ed.) Jon C. Barlow, A. Michael Powell, Barbara Timmermann, Chihuahuan Desert Research Institute, pp. 40-63.
- Scott, Norman J., Jr., 1996. Evolution and management of the North American grassland herpetofauna In: *Ecosystem Disturbance and Wildlife Conservation in Western Grasslands*, (ed.), Deborah M. Finch, USDA Forest Service, General Technical Report RM-GTR-285, September 1996.
- Shantz, H. L. and R.L. Piemeisel, 1924. Indicator significance of the natural vegetation of the Southwestern desert region, *Journal of Agricultural Research*, 28(8):721-803.
- Silvertown, Jonathan and J. Bastow Wilson, 1994. Community structure in a desert perennial community. *Ecology*, 75(2):409-417.
- Sivinski, R. and K. Lightfoot. 1994. Status summary for the grama grass cactus (*Toumeyia papyracantha*), Report to U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service Region 2, Albuquerque, NM.
- Sivinski, R. and K. Lightfoot, 1995. *Inventory of the Rare and Endangered Plants of New Mexico*, 3rd Edition, NM Forestry Division, Santa Fe, Miscellaneous Publication No. 4.
- Smith, Loren M. and John A. Kadlec, 1985a. Comparisons of prescribed burning and cutting of Utah marsh plants, *Great Basin Naturalist*, 45:462-466.

Smith, Loren M. and John A. Kadlec, 1985b. The effects of disturbance on marsh seed banks, *Canadian Journal of Botany*, 63:2133-2137.

Soil Survey Staff, 1975. *Soil Taxonomy*, U.S. Department of Agriculture, Handbook 436, Washington, D.C.: U.S. Government Printing Office.

Stoeser, Douglas B., Michael K. Senterfit, Jeanne E. Zelten, 1989. *Mineral Resources of the Little Black Peak and Carrizozo Lava Flow Wilderness Study Areas, Lincoln County, New Mexico*, U.S. Geological Survey Bulletin 1734.

Suminski, R.R., 1977. Life history of the White Sands Pupfish and distribution of *Cyprinodon* in New Mexico. M.S. Thesis, New Mexico State University, Las Cruces.

Trammell, Michael A. 1995. Effects of exotic plants on native ungulate use of habitat, *J. Wildl. Manage.* 59(4):808-816.

Turner, P.R., 1987. *Ecology and management needs of the White Sands Pupfish in the Tularosa Basin of New Mexico*. Contract No. DAAD07-84-2242. Available from: Environmental Division, Wildlife Branch of the U.S. Department of the Army, White Sands Missile Range, New Mexico.

USDA. April 1994. Animal Damage Control Program; Final Environmental Impact Statement. US Dept. of Agriculture, Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service. 3 volumes.

USDA Forest Service Intermountain Research Station's Fire Sciences Laboratory (IFSL), 1995. *Fire Effects Information System (FEIS)*, Missoula, Montana, <http://www.fs.fed.us/database/feis/>.

U.S.G.S Biological Resources Division, 1998. Declining Birds in Grassland Ecosystems: A Department of the Interior Conservation Strategy, Report From: Department of the Interior Grassland Bird Working Group, Fort Collins, Colorado, December 11-12, 1996. http://www.mesc.usgs.gov/pubs/online/grassbirds/birds_grassland_eco.html

United States Air Force, 1996. *Delineations of Jurisdictional Waters of the United States and Wetlands on Holloman Air Force Base, New Mexico*, U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Fort Worth District, Fort Worth, Texas.

United States Air Force Environmental Technical Applications Center, 1994. Surface Observations Climatic Summaries for Holloman Air Force Base/Alamogordo, New Mexico. USAFETAC, Asheville, North Carolina.

United States Army Corp of Engineers, 1992. *Environmental Assessment for Off-Road "ORV" Concept Development Plan for Holloman Air Force Base*, May 92.

United States Environmental Protection Agency, July 1992. Storm Water Management for Industrial Activities: Developing Pollution Prevention Plans and Best Management Practices, Office of Wastewater Enforcement and Compliance, Washington, D.C.

Umbanhowar, C.E., 1996. Recent fire history of the northern Great Plains, *American Midland Naturalist*, 135:115-121.

VanDevender, Thomas R. 1977. Holocene Woodlands in Southwestern Deserts, *Science* 198:189-192.

VanDevender, Thomas R. and D.H. Riskind 1979. Late Pleistocene and Early Holocene Plant Remains from Hueco Tanks State Historical Park: The Development of a Refugium, *Southwestern Naturalist* 24:127-140.

Vogl, Richard 1974. Effects of fire on grasslands, *In: Fire and Ecosystems*, ed. T.T. Kozlowski, Academic Press, Inc., 139-194.

Watson, A.K. 1980. The biology of Canadian weeds 43 *Acroptilon (Centaurea) repens* (L.) DC. *Canadian Journal of Plant Science* 60:993-1004.

Weddell, B.J. 1996. Geographic overview: climate, phenology, and disturbance regimes in steppe and desert communities, *In: Ecosystem disturbance and wildlife conservation in western grasslands*, USDA Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Forest and Range Experiment Station, General Technical Report RM-GTR-285, pp. 3-12.

West, N.E. 1993. Biodiversity of rangelands, *Journal of Range Management*, 46:1-13.

West, N.E. and M.A. Hassan, 1985. Recovery of sagebrush-grass vegetation following wildfire, *Journal of Range Management*, 38(2):131-134.

West, N.E. and J. Skujins, 1977. The nitrogen cycle in North American cold-winter semi-desert ecosystems. *Oecologia Plantarum*, 12 (1):45-53.

West, S.W. and W.L. Broadhurst, 1975. *Summary appraisals of the nation's ground-water resources - Rio Grande Region*, Geological Survey Professional Paper 813-D, U.S. Government Printing Office, Washington.

Whalen, Michael L. 1978. Settlement Patterns of the Western Hueco Bolson, *Publications in Anthropology* No. 6, El Paso Centennial Museum, University of Texas, El Paso.

Whalen, Michael L. 1980. The Pueblo Periods of South-Central New Mexico, *In: An Archeological Synthesis of South-Central and Southwestern New Mexico*, by S.A. LeBlanc and M.E. Whalen, pp. 388-488, Office of Contract Archeology, University of New Mexico, Albuquerque.

White Sands Missile Range (WSMR), 1994. Draft White Sands Missile Range, Range-wide Environmental Impact Statement, Directorate of Environment and Safety, Environmental Services division, White Sands Missile Range, New Mexico.

Whitford, Walter G., 1995. Desertification: Implications and limitations of the ecosystem health metaphor, *In*:: Rapport, D.J., Gaudet, C.L. and Calow, P., (eds.), *Evaluating and Monitoring the Health of Large-Scale Ecosystems*, pp. 273-293. NATO ASI Series, Vol. I 28, Berlin Springer-Verlag, 456 pp.

Whitfield, C.J. and H.L. Anderson, 1938. Natural vegetation in the desert plains grassland, *Ecology*, 19:26-37.

Whitford, Walter G., 1997. Desertification and animal biodiversity in the desert grasslands of North America, *Journal of Arid Environments*, 37:709-720.

Wilkins, D.W., 1986. *Geohydrology of the Southwest Alluvial Basins Regional Aquifer-Systems Analysis, Parts of Colorado, New Mexico, and Texas*, U.S. Geological Survey, Water-Resources Investigations Report 84-4224.

Williamson, Michael A., Paul W. Hyder, John S. Applegarth, 1994. *Snakes, lizards, turtles, frogs, toads and salamanders of New Mexico, A Field Guide*, Sunstone Press, Santa Fe, NM, 176 pp.

Wimberly, Mark and Alan Rogers, 1977. Cultural Succession, A Case Study. Archeological Survey, Three Rivers Drainage, New Mexico, *The Artifact*, vol. 15., Human Systems Research, Three Rivers, New Mexico.

Wright, Henry A. and Arthur W. Bailey, 1982. *Fire ecology: United States and southern Canada*, New York: John Wiley & Sons, 501 p.

Yard, Helen, 1998. Birds, Bugs, and Exotic Shrubs, Colorado Plateau Research Station, Flagstaff, Arizona. (<http://www.nbs.nau.edu/News/Summer96/helen.html>)

York, J.C. and W.A. Dick-Peddie, 1969. Vegetation changes in southern New Mexico during the past hundred years, pp. 157-199, *In*: W.G. McGinnies and B.J. Goldman (eds.), *Arid lands in perspective*, University of Arizona Press, Tucson.

Zimmerman, Julia A.C., 1996. Ecology and Distribution of *Acroptilon repens* (L.) D.C., *Asteraceae*, U.S. Geological Survey- Biological Resources Division, Colorado Plateau Field Station- Flagstaff, Arizona, 12-13-96,
<http://www.nbs.nau.edu/FNF/Vegetation/Exotics/Acroptilon/Russianknapweed.html#description>.

INTERNET/INTRANET LINKAGES

LINK	DESCRIPTION	SITE ADDRESS
49 th _FW	49 th Fighter Wing Home Page	http://www.holloman.af.mil/49fw/49fw.html
Bird_checklist	Holloman AFB Bird Checklist	http://128.174.5.51/denix/Public/ES-Programs/Conservation/Bird-Checklist/hafb/hafb.html
BASH	Bird hazards to aircraft - a web site of links to information and methods of control	http://www.airsafe.com/birds.htm
BISON-M	N.M. Department of Game and Fish, Biota Information System of New Mexico (BISON-M)	http://www.fw.vt.edu/fishex/states/nm.htm
DENIX	Defense Environmental Network and Information Exchange	http://128.174.5.51/denix/Public/News/news.html
DoD	Department of Defense Instruction - A Search Index	http://www.dtic.mil/adm/dodi_ordering.html
ESA	Endangered Species Act	http://www.fws.gov/~r9endspp/esa.html
FAMNET	FAMNET Crossroads photo gallery of HAFB facilities	http://www.famnet.com/usaf/holloman/gallery.htm
FGDC_Veg	Federal Geographic Data Committee Vegetation Classification and Information Standards	http://www.nbs.gov/fgdc.veg/
Ft_Bliss	Ft. Bliss Home Page	http://www.bliss.army.mil/
HAFB	Holloman Air Force Base Web Site	http://www.holloman.af.mil/
EPA_POLLUTION	Enviro\$en\$E EPA Site for pollution prevention, compliance assurance, and enforcement information and data bases. Or Pollution prevention programs at HAFB	http://es.epa.gov/ Or http://es.epa.gov/program/p2dept/defense/airforce/4384.html
Intl_listing	The World Conservation Union, Species Survival	http://www.iucn.org/themes/ssc/redlist/criteria.htm ;

LINK	DESCRIPTION	SITE ADDRESS
	Commission (IUCN); Preliminary Red List for Endangered Lichen	http://www.sbg.ac.at/pfl/projects/lichen/red_list.htm
MBTA	Migratory Bird Treaty Act	http://www.fws.gov/r9dle/mbta.html
Oliver Lee State Park	Oliver Lee State Park	http://www.alamogordo.com/attract/olee.html
NM_Plants	<i>Inventory of Rare and Endangered Plants of New Mexico</i> , New Mexico Forestry Division, Energy, Minerals and Natural Resources Department	http://www.emnrd.state.nm.us/forestry/endplntlist.htm
NM_Wildlife_Policy	USFWS - State of New Mexico - State Wildlife Policy	http://www.fws.gov/laws/state/newmex.html
NMNHP	New Mexico Natural Heritage Program - Biological Conservation Database	http://nmnhp.unm.edu/
NMNPS	New Mexico Native Plant Society - Otero Chapter	http://www.wazoo.com/~dkeeney/npsoc.html
Pest_Mgmt	AFI 32-1053 Pest Management Program	http://denix.cecer.army.mil/denix/Public/Webnotes/get_text.cgi/denix/Public/Policy/policy.html?public.policy.airforce.instructions/27/0
Spotted_Owl	Mexican Spotted Owl – 50 CFR Part 17	http://www.fws.gov/~r9endspp/r/r93494.html
USACE-Resources	Links to technical and biological resources on the web from USACE	http://www.usace.army.mil/inet/functions/cw/cecwo/reg/techbio.htm
USACE-Abq	Albuquerque District Regulatory Branch – Army Corp of Engineers	http://www.swa-wc.usace.army.mil/reg/
USACHPPM	US Army Center for Health Promotion and Preventive Medicine (Pest Management)	http://chppm-www.apgea.army.mil/ento/index.htm
USFWS_Region2	USFWS Region 2 Listed Species	http://www.fws.gov/~r9endspp/r2spndx.html
Water_classification	Classification of Wetlands and Deepwater Habitats of the United States by Lewis M. Cowardin	http://www.nwi.fws.gov/classman.html

LINK	DESCRIPTION	SITE ADDRESS
Water_definition	Waters of the US - definition	http://www.spa.usace.army.mil/reg/part328.htm
WSMR	White Sands Missile Range Web Site	http://www.wsmr.army.mil/
WSNM	White Sands National Monument	http://www.nps.gov/whsa/